

**THE POSSIBLE FUTURE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE
INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL REPORTING
STANDARDS (IFRS) IN LIBYA**

BY:

MOHAMED ABDURAHMAN

**This thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the West
of Scotland for the award of**

School of Business and Creative Industries

Submission date: April 2021

Author's Declaration

I hereby declare that this dissertation is my original work, that no part of it consists of the work of others, except where this is clearly acknowledged , and that no part of it has been submitted elsewhere for fulfilment of the requirements of this or any other award.

Student's signature:

Signed by: Mohamed Abdurahman

School of Business and Creative Industries

University of the West of Scotland

Date: 30 April 2021.

Table of Contents

Acknowledgements	8
Abstract	9
Chapter One - Introduction	
1.1 General introduction	10
1.2 Background –Accounting and auditing in Libya (history)	10
1.3 Aim, objectives and research questions of the study	14
1.4 Questions for interviewees	15
1.5 Summary of quantitative results	15
1.6 Summary of additional qualitative results (beyond the quantitative)	18
1.7 Structure of the thesis	18
Chapter Two - Background	
2.1 Introduction	23
2.2 Introduction to Libya - historical context (up to 2011)	23
2.2.1 History of the accounting profession in Libya	26
2.2.2 The development of accounting standards in Libya	27
2.3 Global impacts of the IASB and IFRS foundation during their development	29
2.3.1 Principles-based accounting versus rules-based accounting	30
2.4 Challenges for the IASB	32
2.5 Advantages and disadvantages of global standards	35
2.5.1 Advantages of global standards	35
2.5.2 Disadvantages of global standards	40
2.5.3 Balancing the advantages and disadvantages	49
2.6 Conclusion	50
Chapter Three - Philosophical and methodological approach	
3.1 Introduction	53
3.2 Research perspective	53
3.3 Research paradigms	54
3.4 Burrell and Morgan’s paradigm	55
3.4.1 Objectivist and subjectivist dimension	56
3.4.2 Regulatory and radical change of the society	59
3.4.3 The emergence of paradigms	60
3.5 Criticism of Burrell and Morgan’s model	68
3.6 Alternative approaches to mainstream accounting research	70
3.6.1 Chua (1986) - Classification of assumptions	70
3.6.2 Laughlin and middle-range thinking	71
3.7 Applying institutional theory to accounting standard setting	78

3.7.1 Application of institutional theory to IFRS adoption in Libya	79
3.8 Research method – Timing	81
3.8.1 First: descriptive versus explanatory	82
3.8.2 Second: The study and sample context	82
3.9 Limitations of questionnaires	85
3.10 Interviews as a research method	85
3.11 Types of interviews	86
3.11.1 Semi-structured	87
3.12 Shortcomings of interviews	91
3.13 Ethical Consideration	92
3.14 Conclusion	92

Chapter Four- Part A: Literature review (Harmonization)

4.1 Introduction	94
4.2 Introduction to processes of harmonization	94
4.3 Defining harmonization and its major forms	95
4.3.1 De jure harmonization and de facto harmonization	96
4.3.2 Qualitative and quantitative research	97
4.4 Challenges to IFRS harmonization	98
4.5 The global harmonization process	100
4.5.1 Adoption of IFRS	101
4.5.2 Standard-by-standard	102
4.5.3 Optional harmonization of IFRS	105
4.5.4 Not fully converged IFRS harmonization	105
4.6 Harmonization and Islamic Accounting	106
4.6.1 Background to Islamic accounting	107
4.6.2 IFRS and Islamic Accounting	107
4.7 Conclusion	111

Chapter Four Part B -Literature review (Issues for developed and emerging economies)

4.8 Introduction - Developed versus emerging economies	113
4.9 Harmonization of accounting standards in the emerging economies	113
4.10 Adoption of IFRS: Case studies of developed countries	117
4.10.1 Developed countries of western, southern and central Europe	118
4.10.2 United States of America (USA)	126
4.11 Adoption of IFRS: Case studies of emerging countries	128
4.11.1 The outcome of accounting standards on financial performance	128
4.12 Conclusion	140

Chapter Four Part C- Literature review (Context of Libya)

4.13 Context of Libya	142
4.13.1 Introduction	142
4.13.2 The relevance of IFRS to Libya	144
4.13.3 The potential impediments to implementation of IFRS in Libya	145

4.14	Conclusion	153
------	------------	-----

Chapter Five - Quantitative results

5.1	Introduction	155
5.2	Demographic results	155
5.3	Correlation matrices	166
5.4	Question-by-question results	168
5.5	Variation of results based on demographic variables	182
5.6	Conclusion	219

Chapter Six - Qualitative results

6.1	Introduction	220
6.2	The setting of the scene	220
6.3	Emerging themes for question one	222
6.4	Emerging themes for question two	224
6.5	Emerging themes for question three	226
6.6	Emerging themes for question four	227
6.7	Emerging themes for question five	230
6.8	Emerging themes for question six	232
6.9	Application of institutional theory	234
6.10	Summary	236

Chapter Seven - Conclusion

7.1	Introduction and personal reflections	238
7.2	Summary of quantitative results	238
7.3	Summary of additional qualitative results (beyond the quantitative)	241
7.4	Concluding remarks	241
7.5	Contributions to knowledge	243
7.6	Limitations	244
7.7	Recommendations for change	245
7.8	Suggestions for further research	246

References	248
-------------------	-----

Appendices	258
-------------------	-----

List of tables

Table 3.1 - The regulation-radical change dimension	60
Table 3.2 - Three pillars of institutions: a schematic of the theory	77
Table 3.3 – Names of surveyed organizations	84
Table 3.4 - The distribution of questionnaire forms	85
Table 3.5 - Details of interviewees	91
Table 5.1 - Gender distribution	155
Table 5.2 - Age distribution of the sample	157
Table 5.3 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of job title	159
Table 5.4 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of experience	160
Table 5.5 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of place of education	162
Table 5.6 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of academic qualifications	163
Table 5.7 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of training courses attended	165
Table 5.8-(A-C) - Correlation matrices	166
Table 5.9 - The frequency, percentage, and any square measure of the responses of the study sample indicating the extent of Libyan professionals' awareness of IFRS	168
Table 5.10 – Potential positive impact of IFRS on Libyan financial reports	169
Table 5.11 - Factors expected to affect the process of applying these standards in Libya	171
Table 5.12 – Potential impacts of IFRS on financial reporting	174
Table 5.13- Nature of the effects of IFRS adoption	174
Table 5.14 – Negative effects of adoption	175
Table 5.15 – Urgent need to adopt the IFRS, or otherwise	176
Table 5.16 – Concerns of user groups	177
Table 5.17 - Necessary modifications for the IFRS	178
Table 5.18 - Perceptions of IFRS adoption	179
Table 5.19 – Implications of future adoption	180
Table 5.20 – Factors to consider	181
Table 5.21 - Arithmetic mean and T-test values for answers attributed to gender	183
Table 5.22-A-C - Arithmetic mean and F-test value for answers between search variables attributed to age	185
Table 5.23-A-C - Arithmetic mean and F-test value for answers between search variables attributed to Position	192
Table 5.24-A-C - Arithmetic mean and F-test value for answers between search variables attributed to professional experience	197
Table 5.25-A-C - Arithmetic mean and F-test value for answers between search variables attributed to place of education	202
Table 5.26-A-C - Arithmetic mean and F-test value for answers between search variables attributed to qualifications	207
Table 5.27-A-C - Arithmetic mean and F-test value for answers between search variables attributed to accounting training and courses	210
Table 5.28-A-C - Arithmetic mean and T-test value for answers between search variables attributed to variations between two samples	218

List of figures

Figure 2.1 - Advantages and disadvantages of global standards	50
Figure 3.1 - Understanding the nature of social science from two broad oppositional perspectives	56
Figure 3.2 - The subjective–objective dichotomy for analysing assumptions about the nature of social science	59
Figure 3.3 - Four paradigms of analysis in social theory	61
Figure 3.4 - Alternative paradigms of analysis in social theory	70
Figure 3.5 - Dimensions on the choice process for empirical research	72
Figure 4.1 - Methods of harmonization	101
Figure 4.2 - The possible options for Islamic Accounting	109
Figure 5.1 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of gender	156
Figure 5.2 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of age	157
Figure 5.3 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of the job title	159
Figure 5.4 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of experience	160
Figure 5.5 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of place of education	162
Figure 5.6 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of academic qualifications	164
Figure 5.7 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of training courses	165
Figure 6.1 – Emerging themes for question one	222
Figure 6.2 – Emerging themes for question two	224
Figure 6.3 – Emerging themes for question three	226
Figure 6.4 – Emerging themes for question four	227
Figure 6.5 – Emerging themes for question five	230
Figure 6.6 – Emerging themes for question six	232

Acknowledgments

First, I thank God for helping me to complete this work and the thesis and giving me the strength to overcome the many problems on the way.

This thesis is dedicated to the memory of my late parents, Mabruk and Sasiyah, who supported me all throughout my life and to whom I am always grateful for their love and understanding. I am disappointed that they cannot see my achievement. I also want to thank my friend, Dr Matough Ali Issa, who passed away on 12 April 2021, for his kind support.

I would like to thank the many people who supported me throughout this PhD journey: friends, family, fellow students and teachers, although there is no space to name them all. Most importantly, I thank my first supervisor and Director of Studies, Dr Kieran James, and my second supervisor, Dr Abeer Hassan, not only for their wise and useful academic guidance, but also for their understanding and encouragement at difficult times. Dr James was always available to work with me on this project and most key ideas and points we discussed together as part of an active partnership. I thank Dr James and Dr Hassan for advising me to distribute the survey again in 2018 and do interviews. I would also like to thank my long-time proof-reader, Jenifer Spencer, for personal support and encouragement as well as language advice. I also thank Dr Hamdi Alkhazraji for advice on statistics and Dr Said Abdo for additional proof-reading. I also want to thank Professor Sevic Zeljko for working in collaboration with me in developing the original ideas for this thesis topic.

Abstract

The major aim of this research is to examine and evaluate the possibilities for the future implementation of the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in Libya. The data consists of 306 survey responses to an identical questionnaire distributed in 2015 and 2018 and 11 interview transcripts. The key quantitative results are: (a) The majority of the sample believes they had sufficient awareness and knowledge of the IFRS for preparing financial reports; (b) The majority believed that IFRS will have a positive impact on financial reports (c) The respondents thought that the two factors which will most significantly affect implementation in Libya are instability of government (61%) and corruption (59%); (d) After the first two factors, there is a significant drop until we reach the third most significant factor, 'language barriers,' which was selected by 44%, followed by 'low level of education' and 'political factors'; (e) Most respondents did not believe that there was an urgent need to adopt IFRS (181 or 59% compared to 125 or 41%); (f) A higher percentage of women than men were optimistic about the ability of government regulations and training courses, respectively, to assist in the implementation of IFRS; and (i) Survey respondents were more concerned about the negative effects of political instability on IFRS implementation in 2018 than they were in 2015. A significantly lower percentage of respondents in 2018 felt that users perceive that it was necessary to adopt IFRS. One reason for this extremely important result could be that by 2018 people felt that it was more urgent to improve the domestic political stability in Libya rather than worry about accounting issues. My qualitative results highlight the widely-held viewpoint that IFRS standards which do not conform to Islamic requirements can be excluded from the adopted package. Based on Institutional Theory as the underlying framework of the research, I find that stakeholders of IFRS, such as corporations, investors, policy-makers, and national regulators, can in the future take advantage of the normative pressures for the adoption and implementation of IFRS in Libya. I suggest that stakeholders encourage and support more training of appropriate accounting specialists in the application of IFRS in Libya. Accordingly, I recommend that accounting and financial management instructors concentrate on increasing programmes that integrate the IFRS into the content of accounting curricula at all levels of Libyan education.

Keywords *accounting standards; culture; harmonization of accounting standards; International Financial Reporting Standards; IFRS implementation; Islamic accounting; Libya; Libyan politics; politics of accounting standard-setting*

Title: the possible future implementation of the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in Libya

Chapter One - Introduction

1.1 General introduction

The recent history of Libya has been marked by the collapse of institutions and the political and social instability brought about by the never-ending quest of the Western powers to bring their version of democracy to the Middle East and beyond. My focus here is on the possible future implementation of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), but it is clear that this is of secondary importance to the rebuilding of social stability, as some of my survey respondents confirmed. My qualitative results, within an overall mixed-methods approach, are highlighted by the viewpoint in Libya that IFRS standards which cannot be adapted to conform to Islamic requirements can be excluded from the adopted package.

My 306 survey responses are taken from four government-owned financial organizations. I find that younger accountants are more enthusiastic about IFRS adoption than their older counterparts and, as expected, academics and Western-educated auditors and accountants are more likely to support IFRS adoption and believe that it is demanded by users. I gave out identical surveys to the same four organizations in 2015 and 2018. Respondents were more concerned about the impact of political instability on IFRS implementation in 2018, than in 2015. This crucial key finding supports my view that accounting developments can rarely be evaluated outside of their political, social, and economic contexts, and this is especially true for the developing and Arab worlds. With an election planned for a nationwide government on 24th December 2021, I hope that this will be the beginning of a journey towards increased political and social stability for Libya. If IFRS implementation is to succeed, it is vital that there is a large enough base of competent qualified accounting and finance professionals within the country. Furthermore, it is clear that accounting education must respond in a suitable way to the demands of a new and complex accounting regime.

1.2 Background –Accounting and auditing in Libya (history)

It is apparent that many factors have affected the development of accounting systems and accounting operations in developing countries. These factors might be divided into external

factors (the impacts of colonialism, globalization, and MNCs) and internal factors (local laws, taxation, accounting education systems, accounting as a profession, and a host of other political, cultural, and economical factors). Arab countries in general and Libya, in particular, encountered similar factors, which duly impacted the development of the accounting profession during the pre-and post-independence eras. Many developing countries' accounting programmes (including that of Libya) have been influenced by the accounting programmes of the developed imperialist countries such as the UK, USA and Australia (Awayiga, Onumah & Tsamenyi 2010; Yapa, Jacobs & Hout 2010). Understanding accountants' future developmental requirements necessitates an acquaintance with the history of accounting, which can facilitate an understanding of the present and likely future of the accounting profession (Carnegie & Napier 1996). Thus, an examination of the development, challenges, and problems of accounting in developed countries can help in studying accounting development in a particular developing country such as Libya.

In Libya, the practice of accounting/auditing began in the 1950s, with Law Number 31 in 1955 regarding the establishment by the state of a Department of Accounting. The discovery of oil was an important economic event which attracted major investment in the early-1960s. The accounting and auditing offices were directed by foreigners, because qualified Libyan nationals were very thin on the ground at that time (Abozied 2005). Since the Libyan revolution in 1969, the nomination of auditors has been assigned to the Ministry of the Treasury. There have been endeavours to organize accounting and auditing, in addition to legal legislation. Law Number 116 (1973), relating to the accounting and auditing profession led to the first Syndicate Council being formed in 1975 (Beitalmal 1990; Khalifa 1998).

Later, Law Number 79 for the year 1975 was passed, regarding the Department of Accounts, for auditing the public establishments and corporations in addition to public sector companies. However, Abozied (2005) notes that the scope of this law was limited to organizing the administrative and legal points or developing the accounting and auditing professions in Libya. Business experts have argued that several further steps might be taken as valuable efforts to aid implementation of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), and for the evolution of the accounting profession in Libya. These include: (a) implementing adequate professional education and training; (b) strengthening the professional accountancy body, the Libyan Accountants and Auditors Association (LAAA);

and (c) reviewing the consistency of existing laws and the regulatory framework of accounting (Laga 2012).

In the development of Libyan accounting after independence, external auditing was the main driving force behind the professionalization of accounting and its development. Other key factors were international assistance from the United Nations and the arrival of international companies to work in the Libyan market. However, the newly-legislated laws and regulations following independence and the newly implemented educational and professional accounting systems also exerted an internal (Libyan) influence on accounting.

Abozied (2005) perceived a pressing need to evaluate the external factors and their effects on accounting via a historical audit of the political and economic conditions which led to the development of Libyan accounting. He also studied internal factors, via a chronological historical review of relevant aspects of law, such as taxation and commercial law, and the establishment of professional accounting and accounting education in Libya. After examining accounting standards in Libya, he concluded that the local accounting system was mainly imported from developed imperialist countries such as the UK and USA. Moreover, there is no evidence of any modification of these systems to response to the Libyan environment. British and American accounting systems were identified as being directed towards external auditing and foreign financial reports; and this can be seen in the case of Libya (Beitalmal 1990; Khalifa 1998). There were no local accounting principles or auditing standards, nor was there a Code of Conduct for accountants. Since most of the companies working in Libyan markets were domestic companies, they were supposed to achieve economic and social goals, and contribute to the overall development rate, so it was pivotal to establish effective accounting systems to assess their performance. However, there was a lack of quality accounting information available from these companies.

Zakari (2014) studied the opinions of Libyan accounting lecturers, auditors and accountants about perceived obstacles to the adoption of International Financial Reporting (IFRS) in Libya, from a strongly pro-IFRS position. His sole research technique was a questionnaire. A major weakness of the study was the small sample size - only 29 respondents in total. Responses were also highly skewed towards the opinions of lecturers, who made up 75.1% of respondents (22 out of 29), as compared to only 3 auditors (10.3%) and 4 accountants (13.8%). Respondents were asked to rate each obstacle on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging

from SA to SD. The most serious perceived obstacles, as ranked by respondents, were, in order: (a) weakness of professional accountancy body (mean = 4.28; standard deviation = .841); (b) inconsistency of existing laws and regulatory frameworks of accounting in Libya with recent development of accounting profession (3.28, 1.099); (c) lack of an independent oversight body to monitor and enforce accounting and auditing standards and codes. (3.62, .979); (d) inadequate knowledge and lack of technical skills of Libyan professional accountants (3.59, 1.211); and (e) weakness of Libyan accounting education (3.55, 1.183). My results, based on a much larger and more diverse set of respondents, are broadly similar. However, instability of government and corruption are ranked highest in my study, suggesting concern about the increased political instability in Libya after 2014 and especially around 2018. Moreover, in my study, translation issues are ranked higher and general accounting education issues are ranked lower. Different terms and wording within terms also explains why my set of results is somewhat different from those obtained by Zakaria. Notably, he did not include an option relating to Islamic religion and culture.

Masoud (2014) studied the literature on IFRS adoption in various European Union countries and then attempted to draw out lessons and implications for Libya from these experiences. However, he collected no primary data in the form of interviews or questionnaires. Nevertheless, despite these limitations, the lessons drawn from Masoud's study were still useful to me in designing my research, survey and interview questions. Masoud (2014, p. 132) argues that the major obstacles that Libya will encounter in IFRS adoption will include: 'lack of technical skills, training and inadequate knowledge of Libyan professional accounting, the difficulty to develop its existing high-quality accounting systems, amongst disclosure reports, and a regulatory framework to cope with economic and social development, and training of effective accounting'. These factors were also cited as relevant by my survey respondents. Masoud recommends improvement in education and training amongst accountants and stock-market experts. He also agrees with my assessment that lack of primary data is a limitation of his work. My use of my own survey and interview data follows Masoud's proposed research agenda which calls for a move beyond secondary data. He concludes that whether IFRS actually does improve accounting quality and increase economic growth are still unproven assertions for Libya, and even more generally.

1.3 Aim, objectives and research questions of the study

The major aim of the research is to examine and evaluate the possibilities for the future implementation of the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in Libya. To achieve the research aim, I set the following four research objectives:

- (1) Examine and evaluate perceptions about the potential relevance and usefulness of IFRS in developing countries, specifically using Libya as a case study.
- (2) Explore the theories and common practices of accounting in Libya.
- (3) Determine the factors that may affect the implementation of IFRS and the extent to which accountants and auditors might be willing to assist in the implementation of IFRS.
- (4) Determine whether users demand IFRS-based financial statements and whether the technical and personnel base exists to competently supply these statements.

In this study, I attempt to address and satisfactorily answer the following eight (8) research questions:

(RQ1) Using Libya as a case study, what perceptions exist among Libyan accounting professionals about the suitability and usefulness of the IFRS in Libya?

(RQ2) What are presently the main theories and practices used in Libyan accounting?

(RQ3) What factors do Libyan accounting professionals view as the most vital challenges for successful IFRS implementation?

(RQ4) Do users demand IFRS-compatible financial statements be produced for all companies within the Libyan environment?

(RQ5) Does the technical base of expertise exist in Libya at present to successfully implement the IFRS standards at both the organizational and whole-of-society levels?

(RQ6) Are there any Islamic religious factors that will make some or all of the IFRS unsuitable for Libya and what solutions exist for this issue?

(RQ7) What approaches exist for translation of IFRS standards from English to Arabic and does the expertise exist in the country to allow for this to happen?

(RQ8) How did users' perceptions change between 2015 and 2018 about the relative significance of each one of the challenges to implementation?

1.4 Questions for interviewees

(Q1) Based on respondents' personal experience, and with regard to Libyan society and its accounting systems, do they think there is an urgent need to adopt such standards in the Libyan capital market and why?

(Q2) According to respondents' personal knowledge and understanding of Libyan reality and the political changes since 2011, what might be the challenges to the adoption and application of IFRS?

(Q3) In the organization/institution where the respondents work, to what extent do they think that their colleagues may really intend to adopt these standards and what are the reasons for their attitudes?

(Q4) Do respondents think that there are any aspects of Islamic culture that will affect the process of introducing these standards to Libya?

(Q5) IFRS are issued in English but their application in Libya requires Arabic translation. Do respondents think that after the required translation it will have the same intended meaning as in the original language?

(Q6) What are respondents' opinions on the operations and procedures required for preparing financial statements in Libya and how do the users perceive these operations and procedures?

1.5 Summary of quantitative results

(a) Age and years of experience of survey respondents are significantly positively correlated with each other at 1% level.

(b) There is no correlation between age and qualification of respondents, where highest qualification is placed lowest on the list for that variable. This would suggest that some younger people (including academics) are pursuing higher degrees.

(c) There is no significant correlation between qualification and years of experience.

(d) The majority of the sample believed they have sufficient awareness and knowledge of the IFRS for preparing financial reports (Q2.1).

(e) The majority believed that IFRS will have a positive impact on financial reports (Q2.1.1.1).

(f) The majority believed that IFRS plays an important role in improving the quality of financial reports (Q2.2).

(g) Nearly all respondents would be willing to apply the IFRS standards (Q2.2).

(h) Most respondents believe that the Libyan context is not suitable for these standards (although 40% dispute this conclusion) (Q2.2.1).

(i) The results overwhelmingly suggest that close to all respondents (293 or 96%) believe that using IFRS will have a positive impact in Libya (Q3.1). Therefore, the *concept* of IFRS is very widely supported in Libya.

(j) The respondents thought that the two factors which will most significantly affect implementation are instability of government (62%) and corruption (59%). These results support my statements made in the opening section of this chapter.

(k) After the first two factors, there is a significant drop until we reach the third most significant factor, 'language barriers,' which was selected by 44%. After that, in order, we have 'low level of education' and 'political factors'. The accounting profession cannot right the ship by itself because it needs to wait for political stability.

(l) An overwhelming majority (298 or 97%) believed that the IFRS will have potential impact on financial reports (Q3.1).

(m) Most respondents did not believe that there is an urgent need to adopt IFRS (181 or 59% compared to 125 or 41%). (Q4.1). This suggests a very careful attitude, probably because respondents are aware of the current contextual problems within the country.

(n) Users were more concerned with poor quality reporting and low accountability in the public sector as compared to in the private sector.

(o) A clear majority (243 or 79%) perceived that IFRS will improve the quality of financial reporting, while only 63 people (21%) disagree. One conclusion is fairly clear - members of the accounting profession in Libya believed that IFRS-based accounting standards are of a higher quality than the accounting standards or policies used at present.

(p) The respondents believed that each one of the three factors listed individually and separately in Q5.2 to Q5.4 'government regulation,' international guidelines,' and 'training courses' will have a positive impact on IFRS implementation. The percentages of Yes responses ranged from 84% (government regulations) to 98% (training courses).

(q) A higher percentage of women than men were optimistic about the ability of both government regulations and training courses to assist in the implementation of IFRS in Libya. Women appear to be less cynical and more willing to learn from diverse sources than men. Being able to statistically separate out women's and younger people views from the rest is a clear highlight of this empirical work.

(r) Younger people were more positive than older people that IFRS will have potential advantages for financial reporting in Libya. The optimism and energy of these

young people may well prove to be a driving force for change in future years. The overseas, Western education received by many younger respondents clearly was a considerable influence on their worldviews.

(s) Younger accountants were more likely than older accountants to believe that there is a necessity felt by users to adopt the IFRS.

(t) Older accountants were more likely than younger accountants to perceive that the main accounting actors will view IFRS introduction pessimistically.

(u) Younger accountants were marginally more optimistic about the potential of international guidelines to assist in IFRS implementation.

(v) Academics had the highest knowledge of IFRS (and perhaps the highest self-confidence about their own knowledge). Auditors had experience of a much wider range of companies and sectors than do staff accountants, and hence it is expected that their IFRS knowledge will be better.

(w) Senior accountants and auditors, being more global in outlook, were the most optimistic about the proposition that IFRS adoption will have advantages for financial reporting in Libya.

(x) Academics generally perceived that users demand IFRS. Auditors had knowledge about IFRS, but many auditors did not perceive that users demand it. Auditors' opinions may reflect general concerns about the current high level of political instability in Libya. Academics' views seemed to be a function of their Western education and global networks.

(y) More experienced people, who are older on average, perceived that users have less necessity for IFRS adoption. Older people with more experience may have least confidence in their own ability to master IFRS and may be projecting this on to users (consciously or unconsciously). They may be nervous about wholesale change.

(z) The least experienced accountants, followed by the most experienced, thought that the main actors will respond optimistically to IFRS adoption. Those in the middle categories thought that actors will respond pessimistically.

(aa) The respondents with fewer years of working experience generally perceived that IFRS adoption will aid capital markets. The people with less experience have a more global outlook and are not confining their attention to the domestic situation.

(bb) Respondents educated in Libya were less satisfied with their IFRS knowledge than those educated in either UK or USA. The Libyan lecturers may have less knowledge themselves and be poorer in teaching the material, which impacts negatively upon their own

students. They may have both poorer actual knowledge and lower self-confidence about their current knowledge. By contrast, having a British education may assist people in understanding the historical, economic, social, and political context behind the IFRS.

(cc) On average, the higher the person's education level, the more self-confident she/he was about her/his own perceived knowledge of IFRS. This is self-explanatory.

(dd) Survey respondents were more concerned about the negative effects of political instability on IFRS implementation in 2018 than they were in 2015. A lower percentage of people in 2018 felt that users perceive that it is necessary to adopt IFRS. One reason for this extremely important result could be that by 2018 people felt that it was more urgent to improve the domestic political stability in Libya than worry about accounting issues.

1.6 Summary of additional qualitative results (beyond the quantitative)

(a) Noteworthy among the alleged benefits of IFRS adoption were the simplicity of comparing financial data across borders; attracting investors; FDI; and unified language and concepts for accounting and financial transactions.

(b) The prominent alleged challenges were: the lack of professional expertise and knowledgeable accountants; lack of appropriate degrees and further educational development among the Libyan accountants; aspects of prevailing Islamic regulations and culture that run contrary to the Anglo-based ideology and worldview inherent in the IFRS; the incessant modifications to IFRS; the perception of users themselves regarding its implementation; and the inherent difficulties of accurately translating and interpreting the IFRS for its adoption and implementation in Libya.

(c) Interviewees in the qualitative section of the study said that it would be simple to reject some IFRS standards for Libya if they did not match with Islamic requirements.

1.7 Structure of the thesis

The next (second) chapter explores the contextual background for the thesis, and, in particular, the history of accounting standards. I begin with a history of the accounting profession in Libya up until the thesis commencement year 2011 and follow that up with discussion of the development of accounting standards in Libya. Then I look at the situation of the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) in the decade prior to this study's commencement, i.e. 2001-2012. Next, I look at the conceptual debate about principles-

versus-rules-based accounting. I then look at look at the challenges for the IASB; the advantages of global standards; the disadvantages of global standards; and a balancing of advantages and disadvantages. The chapter ends with a conclusion.

Chapter 3 is headed: Philosophical and methodological aspects. I view this chapter as one of the highlights of the thesis, along with the quantitative results chapter. I chose to position this chapter third so as to give the reader a break from the relatively dry historical and country-by-country synopses contained in Chapters 2 and 4. In Chapter 3, I first outline philosophical theories and options about research methods before describing, explaining, and justifying the actual methods used in the present thesis. Within the philosophical part of the chapter, I begin by looking at research perspective and research paradigms. I then introduce Burrell and Morgan's (1979) model of research paradigms, followed by some criticisms of their model. Next, I explore alternative approaches to mainstream accounting research, drawing on the writings of Chua (1986) and Laughlin (1995). The order in which the authors are presented here follows, on purpose, the historical order in which their writings first appeared. Then, I draw these arguments together to present my choice of theoretical framework, i.e. institutional theory. My choice of this theory reflects my own preferences, as well as being a personal response to (some of) the ideas put forward in the philosophical discussion section.

Choice of theory involves deciding on a view about the nature of the world (ontology) and what constitutes knowledge, either past or present, and how it relates to the current focus of investigation. According to Laughlin (1995), the theory dimension relates to the level of prior theorizing and prior theories that can legitimately be brought to bear in the research investigation. This point links to ontological assumptions about the nature of the world under investigation and whether researchers view this through previous theoretical endeavours. High levels of prior theorizing are indicative of an assumed material world, which exists separately from the observers' perceptions of it (as in the critical realism perspective). In the present research, I select institutional theory as my primary framework, as (among other reasons) it has been applied in prior literature on accounting change.

Why did I select institutional theory? Institutional theory focuses on the deeper and most resilient aspects of social structure. It considers the processes by which structures, including schemes, rules, norms, and routines, become established as authoritative guidelines for social behaviour (Scott 2004). Different components of institutional theory explain how these

elements are created, diffused, adopted, and adapted over space and time; and how they fall into decline and disuse. Although the ostensible idea is stability and order in social life, students of institutions must attend not only to consensus and conformity but to conflict and change in social structures (Scott 2004).

I made a conscious decision to place philosophical section first and methodological section second, within Chapter 3, so as to reflect my prior belief that the latter should build upon the former and put its ideas into action. Then, in the methodology section, I first discuss, in order, the following concepts: research method - timing; descriptive-versus-explanatory; study approach; and, in relation to my questionnaires, study and sample context; and sampling. I explain how the identical questionnaire was given out in 2015, and again in 2018, which introduces a crucial and interesting longitudinal aspect to the results. Lastly, in the interests of fairness and honesty, I outline some limitations of questionnaires. Then, I go on to look at interviews as a research method, followed by, in order, types of interviews; my chosen type of interview technique (i.e. semi-structured); and, lastly, shortcomings of interviews. The semi-structured section explains my approach to the interviews, as well as details about how they were conducted. That section also includes details about my choices and actions in regards to the Arabic-to-English translation process. As is conventional in academic writing, a final section, before the conclusion, explores ethical considerations and how they were handled and mitigated in the present project.

Chapter 4 is divided into three parts, Part A, Part B, and Part C. All three parts contain Literature Review content, but I felt that the chapter was too long and should be split into three parts, for the convenience of the reader. I decided *not* to spread the content across three actual chapters, as all parts are intrinsically related, although they cover different broad topic areas. Chapter 4 Part A deals with the financial statement harmonization process. Harmonization is a general term, but it is used nearly always to explain harmonization towards IFRS by initially non-conforming regimes. As usual, my sections are presented in the order of general content moving towards more specific content. After an introduction to harmonization, I look at *de jure* and *de facto* harmonization, and prior qualitative and quantitative research on these topics. After this, I consider the topic of challenges to IFRS harmonization. I then look at various possible approaches to the global harmonization process: adoption of IFRS; standard-by-standard (this subsection is indicative rather than complete): optional harmonization of IFRS, and not fully converged IFRS harmonization.

Each country must choose its own preferred approach out of these four. Because I adopt the writing approach of moving from general to specific, the last key section here, before the Conclusion, looks at the issue of most direct relevance to my study - the harmonization of Islamic Accounting with IFRS. These issues are then explored further in my qualitative results chapter (among other places).

Chapter 4 Part B begins with an introduction, which distinguishes between developed and emerging economies, a distinction which I continue to rely upon and utilize for the rest of the thesis. Here I study how harmonization has occurred in practice for implementing countries and look for commonalities and differences. In order, I study the following countries as typical, important and/or interesting case studies: Belgium, Denmark, Germany, Greece, Poland, and the USA. Developed countries are important to look at due to their experience and expertise. By contrast, emerging countries are important to look at because their situations will be closer to that of Libya. I chose to look at the following emerging countries: Romania, Egypt, Algeria, Tunisia, and Oman. Romania is chosen because it is an example of an extremely enthusiastic ‘gung-ho’ adopter, and a post-communist country (these two factors are almost certainly positively correlated); while the other four countries are chosen because they are Arabic countries, which share common factors such as religion, language, and culture. Next, I look at these five countries again, but in terms of the impact IFRS adoption has on reported financial performance. I then summarize the findings about IFRS adoption in developed and emerging countries.

All of this discussion leads up to the crucial Chapter 4 Part C. This chapter part covers the context of Libya; the relevance of IFRS to Libya, and the potential impediments to IFRS implementation in Libya. Because of a relative lack of accounting research on Libya, this chapter part is more speculative than the preceding ones. It leads directly on to the presentation and explanation of the study’s quantitative results in Chapter 5.

The main focus for readers of this thesis should be the quantitative results and, for that reason, I presents these findings first. I begin by presenting the demographic results section, which summarizes the demographic characteristics of the survey respondents. After this, I discuss all of the statistically significant survey results on a question-by-question basis. Then I explain how the results vary significantly (or not) based on the various demographic

characteristics. Importantly, I am able to advise readers about how the results vary systematically based on gender and age-bracket.

Chapter 6 presents qualitative results concerning the perceived paybacks and challenges of adoption and implementation of IFRS in a developing country. The interviews were conducted with senior managers from Libya, expert in IFRS; the aim is to develop a conceptual framework for the perceived benefits and challenges that come with IFRS adoption and implementation in Libya. This chapter reports the qualitative results from these interviews and identifies a number of apparent benefits and challenges likely to accompany the adoption of and implementation of IFRS. These results build upon, and must be interpreted within the context of, the quantitative results as presented in Chapter 5.

Noteworthy among the alleged benefits were the simplicity of comparing financial data across borders; attracting investors; FDI; and unified language and concepts for accounting and financial transactions. The prominent alleged challenges were: (1) the lack of professional expertise and knowledgeable accountants; (2) lack of appropriate degrees and further educational development among the Libyan accountants; (3) aspects of prevailing Islamic regulations and culture that run contrary to the Anglo-based ideology and worldview inherent in the IFRS; (4) the incessant modifications to IFRS; (5) the perceptions of users themselves regarding its implementation; and (6) the inherent difficulties of accurately translating and interpreting the IFRS for its adoption and implementation in Libya.

After an introduction and personal reflections section, the concluding chapter, Chapter 7, provides a summary of the main quantitative and qualitative results, followed by a section on contribution to knowledge, a section on limitations, a section on policy recommendations, and a final section containing suggestions for further research.

Chapter Two - Background: the history of global accounting standards

2.1 Introduction

For several decades, there have been concerted efforts to reconcile the differences between accounting standards among the various countries to facilitate international trade and enhance the comparability, transparency, reliability and quality of financial reporting globally (Madawaki 2012). The rapid globalization of capital markets and the sophistication of most business transactions, in recent years, have made it even more imperative to reduce the diversity of accounting practices across these countries, which emanates from the differences in their environmental, social, economic, legal, political, and historical contexts. The International Accounting Standards Committee (IASC) was founded in 1973 by a group of professional accounting practitioners charged with the responsibility to formulate uniform and global accounting standards aimed at minimizing the discrepancies in global accounting principles and reporting practices (Madawaki 2012). Over two decades, the IASC vigorously pursued the standardization of accounting principles and convergence of countries' diverse accounting standards into a global set of accepted standards (Carlson 1997).

During the existence of the IASC, a series of standards called the International Accounting Standards was published. However, after 27 years, the slow progress made by the IASC precipitated the need to restructure its activities in order to enhance its effectiveness in working towards and realizing its objectives. Consequently, the IASC was replaced by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) on 1 April 2001. Following its inception, the IASB updated the already existing International Accounting Standards and henceforth began to refer to these standards as International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS).

2.2 Introduction to Libya - historical context (up to 2011)

Libya is a country that in 2012 was emerging as a strong market-based economy and was making bold strides towards economic development (Masoud 2014). With a population of just about 6.155 million, according to World Bank statistics of 2012, Libya is strategically situated in the Middle East-North African economic zone. Aided by the discovery of abundant oil-and-gas assets, the Libyan economy saw an increase in its Gross National per

capita income to \$16,800, according to 2009 statistics of the World Bank. In fact, this global economic body placed the Libyan economy at 54th among the world economies with a GDP growth rate of 2.1 percent annually. With conditions stabilizing somewhat, the Central Bank of Libya announced the annual growth of Libyan economy at 18% in 2013 while the International Monetary Fund expected the growth to further increase to the region of 20% p.a. in the coming years. However, these figures were subject to the political stability in the country (Masoud 2014). Major political instability began in 2011 with the coming of the Arab Spring to Libya and the removal of the long-serving leader Colonel Gaddafi.

All the bodies mentioned above designated Libya as an emerging economy prior to the Arab Spring (World Bank 2013). The situation was improved by the stock-market review and reconstruction efforts that were undertaken in June 2006. Libyan natural resources, specifically oil and natural gas, were exploited to such a degree that the incomes from these industries assisted in the development of a manufacturing base and fundamental development of the Libyan economy. There was a speeding-up of industrial growth, through the theoretical growth stages, as compared to most developed countries, and in moving into the global capital market arena. This also created opportunities for the Libyan economy to become part of the global economic market (Masoud 2014).

Libya, which gained independence from Italy in 1951, is a small country in terms of demography but a country with a large surface area (1,759,540km² or 18th in the world) (CIA World Fact Book 2021). At the time of independence, the country did not have much economic potential. Until 1958, its economy was based on agriculture and even that was not sufficient to be called a strong economy. However, the discovery of large oil and natural gas reserves, east of the Gulf of Sidra and their subsequent production and export since 1959, helped increase the revenues of the country (Bait-El-Mal *et al.* 1973; Kilani 1988). In the next two decades, and up until 1981, the country exported significant quantities of oil. The oil industry in the country experienced a marked change with the nationalization of the foreign oil companies that were operating in the country. This resulted in significant income to the government from oil exports. In September 1973, Libya issued a 16-article law nationalizing 51% of the assets of all remaining oil companies operating in Libya. The financial receipts of Libya increased during this period, and there was also a dramatic increase in the price of petroleum products. Since that time, the economy of Libya has been intricately entwined with the rise and fall of global oil prices. During the period when Gaddafi was at the helm of the

country, he used much of the revenue generated from the oil exports to build the army and the country's infrastructure, such as improvement of the cities and the modernization of the transportation system (Abusneina 1992). This resulted in the mass migration of Libyans from the rural areas towards the cities and, subsequently, heightened levels of unemployment. This forced the government to spend money on agriculture to attract the rural people back to the villages from the cities, which also made farming a more attractive profession. By 2013, 95% of the earnings of the country's exports were from oil exports, and these accounted for one-fourth of GDP (Bayoud 2013).

The oil-boom in the country resulted in fantastic rates of growth for the economy until the early 1980s. However, it was then that the country faced economic sanctions from the international community, and its oil exports were seriously hit. The global oil prices also fell drastically at this time. This saw the GDP *per capita* shrink by more than 40% in the middle- and late-1980s. This sharp fall in the real GDP of the country meant that the government did not have enough cash in hand. This severely affected the level of imports and government spending in the social sector. The reduction of imported material in the Libyan market during that time compounded the debt repayment problems for the country. All of these factors caused the standard of living of the country to decline (Edwik 2007). The depleting government funds also forced a rethink of its economic policy and spending habits, and more strictness in government spending was imposed. However, successive governments in the country took steps to integrate with the global community and slowly the sanctions were lifted. This helped to arrest the slide in the GDP and, in the 1990s the slide was just 3.2%, down from 40% in the 1980s. By the early-2000s, the country had one of the highest GDPs in Africa (Edwik 2007). In the subsequent years, industrial production in Libya increased. The presence of manufacturing industries, including refined petroleum, petrochemicals, liquefied natural gas (LNG), steel and aluminium, textiles, and food processing, meant that the annual earnings of the country from exports surpassed the cost of imports, which were primarily made up of food products and grains (Faraj & Essa 2014).

In earlier years, the lack of opportunity to accumulate personal wealth by the people of the country dissuaded the development of a business class. However, this trend saw some changes during the late-1990s and the early-2000s, when the country saw the emergence of private companies. This was due to falling oil prices in the world and the resultant financial crisis in the country in the late-1980s and early-1990s. This was further aided by liberalizing

some norms for business for the private sector and the privatization of a number of public sector companies (Bayoud 2013).

2.2.1 History of the accounting profession in Libya

The accounting profession in Libya is not well developed, even as it remains influenced by the UK and the US accounting principles. Although international colonialism and international business exerted a significant influence on the accounting profession in Libya for decades (Masoud 2014), it was only after the country's economic policy changed to a centrally-planned economy that the accounting profession slowly began to take shape. In the absence of a standardized code for accounting, the international companies which were active in Libya prepared their accounts in the forms that they wanted and this process influenced the development of accounting practice in Libya (Bakar & Russell 2003).

Since the 1950s, the profession of accounting in Libya has been influenced by the education system in the country and the academics who taught accounting exerted considerable influence on the profession. The rapid change in the social, economic, political and legal environment in the country from the 1950s onwards shaped the way accounting was administered. Accounting became popular as an academic stream in Libya in 1957, with the establishment of the Economic and Commerce faculty at Garyounis University. The UK- and US-based professional accounting bodies, and the universities in these countries, were the ones who trained accountants and developed accounting education (Kilani 1988, p. 175). The US system of accounting particularly had a greater influence on Libyan students in the 1970s, as many of them undertook their studies at American universities. This was because the country had a good relationship with the US at this point in time (Shareia & Irvine 2008).

The Libyan Accountants and Auditors Association (hereafter LAAA), a relatively young professional organization of accountants, compared to Western associations in the same profession, was formed in 1973. The accounting profession became formally organized when the Libyan administration adopted the Certified Public Accountant (CPA) system approximately 40 years ago through the Law No. 116 of 1973.. The role of the LAAA has primarily been to follow and enforce the government regulatory requirements with respect to the accounting profession and practice. However, the organization has not been able to guide the accounting system in Libya to develop and adapt to international standards. Furthermore,

it has played no role in the training or educating of professionals regarding the standards practised in the rest of the world (Faraj 2014).

In Libya, a public accountant needs to be Libyan citizen, with at least a bachelor's degree in accounting, according to Section 24 of the *Accountants Act* (1973), as well as passing the requirements mandated by the Board of Public Accountants (Shareia 2016, p. 24).

The self-regulatory approach, which allowed accountants to regulate themselves, was replaced by the Board of Public Accountants to monitor the public accounting profession. To regulate the accounting profession, Libya has adopted the statutory control approach. This means that the accounting profession in Libya is controlled by the Libyan Commercial and Financial Laws. According to law number 116 of the Accounting Profession Law of 1973, the LAAA is entrusted with the responsibility to establish and monitor the accounting standards in Libya. However, some experts maintained the view that the organization was failing to perform its functions successfully (Libya State 1974). Therefore, there is no Libyan body except the government which now regulates the accounting profession and sets the standards for the profession. This has resulted in companies being directed to manage their accounts in a way specified by the Public Control Office (Kilani 1988).

2.2.2 The development of accounting standards in Libya

The accounting profession in Libya is still relatively young and inexperienced by global standards. The prime focus of accounting in Libya under the Gaddafi government was the formulation of internal financial reports and external auditing. Accounting and auditing were mostly forced by regulation rather than determined by the wish to offer valuable information to the relevant stakeholders (Bait-El-Mal *et al.* 1973; Buzied 1998; Kilani 1988).

Libya started the gradual development of accounting over the period of 1911-51, when Libya was occupied by the Italians and British (Kilani 1988). At the time of independence in 1951, there was no national accounting profession and the larger commercial companies depended upon accounting practices in the UK and Italy. The Libyan Commercial Code (hereafter LCC), initiated in 1953, and the Libyan Income Tax Law (hereafter LITL) of 1973 necessitated businesses to formulate an annual report, comprising a revenue report and a balance sheet. Hence, the LITL impacted the accounting practice in Libya, influencing its financial reporting guidelines and quality.

The most common set of accounting practices was American GAAP. The laws and regulations, especially the tax laws, strongly influenced the preparation of financial reports by companies. These laws that influence financial reporting did not corroborate with the IFRS, and hence the financial reporting system in Libya cannot be said to parallel the IFRS system (Shamsaddeen & Essa 2014).

The discovery of oil in the 1960s produced the finances that Libya needed for development and budgeting. Moreover, after the discovery of oil, a number of American corporations increased their Foreign Direct Investment (hereafter FDI) into Libya. However, the lack of accounting principles, and regular guidelines and practices, created a hindrance for these corporations. Therefore, the American corporations applied their own accounting structures such as the American Accepted Accounting Principles (AAAPs) (Bait El-Mal *et al.* 1973). With the growth of accounting companies, and the neglect of the Libyan practice of accounting and auditing, there was an urgent need for formulating rules to run accounting and create qualified professionals to develop a common system (Shareia 2014).

As in other developing nations, Libya has its own traditional and economic issues that vary considerably from the economic influences in the industrialized nations, especially the Western nations (Bakar & Russell 2003; Kilani 1998). It should be recognized that Libyan culture has experienced exceptional influences that have affected its accounting structure, as explained above. The UK and the USA have also had an influence on Libyan accounting practices (Kilani 1988). Some time ago, Bengharbia (1989) and Selway (2000) both pointed out the cultural difficulties associated with the adoption of external accounting structures. In the same vein, it has been contended that the influences which have affected accounting development in Libya have come from global firms, particularly in the oil sector (Mahmud & Russell 2003; Saleh 2001). Hence, the dissemination of Western accounting principles in Libya has derived from two sources, namely: export firms, particularly the oil firms functioning in Libya, and the Libyan accounting education system. This has created opportunities for the IASB to promulgate its standards (Masoud 2014. p. 128), while groups also exist in Libya which are sympathetic to the IFRS.

2.3 Global impacts of the IASB and IFRS foundation during their development

Over the years, the IASB has undergone several developmental changes and restructuring which have culminated in many apparent successes for the IFRS Foundation. During this era of its development, the IASB has evolved to become the main global accounting standard-setting organization and has promulgated a set of allegedly high-quality standards. The IASB has transformed into a better co-ordinated organization, liaising with all relevant stakeholders to actualize its objectives. Furthermore, its reputation has been enhanced over the years, to a large extent because of the wide acceptance of IFRS (Allen & Ramanna 2010).

In 2002, the European Union (hereafter EU) decided to adopt the IFRS for its publicly-traded companies as part of its plans to generate a common European capital market. Subsequently, the full adoption of the IFRS by the EU, when it stipulated that publicly-traded companies (with some exceptions) should present consolidated financial statements in conformity with the IFRS (Bhattacharjee & Islam 2009), was a monumental achievement for the IASB and inspired many other countries to embrace the IFRS. In fact, almost all industrialized nations have either converged towards or adopted the IFRS. Australia adopted full IFRS from 1 January 2005, and the wave of convergence and adoption has now focused on the developing countries, with Libya also considering IFRS adoption.

The Norwalk Agreement, signed in October 2002, between the Financial Accounting Standards Board (hereafter FASB) and the IASB, was a significant step towards the joint convergence of the US Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP) and the IFRS (Hoogervorst & Seidman 2012). This agreement engendered confidence in the IASB globally and the joint convergence process has resulted in the improvement of the standards inherited from the IASC and subsequently reduced the difference between US GAAP and IFRS. Consequently, the USA appears to be moving (slowly) towards the adoption of IFRS.

Another success of the IASB that is worth mentioning is its ability to liaise or collaborate with other accounting standard-setting organizations such as the International Federation of Accountants (hereafter IFAC). The IFAC serves the public interest by establishing and promoting adherence to international standards, facilitating co-operation with member firms, and serving as a spokesperson for the international profession on relevant policy issues. It works with the FASB and other international organizations such as the United Nations

(hereafter UN), World Trade Organization (WTO), World Bank, International Monetary Fund (IMF) and many others to advance its principal objectives of promulgating the IFRS and the convergence of national accounting standards with the IFRS. Other countries with prominent capital markets that have adopted IFRS, or an accounting regime that is essentially its equivalent, include Australia, Hong Kong SAR, Singapore, South Africa and Zimbabwe (Bhattacharjee & Islam 2009). Meanwhile, other countries are working to align or harmonize their national accounting standards with the IFRS by making the necessary modifications.

2.3.1 Principles-based accounting versus rules-based accounting

The IFRS are generally principles-based, because they derive from the British tradition of accounting. Recently, there has been much debate about whether principle-based accounting is more efficient than rules-based accounting (e.g. Sargeant 2014). This debate intensified after the infamous American accounting scandals of Enron and WorldCom.

In essence, rules-based accounting comprises a list of detailed rules that must be followed when preparing financial statements (Kimble *et al.* 2010; Wustemann & Wustemann 2010). Some US-based accountants favour the prospect of using rules-based standards because the presence of such rules saves them from legal action should investors lose money after reliance upon the financial statements. Strict rules diminish the possibility of court claims. Moreover, a set of rules in place can increase accuracy and reduce the ambiguity that can lead managers to resort to aggressive reporting decisions. Although the complexity of the rules makes it hard to prepare financial statements, supporters of a rules-based approach argue that compliance with such guidance is easier, since the requirements are prescriptive and leave little room for misunderstanding. Furthermore, rules-based approaches are easier to enforce.

Principles-based accounting, such as British and Australian GAAP, is used as a conceptual basis for IFRS. A simple set of key objectives are set out to ensure good reporting. Common examples are provided as guidance and to explain the objectives. Although some rules are unavoidable, the guidelines or rules set are not meant to be used for every situation. The true-and-fair override in principles-based accounting means that rules need not be followed in those rare cases where to do so would mean that the financial statements do not present a true and fair view. The fundamental advantage of principles-based accounting is that its broad guidelines can be practical for a variety of situations (Dennis 2008; Kimble *et al.* 2010). The problem with principles-based accounting is that the lack of detailed guidelines can produce

unreliable and inconsistent information that makes comparison of one organization with another more difficult. Moreover, principles-based accounting can sometimes encourage managers to manipulate accounts to achieve desired results.

Nevertheless, a report published by the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Scotland (ICAS) (2006) stated that to take the view that rules-based accounting standards allowed the failure of Enron to develop undetected implies that rules-based accounting standards should not continue. In fact, even many proponents of rules-based accounting now believe that adoption of principles-based standards would address the problems inherent in rules-based standards. So there has been some shift, with the rules being renamed as 'guidance', reflecting a degree of ground-shifting which is indicative of the new thinking. Principles, on the other hand, have been relabelled as 'objectives', which could also limit the bounds of judgement in any one area of financial statement preparation.

To choose the best method(s) of accounting, it must be ensured that the information provided in the financial statements is relevant, reliable and comparable across reporting periods and objects. Therefore, most British-trained and -influenced accountants are more likely to be inclined towards principle-based accounting (Sargeant 2009). The report mentioned above, published by ICAS (2006), concludes that a principles-based approach to standard setting is desirable and essential to serve the needs of business and the public interest and the global convergence of accounting standards. The report, however, also points to several issues with the principle-based standard-setting approach that should not be ignored. Such issues include the need for a change in the global profession, with preparers and auditors assuming more responsibility for their judgements; the documentation of the key judgements inherent in the financial statements, and the necessity for the regulators to accept a range of judgement-based outcomes. In contrast to this, the report also highlights the unnecessary complexities that the rules-based accounting system generates and how such a method often does not lead to a true-and-fair view or fair financial presentation and gives rise to financial irregularities and engineering of information (Chanchani & Willett 2004).

An Islamic perspective may stand in between these two approaches, the rule-based and principle-based approaches. The argument behind this is that a rules-based approach cannot be completely followed, due to the fact that Islamic rules, specifically the *Shari'ah* rules

(شريعة), may clash with the rules set for accounting procedures. In contrast, the principle-based approach sets the generally accepted principle, which may be adopted in an Islamic context, but only after local modifications. Therefore, it can be argued that the accounting principles followed in an Islamic context can be a mixture of both rule-based and principle-based approaches. However, the application and implementation of these rules will still vary from country to country (Carmona & Trombetta 2008).

2.4 Challenges for the IASB

Despite the apparent success of the IASB, there are a number of challenges that it needs to address in the years ahead:

(i) Continued convergence and adoption

The IASB is dedicated to the promulgation of the IFRS, its convergence and possibly, adoption by the various countries globally. There is no doubt that the IASB has made good progress on the above issues, as is evident in the convergence and adoption of the IFRS by most developed countries. However, the IASB needs to do more public-relations work to convince many developing countries of the relevance of convergence and possible IFRS adoption. This is imperative, because many developing countries perceive convergence toward or adoption of the IFRS as a form of neo-colonialism by the Western powers that will be detrimental to their self-determination (Rodrigues & Craig 2007).

(ii) Improving the quality and implementation of the IFRS

Globalization and international trade are dynamic processes; hence, there is a tendency for financial transactions to continue to become more sophisticated. Consequently, the IASB must continue to improve the quality of its standards and ensure their relevance to the rapidly-changing world. For instance, the Global Financial Crisis (hereafter GFC) of 2008-09 raised concerns about the suitability of the IFRS for financial reporting across the world (Mala & Chand 2012). For example, following the GFC, the IASB faced pressure from various financial institutions, regulators, policy-makers and finance ministers to review its rules on Fair Value Accounting (FVA). Therefore, based on lessons learned from the GFC, the IASB has undertaken measures to improve financial reporting requirements, which should subsequently strengthen the global position of IFRS.

(iii) Need for better and fair representation

It is worth noting that, despite the positive relationship between the IASB and the Middle Eastern countries, the latter still do not have any role or presence or special consideration as a specific region within the IASB's agenda, nor has there been engagement during a standard-setting process. The regional representatives were, as at 2009, mainly from the EU, North America, Japan, Australia and South Africa (Abd El Razik 2009). Abd El Razik therefore points out that the Middle Eastern countries believe that their region should be more actively consulted, while understanding and enforcing accounting standards from around the globe. According to the Chairman of the International Financial Reporting Interpretations Committee (IFRIC), Robert Garnett '*with oil revenues being directed into large investments, the region is increasingly being seen as a potential partner*' (Abd El Razik 2009, p. 1) Taking into consideration the role the Middle East plays in world politics, investments and capital markets, this shows the importance of adapting IFRS to the region, whilst recognizing the totally different environmental factors that must be considered by the IASB. The applicability of standards, for a particular nation, usually depends on the culture, legal system, taxation, types of business organizations and ownership, as well as the state of development of the accounting profession in that nation. Furthermore, previous studies have shown that all these factors are indeed significantly different between the Middle Eastern countries and the rest of the world (Askary 2006). Thus, if the IASB is talking about global convergence of accounting standards, it needs to understand that there are vibrant and evolving markets in other parts of the world, other than Europe and North America, which have special features which need to be understood.

Thus, for the IASB to truly establish itself as a global organization there needs to be a better and fairer representation on its committees by well-qualified people from all parts of the world. At present, the members of the various IASB sub-groupings (including the Monitoring Board; Trustees of the IFRS Foundation; IFRS Advisory Council; IFRS Interpretation Committee and the various working groups) are predominantly from the developed countries. This confirms the worrying dominance of North American and European countries in the affairs of the IASB, which wrongly portrays the organization as a tool to foster the interests of the Western World to the detriment of the developing countries (Addis 2012). The lack of adequate representation of Middle-Eastern and African countries and, to a lesser extent, Asian countries on these IASB committees suggests that the IASB falls short of the requirement of a fair and balanced global organization.

In contrast to this situation, according to Abd El Razik (2009), Middle Eastern countries are appropriately represented in many other international organizations, including the World Bank, United Nations, and the World Trade Organization. These international bodies give special attention in their periodic reports to Islam as a religion, as well as the needs and demands of its followers, not least because of the perceived current and prospective potential of these countries and regions. Yet, of the 49 members of the IFRS Advisory Council of the IASB, Middle Eastern countries were represented by only two members between 2001 and 2005. Furthermore, in 2012, Middle-Eastern countries were not represented by any members at all (Madawaki 2012). The IFRS Advisory Council still contained no Middle Eastern members as at 2021 (IFRS, 2021). It could be argued that the current trend must be reversed in order to incorporate these neglected parts of the world in the affairs of the IASB so as to enhance the reputation of the organization. Otherwise, it may fail to achieve its goals.

(iv) Lack of enforcement mechanism

The convergence toward or adoption of the IFRS is not mandatory, rather it is voluntary. Nevertheless, many financial institutions, regulators, policy-makers and researchers have strongly advocated the need for the IASB to have some form of enforcement mechanism to ensure that its standards are effectively implemented by those countries that have accepted convergence or adoption. The lack of an enforcement mechanism by the IASB, to regulate and monitor the implementation of the IFRS in those countries that have voluntarily converged, is a formidable hindrance to the aspirations of the organization. Hence, IASB must vigorously search for a way to overcome this obstacle for any hope of actualizing its objectives. Following the growing adoption of the IFRS globally, the IASB must be sensitive and vigilant to tackle any risk of possible divergence from the IFRS in those countries that have already adopted these sets of standards. Countries such as Australia have used pre-existing national enforcement bodies, but in developing countries enforcement is often weak.

(v) Governance and accountability

Although the IASB is an independent and not-for-profit organization, there is a need for the organization to be open to public scrutiny. This is even more relevant considering the fact that many countries have either converged to or adopted the IFRS and many more are considering doing the same. Hence, there is need for the IASB to develop further and to enhance the IFRS Foundation's public accountability.

2.5 Advantages and disadvantages of global standards

When considering IFRS adoption, the net value of IFRS to a country arises from two factors: firstly the value of having a shared body of accounting standards and secondly the enhanced quality of local governance institutions (Mala & Chand 2012). The then Chairman of the IASB, Sir David Tweedie, in his testimony before the Committee on Banking, Housing and Urban Affairs of the United States Senate (2004), summed up the case for international accounting standards thus:

'As the world's capital markets integrate, the logic of a single set of accounting standards is evident. A single set of international standards will enhance comparability of financial information and should make the allocation of capital across borders more efficient. The development and acceptance of international standards should also reduce compliance costs for corporations and improve consistency in audit quality' (Tweedie 2004, p. 3).

Advantages and disadvantages of the IFRS are considered next.

2.5.1 Advantages of global standards

The advantages can be considered based on four main headings: efficiency savings, improved information, facilitating international trade and assisting emerging economies.

2.5.1.1 Efficiency savings

IFRS are developed specifically for wide international use, with proponents arguing that adopting a common body of international standards leads to lower information processing and auditing costs for capital market participants (Barth 2007). A single accounting standard regime will achieve comparability, thus leading to a reduction in information-processing costs, associated with different national accounting standards, and thereby resulting in a reduction in the overall cost of capital (the annual cost of resources demanded by capital-providers). It will also reduce the information asymmetry in the market (Ramanna & Sletten 2009). Therefore, countries can expect to lower information processing and auditing costs for capital market participants (Barth 2007, 2008).

By eliminating international differences in accounting standards, and standardizing reporting formats, IFRS eliminates many of the adjustments analysts have historically made in order to make companies' financial statements more comparable internationally (Ball 2005). IFRS adoption could therefore reduce the cost to investors of processing financial information. The gain would be greatest for institutions that create large, global, standardized-format financial databases. The development and acceptance of international standards should also reduce compliance costs for corporations and improve consistency in audit quality (Tweedie 2004).

Harmonization could also lower monitoring costs for regulators, such as stock exchanges (Ampofo & Sellani 2005).

According to proponents of harmonization, IFRS adoption will offer several financial, strategic, and commercial advantages for the Multinational Corporations (MNCs) by saving on the costs of preparing different sets of financial reports when listing on foreign capital markets (Ampofo & Sellani 2005; Chand 2005; Saudagaram & Diga 1998; Tondkar *et al.* 1989). Chen *et al.* (1999) argue that harmonization will facilitate business transactions beyond national boundaries and minimize the cost of preparing two or more sets of financial statements using different accounting standards. It will eradicate the duplicative costs of national and international standards. Subsequently, it will be beneficial to poorer nations (e.g. developing countries) that cannot afford the cost of national accounting standard-setting institutions (Ampofo & Sellani 2005; Gangolly *et al.* 2002; Saudagaram & Diga 1998).

One goal of adopting IFRS and harmonizing accounting systems is to provide financial markets with high-quality information, improving their efficiency and lowering the cost of capital and increasing the possibility that companies can access capital (Guggiola 2010). The standards are intended to help to eliminate barriers to cross-border trading in securities by improving comparability, which in turn will increase market efficiency and reduce the cost of capital-raising. Reducing the cost of processing financial information and improving information will increase the efficiency with which the stock-markets operate. The increased transparency promised by IFRS. Therefore. Could increase the efficiency of contracting between firms and their managers, reduce agency costs between managers and shareholders, and enhance corporate governance. The increased transparency leads to a similar increase in the efficiency of contracting between firms and lenders (Ball 2005). The effects on efficiency of financial markets are widely claimed because the adoption of IFRS will contribute to improving the quality of the information provided to investors and analysts.

2.5.1.2 Improved information

The adoption of IFRS will lessen the possible different accounting understandings and interpretations which are a result of applying different standards, and help investors to pursue various strategies, including global investment diversification. There are several advantages that adoption of IFRS worldwide can provide for equity investors. IFRS promises more accurate, comprehensive, and timely financial statement information, as compared to the

national standards they replace for public financial reporting in all countries (Ball 2006). As a consequence, better-informed decisions in the equity markets may occur, and hence lower risk for investors. In addition, studies demonstrate that adopting IFRS increases private equity investment (Cumming & Johan 2007), foreign direct investment (Marquez-Ramos 2008; Li & Shroff 2009). Institutional investment (Florou & Pope 2009), and trading undertakings of singular stakeholders (Brüggemann *et al.* 2009).

In addition, adoption of IFRS offers the potential for reducing the complexity of financial reporting, especially for large MNCs that currently prepare many different sets of financial statements in many different forms (Flynn 2008). Companies with subsidiaries in countries that require or permit IFRS may be able to use one accounting language company-wide. Companies also may need to convert to IFRS if they are a subsidiary of a foreign company, and thus required to make use of IFRS, or if they have foreign investors. To satisfy the foreign investors' interests by using one set of financial reporting standards (and not one set in each country) is claimed to reduce confusion, as well as error and fraud and will lead to an increase in the degree of governance and trust.

However, there is no general agreement on the improvement of predictability of earnings as a consequence of IFRS adoption. Moreover, any observed reduction in earnings management may not be attributable to, or be a consequence of, IFRS adoption (Guggiola 2010).

2.5.1.3 Facilitating international trade

Adopting IFRS to lower information costs is conceptually distinct from adopting IFRS due to its network benefits. The concept of network benefits was defined by Ramanna and Sletten (2009) as the value perceived from others using IFRS. In addition, it refers to the idea that IFRS becomes more appealing as more countries adopt it. Therefore, institutional forces can contribute, in interdependent and mutually reinforcing ways, to providing a more powerful social incentive to adopt (Scott 1995).

IFRS creates a global network where countries will gradually choose to adopt IFRS to enhance their participation in global trade, investment and debt flows. The observed increase in IFRS adoption across countries can be attributed to the growing value of this IFRS 'network'. Countries where foreign trade is an important part of the economy can be expected

to be motivated to adopt IFRS. Even countries with low levels of foreign capital and trade can choose to adopt IFRS if they are expecting or wanting growth in these areas.

Such a network will also enhance trustworthiness and transparency in reported financial statements, which will subsequently attract foreign investment capital. Increased investment will promote prosperity and mitigate poverty in developing and ex-communist countries. Historically these countries suffered not from labour shortages, but from capital shortages. Ramanna and Sletten (2009) concluded that, in taking the decision to adopt IFRS, countries benefit from perceptions of a network: the benefits are lower costs of transactions for foreign financial statement users. Thus, a country may adopt IFRS even if its domestic standards are already well-suited to its domestic institutions (Ramanna & Sletten 2011). Some might point to the waste in creating national standards pre-IFRS, but they contributed to creating economic growth in that former era. There can still be net gains associated with IFRS adoption for these countries. However, they must also establish a stable political and economic infrastructure to support their own commerce (Mwaura & Nyaboga 2009).

The increasing integration of global capital markets, accessibility of foreign stocks and the rapid growth of international capital flows will continue to intensify the clamour for the harmonization of IFRS (Gangolly *et al.* 2002; Murphy 2000; Street & Shaughnessy 1998). Companies may also benefit from using IFRS if they wish to raise capital abroad to access international capital and investments (Singhal 2012). An example of this in the late-1980s relates to German companies which increasingly needed capital (Hibbard 2012). This generated an impetus by various groups led by the listed companies to adopt international accounting practices (usually American or British) as international capital markets required relevant, reliable, and comparable accounting information. Differences between financial reports consistent with the US GAAP and German standards harmed the credibility of German accounting principles in the international community and increased pressure on the German legislators. As a result, in 1988, Germany enacted the ‘alleviation law regarding raising of capital’ to improve the competitiveness of German companies. The companies listed on the stock markets prepared consolidated statements according to internationally accepted accounting standards, namely IAS or US GAAP. Since then Germany has been on a gradual transition to the full implementation of IFRS (Hibbard 2012).

2.5.1.4 Assisting emerging economies

The relative quality of local governance institutions, such as the Libyan Association of Accountants and Auditors (hereafter LAAA) in Libya, is reflected in the poor quality of the local accounting standards. These low-quality standards are thus an important determinant in the decision to adopt IFRS (Ball 1995). Local accounting standards are part of a complex system of governance factors that include auditor training, auditing standards, enforcement (regulatory and judicial), protection of property rights, government corruption, and the role of the media (Ball 2006; Leuz *et al.* 2003; Ramanna & Sletten 2009). In such countries, the regulatory systems and accounting profession are not mature enough to develop appropriate accounting and financial reporting regulations, which increases the benefits to be gained from IFRS adoption (Irvine & Lucas 2006). However, the contents of the IFRS are influenced by the mature international political economy, making it difficult to provide reporting standards that are uniquely suited to any given country's circumstances; they may not fit emerging economies in particular (Leuz & Wysocki 2008).

The quality of extant governance institutions, e.g. professional accounting bodies, affects a country's ability to facilitate the efficient allocation of capital in an economy (Ramanna & Sletten 2009). Generally, governance institutions of a high quality render IFRS adoption less attractive. The presence of existing high quality institutions would incur high opportunity and switching costs to adopt IFRS, such as training the employees about the new standards; altering the current accounting practices; and adopting any new changes (Chand 2005, p. 212). The opportunity costs arise from waiving the benefits of any past and potential future innovations in local reporting standards specific to their economies.

IFRS adoption is different for countries where local governance institutions are not well developed or of a high-quality. Extremely weak institutions exist in troubled or failed states, with no or minimal interest in IFRS adoption. Thus, countries with less developed institutions have lower opportunity and switching costs, which might persuade these countries to adopt IFRS if such countries are in fact capable and willing to make cost-benefit exchanges or compromises (Aspden 2014).

Interestingly, even countries with well-developed institutions require preparation for IFRS conversion. For example, in the USA, regardless of the many advantages and disadvantages of the conversion from GAAP to IFRS, neither the profession nor academia was well-

prepared. For example, all accountants must become fluent in IFRS terms, along with GAAP. The impact on accounting education is also potentially great, as educators need to be aware of IFRS, its principles, and its impact on the accounting world (Paul & Burks 2014).

In the Middle East, the leadership of the entire Gulf Co-Operation Council region (hereafter GCC) including Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, the United Arab Emirates, Qatar, Bahrain, and Oman, believes that following the same financial reporting standards will aid in a move to a more outward-looking international focus (Mala & Chand 2012). The Middle Eastern countries are currently diversifying economically, especially into financial services, increasing their market share and influencing market change across the world and are also a global crossroad for trade, logistics, and finance. The region is excellently placed geographically, at the junction of the traditional markets of the West, the tiger economies of the East and the emerging economies in Africa (Aspden 2014). Thus, it can be argued that adoption of IFRS by these countries will help place the emerging Middle East region firmly at the centre of global trade. An example of such adoption to enhance an outward-looking focus is the United Arab Emirates (hereafter UAE), which has increased its trade links with EU countries significantly since the turn of the millennium (Looney 2003). It is thus obvious that the UAE's move towards adoption of IFRS is related to its trading relationships, and the EU's requirement for listed consolidated entities to adopt IFRS (Irvine & Lucas 2006).

IFRS has also been put forward as a way of controlling fraud and money-laundering, a common problem in developing and emerging economies. It has been recognized that developing and emerging economies often have a culture of fraud, particularly bribery and corruption. Financial scandals in the UAE have damaged its reputation as a reputable investment centre. However, if the adoption of IFRS is likely to negatively impact on financial results, this may actually increase other forms of financial statement fraud.

2.5.2 Disadvantages of global standards

The disadvantages can be considered based on five themes: religious diversity, coercion; differences in taxation and legal System, public sector differences and cultural problems.

2.5.2.1 Religious diversity

Religion plays an important role in defining national culture in many parts of the world and can have a significant effect on business practice (Azmi 2011). The *Qur'an*, for example, provides guidance on issues such as making charitable contributions and charging interest on

loans. In some Islamic countries, banking companies operate under *Sharī'ah*, the Islamic law of human conduct, derived from the *Qur'an*. Because traditional accounting rules do not cover many of the transactions carried out by Islamic financial institutions (IFIs), which are defined as all financial institutions that operate in line with the *Sharī'ah*, the Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI), a standard-setting body based in Bahrain, has been active in developing and promoting Islamic accounting standards.

A key factor affecting many countries is the use of Islamic finance, which is carried out principally in emerging markets. As a result, there are different accounting practices applied to Islamic finance transactions, depending on the local or national framework applied. Some countries have already adopted or are in the process of converging to IFRS; however, many Arabic countries remain under a local version of GAAP that incorporates some form of Islamic accounting standards. This has led to concerns about whether local GAAP views can be reconciled with IFRS and, if they cannot, what impact it will have on IFRS adoption in those countries. Full adoption means IFRS will have to be applied to the accounting for all transactions, whether conventional or Islamic (Azmi 2011). It is obvious that new or substantially altered IFRS are needed that can incorporate properly *Sharī'ah* compliant measures and mechanisms regarding fiscal dealings in numerous emerging, and developing economies, so as to address the requirements of these countries.

Islamic regulation prohibits the charging or disbursement of interest; however, no aspect of IFRS is compatible with this fact (Hussain *et al.* 2002). Religious belief is, for that reason, one of the cultural issues that should be considered when bearing in mind accepting IFRS. Lewis (2001) points out that Islam has many guidelines, grounded on the *Sharī'a* about the way business should be led, the way accounting must be carried out, and the way banking and finance should be conducted. Lewis (2001, p. 104) states that 'Islamic economic and financial principles have a direct impact upon accounting practices and policies. These principles include, most importantly, the institution of *Zakāh* (the religious levy) and the prohibition of *ribā*¹ (usury), and the institution of an interest-free economic system'. Moreover, it also provides a set of applied business ethics.

¹ Several alternative English spellings of this term exist, including *ribā*.

According to Gambling and Karim (1986), there are three key differences between *Shari'ah*-based Islamic fiscal practices and those of the Western world. The first is a complete ban on participation in businesses with activities which are *haram* (prohibited) for Muslims, for instance gambling, alcohol, and pork products. The second is the prohibition of *riba*. While this is usually precisely interpreted as usury, its generally familiar meaning is interest. In Islam, it is not acceptable for a creditor of cash to require a pre-determined and fixed profit per period, whereby the debtor accepts all risk of loss. The third is the endeavour to stop *Gharar*, which can be interpreted as speculation. These three differences characterize a hindrance to the embracing of Western accounting standards, and especially those which involve the restructuring and repayment of debt (White 2004).

Sulaiman (2003) points out that it is not only *Shari'ah* that is at odds with certain facets of Western accounting, but there is also a necessary increase in data for which Western accounting does not have any facility, particularly regarding the disbursement of *Zakah* (charitable giving). The precise calculation of *Zakah* to be paid is difficult. For instance, it is allocated at a rate of 2.5% on any cash which has not been used for a year and also on payments. *Zakah* payable for trading businesses is calculated on clear revenue and clear value. Asset revenue, on the other hand, is subject to 10% *Zakah*. Ibrahim (2000) claims that providing a reasonable basis for the calculation of *Zakah* is one of the main aims of Islamic accounting. Consequently, there is a necessity for an accounting system which can appropriately compute and reveal the quantity of *Zakah* to be paid (Taheri 2000).

The conventional Western management of assets and liabilities on a balance-sheet is obviously not suitable for these calculations and cannot offer the data needed for the precise calculation of the amount of *Zakah* to be paid (White 2004).

The work of AAOIFI inspired the Malaysian Accounting Standards Board (MASB) to develop MASB i-1, the presentation of Financial Statements of Islamic Financial Institutions, in 2001. MASB i-1 states that the general purpose of financial statements is to provide information about the financial position, performance and cash flows of IFIs which are useful to a wide range of users in making economic decisions. It also portrays aspects of management's stewardship of the resources entrusted to it. The information provided allows users to assess the degree of compliance of the IFIs with the prescribed *Shari'ah* requirements. In developing MASB i-1, the MASB consulted with the Malaysian Central

Bank's National *Sharī'ah* Council on issues relating to *Sharī'ah*. In April 2004, the MASB announced that it would introduce four new Islamic accounting standards related to *ijarah* (leasing), *Zakāh* (income tax), *tankful* (insurance), and *Mudarabah* (deferred payments) (Azmi, 2011). The IASB should work with or learn from Malaysia on such standards.

Once seen as a niche area, Islamic or *Sharī'ah*-compliant finance has been expanding rapidly and is now an increasingly important element of the global economy. Modern *Sharī'ah*-compliant products impact the full spectrum of banking, capital markets, asset management and insurance (*takaful*) businesses. Many of the growing number of companies being attracted to the Islamic finance sector are conventional institutions looking to tap into rising market demand, alternative investment opportunities and fresh sources of funding (Taheri 2000). As the sector continues to grow, the question of how best to account for Islamic finance on an international basis is coming to the fore (Azmi 2011; Ibrahim 2000). This may conflict with the requirements of IFRS, and thus impede access to international capital and investments and affect the confidence of global stakeholders and international acquisitions and mergers (Singhal 2012). This challenge is especially pressing for global groups with diverse international stakeholders and extensive financial reporting obligations, which need to align accounting for Islamic finance with the treatment of their conventional business divisions. At the same time, the pursuit of alignment must not compromise *Sharī'ah* principles from the religious perspective (Azmi 2011; Sulaiman 2003).

There is also a problem with standardization in the different ways Islamic finance products are used. While these products are based on classical contracts, the way they are used varies from country to country due to different legal and *Sharī'ah* frameworks. This makes consistency in product accounting within the Islamic regions difficult to achieve and is why the principles-based approach and substance over form principles of the IFRS have become more relevant in Islamic contexts and are considered appropriate accounting ideas to support (Azmi 2011).

A key tenet of IFRS is the concept of 'substance over form', whereby a transaction is measured and reported in accordance with its economic substance rather than its legal form (Azmi 2011). Companies thus will have more flexibility in applying accounting principles with IFRS, because it is essentially principles-based. Transactions may be required to be reported using the substance-over-form criteria. Thus, professional judgments will be

exercised which may lead to enhanced disclosure to support these judgments (Flynn 2008). However, because Islamic finance transactions are legally underpinned by *Shari'ah* principles, it is argued that it may sometimes be inappropriate to apply substance-over-form to such transactions (Azmi 2011). Therefore, it can be anticipated that Islamic-related issues may sometimes constitute a hindrance for implementing the IFRS in the Islamic countries.

2.5.2.2 Coercion

Some researchers have considered harmonization of accounting standards to be an inappropriate imposition of the policies and standards of the developed nations onto the developing nations (Saudagaram & Diga 1998). In this era, most of the developing nations are striving to be self-determined by breaking free from their colonial pasts. Hence, developing nations are likely to approach harmonization with scepticism, because the developed nations arguably benefit most from the concept (Graham & Neu 2003).

The level of coercion is also dependent upon who regulates any convergence (Martinez-Diaz 2005). This regulatory aspect differs from country to country and particularly from continent to continent. In many cases, actors from different regulatory fields become involved in the enforcement of these standards, but this authority to enforce the standards has to be obtained from the legal provisions of the individual country or nation state (Zori 2013). Although the IASC/IASB has no authority to enforce IAS/IFRS in its follower states, the International Organization of Securities Commissions (hereafter IOSCO) has delivered substantial support for the agreement with IAS/IFRS. A large number of emerging and developed nations everywhere in the world have acknowledged IAS/IFRS, owing to the efforts of IASB and numerous international institutions (Ali 2005).

Nevertheless, specific empirical studies have revealed that not all developing countries have accepted the IFRS with enthusiasm. For instance, this has been confirmed in a number of studies, such as those by Abd-Elalam and Weetman (2003), Akhtaruddin (2005), Dahawy and Conover (2007), Hossain *et al.* (2006), Joshi and Ramadhan (2002), Owusu-Ansah (2000) and Samaha and Stapleton (2008), which have established that firms in a number of developing countries have not welcomed the mandatory accounting standards when formulating their financial statements. For example, in a study in Pakistan, Islam (2006) found that the ratio of acquiescence for Pakistani businesses to apply 21 mandatory accounting standards was only moderately high, 72.79%. Companies whose securities are

traded on the international as well as domestic market are dependent on investor support and need to utilize the IFRS.

In many countries in Africa, the different industry regulators, such as the securities regulator, insurance regulator and banking regulator, have played an important role in arriving at the decision to adopt IFRS. In some African countries, some industry regulators may have oversight responsibility to prescribe the accounting standards that should be used by industry players. For instance, the *Central Banks Act* sometimes gives Central Banks the legal right to determine which accounting standards should apply to all banking entities (Nobes & Zeff 2008, 2010).

In other countries, there is a separate accounting regulator, which has the legal mandate to prescribe the accounting standards to apply to all public interest entities (Zori 2013). Accounting regulators often have the authority to make pronouncements on the adoption of IFRS. This authority, possessed by the accounting regulator, is usually driven by the constitution, via the issuance of an act or certain by-laws. To understand the version of IFRS adopted in a country, it is therefore important to review the pronouncements of the accounting regulator or the institution which has the legal authority to make such pronouncements (Zori 2013). It is also important to read the pronouncements carefully.

Countries where local governance institutions are not well developed are likely to suffer from corrupt, slow-moving or ineffectual governments that are resistant to or incapable of change (La Porta *et al.* 1999). At the extreme, countries with weak institutions are failed states, where the adoption of IFRS is unlikely to be of any interest or consequence (e.g. Afghanistan or Somalia). Thus, among countries with less developed institutions, the decision to adopt the IFRS is affected by both the local political culture and international political pressure.

International power politics also arises, since powerful countries are more likely to be able to influence the adoption of IFRS and thus they certainly aid in spreading the influence. For the less powerful countries, there is little political resistance to adopting global standards. Thus, less powerful (developing) countries are more likely to adopt IFRS. In addition to country-level power politics, the perception of IFRS as a Western institution from a Western, developed culture is likely to affect their acceptance in a country (Ciesielski 2007, Ding *et al.* 2005; Norris 2007). In countries that are culturally more accepting of Western institutions,

the adoption of IFRS is more politically feasible. In countries where Western institutions are non-native, adoption of IFRS can be viewed as giving up authority to a Western standard-setter. Thus countries that are culturally closer to Europe, with the majority of their populations being at least nominally Christian, are more likely to adopt IFRS, e.g. Poland and Romania. Ramanna and Sletten (2009) suggest that the former colonial countries, because of prior colonization by Great Britain, are more likely to be comfortable with Western institutions like IFRS and this leads to a higher probability of IFRS adoption. Examples are Fiji, Hong Kong, India, Kenya, Nigeria and Singapore.

2.5.2.3 Differences in tax law and legal system

Accounting guidelines vary from nation to nation, contingent on the legal system utilized. In nations that use common law, accounting guidelines are liberated from the law and accounting principles are prepared and designed by specialized businesses; moreover, corporate law is not extremely detailed (Alexander *et al.* 2007). In contrast, in code law countries, corporate law is considerably more comprehensive and descriptive, and the government regularly sets and enforces accounting principles (Alexander *et al.* 2007). Meek and Saudagaran (1990) explain that, in common law nation states, bounds of behaviour are recognized by law but, within these bounds, specialized judgement is essential. Accounting guidelines in code law countries, by contrast, are commonly very inflexible, with the laws mandating extreme levels of detail.

Both Ding *et al.* (2007) and Hope (2007) argue that legal systems and the variance in their legal origins have an important influence on the role assigned to accounting information. In addition, the implications of conflicting IFRS- and tax-orientations of some countries have been acknowledged as the most significant impediment to convergence (Larson & Street 2004). However, there are widely divergent legal systems in operation across the countries that have adopted, or plan to adopt, IFRS, be they civil (code) law, common law or some alternative framework. It is therefore evident that IFRS is not tied to any particular legal code and that accounting and legal frameworks need to operate side-by-side, even if they are sometimes at odds (Alexander *et al.* 2007). Accordingly, the relevant local legal rights will be important in deciding how to apply IFRS principles to a particular transaction, but local law may not ultimately determine the accounting treatment.

2.5.2.4 Public sector differences

Public sector accountability means that in public services ‘those who are charged with drafting and/or carrying out policy should be obliged to give an explanation of their actions to their accountants’ (Glynn 1985, p. 143). Harmonization of accounting practices in the public sector has become very problematic worldwide. Harmonization procedures promise higher quality financial reporting and, likewise, improved comparability between accounting structures (Crisan 2014). Accounting harmonization in the public sector is accomplished through International Public Sector Accounting Standards (hereafter IPSAS). IPSAS are issued and settled by the IPSAS Board of the IFAC, which is the global organization of the accounting profession. The IPSAS Board emphasizes the accounting and financial reporting needs of the public sector whether it is an agency/organization/entity. Although many IPSAS are close to IFRS, there are major deviations. Moreover, it has been claimed that IPSAS cannot successfully solve public sector problems (Sanderson & Van Schaik 2008).

It has been argued, that as these standards have become a reference for the setting of public sector accounting systems, IPSAS deserve the attention of accounting policy-makers, practitioners and scholars (Christiaens *et al.* 2013). According to Nweze (2013), public sector accounting (PSA) is a procedure of recording, briefing on, examining, collaborating on and understanding the financial transactions of government components and activities. It encompasses all stages of dealings concerning the receipt, custody, and payment of government resources. According to Okoye and Ani (2004), the purposes of public sector accounting are: to establish the accuracy and rationality of transactions and their agreement with traditional rules; to offer proof of accountability for the stewardship of government assets, and to make accessible dynamic facts for good control and practical management of government undertakings. The World Bank has recognized the productivity and strength of the public sector, as ‘one of the most operational influences for supporting competitiveness and fortifying impartiality in society’ (World Bank 2006).

2.5.2.5 Cultural problems

It is widely acknowledged that IFRS has the capacity to enable cross-border comparability, increase reporting clarity, decrease information charges, decrease information irregularity and, thus, intensify liquidity, competition and marketplace effectiveness (Ball 2006; Choi & Meek 2005). However, Armstrong *et al.* (2007) and Soderstrom and Sun (2007) warn that cultural, political and business differences might still create problems for the emergence of a distinct global financial communication network, because a single set of accounting standards

cannot reflect all the differences in national business practices stemming from differences in organizations and cultures. Similarly, Ball (2006) suggests that differences in cultures and types of family bonds make it more challenging for some countries to adopt such standards. This fact is not very obvious to the current IASB team of representatives because such close family ties are not the same around the world; they differ from one region to another. According to Mir and Rahaman (2005), the IASB does not consider these facts because no one can, or will, bring this type of concern to their agenda. The problem is that those who are influenced and concerned by them are not represented or are not following up or attending the IASB meetings on a regular basis. An effort to present this type of cultural difference by Middle Eastern accounting professionals would lead the IASB to be more convinced of the appropriateness of inviting a Middle Eastern representative into its structure, which would also enhance the degree of understanding of new standards and make them more relevant to the end-users.

Moreover, emerging countries have already documented their wish to contribute to the debates on globalization. Consequently, they have worked hard at embracing IFRS alongside local cultural factors. However, several authors demand that the implications of IFRS for emerging economies be acknowledged (Mir & Rahaman 2005, p. 816). They draw attention to the need for contextualized studies of accounting (Reiter 1998, p. 160). Although developing markets characteristically experience more ongoing issues than those in emerging countries, and consequently do not confront the same fiscal restrictions, they nevertheless face several challenges in adopting IFRS, such as changing culture and the emerging structures of regulation and responsibility (Odia & Ogiedu 2013).

As the accounting practices performed in specific states reflect their distinctive cultures and principles (Deegan 2002, p. 43), it would be unwise to accept that one single regulatory agenda is suitable for the fiscal reporting requirements of all nations (Rodrigues & Craig 2006, p. 14). Equally, as emerging countries and developing economies have incorporated IFRS, inadequate attention has been paid to concerns of national culture and regulatory substructure, which result in problems in application. The earlier findings of studies on Fiji and Papua New Guinea (Chand 2005, p. 222) and Bangladesh (Mir & Rahaman 2005) reinforced the difficulty of imposing Western-style systems of regulation on developing countries. In fact embracing globalization and adopting IFRS imposes challenges, as it makes

mandatory the necessary reforms of a country's regulatory, legal, and economic structures, as well as adaptation of its culture to that of the West (Odia & Ogiedu 2013).

2.5.3 Balancing the advantages and disadvantages

When deciding on harmonization, countries must weigh the alleged benefits and alleged costs of global accounting standards before deciding upon a final approach to take. On the support side of the IFRS, there is no doubt as to the success achieved in developing a comprehensive set of 'high-quality' international standards, thus persuading almost 100 countries to adopt them, as well as working on convergence in standards with important non-adopters such as the US (Doupnik & Perera 2014; Mustata & Matis 2010). Thus each country must contemplate the benefits, as well as the costs, of harmonization before considering adaptation of, adoption of or convergence with IFRS. The debate for and against harmonization is ongoing due to the several perceived advantages and disadvantages associated with the harmonization process (Barth *et al.* 2008; Chalmers *et al.* 2011).

Despite the challenges, there seems to be a worldwide trend towards convergence to IFRS (Akwasi & Robert 2005; Baskerville & Evans 2011; Jaggi & Low 2000). Moreover, the degree of harmonization has been acknowledged through studying the divergence among practices in various countries, but also by investigating the behaviour in the same geographic context (Akwasi & Robert 2005; Laga 2012). However, recent studies have suggested that harmonization of accounting standards to promote comparable accounting practices does not achieve the expected and desired comparability (Catuogno & Allini 2011; Nobes 2009; Pocrnjic & Pervan 2013; Taplin 2010).

Figure 2.1 - Advantages and disadvantages of global standards

Advantages		Disadvantages	
1	Efficiency savings	1	Religious diversity (Islamic issues)
2	Improved information	2	Coercion - forced implementation (no ownership)
3	Network benefits	3	Differences in taxation law and legal systems
4	Assisting emerging economies	4	Public sector differences
		5	Cultural problems

The advantages and disadvantages of global accounting standards demonstrate, respectively, both the success achieved by the IASB and the concerns about the claims that the IASB makes. Thus, the debate for and against harmonization is ongoing, due to the several perceived advantages and disadvantages associated with the process of harmonization.

2.6 Conclusion

The business environment is being influenced more and more by globalization and the globally accepted norms for various business processes are being adopted. Such also is the case with accounts and auditing, as various companies across the world are adopting a common international code for accounting - the IFRS. Whilst this set of international standards in accounting has brought some advantages, it has also revealed certain difficulties and disadvantages.

The chapter has shown that all or most emerging nations must consider their specific positions and not assume that accounting needs among emerging countries are similar. Islamic emerging nations require an accounting system that helps them observe their religious requirements and reflects the financial basics of *Sharia'a* law, for instance, the planning of factual statistics for *Zakāh* purposes, the prohibition of *Riba* (interest), and the use of accounting as a method to fulfill Islamic responsibility. The suitability of IFRS to emerging countries and developing economies is contingent on the context of each nation. The current

research focuses on Libya as an example to examine the potential implementation of IFRS. Several influences distinguish this country from other emerging nations; for instance, it would be categorized as a moderately rich country, and Libyan commercial law is greatly dependent on Islamic *Sharia'a* guidelines compared to most other emerging countries.

Thus, the procedure for changing from local accounting standards to IFRS is not likely to be a simple matter, because accountants may consider that the gap between indigenous accounting practices and IFRS is wide. Moreover, this situation arises at a period when the IFRS is undergoing major modifications to meet concerns raised by users of the standards and to address particular flaws of its accounting structure that were formerly not sufficiently identified. In practice, applying IFRS in Libya will experience quite a few difficulties, most of which are based upon the dearth of technical abilities and insufficient awareness among Libyan accounting professionals. The overall need is to develop a high-quality accounting system, including disclosure reports, and draw up a legislative agenda to bring about commercial and social improvement, and training of active accounting staff.

In light of the advantages and disadvantages of IFRS adoption, and linking them to the aim of this thesis, which is the possible implementation of IFRS in Libya, it is important to further examine the issues around harmonization of standards by countries with developed and emerging economies. This topic is covered in the literature review in Chapter 4. However, in the next chapter, Chapter 3, I explore philosophical issues in relation to accounting and introduce my primary theoretical framework, namely institutional theory. The study's actual research methods are explained and justified in the second half of Chapter 3.

Chapter Three – Philosophical and methodological aspects

3.1 Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to discuss philosophical and methodological aspects relevant to the present research on the implementation of IFRS in Libya. After the introduction, Section 2 explains the concepts behind the term ‘research’ in the context of financial accounting. Section 3 begins with an explanation of the term ‘paradigm’ and highlights its importance and utility in accounting research. It also presents paradigms that have emerged in social research and which I used in the context of this study. Section 4 outlines and discusses Burrell and Morgan’s (1979) model and its philosophical assumptions regarding social science and society and presents the four paradigms set out in the model. I also highlight their importance and limitations for the understanding of accounting research. Section 5 presents criticisms of the Burrell and Morgan model that precipitated the emergence of alternative research approaches and their orientation. Section 6 presents alternative research perspectives from Chua (1986), i.e. the interpretive approach and critical approach, both viable alternatives to the current mainstream approaches, and Laughlin’s (1995) three dimensions. Section 7 presents the choice and justification of the selected paradigm for this study. It also presents the theoretical framework for the present research project on IFRS in Libya. I then introduce, explain, and justify my actual research methods used. In this study, I adopted a mixed methods approach, utilizing a questionnaire and semi-structured interviews.

3.2 Research perspective

Academic business research is a category of research that includes research in areas such as organizational behaviour, marketing, accounting, business ethics, finance, HRM and strategy, and which primarily draws upon the social sciences for conceptual and theoretical inspiration (Bryman & Bell 2011). Within interpretive and critical approaches, inspiration is also taken from ideas in anthropology, criminology, philosophy, psychology, and sociology. Critical research in the field of accounting is now grouped together under the umbrella heading of ‘critical accounting’ or ‘critical perspectives on accounting’. Within accounting research, Ryan and Scapens (2002, p. 7) define research as ‘a process of intellectual discovery, which has the potential to transform our knowledge and understanding of the world around us’. This would suggest that knowledge relating to accounting issues can be gained through discovery, interpretation and communication.

3.3 Research paradigms

The discussion below contains a critical reflection on Burrell and Morgan's (1979) approach to research paradigms. This discussion begins with a consideration of the purpose and meaning of research paradigms, as a set of fundamental beliefs that affect the way the researcher conducts her/his social research and the research method choices made in a particular research study.

A paradigm serves as an intellectual boundary that captures a researcher's ontological, epistemological and methodological beliefs or presumptions. Consequently, a paradigm concerns how a researcher understands the phenomenon of interest in terms of what she/he believes. Therefore, the understanding of the paradigm should be linked to the theory and methods used, i.e., 'what should be studied, how research should be done [and] how results should be interpreted' (Bryman & Bell 2011, p. 24). The prevailing paradigms are increasingly challenged by the growth of anomalies that are inconsistent with the paradigm's assumptions and established findings; this is resolved when the old paradigm gives way and a new one emerges (Bryman & Bell 2011). In other words, there is a dialectical process of struggle in which the development of 'new' theory is necessarily mediated by the detection of inconsistencies and anomalies in its predecessor (Willmott 1993). This reflects the tools of Marxism whereby progress occurs through a struggle between opposites - this dialectical concept of development occurs both in material reality and in the progress of ideas. There is also a dialectical relationship between ideas and material reality (Marx & Engels 1987).

Scholarly disciplines, including those within social science, have an underpinning philosophy (L'Huillier 2011, p. 16). Summer *et al.* (1990, p. 362) explain a paradigm as the philosophy of a discipline, comprising 'a set of attitudes, values and beliefs' that endeavour 'to establish the ultimate aim of the discipline' as well as 'the choice of constructs' (theories and models) and 'choice of methods' to achieve research aims. Scholars in social science have constructed several paradigms based on specific worldviews through which they assume valid or useful understandings of social phenomena can be generated. Particular research methods to carry out research work must be consistent with the foundational assumptions of the chosen paradigm. This is necessary for conclusions to be accepted as trustworthy.

An important feature of paradigms is that they are incommensurable (that is they are inconsistent with each other because of their divergent assumptions and methods) (Bryman &

Bell 2011 p. 24). It should be borne in mind that paradigms are principally human constructions and thus cannot be verified in any objective sense (L'Huillier 2011). A paradigm or worldview is thus a rudimentary set of beliefs or assumptions that may be implicit or made explicit and used to guide a researcher's efforts. Although paradigms are human-made constructions of worldviews, their authors and users, nonetheless, have at hand, established knowledge and truth claims which can be consciously or unconsciously reproduced or challenged in scholarly work, policy, and practice (L'Huillier 2011, p. 16). Since the researcher's assumptions are socially constructed, as they are based on trust or commitment of the researcher to previously established truth claims or knowledge, they allow different ways for the researcher to approach a research question; practically conduct the inquiries; interpret the findings; and make strategic choices (Gioia & Pitre 1990; Guba & Lincoln 1998).

A clear effect upon research methods is the theme(s) of the research (Krauss 2005). However, this is also functionally informed by the research stance. The research paradigm used affects understanding about the research area (Bryman & Bell 2003). It holds a rudimentary aspect of philosophy, such as in terms of whether the interest is to practically challenge the status-quo or how loosely or tightly defined the discussion will be. Consequently, the research paradigm is significant in conducting research, including drawing conclusions and interpreting consequences. Whatever the paradigm used, a researcher is affected by its logical assumptions concerning ontology, epistemology, and human nature. These philosophical expectations help shape the researcher's viewpoint and approach (Burrell & Morgan 1979).

3.4 Burrell and Morgan's paradigm

Burrell and Morgan (1979, p. viii) crafted a two-by-two matrix 'founded on mutually exclusive views of the social world'. Their model provides a map of paradigms that represents their understanding of some of the philosophical assumptions that 'underwrite' different approaches to social science research: (a) the subjective-objective dimension, (ii) regulation-radical change dimension. Their framework produces a continuum style line ranging from 'positivist approach' to a 'phenomenological' standpoint on their subjective-objective scale and regulation- radical change dimension on the other axis. Figure 3.1 outlines the assumptions that are relevant to understanding the nature of social science from the two broad oppositional perspectives. The framework is in the form of a two-by-two

matrix and was developed from bipolar views of society and how change might come about and the nature of problems in society and how they might be addressed (Morgan & Smircich 1980).

Figure 3.1 - Understanding the nature of social science from two broad oppositional perspectives

(Adapted from: Burrell & Morgan 1979)

3.4.1 Objectivist and subjectivist dimension

Burrell and Morgan (1979) suggest that each paradigm contains assumptions that can be represented as either:

- (a) Objectivist where there is an external viewpoint from which it is possible to view the organization, which is comprised of consistently real processes and structures or
- (b) Subjectivist where an organization is a socially constructed product, a label used by an individual to make sense of their social experience, so it can be understood only from the point of view of individuals who are directly involved in its activities (Bryman & Bell 2011, p. 24).

Guba and Lincoln (1989) likewise draw a distinction between these two very broad research methodologies as scientific and naturalistic. A set of alternative terms are suggested by Hussey and Hussey (1997). Objectivist can be referred to as quantitative, positivist, scientific, experimentalist, traditionalist, and functionalist. Subjective is also known as qualitative, phenomenological, humanistic, and interpretivist. Methodologies are also classified as either quantitative or qualitative by L'Huilier (2011). Usually, but not always, the objective approach aims to describe and explain the status-quo rather than change it. However, the Marxist approach aims at social change, but still accepts the existence of a material reality,

which can be known and understood (whilst also allowing for different interpretations of that one reality).

Figure 3.2 illustrates the conceptual distinctions existing between subjective and objective approaches to organizational analysis. In practice, researchers might mix together aspects of both perspectives, as with the Marxist approach referred to above. The subjective-objective axis concerns the types of interpretations made in terms of philosophical assumptions concerning ontology, epistemology, and human-nature. The choice made along the dimension of subjective and objective is associated with the specific methodological alternatives of ideographic and nomothetic, as we shall see.

Ontology is the view of how one perceives a reality. It relates to the nature of existence. It is concerned with what is the nature of the knowable, or what is the nature of reality. Ontology can be understood from two polar perspectives of realism and nominalism. Realism assumes that the real world has hard, intangible structures that exist irrespective of our labels, thus the social world exists separately from the individual's perception of it. Nominalism assumes that society is relative, and the social world is understood through names, concepts and labels that make individual structures reality. The Marxist perspective within critical realism brings out aspects of both approaches.

Epistemology relates to the nature and understanding of knowledge; the theory of how knowledge is constructed; and the nature of the relationship between the knower (inquirer) and the known (or knowledge). Positivism seeks to explain and predict what happens in the social world by searching for patterns and relationships, with hypotheses being developed and tested (Watts & Zimmerman 1978, 1986, 1990).

Positivism usually is associated with quantitative methods. There exists the idea or belief that the data exists independently of the researcher and that there can be an objective, disinterested gaze. My quantitative results chapter owes something to positivism, without accepting fully all the tenets of a positivist worldview. I believe that the survey responses were created, and now exist, outside of my direct control, but I did choose which questions to ask and how to ask them. This reflects a set of values and beliefs. I also interpreted the meaning of the results, and individual readers might contest one or more of my interpretations. In contrast to positivism, anti-positivism rejects the belief that simply

observing behaviour can help people to fully understand it, with social science being unable to create true objective knowledge of any kind. Under this (extreme) approach, interpretation is everything and, of course, these may and do vary. In its extreme form, this approach is akin to postmodernism in its various guises.

Human-nature relates to the relationship between human beings and their environment. Determinism sees a person as being determined by the situation and environment she/he is in. Voluntarism, alternatively, sees a person as possessing completely autonomous and possessing free will. The reality, to me, would encompass aspects of both perspectives. Even the twentieth century French existentialist philosopher Jean-Paul Sartre (1943) accepted that not only is there freedom in the world (as consciousness implies or even equals freedom), but there are also limits to freedom. Limits to freedom include obstacles in the natural world as well as, paradoxically, other people's freedom. Limits also include factors such as the family and the location into which one was born.

Methodology relates to the process of understanding regarding how the researcher should go about developing new knowledge (Allison & Hobbs 2006, p. 56). Nomothetic and ideographic methods represent two different methodologies to understand social life. A nomothetic method focuses on general statements that account for larger social patterns that form the context of single events or individual behaviour and experience. The nomothetic approach involves hypotheses testing and employs methods such as surveys and other standardized research tools. An ideographic method focuses on detailed observation of society, individual cases or events. Ethnographers, for example, observe the minute details of everyday life to construct an overall portrait. In my quantitative results chapter, my approach is predominantly nomothetic, whereas the qualitative results chapter utilizes primarily the ideational approach. Flexibility was required to shift from one approach and then back to the other, depending upon which set of primary-data was being looked at.

The subjective-objective dimension

Figure 3.2 - The subjective–objective dichotomy for analysing assumptions about the nature of social science

(Adopted from: Burrell & Morgan 1979, p. 3)

The ontological and epistemological positions of the researcher and human nature direct the methodologies, which will in turn guide the choices of methods and techniques employed in the research work, as well as how the results are interpreted and reported (Allison & Hobbs 2006, p. 56). The recording technique, or the way information is captured, is a subcomponent of the methodology. Any discussion of these concepts necessarily overlaps, and one cannot discuss one without the other or necessarily separate them (Allison & Hobbs 2006, p. 56).

3.4.2 Regulatory and Radical change of the society

Each paradigm also makes assumptions about the function and purpose of scientific research in investigating the world of business as either:

- a) Regulatory- the purpose of business research is to describe what goes on in the organisations. There is a room for minor changes that may result in improvements in the organisation, but not to make any judgement of it; or
- b) Radical- the point of management and business research is to make judgement about the way that organisations ought to be and to make suggestions about how this could be achieved (Bryman & Bell 2011, p. 24).

This dimension incorporates the sociological dimension, involving a view of society. The regulatory view of society sees society evolving from the status quo. Taking a regulatory

view of society requires the researcher to assume that society evolves incrementally and rationally. In this sense, society is viewed as unified and cohesive (Burrell & Morgan 1979). This is the functionalist or conservative view of the world. The regulatory view of society forms the basis of modernism whereas a radical change perspective is the bed rock of postmodernism (Holden & Lynch 2013). This statement is only partially correct, as Karl Marx was a modernist economist and philosopher who supported radical social change in the direction of communist revolution.

Taking a radical change view of society, the researcher assumes that there is a persistent conflict in which humans struggle to remove the existing domination of the societal structures (Burrell & Morgan 1979). The sociological dimension discussed above suggests to researchers that differing sociological perspectives do exist, and a radical view of society could provide new and creative approaches to research, particularly as business-school research has traditionally adopted a rational and incremental view of society and social change, following the American case of Democrats and Republicans (Holden & Lynch 2013).

Burrell and Morgan (1979) suggest a replacement of the order-conflict distinction. They argue that regulation and radical change should become the new central themes. Table 3.1 provides a list of the characteristics of regulation as opposed to radical change.

Table 3.1 - The regulation-radical change dimension

The sociology of regulation is concerned with:	The sociology of radical change is concerned with:
a- the status _quo	a- radical change
b- social order	b- structural conflict
c- consensus	c- modes of domination
d- social integration and cohesion	d- contradiction
e- solidarity	e- emancipation
f- need satisfaction	f- deprivation
g- actuality	g- potentiality

(Adapted from: Burrell & Morgan 1979, p. 18)

3.4.3 The emergence of paradigms

As a range of potentially useful paradigms to outline classifications for sense-making, i.e. analysis, Burrell and Morgan (1979, p. viii) crafted a two-by-two matrix ‘founded on mutually exclusive views of the social world’. Their model provides a map of four possible types of research paradigm that represents their understanding of some of the philosophical

assumptions that ‘underwrite’ different approaches to social science research, as shown in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3 - Four paradigms of analysis in social theory

(Adapted from: Burrell & Morgan 1979)

Each paradigm shares a common set of features with each of its horizontal and vertical neighbours but not so with its diagonal opposite. However, regardless of any commonality of features, each paradigm stands alone in generating a distinctive analysis of social life that is ‘in fundamental opposition to those generated in other paradigms’ (Burrell & Morgan 1979, p. vii). However, although they are useful, it is argued that these dichotomies artificially separate categories which are actually along a continuum, as is the case with all static frameworks (Allison & Hobbs 2006, p. 56).

Burrell and Morgan (1979, p. 23) suggest that their model portrays social phenomena as ‘four distinct sociological paradigms which can be utilised for the analysis of a wide range of social theories’. They argue that the paradigms are distinct, implying that any attempt by the researcher to shift paradigms, or conduct inter-paradigm activities, necessarily requires radical changes in meta-theoretical assumptions. Thus, they argue that researchers need to have a clear understanding of their paradigm because it affects the concepts and analytical tools used to conduct their research. Each paradigm defines an intellectual perspective through which a different view of social reality can be expressed and validated (L’Huillier 2011). Burrell and Morgan’s (1979) four paradigms are discussed briefly below. But we note Allison and Hobbs’ (2006) point cited above that really the four paradigms are end-points at the end of a continuum.

3.4.3.1 The functionalist paradigm (objective-regulation)

The major frameworks for research in academic sociology and the study of organizations conform to the functionalist paradigm (Burrell & Morgan 1979). Mingers (2001) is of the view that the functionalist paradigm is considered to be the primary paradigm for organizational study. It seeks out rational explanation of social affairs and the human actions and beliefs which can help to understand organizational behaviour by using hypothesis-testing. Therefore, this sociological paradigm is considered to be deeply rooted in logical positivism, i.e. that the world exists 'out there' independently of the researcher and can be objectively known and studied.

According to Ardalan and College (2010), the functionalist paradigm assumes that society follows a certain order and its existence is concrete. It further assumes that scientific theories in the real world can be assessed objectively with reference to empirical evidence. Thus, research adopting this paradigm searches for rational explanations of social matters, and it has become dominant in academic sociology, especially in North America, and in mainstream accounting and finance research.

Researchers working from the functionalist paradigm are concerned with the sociology of regulation from an objectivist perspective. They are committed to a philosophy of social-engineering as the basis for social change. Functionalist researchers present the world as highly rational and orientated towards social order and work towards 'stability or maintenance of the status quo' (Gioia & Pitre 1990, p. 585). They seek to generate knowledge that can be used to provide solutions to practical problems, characterizing people as passive objects rather than makers of social reality. Because of his detailed study of how surveillance and discipline operates in modernist-era prisons, French philosopher Michel Foucault has (wrongly) been labelled a neo-functionalist.

The functionalist researcher adheres to the view that human affairs can be studied in the manner of the natural sciences, using a deductive form of logic – theories and hypotheses can be tested for a cause-and-effect order. They use a static design whereby concepts, variables, and hypotheses are selected before the study begins and remain fixed throughout the study thus separating theory from observations that may be used then to verify or falsify a theory (Chua 1986; Guba & Lincoln 1998). Examples of functionalist research programmes and

theories in accounting and finance include the efficient market hypothesis, capital markets research, and positive accounting theory.

With reference to Figure 3.3, those that work from the functionalist paradigm approach the above concerns from a realist, positivist, determinist, and nomothetic standpoint. As a result, the functionalist paradigm is positioned in the bottom-right quadrant of the matrix as it seeks to understand society and its composite parts at an 'objective' level that 'specifies the precise nature of laws, regularities and relationships among phenomena' (Morgan & Smircich 1980, p. 493).

Mainstream accounting and finance research (e.g. capital markets research in accounting) is grounded in a set of philosophical assumptions based upon the instrumentalist and positivist perspectives, which are characterized by an ontological belief about a generalizable world waiting to be discovered (Baker & Bettner 1997; Laughlin 1995). The mainstream of accounting research is inspired by the functionalist paradigm. In relation to accounting, researchers traditionally emphasize the importance of means over ends (Chua 1986); hence the never-ending myopic discussions of t-statistics and research method, rather than usefulness of the results or even actual knowledge gained.

3.4.3.2 Interpretive paradigm (subjective-regulation)

The interpretive researcher is concerned with the sociology of regulation from a subjectivist perspective. This is another very important paradigm, as explained by Burrell and Morgan (1979). These authors argue that the interpretivist paradigm can give us an understanding of the fundamental nature of the social world and help us to understand the world as it is at the level of subjective experiences. Explanations in this paradigm must only be seen in the context of individual consciousness and subjectivity.

Researchers working from the interpretive paradigm share with functionalist paradigm researchers a commitment to an ideological perspective that deals with issues examining natural order and regulation while at the same time 'ignoring modes of domination, conflict and radical change' (Morgan & Smircich 1980, p. 492). However, the interpretive researcher rejects the view that human affairs can be studied in the manner of the natural sciences. Instead, interpretive research is concerned with the sociology of regulation, from a subjective perspective, that is, research into society as it is. Social reality is viewed as emergent and

subjectively created. Social order is presumed (Chua 1986); and ‘people are purposeful and basically orderly’ (Hooper 2001, p. 59). However, if conflict is perceived as dysfunctional, then the organization needs to resolve it. Therefore, the researcher assumes regulatory rather than radical change is needed.

An interpretive methodology attempts to describe, understand and analyse the meaning the humans apply to symbols and structures in which they find themselves. Symbolic interactionism, grounded theory, and ethnomethodological approaches are within this school of thought (Laughlin 1995; Parker & Roffey 1997). Interpretive research has been subjected to criticism from the critical researchers’ camp. Critical researchers criticize interpretive studies because they frequently do not incorporate a programme for social change (Wanderley & Cullen 2012, p. 29) other than practical ways to reduce conflict so as to improve social cohesion. The main distinction between interpretive research and critical research studies is that the latter have a concern regarding the political and social implications of research findings (Baker & Bettner 1997).

Ardalan and College (2010) indicate that the interpretive paradigm views the society or social world as a process created by individuals. The core aim of interpretive researchers is to find the order that prevails within the phenomenon under consideration; however, these phenomena are not considered to be objective. In cultural science, interpretive researchers believe that the subject matter is spiritual in nature and cultural phenomena are seen as external manifestations of inner experiences. Therefore, cultural research should apply analytical methods based on the kind of understandings which an academic scholar can have recourse to, to explain human beings, their feelings and thoughts, and the ways in which these are reflected in their actions.

By adopting an interpretive methodology, the researcher is seeking to understand the deeper meanings that these structures have for the human actors. Thus, the interpretive researcher seeks explanations from within the frame of reference of the study’s participants rather than that of the researcher (Burrell & Morgan 1979). Interpretive research relies on observation and linguistic cues (Hooper 2001) in order to ‘enrich people’s understanding of the meanings of their actions’ (Chua 1986, p. 615). Interpretive researchers oppose the concept of the neutrality of the world of facts; but accept as revealed truth a shared consensus of individual actors’ interpretation of meaning (Baker & Bettner 1997). Consequently, interpretive research

is unique - it has modest technical applications because universal laws underpinning reality are neither proposed nor believed in (Lehman 2006, cited in L'Huillier 2011, p. 25).

With reference to Figure 3.2, proponents of the interpretive paradigm approach the above concerns from a nominalist, anti-positivist, voluntarist, and ideographic standpoint. As a result, the interpretive paradigm is positioned in the bottom-left quadrant of the matrix as the researcher seeks to understand society and its composite parts at a subjective level. It appears on the left of the objective-subjective continuum as researchers share the assumption that reality is a 'projection of human imaginations' (Morgan & Smircich 1980, p. 494); and, as such, challenges the notion that social processes must conform to certain criteria or universal laws (Chua 1986).

Interpretive accounting research allows for the investigation of market behaviour alongside ethical, political, cultural, and social issues. Moreover, it is argued by some that neither accounting nor finance are fixed objective essences (Ardalan & College 2010) and it is clear that the world is not homogeneous and that there are disparities between countries. Therefore, financial and social patterns and tendencies are also different across countries. In this research, the IFRS implications in Libya will be judged within the context of the changing nature of Libyan society and societal factors.

3.4.3.3 Radical humanist paradigm (subjective-radical change)

The third paradigm in Burrell and Morgan's (1979) classification is the radical humanist paradigm and its concern is to develop a sociology of radical change from a subjective position. Researchers adopting the radical humanist paradigm are more concerned about the social constraints which are responsible for limiting human potential. Here, researchers argue that current ideologies and practices separate people from their true selves (Bettner *et al.* 1994). Therefore, this paradigm is used to justify revolutionary change, and hence it is usually anti-organization in scope (although this is not always the case, e.g. for a researcher studying a militant labour union). Moreover, its theorists actively work to remove the social constraints which restrict potential.

The subjective approach of the radical humanist paradigm emphasizes human consciousness and holds that it is dominated by the ideological superstructure within which the person interacts (Burrell & Morgan 1979). This paradigm assumes that reality is socially-created and

sustained. It describes the process of creating reality as something, which rebounds back on itself so that society and individuals are prevented from attaining their highest possible potential. These social theorists regard the order that prevails in society as a vehicle for ideological domination. Their main concern is how ideological domination happens and finding ways for human beings to free themselves. Chua (1986, p. 619) believes that 'human potentiality is restricted by prevailing systems of domination which alienate people from self-realization' and that ideological concerns may be embedded in our 'taken for granted beliefs about acceptable social practices'. Moreover, it is assumed that truth is historically specific, relative to a given set of conditions, and thus one should not search for generalizations for the rules of notion of societies (Ardalan & College 2010).

Gioia and Pitre (1990, p. 588) indicate similarities between radical humanism and interpretivism: 'Theory building in radical humanism is similar to that of interpretivism. The radical humanist paradigm provides the means with which to critique 'the status quo' from the viewpoint that 'the status quo' is a social construction whereby the actors 'perform' 'within a matrix of inter-subjective meanings' (Chua 1986, p. 621). But the important distinction is in having a more critical or evaluative stance. The goal of this paradigm is to free human beings from sources of domination, alienation, exploitation, and repression by critiquing the existing social structures with the intent of changing them. However, in making a case for social change from the status quo to a better world, such a critical approach goes beyond merely interpreting the real world to attempting to change it (Laughlin 1995).

This requires researchers to 'learn' the language of the players within this matrix because language itself may be a medium of repression and social power (Burrell & Morgan 1979) as ideological constructs may be embedded in the language itself (Chua 1986). This Foucauldian view is supported by Jonsson and Macintosh (1997), who claim that producing narratives of systems is not simply an act of translation and interpretation of beliefs, actions, and communication practices but rather it is 'first and foremost a political act' (Jonsson & Macintosh 1997, p. 378), as words are always an important element of any power-knowledge structure.

The radical humanist paradigm is orientated towards radical change, modes of domination, emancipation, deprivation, and potentiality. Researchers in this paradigm share the assumption that there are structures that run below the surface of social existence, which

shape and drive the individual's social interactions including communication patterns and behaviour (Burrell & Morgan 1979; Jonsson & Macintosh 1997). Radical humanist paradigm researchers approach these concerns from a nominalist, anti-positivist, voluntarist, and ideographic standpoint and are committed to exposing and removing restrictive conditions, systems, and ideologies that prevent human potentialities from flourishing (Chua 1986).

3.4.3.4 Radical structuralist paradigm (objective-radical change)

Finally, in the top-right-hand corner of the quadrant, is the radical structuralist paradigm. Schools of thought in this paradigm are located on the objective continuum. This paradigm believes that reality is objective and concrete, as this views society as a potentially dominating force. Consciousness is considered to be the basis for a radical critique of society (Nepomucene 2003). This paradigm is based on four central notions. Firstly, there is the notion of totality; this highlights that the totality shapes and presents in all of its essential parts. Secondly, there is the notion of structure, which concerns the configurations of social affairs. Thirdly, the idea of contradiction is that structures or social formations contain inconsistencies and antagonistic relationships, which will act as the seeds of their own growth or decay. For a Marxist researcher, tensions exist within the system as a whole, due to the contradictory tendencies in the system and this produces forward movement or decay as one side grows stronger and the other weaker. One existing tendency may become so weak that it is replaced by a new one, as often happens with rival political parties over a period of time.

Finally, there is the idea of crises. Inconsistencies within a given totality reach a point at which they can no longer continue. The findings of studies of political and economic crises show the point of transformation from one set of structures to another, which has a fundamentally different nature (Ardalan & College 2010). For Marxists, crises occur due to labour-power, which creates new value and surplus-value, being replaced by machine-time, which does not. The capitalist may confuse herself or himself by failing to recognize this truth, since capitalist ideology and assumptions obscure the source of value and thus attribute it to the whole of the invested capital.

Radical structuralist researchers approach radical change from an objectivist stance. They are committed to radical change, emancipation, and potentiality by concentrating on structural relationships within a realist social world. The researchers see 'change' occurring not as a response to the raising of individual's self-conscious processes (radical humanist position),

but as a result of changes in concrete structures. Reality is seen to exist outside the minds of the human actors. The radical structuralist seeks emancipation by changing the restrictive structures directly. Thus, they have a definite end in sight, i.e. to change or remove conditions and restrictive structure that stand in the way of individuals to achieve full potential (L'Huillier 2011, p.24). This view is also known as 'critical realism'. A prime example is Marxist-Leninist thought as reflected in the philosophies of (say) Louis Althusser.

3.5 Criticism of Burrell and Morgan's model

Highly influential though it was, and arguably still is, the core arguments of Burrell and Morgan (1979) did not escape serious criticism. Donaldson (1985) was one of the early critics, arguing that there was actually no need for paradigms other than the functionalist one. Hassard (1990) expressed worries regarding progress in science if the incommensurability of paradigms continued on indefinitely. For his part, Willmott (1990) developed a strong critique based on the idea that the paradigmatic system suggested by Burrell and Morgan is a 'new dogma' that is not sustained theoretically. Willmott (1993, p. 683) argues that 'the reader repeatedly encounters the thesis that analysis is, and must remain, confined within the structure of the matrix. To be located in a particular paradigm is to view the world in a particular way'.

Willmott (1993) is critical of the polarization of 'subjective' versus 'objective' approaches to social science inherent in the model. He argues (*ibid*, p. 682) that the support that Burrell and Morgan's model gives to theory development is, at best, ambivalent, because its division of social and organizational analysis into four, mutually-exclusive paradigms lacks credibility, and is therefore poorly equipped to counter the power and hegemony of functionalism. Moreover, the central argument of exclusive paradigms unnecessarily constrains the process of theory development within polarized sets of assumptions about science and society. Reed (1985) suggests that the boundaries between the paradigms are not clear; and that overstatement of the differences between them leads to isolationism and reduces the potential for creative theoretical development (Kakkuri-Knuuttila *et al.* 2008, p. 268).

Discrediting the functionalist stance can be done without relying on dubious arguments that organizational analysis rests on four, mutually-exclusive paradigms. The presumed mutual-exclusivity (i.e. development can occur within the specific paradigm but not across

paradigms) hinders theory development, and those who firmly oppose its demands are unlikely to use the theory as a strategic device. Kakkuri-Knuuttila *et al.* (2008) argue that strict distinctions between objective and subjective approaches to research make no sense. The search for universal laws to explain the causes of social action has already been broadly discredited amongst social scientists. On the other hand, purely subjectivist accounts of areas of social science such as accounting cannot shed light on accounting as a contextual phenomenon. Interpretations and conclusions remain tied to the understandings of individuals.

This constitutes the basis from which Kakkuri-Knuuttila *et al.* (2008) derive their key point. Interpretive research in accounting ‘straddles paradigms’. It combines subjectivist and objectivist features that allow for mixed methodological arguments. Central to interpretive accounting research is the debate on how social reality emerges from subjectivist understandings and how reality manifests itself through interaction. Kakkuri-Knuuttila *et al.* (2008) consider Burrell and Morgan’s (1979) framework as an important starting point in this debate. Buchanan and Bryman (2007) argue that the ‘paradigm wars’ became ‘paradigm soup’ because of the increased epistemological diversity within business and organizational research, much of which routinely and happily mixes the paradigms’ approaches (Bryman & Bell 2011, p. 26).

In their later works, Burrell and/or Morgan seemed to become less determined in their views regarding paradigm closure and incommensurability (Burrell 1996; Morgan 1986; Morgan & Smircich 1980). For Willmott (1993, p. 682), following Thomas Kuhn, with respect to the natural sciences, theory development involves a process in which all accumulation of anomalies in existing theories stimulates (or supports) the plausibility and development of alternative theorizing, whilst recognizing that ‘old’, discredited theory is not the same as its ‘new’, enlightened successor.

Although it has been criticized, Burrell and Morgan’s (1979) model has encouraged researchers to explore the assumptions that they make about the nature of the social world and how it can be studied. The subsequent paradigm debates highlight the relationship between epistemology and ontology in financial accounting research. In addition, the research strategy choice of which paradigm to adopt also has implications for the design of the research and the data-collection approach.

3.6 Alternative approaches to mainstream accounting research

The accounting literature has developed a number of responses to the challenge of combining subjectivist insights with an objectivist posture that have come to characterize innovative accounting fieldwork in particular (Ahrens 2008, p. 292).

3.6.1 Chua (1986) - Classification of assumptions

Chua (1986) departed from Burrell and Morgan (1979) by reclassifying methodological perspectives as mainstream, interpretive, and critical. Burrell and Morgan's framework was also criticized by Chua (1986) regarding the strict dichotomies, such as human beings assumed to be determined by their environment *or* completely autonomous and free-willed, when obviously both aspects are in play together (which creates tension).

Particular accounting theories may then be classified using Burrell and Morgan's four paradigms: functionalist, interpretive, radical humanist, and radical structuralist. Chua (1983, p. 603) considers these four paradigms and recognizes that, within accounting research, there are three main approaches: mainstream, interpretive, and critical perspectives. Figure 3.4 shows the types of accounting research as suggested by Chua (1986).

Figure 3.4 - Alternative paradigms of analysis in social theory
(Adapted from: Chua 1986)

Chua (1986) states that, within accounting research, positivistic research dominates, emphasizing quantitative methods of data-collection and analysis. This stance assumes that empirical reality is objective and external to the subject, with human beings characterized as passive objects rather than as makers of social reality. The single goal of utility-maximization or wealth-maximization is often assumed for individuals and firms, as in positive accounting theory. Societies and organizations are assumed to be essentially stable with dysfunctional conflict being managed through the design of appropriate accounting controls. Chua (1986, p. 601) states that the majority of the accounting research output is positivistic, asserting that:

Mainstream accounting research ... with its emphasis on hypothetico-deductivism and technical control, possesses certain strengths but has restricted the range of problems studied and the use of research methods.

Baker and Bettner (1997, p. 293) agree with Chua, stating:

We argue that the type of research prevalent in the mainstream accounting journals, which is characterized by a positivist methodological perspective and an emphasis on quantitative methods, is incapable of addressing complex accounting ramifications.

Interpretive research is not a dominant strand of accounting research, but Chua (1986) believes it could be of benefit in the furtherance of knowledge. Interpretive researchers seek theoretical explanations of human intentions as garnered via subjective interpretation, i.e. actors are studied in their everyday world. The critical perspective in accounting is not deemed a dominant form of accounting research; it considers the accounting scene as a place where fundamental conflict is endemic. Those with Marxist views position the economic base as primary and accounting, as part of the superstructure, as being essentially determined by the economic base. Conflict arises because of injustice and ideologies in the social, economic, and political domains, which hinder the creative dimensions in people. This form of accounting research aims to identify and remove the domination of both exploitation and ideological practices.

3.6.2 Laughlin and middle range thinking

Laughlin (1995) presented three accounting research categories: positivist, interpretative, and critical, similar to Chua's three research approaches. Laughlin (1995) developed a useful model for characterizing accounting research, which extended prior work by Burrell and Morgan (1979), Chua (1986), Hopper and Powell (1985) and Laughlin and Lowe (1990).

Laughlin classified accounting research along three dimensions, incorporating:

- 1) The level of method chosen, where high represents quantitative hypothetical studies and low represents more qualitative approaches.
- 2) The level of prior theorization (i.e. the extent to which previously developed theoretical models from other disciplines, such as economics or psychology, provide the basis for the research).
- 3) The level of emphasis on change (i.e. in a social sense).

Figure 3.5 - Dimensions on the choice process for empirical research
(Source: Laughlin 1995)

Laughlin's model shows that positivist perspectives are characterized by a high level of theory in the methods chosen to pursue the research, with a high level of prior theorization, and a (very) low emphasis on social change (see Figure 3.5). By contrast, interpretive perspectives are characterized by lower levels of theory in the methods chosen to pursue the research, lower levels of prior theorization, and medium to low levels of emphasis on change. Thus, this model describes research as existing along continua, which extend from the positivist perspective characteristic of mainstream accounting research out to more interpretive and critical perspectives.

These areas are expressed in the context of choices that have to be made before undertaking any empirical investigation. Laughlin (1995, p. 66) categorized these concerns in a cluster under three broad headings:

- (a) Methodology choice - involves taking a position on an amalgam of the nature and role of the observer in the discovery process (Burrell and Morgan's 'human nature' assumption) and the level of theoretical formality in defining the nature of the discovery methods (Burrell and Morgan's 'methodology');
- (b) Theory choice- involves deciding on a view about the nature of the world, (Burrell and Morgan's 'ontology'), and what constitutes knowledge, either past or present, and how it relates to the actual focus of investigation (Burrell and Morgan's 'epistemology' assumption); and
- (c) Change choices- involve taking a position on whether the investigation is intentionally geared to achieve change in the phenomena being investigated (Burrell and Morgan's 'society' assumption).

The nature of broad streams (schools) of thought (social and political), and allied approaches, according to the three-way choice criteria described in theory, methodology and change choices, are summarized in Figure 3.5.

3.6.2.1 Methodological choice

Rather than extreme positions of quantitative or qualitative methods, Laughlin (1995) suggests a mid-position for methodological choice, where a mid or mixed approach may be adopted. The mixed-methods research approach contains elements of both qualitative and quantitative approaches. According to Creswell (2009), this research approach involves different philosophical assumptions, the use of qualitative and quantitative approaches, and the mixing of both approaches in a study. A researcher may identify statistically significant relationships, when analysing data collected quantitatively, but she or he may also search for patterns, themes, and holistic features in analysing qualitative data. The researcher should determine the approach to apply in the research she/he intends to conduct, based on the purpose(s) of the study - this could be quantitative or qualitative but also a mixed method approach. Mixed-methods research can serve a variety of purposes. These include triangulation, development, initiation, and expansion (Greene, Caracelli & Graham, 1989).

The mixed-methods design model commonly used is the triangulation model (Creswell 2009). In this model, the researcher can collect two types of data at once. He/she can administer surveys and he/she can also conduct interviews to gather additional details. A triangulation model allows the researcher to collect both qualitative and quantitative data concurrently. In such an approach, the researcher can find out whether the data exhibits any pattern(s) that is evident in both sets of data. Comparison of information is valuable in that it enhances the usefulness and power of data.

Development assists in a total understanding of the research problem whereby the findings from one method help develop or inform findings from the other method (Greene *et al* 1989). For example, statistical data collected from a questionnaire method can often shape interview questions for the qualitative part of the study, and vice-versa (Biber 2010). Initiation deals with discovering paradoxes and contradictions that lead to a re-framing of the research question(s) or initiating new or follow-up studies. The desired effect of ongoing study would be to add new insight into the existing theory on the phenomenon under investigation. Expansion uncovers completely new topics thus leading to extending the breadth and range of inquiry (Greene *et al.* 1989), leading to pursuit of new or modified questions (Biber 2010). In some cases, a research project never ends, as long as the researcher still maintains strong working relationships with her/his willing set of interviewees - and articles keep being written.

3.6.2.2 Theoretical choice: institutional theory

Choice of theory involves deciding on a view about the nature of the world (ontology) and what constitutes knowledge, either past or present, and how it relates to the current focus of investigation. According to Laughlin (1995), the theory dimension relates to the level of prior theorizing and prior theories can legitimately be brought into the research investigation. This point links to ontological assumptions about the nature of the world under investigation and whether researchers view this through previous theoretical endeavours. High levels of prior theorizing are indicative of an assumed material world which exists distinct from the observers' projections and biases (as in the critical realism perspective). In the present research, I select institutional theory as my primary framework, as it has been applied in prior literature on accounting change.

Why did I select institutional theory? Institutional theory focuses on the deeper and more resilient aspects of social structure. It considers the processes by which structures, including schemes; rules, norms, and routines, become established as authoritative guidelines for social behaviour (Scott 2004). Different components of institutional theory explain how these elements are created, diffused, adopted, and adapted over space and time; and how they fall into decline and disuse. Although the ostensible subject is stability and order in social life, students of institutions must attend not just to consensus and conformity but to conflict and change in social structures (Scott 2004). The IFRS is an example of a set of techniques or practices which have attained global domination and hegemony through pressure and persuasion. The vocabulary and practices of IFRS dictate and dominate every aspect of financial statements and the whole accounting ecosystem. Therefore, institutional theory is extremely suitable for the present study, where the case reveals isomorphism in the form of pressure coming from various high-status sources, both internal and external to the country.

There is general agreement among researchers on the unified definition of the term 'institution'. For Scott (2001), institutions are social structures that have attained a high degree of resilience. As shown in Table 3.2, institutions comprise cognitive, normative, and regulative elements. These elements, in association with activities and resources, provide stability and meaning to social life. Institutions operate at different levels of jurisdiction, from the world-system to localized interpersonal relationships. Institutions, by definition, signify stability but are 'subject to change processes, both incremental and discontinuous' (Scott 2001, p. 48).

The institutional environment can strongly influence the development of formal structures in an organization, arguably often more deeply than market pressures. Innovative structures that improve technical efficiency in early-adopting organizations are legitimized in the environment. Ultimately, these innovations reach a level of legitimization, whereby failure to adopt them is seen as irrational and/or negligent or they become legal mandates. At this point, new and existing organizations will adopt the structural form, even if that form doesn't improve efficiency (DiMaggio & Powell 1983). Meyer and Rowan (1983) argue that often these ineffective structures are merely accepted as tokens, in order for the organization to gain or maintain legitimacy in the institutional environment.

Organizations adopt the vocabularies of the structures prevalent in their environment, such as specific job titles, procedures, and organizational roles. The adoption and prominent display of these institutionally acceptable trappings of legitimacy help preserve an aura of organizational action based on 'good faith'. Legitimacy in the institutional environment helps ensure organizational survival. However, these formal structures of legitimacy can reduce efficiency and hinder the organization's competitive position in its technical environment. To reduce this negative effect, organizations will often *decouple* their technical core from these legitimizing structures. Organizations will minimize or 'ceremonialize' evaluation, and neglect actual implementation of a programme, as they pursue external (and internal) confidence in formal structures, even while some of those structures might actually reduce their efficiency.

Bjorck (2004) explains enactment and (re-)production of institutions, arguing that the social structures discussed above are both imposed on and upheld by the actors, whether they are individuals or organizations. One cognitively-oriented view is that a given institution is encoded as an actor through a socialization process. When internalized, it transforms to a script of patterned behaviour, such as that Sigmund Freud (1962, 2002) wrote about regarding the internalization of the superego. As soon as the actor behaves according to the script, the institution is enacted. In this manner, institutions are continuously (re-)produced. The enactment of an institution externalizes or objectifies it - other actors can see that the institution is in play, and a new round of socialization starts. After some time, the institution (and the resulting behaviour) becomes sedimented and taken-for-granted. By then it might be difficult for the actors even to realize that their behaviour is in fact partly controlled by an institution and script. Acting in accordance with the institution is viewed as rational by those who share the institution (Ali-Hassan 2005).

DiMaggio and Powell (1983) conclude that the net effect of institutional pressures is to increase the homogeneity of organizational structures in an institutional environment. Firms will adopt similar structures as a result of three types of pressures: Coercive, Normative and Mimetic. The three pillars of institutions, as outlined by Scott (1995), are summarized in Table 3.2 and a brief explanation follows.

A) Regulative

Institutional constraints and regulative behaviour elements stress the importance of the regulative process rule-setting, monitoring, and sanctioning activities (Scott 2008, p. 54). Thus, most economists and rational choice theorists have stressed regulative elements (e.g. Moe 1984; North 1990; Williamson 1975). Many researchers have considered the impact of governmental organizations, legislation, and court decisions - all primarily regulative agents - on the structure and activities of organizations. Regulative systems that depend more on external controls - surveillance and sanctioning - are more likely to elicit strategic responses. Compliance with regulations is positively associated with the resources devoted to enforcement (Mezias 1995). Regulatory elements have received attention from institutional economists and political scientists studying rational choice. However, there is growing recognition that, although regulative features are more visible, they can also be more superficial, thinner, and less consequential than normative and cultural elements. Regulatory systems are also more fast-moving and easier to manipulate than other elements, and often give rise to manipulation, gaming, and decoupling, rather than compliance (Evans 2004; Roland 2004). Force, fear, and expedience are central ingredients of regulative pillars, but can be mitigated by the available rules, both formal and informal (Scott 1995, p. 36). Rules alone are not enough to create legitimacy - any basis for change has to cultivate a belief in the change's legitimacy. Coercive pressures come from legal mandates or influence from organizations that the organization is dependent upon.

Table 3.2 - Three pillars of institutions: a schematic of the theory
(Adapted from Scott, 1995)

	Regulative	Normative	Cognitive
Basis of compliance	Expedience	Social obligation	Taken for granted
Indicators	Rules, laws, sanctions	Certification, accreditation	Prevalence, isomorphism
Basis of legitimacy	Legally sanctioned	Morally governed	Culturally supported, conceptually correct
Mechanisms	Coercive	Normative	Mimetic

B) Normative

Normative elements 'introduce a prescriptive, evaluative, and obligatory dimension into social life' (Scott 2008, p. 54). Normative systems include both values and norms. Values are

conceptions that can be applied when constructing standards as a basis for comparison and assessment of existing structures or behaviours. Norms specify how things should be done: they define legitimate means to pursue valued ends. Thus, normative systems define goals or objectives as well as the way(s) recommended pursuing them (Scott 1995, p. 37).

Scott (2004) emphasizes the power of normative agents, such as professional associations, in shaping organizational forms and processes, with those normative elements relying more on internalization processes being less likely to induce only lip service or resistant responses. The normative approach to institutions emphasizes how values and normative frameworks structure choices in a social context that specifies means to particular ends. Actions taken acquire justification in terms of social roles and guidelines for behaviour by socially-mediated normative frameworks. Actors conform because it is expected for them to do so and they are obligated to act as such in normative institutions, the stabilizing influence of social beliefs and norms being both internalized and imposed by others. Normative pressures towards homogeneity come from the similar attitudes and approaches of professional groups and associations, whose members are brought into the firm through hiring practices.

C) Cognitive

Cultural-cognitive elements emphasize the ‘shared conceptions that constitute the nature of social reality and the frames through which meaning is made’ (Scott 2008, p. 57). More recent organizational sociologists and cultural anthropologists have emphasized cognitive elements (e.g. DiMaggio & Powell 1991; Douglas 1986; Scott 2004; Zucker 1977), while theorizing and research has emphasized the cultural-cognitive elements as a basis for institutional analysis (Scott 2008). Cultural cognitive frameworks create and sustain the deeper foundations for institutional forms. In formulating the classificatory systems, assumptions, and premises that underlie institutional logics, they provide the infrastructure on which not only beliefs, but norms and rules rest (Scott 2004). Mimetic pressures occur within this pillar regarding copying successful forms of competitor behaviour and applying them.

3.7 Applying institutional theory to accounting standard setting

For organizations to survive, they have to conform to the rules and belief systems prevalent in the environment (Scott 1995), because it is through institutional isomorphism, both structural and procedural, that organizations gain their legitimacy (Suchman 1995). For instance, multinational corporations (MNCs), operating at the global level, will face diverse pressures,

depending upon each host-country's institutional environments. There is substantial evidence that firms in different types of economies react differently to similar challenges (Knetter 1989). Social, economic and political factors constitute the institutional structure of a particular environment, which provides firms with advantages for engaging in specific types of activities there. Institutional theory has been adopted in numerous studies both in developed and emerging countries. Developments in Egypt and Romania illustrate the theory's application within the context of this thesis. Interested readers are referred to Hossan (2008) regarding Egypt and Albou *et al.* (2011) regarding Romania.

3.7.1 Application of institutional theory to IFRS adoption in Libya

In this thesis, I use functionalist/objective and interpretivist/subjective approaches, as I believe that the strict distinction between objectivist and subjectivist approaches to research is too restrictive. Universal laws cannot explain the causes of social action nor can purely subjective accounts describe the contextual phenomenon as defined by interpretive methodology. Burrell and Morgan (1979) adhere to the lower (non-radical) section of the matrix, as they share with the functionalist paradigm a commitment to ideological perspectives that deal with issues examining natural order and regulation. It is considered here that using both interpretive and functionalist approaches permits complementarity and comparison.

Quantitative methods in research help researchers to detect the variations between elements, but they do not allow researchers to prove why these differences emerge. Therefore, in order to understand the issue under study, a mixed-methods approach will help me to generate important insights. Therefore, both subjectivist and objectivist approaches were selected for this study in order to gain an in-depth understanding of the issues under consideration in this research. I collected two types of data, administering surveys and also conducting interviews to gather additional details. This allows triangulation, an approach which allows the researcher to find out whether the data exhibits any pattern(s) that is evident across both sets of data. Comparison of information is valuable in that it enhances the explanatory usefulness of data. Thus, there are two separate Results chapters in this thesis - the first reports the quantitative results, whilst the second reports the qualitative results.

As mentioned above, I selected institutional theory as my framework because it has been previously applied in accounting change literature and reflects my prior understanding and

beliefs about how society operates. Decoupling is an especially important and relevant concept in the developing world, as it is a key way to resist and undermine Western hegemony whilst still paying lip-service to it. Institutional theory focuses on the deeper and more resilient aspects of social structure. It considers the processes by which structures, including schemes; rules, norms, and routines, become established as authoritative guidelines for social behaviour (Scott 2004). I consider that institutional theory allows the inter-play between institutions, routines, and politics (in the Libyan context) and highlights the complexity of bringing about accounting change in an emerging Islamic country. For example, each developing country, including Libya, has its unique mixture of intra-country specific legal, economic, social, and political institutions, which can be examined through the lens of institutional theory. The recent overthrow of Colonel Gaddafi, and the subsequent breakdown of structures and institutions, shows the vulnerability of Libya to events imposed from the outside. Structures in Libya proved their internal weakness as they could not cope with externally imposed regime change. Thus, talking about IFRS adoption in Libya now (but not when I began this project), while ignoring the collapse of institutional structures post-Gaddafi, would be akin to rearranging deckchairs on the Titanic.

Institutional theory also enables me to examine the processes of developing financial accounting standards in Libya. The institutional analysis can highlight the changes in the patterns of coercive (regulatory framework), normative (professional activities), and mimic mechanisms (sources of experience good practice) over time. I gave out my survey in both 2015 and 2018 so as to record how views changed in response to changes in political events and institutional structures. Institutional theory will assist in understanding the development/adoption of IFRS in Libya, where the framework encourages the processes of legitimation through isomorphic mechanisms. The theory also assists in revealing the pursuit of social legitimacy and power.

Institutional theorists argue that the processes of isomorphism and/or legitimacy represent the central forces. Thus, it is considered that this theory has the potential for explaining why and how several practices have emerged and changed in Libya. This is because various shifts involved in the development of new systems such as IFRS require social legitimacy as a driver, in addition to competitive advantages. In fact, it would be my opinion that the seeking of social legitimacy is the real key.

I also adopt a regulatory rather than radical approach. Social legitimacy is one of the central themes to understand social and political motives behind the development of new societal practices, as in the context of Libyan accounting regulation. This is because the government needs to legitimize its policies and strategies of activities and secure its position. In the case of IFRS adoption, in regard to developing Libyan standards, the process requires IFRS to be adapted to meet the Libyan contextual environment through developing rules such as reporting regulations and improving the culture of accounting professionalization. In recording views about IFRS adoption, in both 2015 and 2018, this thesis allows us to observe how the average opinion changed in response to generation-defining political and social changes. IFRS adoption must be seen within the overall context of a society which desperately needs to regain political and social stability. If this thesis was not presented with this caveat, then the whole thesis might fail to meet standards of social relevance and critical realism.

3.8 Research method - Timing

I now go on to describe and justify the research methods used, having explained the philosophical issues and selection of theory. The time horizon is recognized as the time framework for the project as planned to completion (Saunders *et al.*, 2007). There are two different types of time horizons: cross-sectional and longitudinal (Bryman, 2012). Cross-sectional is when a particular topic is studied at a particular point in time - the data is collected over a narrow time window. It aims 'to find information on the relationship between organisational environment and the effects on organisational behaviours in respect of knowledge management' (Adam & Schvaneveldt 1991). The end result is to gain knowledge on the relationships between and within the gathered data at the present time. When there is a tight time constraint, this is the preferred method of choice. This was my original plan for data-collection. However, I switched university after the first round of collecting survey data in 2015. At my new university, I then agreed with my Director of Studies to collect new data, using the same survey instrument, in 2018. These events turned out to be fortuitous because it meant that I could obtain both cross-sectional and longitudinal data.

Longitudinal research is carried out when there is development or change that occurs over a longer period of time - this approach is most beneficial when researching human behaviours

and development. The ultimate example here might be Marxist Historical Materialism research, which can study developments in the mode of production over hundreds of years as part of the same project. Furthermore it is an extremely important approach if the aim is to examine broad social or economic changes over time (such as, in my case here, the 2015-18 period). Thus, the best way for the reader to approach my results is to view the qualitative results as illuminating and supportive, but the quantitative results as fundamental and foundational.

3.8.1 First: descriptive versus explanatory

Descriptive research is based on depicting and analyzing the characteristics of a specific problem or phenomenon that has a predominant characteristic. I used the descriptive approach, as I aimed at a complete and accurate description of the factors that affect the development of accounting systems and accounting operations in one developing country. These factors may be divided into external factors (the impact of colonialism, globalization, and multinational companies) and internal factors (local laws, taxes, accounting education, and the accounting profession).

Study Approach

To achieve the goals of the study, I used the descriptive method. This involved a field survey approach, which is based on describing the phenomenon and identifying its elements and components by collecting data and analyzing, interpreting, and commenting on them to reach accurate and insightful conclusions about the phenomenon under study.

3.8.2 Second: The study and sample context

Sampling

Saunders *et al.* (2012) write that ‘it may be possible to collect and analyse data from every possible case or group member’, which is termed a census. This is an alternative method to sampling. However, they also articulate some potential hindrances that may make a census approach impossible or infeasible, including restrictions on time available, the costs of gathering all the research data, and issues associated with accessing the data required.

Sampling may be defined as the process of analyzing statistical data where a fixed number of observations are taken from a greater population. Fink (2003, p. 1) states, ‘A good sample is a miniature version of the population of which it is a part - just like it, only smaller’. It was more expedient for me to use a sampling method, due to the restrictions of time and access.

This minimized the quantity of data that I needed to collect (as opposed to the adoption of a census approach).

I define the research context as ‘the complete gathering of elements that share common features and it is also known as’ a group of units that share a set of features that make them similar. It is the society from which we chose the study sample and it is the society that we want to generalize the results to and across.

For the sampling of data for the questionnaire, a convenience sampling method was used. Convenience sampling (also known as haphazard sampling) ‘involves selecting haphazardly those cases that are easiest to obtain for your sample’ (Saunders *et al*, 2012). Convenience sampling has many advantages, such as the low costs associated with using this method and the shorter time required to implement it.

Saunders *et al*. (2012) claim that convenience sampling does have its own set of disadvantages: ‘it is prone to bias and influences that are beyond your control’ and further bias and influence may emerge in the study due to the ease and *ad hoc* nature of gathering the selected participants into a combined group for analysis.

I included government agencies whose nature of work obligates them to apply IFRS, so the study community was limited to the elite of the Libyan financial companies and financial institutions that have dealings with international markets. I gave the surveys to four government-owned entities: (1) the Libyan Audit Bureau, (2) the Libyan Foreign Bank, (3) the Libyan Stock Market, and (4) the Mellitah Oil and Gas Company. In some cases, I went to employees’ offices and waited around for the people to complete and return the forms. In other cases, the companies distributed the surveys to their own workers and I returned several days later to collect them all. I selected these four entities for two main reasons. Firstly, I believed that these entities would help me to achieve the goals of this research. Secondly, the nature of the work of these bodies is external financial dealings, which made it easier for me to learn the main reasons and factors for not applying the IFRS correctly in Libya.

To summarize, workers from four carefully-chosen organizations made up the sample size for the 2015 survey (see Table 3.3). In 2018, I distributed the same survey forms to the same four organizations to enhance comparability of data across the two dates. The total number of

completed survey forms received in 2015 was 160 and the total number of completed survey forms received in 2018 was 146 (total = 306). Of course, it may not have literally been the same set of individuals in 2018, as compared to three years earlier, due to regular turnover of staff. I conclude that my sampling approach was a mix of purposeful and convenience methods. The choice of the four organizations was primarily purposeful, but, within each organization, respondents were mostly chosen based on convenience.

Table 3.3 – Names of surveyed organizations

Number	Companies
1	Libyan Audit Bureau
2	Libyan Foreign Bank
3	Libyan Stock Market
4	Mellitah Oil & Gas Company

(Source: Information and Documentation Management)

Table 3.4 explains the study sample. Overall, I received back 306 usable forms out of the 320 which were distributed. This sample size can be viewed as good-to-very-good (Ndunat & van Zyl 2020, p. 958). Given the small size of Libya’s relatively educated and proficient financial elite, the sample size of 306 (which is for 2015 and 2018 combined) should be seen as more than reasonable under the circumstances. Table 3.4 shows a fairly well-spread sample, although the numbers of useable responses were skewed towards the Audit Bureau and the Foreign Bank. It was not feasible or worthwhile to get the exact same number of respondents from each place, as this would have unnecessarily reduced the total sample size and by a considerable amount.

Table 3.4 - The distribution of questionnaire forms

SOLVED FORMS		EXCLUDED FORMS	DISTRIBUTED FORMS	RESOURCES
THE RATIO %	THE NUMBER			
34%	103	7	110	Libyan Audit Bureau
31%	96	4	100	Libyan Foreign Bank
16%	49	1	50	Libyan Stock Market
19%	58	2	60	Mellitah Oil & Gas Company
100%	306	14	320	TOTAL

3.9 Limitations of questionnaires

One of the frequent limitations in using questionnaires is the low response rate, which might lead to the full picture about respondents' attitudes not being revealed. I avoided this issue because I distributed questionnaires to four large and significant financial organizations. Furthermore, there was very little or no contact between me as the researcher and the individual study participants, which enhances the integrity of the data. I worked as an external auditor in Libya, but I had existing connections within the other three organizations due to the nature of my auditing work. In addition, another limitation could be the participants not fully understanding the questions leading to key information not being forthcoming. Moreover, a lengthy questionnaire may leave the participants not fully completing or disregarding the later questions due to time constraints. I used the responses to the survey questions to develop insightful and relevant interview questions. The research method for interviews is next.

3.10 Interviews as a research method

As suggested by Cassell and Symon (2010) 'the interview remains the most common method of data gathering in qualitative research'. According to a classic source on interview-based research activities: '[a]n interview is a conversation between two or more people that has a

purpose in mind' (Kahn and Connell 1957) Interviews enable researchers to gather valid and reliable primary data that will help to answer the researcher's questions and satisfy her/his research objectives. Similarly, Kvale (1996, p. 14) states that: '[a]n interview is literally an inter-change of views between two persons conversing about a theme of mutual interest'. So, in essence, an interview is still a conversation, but is usually more structured than a conversation, and has a specific purpose, at least as far as the interviewer is concerned. An interviewee might get involved for a mix of personal reasons and/or a desire to share knowledge and perspective with the researcher. The interviewee may want to share a grievance or promote a cause or a prior achievement. Therefore, the researcher must aim to be aware of what motives might be driving or prompting interviewees to get involved. If necessary, bias should be corrected for by the researcher's interpretations of interview data and by accessing interviewees who have diverse backgrounds and/or opinions.

3.11 Types of interviews

There are three fundamental types of research interviews, which are:

- Structured;
- Semi-structured; and
- Unstructured.

The **structured** approach is when all questions are completely predetermined, as is the precise ordering of the questions within each interview. These types of interviews are usually quite quick to complete. Therefore, in a short period of time many interviews can be conducted to achieve a large sample size. However, structured interviews are not very flexible and there is no opportunity to ask new questions, during the interview, as it is essential to follow the interview guide. An example would be employees of a market research firm surveying members of the public in a shopping mall or airport about their opinions, using a standardized list of questions.

By contrast, the **unstructured** approach allows maximum flexibility in the conduct of interviews. These are sometimes known as informal interviews. There is no need for a schedule for this type of interview and open-ended questions can be asked at any point, as well as adding new questions to the interview. They are more flexible and versatile, as the interviewer can adapt or change questions depending on the answers received. This gives the interviewee the chance to talk in-depth, choosing her/his own words, and the opportunity to investigate for a greater understanding of the situation. This may be time-consuming and

expensive compared to collecting data through structured interviews. They are best used in exploratory research contexts where the interviewer begins with a low knowledge and cultural base. For this reason they are useful for ethnographical research in places where the culture differs significantly from the researcher's home-culture. Conversations with research participants, before and after semi-structured interviews, may also take this format. The emphasis is more about learning background things about the context and setting rather than getting answers to pre-specified questions. Possibly the researcher is not yet at the point where she/he can formulate specific questions, at the required skill level; and does not want to risk losing the respect of respondents. Unstructured interviews might well take place at *kava* drinking sessions in Pacific Islands-based research.

3.11.1 Semi-structured

The type of interview chosen for this research project was semi-structured, which allows new ideas to open up during the interview by asking repeated sets of open-ended questions. It allows the interviewee the freedom to express her/his views, offering the interviewer the opportunity to obtain further responses. As an anonymous (2015) contributor explains: '[c]onducted conversationally with one respondent at a time, the semi-structured interview employs a blend of closed- and open-ended questions, often accompanied by follow-up why or how questions'. One of the main advantages of this type of interview is that the researcher can cover a range of topics with open-ended questions. Williams (2015) argues that semi-structured interviews give the interviewee every chance to investigate her/his life history and explain the memories which she/he might have about important events from the past.

Semi-structured interviews are frequently used in qualitative analysis, sometimes in combination with the participant-observation method. The interviewer would already have her/his questions ready to ask, but she/he may not ask them all, in order, depending on which direction the interview is flowing. An interviewer is careful not to disturb a conversation's flow or a respondent's train of thought. To do so might be perceived as heavy-handed, clumsy, arrogant or disrespectful. All the questions may not be asked or answered; instead, the interviewer may have to come up with some other questions, as the interview is taking place, depending on the answers to all the previous questions. Some of these new questions may simply be the interviewer's attempt to get herself or himself up to speed once the conversation ventures into unfamiliar terrain. Williams (2015) states that: 'the order of questions may also change depending on what direction the interview takes. Indeed,

additional questions may be asked, including some which were not anticipated at the start of the interview, as new issues arise'. A good interviewer will always remain alert and adaptable so as to be able to keep up with rapid changes of topics and unexpected digressions. Even if responses go outside the research topic, they may still provide useful background context (perhaps about intentions or values) and, in some cases, the researcher might return to these in follow-up projects. Even jokes and anecdotes can be illuminating. Significantly, Neergaard and Ulhoi (2007) state that: '[t]he goal of qualitative research is to develop concepts that enhance the understanding of social phenomena in natural settings, with due emphasis on the meanings, experiences, and views of all participants'.

I selected a semi-structured interview approach for the present thesis. I first compiled a list of themes and questions that were to be covered within each interview conversation. This approach was chosen as it is suitable for exploring the respondents' perceptions and opinions and also enabled me to probe for more information and to obtain clarification of earlier answers (Barriball & White 2013). The questions were open-ended questions that allowed the participant to answer in full, expressing his/her views and opinions, which would not have been possible had another technique been used. This technique did not only permit genuine information about motivations and challenges to emerge, but also allowed interviewees to open up about any frustrations that they experienced.

During my 2018 trip to Libya, I revisited the four chosen organizations both to give out the survey forms for a second time and to complete the interviews. Some of the interviews were with people from my former organization (Libyan Audit Bureau). The interviewees were all personal contacts and were approached directly rather than via some senior contact point within each organization. Therefore, the sampling method chosen can best be described as convenience sampling. Ten were from the four organizations mentioned previously, and one more was from the private sector. One of the interviewees (referred to throughout this thesis as MAM) sadly passed away in April 2021. It was *not* snowball sampling. For structured interviews, it is suggested that there should be a sample of 5-25 participants. For this research project, eleven (11) interviewees took part; I chose to interview only general managers because of their strategic positions within each organization. Other employees (such as frontline staff, CEOs or global managers) were beyond the scope and focus of this study. Indeed other researchers might want to replicate this study with different target groups. Oakley (1981) reminds us that 'it is important to note that while the interviewer must treat the

interviewee as an object or data-producing machine which, when handled correctly will function properly, the interviewer herself/himself has the same status from the point of view of the person/people, institution or corporation conducting the research'. All interviewees were treated with respect and politeness, within the Arabic cultural context, which was shared by both researcher and all interviewees.

The average interview time was 45 minutes. The shortest interview was 38 minutes and the longest interview took 1 hour and 24 minutes. Due to Arabic cultural factors, some respondents refused to give me their permissions to record their interviews and I was forced to reluctantly accept this additional constraint on the data-collection process. It is important to respect the wishes of interviewees in regard to such a sensitive matter as tape-recording. However, I did take detailed shorthand notes, which I studied carefully in the evenings following each interview.

I carried out the translation process from Arabic to English manually. I transcribed the interviews in Arabic, one-by-one, after listening to the (Arabic language) interview recordings or reading my interview notes. I then created themes as they emerged from the transcripts. Questions 1 and 3 are about the theme of willingness to adopt; Question 2 is about political concepts; Question 4 is about Islamic cultures; Question 5 is about language barriers, whilst Question 6 is about financial statement preparation. I then translated all responses into English for each participant in succession. I subsequently put all English responses to Question 1 together and so on for the responses to all the other questions. Every part of each interview was translated, not just key quotes.

The interview questions are reproduced here as follows:

(Q1) From your personal experience, and with regard to Libyan society and its accounting systems do you think there is an urgent need to adopt such standards in the Libyan capital market and why?

(Q2) From your personal knowledge and understanding of Libyan reality and the political changes since 2011, what might be the challenges to the adoption and application of IFRS?

(Q3) In the organization/institution where you work, do you think you or your colleagues may really intend to adopt these standards and what are the reasons for their attitudes?

(Q4) Do you think that there are any aspects of Islamic culture that will affect the process of introducing these standards to Libya?

(Q5) IFRSs are issued in English but their application in Libya requires Arabic translation. Do you think that after the required translation that the criteria will have the same intended meaning as in the original language?

(Q6) What is your opinion on the operations and procedures for preparing financial statements in Libya and how the users perceive these operations and procedures?

(Q7) Do you want to add or clarify any points that may be significant in adopting IFRS?

It should be noted that, due to internal political and security reasons, some respondents did not offer me detailed and candid answers, in large part due to the sensitivity of, and divided views about, recent events in Libya. Because of the lack of interesting and candid answers, I chose to primarily highlight the quantitative results, rather than the qualitative results and thus I have placed the quantitative results chapter first, ahead of the qualitative one. Details of all interviewees can be found in Table 3.5 (below).

Table 3.5 - Details of interviewees

Respondents	Age	G	Job Title	Organization	Experience (years)	Qualification
ISA Res 1	55	M	GM	LSM	30	M Acc., Libya
MOA Res 2	50	M	GM	LAB	26	PhD Acc., Serbia
SAB Res 3	54	M	GM	LFB	31	PhD Bus. Mgt., Egypt
BMK Res 4	37	M	GM	LFB	11	Bachelor Acc., Libya
AMB Res 5	47	M	GM	LSM	10	Bachelor Acc., Libya
MAM Res 6*	55	M	GM	LAB	15	PhD Acc., UK
ESA Res 7	55	M	GM	LFB	30	M Acc., Libya
MA Res 8	49	M	GM	LAB	15	PhD Finance Banking, Serbia
TMA Res 9	46	M	GM	LAB	20	PhD Acc., Jordan
MAA Res10	44	M	GM	MOGC	19	HD Finance & Banking, Libya
AAA Res 11	43	M	GM	PS	18	M Finance Planning, Libya

Libyan Audit Bureau (LAB), Libyan Foreign Bank (LFB), Libyan Stock Market (LSM), Melita Oil and Gas Company (MOGC), Private Sector (PS). *denotes a now deceased person.

3.12 Shortcomings of interviews

One of the limitations of interviews is that the interviewer may send unconscious signals which may lead the respondent to give answers that are expected by the interviewer. Furthermore, the interviewer may not know whether the respondent is lying, which throws the validity of the information gathered into doubt. The researcher should maintain his/her own composure and let the interviewee flow to avoid having biased data (May 1997). All facts, as opposed to opinions, presented by interviewees should be checked against reliable secondary sources and facts given by other interviewees. Lastly, such interviews are time-consuming in terms of writing the questions, finding interviewees, and interviewing.

3.13 Ethical Consideration

Blumberg *et al.* (2005) define ethics as ‘referring to the appropriateness of one’s project.’ This research was carried out in conformity with the University of the West of Scotland’s ethical guidelines and was approved by an Ethics Committee. Before interviews and questionnaires were handed out, a cover note was given to let the participants know the purpose of the study and the researcher’s aims and objectives. Furthermore all participants were made aware that the questionnaire and interviews were to be confidential. Saunders *et al.* (2009) suggest that: ‘[y]ou will also need to gain informed consent from those whom you wish to be your intended participants as well as those who act as organisational gatekeepers, granting you access’. Consent was received from the participants and they were assured that the interview data obtained would not be misinterpreted or misused in any way. Each participant was given the right to withdraw from his interview at any time with no pressure, as all meetings were voluntary. To report results of this research, initials are used to identify each study participant. This ensures effective anonymity within the context of the study as combinations of initials are not idiosyncratic enough to allow for identification.

3.14 Conclusion

I used the first part of this chapter to explain various philosophical viewpoints presented in the accounting literature by, in historical order, Burrell and Morgan (1979), Chua (1986), and Laughlin (1995). The first authors presented four widely-accepted paradigms. A key section presented alternative perspectives from Chua, i.e. the interpretive approach and critical approach, both viable alternatives to the current mainstream approaches, and Laughlin’s three dimensions. The next section presented the choice and justification of the selected paradigm for this study together with the theoretical framework for the present research process on IFRS in Libya. I then introduced, explained, and justified my actual research methods and presented a section which addressed ethical considerations and the steps taken by me to address and mitigate these. A key table lists details of the study’s 11 interviewees.

From my viewpoint, highlights of my research method include the following: (a) use of both questionnaires and interviews as part of a strategic mixed-method approach; (b) a good sample size of 306 being reached for the surveys, and all of these respondents being knowledgeable financial experts, sub-divided into the categories of owners/partners, auditors, staff accountants, senior accountants or academics; (c) the identical questionnaire was distributed to the same four organizations, in both 2015 and 2018, which, importantly,

allowed for the results to adopt a longitudinal perspective; and (d) the results are presented in a way that enables me to document and present significant differences in certain responses based on gender, age-bracket, and qualifications. This was achievable due to accessing reasonable numbers of male and female respondents across various different age-brackets, job descriptions, and qualification levels.

Chapter 4 Part A: Literature review (harmonization)

4.1 Introduction

The adoption of IFRS for listed companies in many countries has been one of the most important developments in the recent history of accounting (Daske *et al* 2008). This worldwide reform has involved adapting domestic accounting practices, to some extent, to harmonize them with the practices of the IFRS, and about 120 nations presently allow their listed companies, and in some cases other types of companies as well, to apply IFRS. It has become an international trend, generally recognized around the world as ‘best practice’ (Obaidat 2007).

After the adoption of IFRS, most countries are faced with the daunting task of effectively implementing these standards in practice; hence in this study the words ‘adoption’ and ‘implementation’ have very different meanings. In fact, it is generally agreed that developing economies face a variety of challenges in regard to implementing IFRS. Furthermore, the adoption process and its results differ from one country to another (Albu *et al.* 2011). In certain developing countries, for example, in Mauritius (an Indian Ocean island nation), the implementation of IFRS was considered a success, as it was carried out in phases (Boolakay 2010). Other countries, for example, Zimbabwe, reviewed the IFRS and adopted only those aspects regarded as relevant to their national development (Chamisa 2000). In contrast, countries such as Kuwait and Pakistan, adopted IFRS without modifications, which subsequently led to a high level of non-compliance and resulted in the failures of their implementation processes (Mir & Rahaman 2005).

Part A of this chapter is organized as follows: Section 4.2 provides an introduction to the process of harmonization; Section 4.3 defines harmonization and its major forms; Section 4.4 discusses challenges to IFRS harmonization; Section 4.5 explains the global harmonization process, whilst harmonization within an Islamic context is discussed in Section 4.6. Section 4.7 offers a concise conclusion to this part-chapter.

4.2 Introduction to processes of harmonization

The aim of this section is to conduct a critical analysis of the literature regarding the harmonization of accounting standards and, in the process, to examine how different

countries have applied the harmonization process. The harmonization process is examined from a global perspective then narrowed down to the Islamic context, and further down to the Libyan perspective, which is the main focus of this study. Harmonization stems from the idea of a single global set of accounting standards, which is clearly conceptually appealing (Barth *et al.* 2008; Boolaky 2010; Chalmers *et al.* 2011). However, the harmonization process, in relation to IFRS, may in some cases involve different stages, formats, and approaches, particularly when countries are involved in the processes of compliance with new accounting standards and compromise is probable (Callao *et al.* 2007; Chua & Taylor 2008; Dhivya, 2011; Doupnik & Perera 2014).

Globally, harmonization in some form has been taking place for several decades. As indicated above, harmonization is an ongoing process. While some countries have been striving to harmonize their domestic standards with the IFRS, others have progressed to the stage of implementation. Consequently, some researchers have investigated the degree of harmonization between the domestic accounting standards of a given country (or a country's accounting policies) with the IFRS. In its simplest form, harmonization occurs whenever a country aligns its domestic accounting standards to agree with the IFRS over a period of time (Ernst & Young 2011; Fontes *et al.* 2005; Gyasi 2010; Jaafar & McLeay 2007; Kvaal & Nobes 2011; Qu *et al.* 2012). However, for countries which are less developed, following the IFRS has not always proved to be entirely beneficial, while some developing-country organizations are not comfortable with following these standards (Catuogno & Allini 2011; Nobes 2009; Pocrnjic & Pervan 2013; Taplin 2010).

4.3 Defining harmonization and its major forms

Various authors have attempted to define harmonization. For example, Nobes and Parker (2012) define the harmonization of worldwide accounting standards as the process of reconciling different points of view. From their perspective, harmonization attempts to 'increase the compatibility of accounting practices by setting bounds to their degree of variation' (Nobes & Parker 2012, p. 81). This implies the harmonization of dissimilar accounting standards with global IFRS standards. However, this does not mean eradicating the other standards completely; rather, as argued by Choi and Mueller (1978), harmonization means that different standards may prevail in particular countries, as long as they are in harmony with each other. Harmonization thus refers to a process of reducing unnecessary

differences in accounting across countries, while retaining a degree of flexibility. Harmonization allows different countries to have different standards as long as the standards do not conflict. Research into the harmonization process reveals two distinctive forms: *De jure* harmonization and *de facto* harmonization, which are discussed below.

4.3.1 De jure harmonization and de facto harmonization

The literature reveals that harmonization can be examined in terms of adopted standards or accounting behaviours (Ding *et al.* 2007; Fontes *et al.* 2005; Jaafar & McLeay 2007; Nair & Frank 1980; Nobes 2004; Tay & Parker 1990). Hence, IFRS harmonization can take two main forms: material (*de facto*) harmonization and formal (*de jure*) harmonization (Nobes, 2011).² Formal harmonization, also known as *de jure* harmonization, focuses on harmonization of adopted standards and other regulations. *De facto* is about the process of actual implementation, in the form of observed practices and the basis for achieving formal harmonization. For example, an early study by Evans and Taylor (1982) investigated the impact of five IAS on 50 corporate financial reports from five nations for the period 1975 to 1980. They found that the IAS had a slight influence on corporate accounting activities. In addition, the accounts of 200 US companies were examined by Nobes (1990) who concluded that there was less than 50% compliance with IAS where US GAAP is silent on specific matters. In a study relating to a single accounting issue, goodwill accounting, Cairns (1996), found that 50 international corporations displayed a lack of conformity with IAS.

Formal harmonization, also called *de jure* harmonization, focuses on the harmonization of rules and regulations (Van der Tas 1992) and is viewed from a theoretical perspective in terms of similarities and differences between rules and regulations of various countries. Harmonization has been characterized as a ‘moving target’, and surveys by international accounting firms have been utilized to study the extent of *de jure* harmonization. For instance, Larson and Kenny (1999) investigated harmonization between 1991 and 1995 exploiting data from Coopers and Lybrand (1991, 1993) and PW (1995) studies. However, such studies have been criticized on the basis that they were not adequately reliable and hence conclusions drawn may not be suitable (Nobes 1987).

² De jure (‘by law’) imposed by law; de facto (‘by fact’) by fact or circumstance.

4.3.2 Qualitative and quantitative research

Prior studies on accounting harmonization may also be characterized as either qualitative or empirical. Many of the qualitative studies on accounting harmonization have focused on the perceived merits of harmonization and the implications for standard setters. Vishwanath and Kaufmann (2001) investigated the role of increased transparency in enhancing financial stability and suggested specific recommendations on policy-making and enforcement for the effective operation of financial markets. They argue that transparency is indispensable to the financial sector and describe its desirable characteristics: access, timeliness, relevance, and quality. The findings emphasize the developing institutional infrastructure, standards, and accounting practices that are needed to promote transparency. The study also recommends the implementation of incentives for disclosure and establishing regulations. It shows the limits which exist for transparency because of the lack of adequate enforcement. These authors go on to make the further point that adequate enforcement is predicated on broader reforms in the public sector.

In another empirical study, Boolaky (2006) used content analysis to compare IFRS with the Local Accounting Standards (LAS) of South Africa (SA), Mauritius and Tanzania. The findings revealed that, except for Tanzania, the local accounting standards of the two other countries at that time were more or less similar to IFRS. As regards the level of harmony between the local accounting standards and IFRS, the score-card revealed that the accounting standards of SA were most in harmony with IFRS, followed by Mauritius. Similarly, Canibano and Mora (2000) empirically analyzed prior research on accounting harmonization. The study focused on the processes of harmonization of accounting practices within the European Union. Predictably, the findings showed that there had been greater conformity in the accounting practices of companies operating in the international arena.

In another study, Stergios and Laskaridou (2008) used data from Greek listed companies on the Athens Stock Exchange to analyze whether, by aiming at compliance with IFRS, the country had reached the desired level of harmonization. The results showed that, across a three-year period, there had been a positive and statistically significant improvement in disclosure quality after IFRS/IAS adoption. They also put forward the view that harmony should reflect properly the different circumstances under which firms operate in their quests for efficiency and conformity. Likewise, Pocrnjic and Pervan (2013) empirically analyzed harmonization of financial reporting, its development, the effects of globalization on financial

reporting harmonization and how financial reporting harmonization is measured. The authors indicate that harmonization of financial reporting is an outcome of the globalization of financial markets and of economic integration.

4.4 Challenges to IFRS harmonization

The following cultural, economic, legal and financial factors are perhaps the greatest challenges for the implementation of IFRS in developing economies:

1. Cultural factors

Hofstede's Model has been the key model employed with respect to cultural contextual factors that explains the effects of culture on accounting systems (Chow *et al.* 1995). The main cultural factor is the deficiency of accounting specialists in emerging nations, owing to the flaws or insufficient standards in accounting education. Chow *et al.* (1995) further added that new standards may not be appropriate to a new nation, owing to the cultural differences. Gray (1988) contends that the culture of emerging nations tends to be collectivist, where culture and individuals' ideal characteristics differ by social role, and behaviour is influenced by contextual factors (Church 2006), which in turn involves a low level of accounting expertise. Additionally, Gray (1988) has shown that a high level of uncertainty avoidance is prevalent in emerging countries, i.e. 'the extent to which the members of a culture feel threatened by uncertainty and ambiguity along with their eagerness to avoid such situations' (Hofstede 2001, p. 83), created by cultural factors. This may affect the level of freedom of information and disclosure acceptable in these nations (Kantor *et al.* 1995). Therefore, external auditors might encounter problems obtaining information required, particularly the negative information that might damage organizations (Arpan & Radebaugh 1985).

2. Economic factors

Cooke and Wallace (1990) found that accounting standards have a close relation with the business environmental issues that determine economic growth. Similarly, Sedaghat *et al.* (1994) highlighted the positive relation between financial growth and accounting information in emerging nations. Governments in several nations with emerging economies tend to interfere in economic development in their attempts to create radical economic structures. The extent to which the government interferes in the country's economy is positively associated with the set of accounting standards in use. For example, if the government is the

key handler of accounting standards, this would influence the accounting standards that are used in the country (Zeghal & Mhedhbi 2006).

The World Bank ranks many Arab countries, such as Egypt, as low income, while others are classified as high income, such as the Gulf countries. According to Kantor *et al.* (1995), the majority of Arab countries had economically inefficient stock markets at that time and they suggested that the accounting systems in the Arab countries aim mainly to fulfil the governments' needs. However, some of the Arab countries subsequently started to change the nature of their systems in order to increase the efficiency of their stock markets (Zeghal & Mhedhbi 2006). Those developing countries that have substantial FDI are more likely to view the adoption of IFRS positively than those that do not. This is due to the need to satisfy the foreign investors who have invested in these countries and to maximize their shareholders' wealth (Chamisa 2000).

3. Legal factors and sources of finance

In the emerging nations, the legal system is another factor that impacts accounting structures. Although some developing nations are affected by the legal systems of the advanced countries, the legal systems, in the Arab states are influenced by the tenets of the Islamic faith. Therefore, the accounting systems in the Arab states are subject to particular requirements that are different from those in emerging nations where there is a strict partition between government and faith.

4. Sources of finance

The basis of the economy is an additional important issue that impacts the accounting systems in emerging countries. For instance, Nobes (1998) demonstrated that the differences in sources of finance across different nations might result in differences in their accounting systems. Nobes (1998) pointed out that the sources of finance might be internal, for instance from government, family, and banks, or they might be from external sources, such as stakeholders, FDI, and IMF. He also emphasized that the majority of the emerging nations including his subject of study, the UAE, are grounded on internal finance sources, which need appropriate and regular accounting data to ensure transparency of financial information and disclosure of financial information that is relevant to the domestic stakeholders. However, the progress of the stock market in the UAE developed significantly to include external economic suppliers that need better disclosure to the wider community so as to

increase the commercial capacity of the stock market (Tyrrall *et al.* 2007). It is significant that the World Bank and the IMF require the implementation of IFRS in order to offer capital to emerging countries (Karim 2001).

However, in more recent research, Ramanna and Sletten (2011) did not find that adoption decisions are related to the level of (or expected changes in) foreign trade and investment flows. Rather, they argue that a country is more likely to adopt IFRS when its trade partners or regional neighbours adopt it.

4.5 The global harmonization process

The accounting world has continued to evolve. The existence of multiple different accounting standards worldwide raises the need for common ground in terms of accounting principles. According to Nobes (2011) and Saundi (2010) the IASB reported that more than 100 countries, as at that date, required or permitted the use of IFRS. As indicated above, harmonization is often regarded as important as it enables financial information to be interpreted and understood internationally. However, the IFRS has to be harmonized with the country-specific standards and sometimes this process varies among countries.

The global variations in IFRS implementation were considered by Nobes and Zeff (2008) who discussed the different ways of harmonization. The first involves following the standard-setter's process of setting accounting standards and accepting everything. The second is endorsing IFRS on a standard-by-standard basis, as issued by the IASB, with the possibility existing of not fully endorsing some of the standards. The third is making it optional for corporations to adhere to the standards issued by the IASB. Finally limited acceptance of IASB standards is possible. These different methods of harmonization on a voluntary basis are illustrated in Figure 4.1 and will be considered below.

Figure 4.1 - Methods of harmonization

(Source: Adopted from: Zeff & Nobes, 2010)

4.5.1 Adoption of IFRS

This is the unmodified and simplest form of IFRS harmonization, where regulations require companies to comply with IFRS, as issued by IASB. Since the official announcement of the mandatory adoption and implementation of IFRS in the European Union in 2002, accounting research has examined this process, especially the impact, progress, and difficulties which it has generated (Callao *et al.* 2007). Malaysia and Japan offer useful examples regarding adoption of IFRS and are now considered.

On 1 August 2008, the Financial Reporting Foundation, which oversees the operations of the Malaysian Accounting Standards Board (MASB), issued a statement about their plan for the full convergence of the MFRS with the IFRS by 1 January 2012. On 17 November 2011, the MASB also issued a new MASB-approved accounting framework, the Malaysian Financial Reporting Standards (MFRS Framework), which is a fully IFRS-compliant framework and equivalent to IFRS. The MFRS Framework comprises standards as issued by the IASB that were effective after 1 January 2012. It also comprises new and revised standards more recently issued by the IASB and first effective after 1 January 2012, such as standards on financial instruments, consolidation, joint arrangements, fair-value measurement, and

employee benefits. The adoption of the MFRS Framework allowed Malaysian entities to assert that their financial statements were in full compliance with IFRS.

Some countries retain their indigenous standards and harmonize these with IFRS, by converging their indigenous standards with IFRS over time. Japanese Accounting Standards ('Japanese GAAP') are developed by the Accounting Standards Board of Japan (ASBJ), which was established in 2001. Under an agreement between the ASBJ and the IASB, known as the Tokyo Agreement (August 2007), the ASBJ had been working to converge the requirements of Japanese Accounting Standards with IFRS. The achievements under the agreement were jointly announced in June 2011 by the ASBJ and the IASB. Meanwhile, Japanese GAAP is not identical to IFRS but, since 2008, it has been considered by the EU to be equivalent to the IFRS adopted by the European Union (EU). Japanese listed companies, or those applying for a listing, use designated IFRS in their consolidated financial statements on a voluntary basis, and must establish internal processes to ensure appropriate reporting under designated IFRS. Officers and employees in place must have sufficient knowledge of the subject.

4.5.2 Standard-by-standard

Standard-by-standard adherence can take two major forms: standards as issued by the IASB and standards as issued by the IASB with some exceptions.

Standard-by-standard as issued by IASB

Different parts of the world have different forms of harmonization - the response of the EU countries has been mainly to endorse the IFRS (Zeghal *et al.* 2011). This involves detailed scrutiny of all IFRS output, standard-by-standard, amendment-by-amendment, and many bodies are involved in this process (Martins *et al.* 2012; Pocrnjic & Pervan 2013). According to Nobes (2011), parts of a standard or even a complete standard may not receive support. For example, parts of IAS 39 (on the recognition and measurement of financial instruments) have been removed. Canada has adopted IFRS, as issued by IASB, and its accounting procedures for regulatory assets and liabilities have been changed accordingly. The country made a public commitment towards IFRS because it was perceived to be a single set of high-quality global standards. In January 2006, Canada's Accounting Standards Board (hereafter AcSB) ratified a new Strategic Plan for the Direction of Accounting Standards that significantly affected the way financial reporting is carried out in Canada. The AcSB pursued

separate strategies for three major categories of reporting entities: public companies, private businesses, and not-for-profit organizations as follows:

(a) For public companies: The AcSB wanted to move to a single set of globally-accepted standards and concluded that this objective would be best served by converging Canadian GAAP with IFRS over a transitional period. Thus, since 2011, Canadian GAAP has ceased to exist as a separate, distinct basis of financial reporting for their public companies. A long-term weakness of this situation is that local expertise in debating and preparing standards is rarely tested any more in practice and so these talents may disappear over time. Furthermore, the country's complex standard-setting apparatus is replaced with a simple rubber-stamping system which non-professionals can do. This has happened in Australia, to a large extent, since IFRS adoption in 2005.

(b) For private businesses: The AcSB has begun, as a matter of urgency, a comprehensive examination of their financial reporting needs and will determine the most appropriate model for meeting those needs. Applying the IFRS for SMEs has been considered but was rejected.

(c) For not-for-profit organizations: The AcSB continues to apply those elements of GAAP for profit-oriented enterprises that are applicable to their circumstances and develops other standards dealing with the special circumstances of the not-for-profit sector.

Standard-by-standard, as issued by IASB, but with deletions

Historically, Europe has experienced some difficulties when trying to make meaningful comparisons of financial statements across borders. This is mostly due to diverse legal systems, combined with other political and economic factors. Prior to harmonization, each European country reported financial statements using extremely diverse, country-specific accounting systems (Kvaal & Nobes 2010, 2011; Li 2010). Consequently, members of the EU were the first countries to move towards harmonization of accounting standards (Chua & Taylor 2008; Gebhard & Novotny-Farkas 2011). The EU issued several directives in the 1970s and 1980s to harmonize financial reporting practices so as to reduce diversity and facilitate cross-border investments and cross-listings. In the 1990s, accounting harmonization progressed with the improvement of IAS (the precursor of IFRS), harmonization events in the EU economy (e.g. adoption of a single currency), and political changes. IFRS adoption was not mandatory until 2005, but firms in some European countries were allowed to use IAS as a

substitute for domestic accounting standards by the late-1990s. The EU has achieved its harmonization objectives through the Directives, namely the Fourth and Seventh EC (European Community) Directives, which must be incorporated into the laws of the member states (i.e. the countries in the EU). One important aspect of the regulation of IFRS is that it must be endorsed for use in the EU countries and a part of this is an endorsement mechanism, as established by the EU Commission. The essence of the endorsement mechanism is to obtain political and legal endorsement for IAS.

The implementation of IFRS has generated major impacts in most European countries (Chalmers *et al.* 2011; Zeghal *et al.* 2011). Over the last few years, the European Federation of Accountants (*Federation des Experts Europeans* - FEE) has been actively involved in the debate on financial reporting strategies in Europe. The EU Commission proposed a regulation on the application of IFRS to introduce a requirement for listed companies to use IFRS with effect from the 2005 financial year for their consolidated accounts. Under this situation, individual member states of the EU have the option of applying IFRS to companies' individual accounts. In March 2002, the European Parliament voted and approved the IAS regulation. Its enforcement is built substantially on effective policing by the national enforcement bodies of member states. Enforcement bodies should provide information to other regulatory or supervisory authorities or private oversight bodies with a view to them imposing sanctions where appropriate.

IFRS issued by IASB have been adopted by the EU with deletions. Notwithstanding, the titles and numbering of the standards have not changed. For instance, IAS 39: *Financial Instruments: Recognition and Measurement* generally requires measurement at fair-value, ideally based on a quoted price in an active market. However, in the absence of an active market, IAS 39 requires the use of techniques that involve net present values of cash flows discounted at appropriate rates of interest. IAS 39 was subsequently amended, removing the option to record financial liabilities at fair-value, and the ARC approved the amended version (Gebhardt & Novotny-Farkas 2011; Marques-Ramos 2011). All listed EU companies have been required to use IFRS since 2005. In order to be approved for use in the EU, standards must be endorsed by the Accounting Regulatory Committee (ARC), which includes representatives of member state governments and is advised by a group of accounting experts known as the European Financial Reporting Advisory Group (Guggiola 2010; Jagtab 2013).

As a result IFRS as applied in the EU may differ from that used elsewhere. It is important to note that part of the standard IAS 39 was not originally approved by the ARC.

4.5.3 Optional harmonization of IFRS

Although IASB recommends adoption of IFRS by countries, it is not compulsory for all countries to adopt IFRS - it is optional. There are three basic approaches to harmonization of IFRS at country level - countries that unite their accounting standards with IFRS; countries that have allowed voluntary/optional use of IFRS, and countries that require IFRS adoption only for some types of companies. Taiwan is a good example of a country that implements IFRS adoption with optional aspects. On 14 May 2009, the Financial Supervisory Commission (FSC) of Taiwan announced its roadmap for the implementation of IFRS in Taiwan. The IFRS implementation plan was in two phases. Listed companies and financial institutions supervised by the FSC, except for credit cooperatives, credit card companies and insurance intermediaries, were required to adopt Taiwan-IFRS, starting in 2013. However, adoption in 2012 was optional for companies that had already issued securities overseas or had registered an overseas securities issuance with the FSC or had a market capitalization of greater than NT\$10 billion (Kvaal & Nobes 2010).

Convergence in the context of harmonization means the process of converging or bringing together international standards issued by the IASB and existing standards issued by national standard setters, with the aim of eliminating alternatives in accounting for economic transactions and events (Marques-Ramos 2011; Mustata & Matis 2010; Obazee 2007). Optional harmonization of IFRS has important implications, as the ultimate objective of convergence is to achieve a single set of internally-consistent, high-quality global standards, issued by the IASB and adopted by national standard-setters (Guggiola 2010; Jaafar & McLeay 2007; Pocrnjic & Pervan 2013). Hence, convergence is a process which promotes reduction of differences between IFRS and the accounting standards of countries that retain their own standards. Consequently, optional harmonization of IFRS can defeat the primary purpose of convergence, thereby reducing cross-border comparability and free flow of capital across jurisdictions.

4.5.4 Not fully converged IFRS harmonization

Despite the benefits of IFRS, several countries have adopted IFRS with exceptions, i.e. not fully adopting the IFRS model. Under the convergence approach, some countries do not either adopt IFRS as issued by the IASB or incorporate IFRS into their accounting standards

directly. Such countries maintain their own local standards but make efforts to converge these bodies of standards with IFRS over time (Barth *et al.* 2008; Chalmers *et al.* 2010). The implication of such practice is that there are different versions of IFRS in different countries. China and Venezuela are examples of countries using this type of not-fully-converged approach.

China has moved its standards closer to IFRS without incorporating IFRS fully into its national financial reporting framework. However, China has indicated that it intends to eventually eliminate the existing differences between its Accounting Standards for Business Enterprises and IFRS (Baker *et al.* 2010; Qu *et al.* 2012). The Accounting Regulatory Department of the Ministry of Finance of China is the official standard-setting body in the People's Republic of China. The department is responsible for the setting of accounting standards for business enterprises. China has adopted national accounting standards that are substantially converged with IFRS as a set of high-quality global accounting standards. All Chinese companies whose securities trade in a public market in China are required to use Chinese Accounting Standards for Business Enterprises (ASBEs) for financial reporting within mainland China. However, Chinese companies whose securities trade on the Stock Exchange of Hong Kong may choose among IFRS, Hong Kong Financial Reporting Standards (HKFRS), and Chinese Accounting Standards (ASBEs) for purposes of financial reporting to Hong Kong investors. Those reports are in addition to the ASBE financial reports that the Chinese companies issue within mainland China. As of 30 June 2014, a total of 296 Chinese companies were trading in Hong Kong. Based on accounting law in China, all the Chinese companies must comply with the accounting standards issued by China's Ministry of Finance. Since foreign companies do not trade currently in Chinese securities markets, there is no relevant regulation on whether those companies are permitted to use IFRS.

4.6 Harmonization and Islamic Accounting

Islam is an ethical religion with strong ethics and codes of conduct when it comes to business – in terms of social justice, fairness, and equality. With regards to this, loyalty to *Sharia'a* has obliged the IFIs to set their own accounting strategy, as a result of their discontent with conventional accounting (Suandi 2013). According to Ibrahim (2003), Islamic accounting can be distinguished as the accounting process which offers suitable information to stakeholders

of any unit which will allow them to make sure that the unit is always functioning within the bounds of the Islamic *Sharia'a* and operating to further its socioeconomic objectives.

4.6.1 Background to Islamic accounting

In this context it is necessary to set out the background of Islamic accounting. The history of Islamic accounting emanates from Islamic finance, which started from the period between the 6th and 12th centuries when Islamic commercial bonds were utilized as financial goods. However, they eventually disappeared when Islamic civilization weakened in the thirteenth century (Jamaldeen 2012). Islamic finance re-emerged in 1963, when Mit Ghamar in Egypt established a savings bank with the idea of profit-sharing (Jamaldeen 2012; Sharawy 2000). Although it was shut in 1967 for political reasons, Mit Ghamar stimulated the growth of many other Islamic banks in later periods. There was an increase in the number of Islamic banks in the late 1970s and early 1980s. However, the changing political circumstances in many Muslim countries saw the creation of some Islamic financial institutions minus the label of Islam to avoid the negative worldviews towards the religion (Sharawy 2000).

The Islamic context shows how religious and cultural factors present serious challenges to the harmonization process. Although the banks follow IFRS, the harmonization of IFRS in Islamic states has been quite limited. Unlike other Islamic countries around the world, the UAE desires to participate in FDI. One challenge for the UAE is likely to be the culture of secrecy, common in countries that have not previously been required to report financial information to a regulatory body. However, this could be alleviated by the ease with which expertise can be imported, particularly given the UAE's tax incentives (Nasir & Zainol 2007).

4.6.2 IFRS and Islamic Accounting

Although IFIs have now become an important part of the international financial services landscape, the differences between Islamic principles and generally accepted principles in accounting have made Islamic accounting difficult to harmonize with IFRS (Saundi 2010). Fisho-Oridedi (2000) notes that the reappearance of Islamic thinking, as well as its economic system in the early 1960s, happened at the same time as economic nationalism in many states in the Middle East, including the Gulf Co-operation Council (GCC), which was trying to take back its natural resources from foreign interests.

The specific requirements of the Islamic world have been the driving force behind the development of Islamic accounting. This, therefore, means that Islamic accounting cannot easily be harmonized with conventional accounting. In the same manner, *Sharia'a* principles will influence, but not determine, the accounting treatment of Islamic finance products and transactions under IFRS. It is also important to note that the accounting treatment does not determine whether a transaction is permitted under *Sharia'a* law or not.

In an attempt to ease the harmonization process, the Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (hereafter AAOIFI), a non-profit organization based in Bahrain, has played a very important role in preparing accounting, governance, and ethical standards for IFIs (Saundi 2010). Currently, accounting standards authorities in some countries have also developed Islamic accounting standards focusing on guiding IFIs, based on the AAOIFI's standards and pronouncements. Indonesia, for example, has developed its own Islamic accounting standards but also refers to the AAOIFI's standards and pronouncements for issues unspecified in its own standards.

IFRS do not fully cover the characteristics of transactions of Islamic financial institutions and there are definitely areas of Islamic finance that are not adequately covered by global standards, as Islamic financial transactions are unique compared to conventional ones. For instance, the payment of *Sharia'a* funds is an Islamic investment transaction. These funds should be reported as liability under IFRS, although they do not completely match the characteristics of a liability. Hence, many countries either fully adopt or use as references the AAOIFI's standards to develop Islamic accounting standards for setting local standards for IFIs. Although differences in those Islamic accounting standards still exist, all of them take Islamic law as the common basis for setting their standards (Suandi 2012). IFRS is clearly different from Islamic accounting as the latter attempts to comply with *Sharia'a* to achieve socio-economic objectives. On the other hand, adopting IFRS may result in improved comparability and foreign mutual ownership (DeFond, Hu, Hung & Li 2011), leading to situations where IFIs may have to bear the consequences of using separate standards.

Abdullah (2010) identifies four possible options or available choices for Islamic accounting regarding the harmonization process with the IFRS, and these are illustrated in Figure 4.2. The first is exclusivity: Islamic transactions are treated with separate standards which exist alongside the conventional counterpart. Exclusivity means that Islamic accounting becomes a

parallel scheme of accounting in concert with its conventional counterpart (Mohamad 2010). Hence, any Islamic financial apparatus will utilize Islamic accounting practices. The second choice is adaptation, where IFRS are altered to embed Islamic principles. With this option, it is possible that major changes to IFRS may have to be applied. The third one is convergence, where IFRS are adjusted - both sides function together to attain harmony. The last option is adoption, which can be divided into authorization and pure adoption. In the option of authorization, certain exemptions are still allowed, while pure adoption does not allow for any exemptions (Suandi 2012, p. 253).

Figure 4.2 - The possible options for Islamic Accounting

(Source: adopted from Abdullah 2010)

Although harmonization may be contextualized in the Islamic context, it is clear from the above explanation and diagram, that it is difficult to adopt current Western or conventional accounting to create a form of accounting acceptable to Islam. This is because IFIs differ from their conventional counterparts by having to adhere to Islamic principles and rules, and also by trying to achieve socio-economic objectives encouraged by Islam. However, choosing

one option over others may result in different consequences (Callao *et al.* 2007). As a result, Nasir and Zainol (2007) also doubt whether it is feasible to create a common accounting language, since IFRS, which is dominated by Anglo-American accounting thought and practices, is trying to achieve very economically-oriented objectives. It is thus different from Islamic accounting, which attempts to comply with *Sharia'a* to achieve socio-economic objectives. On the other hand, DeFond *et al.* (2011) point out that adopting IFRS may result in improved comparability and foreign mutual ownership. IFIs may thus have to bear the consequences of using separate standards. These religious issues may, therefore, pose ongoing challenges for the harmonization process in the Islamic countries.

Exclusivity & adoption

There are two polar extremes, exclusivity and adoption. Exclusivity is where Islamic transactions are treated with separate standards, which exist alongside their conventional counterparts. Mohamad (2010) argues that any Islamic financial transactions can only be documented by utilizing Islamic accounting principles. At the extreme, countries could explicitly prohibit reporting under IFRS. Adoption of IFRS means full-scale implementation or usage of IFRS without any variation (Odia & Ogiedu 2013). It has been argued by Obazee (2007) that the main hindrances in the adoption process of IFRS in Europe, America, and the rest of the world are not necessarily methodical but cultural issues, mental models, legal impediments, educational needs, and political influences. These assertions have been evident in Islamic countries due to the above-mentioned cultural issues.

Adaptation

Depending on local political, economic, and legislative factors, some countries may require financial reporting to comply with their own standards without formally recognizing IFRS. Alternatively, they could permit all companies to report under either IFRS or domestic standards, or they could require domestic companies to comply with domestic standards and permit only cross-listed foreign companies to comply with either. For example, for the UAE to attract FDI there are requirements for a globalized set of accounting standards (AME Info, 2005c). With no tax on income or profits and 100% foreign ownership, the attraction of this onshore capital market is obvious and increases the need for the UAE to demonstrate integrity, transparency, and efficiency. Maintaining and attracting investment in such a context can be achieved by adapting IFRS and establishing a regulatory regime to supplement them. This is a challenge for countries with authoritarian governments, as they move towards

'demands for greater accountability and wider political participation' (Reed 2006, p. 40) and this makes the harmonization process more challenging. Even in cases where they have greater wealth, emerging economies often face implementation difficulties as they struggle to adjust their existing systems to cope with changing forms of accountability and regulation. This is certainly the case in the UAE (Irvine & Lucas 2006). Further, studies on Fiji and Papua New Guinea (Chand 2005, p. 222) and Bangladesh (Mir & Rahaman 2005) have illustrated the difficulties of imposing Western-style systems of regulation on developing countries.

Convergence

Convergence, in the context of harmonization, means the process of converging or bringing together international standards issued by the IASB and existing standards issued by national standard-setters, with the aim of eliminating accounting alternatives. The ultimate objective of convergence, for IFRS supporters, is to achieve a single set of internally-consistent, high-quality global accounting standards, issued by the IASB and adopted by all the national standard setters. As stated by Obazee (2007), the convergence stage might be either by adoption, which can be defined as a complete replacement of national accounting standards with IASB's standards, or by adaptation, which can be defined as modification of IASB's standards to suit peculiarities of local market, economy, and cultural environment (e.g. Islamic cultures) without compromising the accounting and disclosure requirements of the IFRS. However, due to the religious and cultural challenges discussed above, it appears convergence in the Islamic context remains a crucial challenge. The adoption of IFRS, however, is considered to be one of the most major and vital factors in the Islamic countries' economic and financial ambitions, which include attracting international capital (Irvine & Lucas 2006). Convergence with IFRS in Islamic countries leads to compliance with the IFRS as a core platform. IFRS convergence can also help to guide in providing the input and essential feedback to the IASB on the overall adequacy and preciseness of proposed and current IFRS for Islamic financial transactions.

4.7 Conclusion

According to Daske *et al.* (2008), the adoption of IFRS for listed companies in many countries has been one of the most important developments in recent accounting history. This worldwide reform has involved adapting local accounting practices, to some extent, to

harmonize them with IFRS rules. Around about 120 nations presently allow their listed companies, and, in some cases, other sorts of companies too, to apply IFRS. It has become an international trend, generally recognized around the world as 'best practice' (Obaidat 2007). Those countries and companies which want to resist IFRS are finding it increasingly difficult to stand against the tide. After the acceptance of IFRS, most countries are faced with the difficult prospect of effectively implementing these standards. In fact, it is agreed that developing economies face a range of serious challenges in implementing IFRS. In addition, as Albu *et al.* (2011) explain, the implementation process and its effects are not the same from nation to nation, and so the experiences of a number of countries must be examined.

In Chapter 4, Part B, I look at the implementation processes in a carefully chosen set of developed and emerging economies, including four key Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region Arab countries - Tunisia, Algeria, Egypt, and Oman. I then go on to discuss potential implementation prospects and issues for Libya, in particular, drawing upon lessons learned from my discussion of the other selected countries' experiences.

Chapter 4 Part B - Literature review (issues for developed and emerging economies)

4.8 Introduction - Developed versus emerging economies

Research on harmonization has been extensively undertaken by academics and other interested stakeholders (for example, financial regulators) by approaching this topic at either country level or company level (Murphy 2000). Most of the research studies at country level have focused on developed countries, partly due to the fact that most of these nations have either completely implemented the IFRS or adjusted their domestic accounting standards to incorporate IFRS (Saudagaram & Diga 1998). The other reasons for the proliferation of studies on harmonization in these countries may be because of the domination of the global financial markets by such developed countries and also the availability of research data and funding in these countries. Nevertheless, researchers have started paying attention to the harmonization of accounting standards in developing countries, due to the increasing trend of developing countries considering adoption of these standards. Yet, there is still a lack of research on attempts at harmonization and issues involved in the harmonization of accounting standards in African states, particularly, North African countries, e.g. Libya. Hence, this research addresses the feasibility and prospects for harmonization of the national accounting standards with IFRS in the developing nation of Libya. It also compares the harmonization process in Libya to that already embarked upon in other developing countries.

Thus, Section 4.9 discusses the harmonization of accounting standards in the emerging economies. This is followed by case studies of IFRS adoption in developed countries, in Section 4.10, and in emerging countries, in Section 4.11. In the concluding Section 4.12, I offer concluding remarks about IFRS adoption in developed and emerging countries.

4.9 Harmonization of accounting standards in the emerging economies

The ultimate objective of the IASB, targeted at reconciling the diverse accounting standards of the various countries with the IFRS, will remain elusive without the harmonization of accounting standards in developing countries. Following the adoption of the IFRS, by almost all the industrialized countries, pressure is now increasingly on the developing countries to adopt these standards so as to complete the implementation of global accounting standards (Zeghal & Mhedhbi 2006). While proponents of harmonization highlight its relevance, in facilitating international trade and other benefits, as elaborated in the previous sections,

opponents of harmonization consider it unnecessary and misleading in so far as developing countries are concerned (Belkaoui 1994; Saudagaram & Diga 1998). In fact, they argue that it could be economically damaging, because of the imposition of inappropriate accounting concepts and techniques, which originated from developed countries.

To comprehend fully the possible necessity, risk, and subsequent impact of harmonization of accounting standards in developing countries firstly requires a clear understanding of the concept of developing countries and the accounting standards that characterize these countries. The concept of ‘developing countries’ refers to nations with low standards of living, poorly developed technical infrastructure, and a low Human Development Index (HDI)³ in comparison with more developed states. Hence, developing countries suffer from similar characteristics to varying degrees, depending on the country. The negative features exhibited by such countries include (Farang 1991; Samuels 1990; Wallace 1990; Wallace & Briston 1993):

- (i) the absence of or dormant capital and money markets, meaning that, consequently, the government is the dominant market force in these countries;
- (ii) low levels of technology, productivity, growth rate, per capita income and gross domestic product;
- (iii) high levels of foreign debts, population growth and dependency burdens, unemployment and underemployment;
- (iv) significant economic dependence on agricultural production and natural resources;
- (v) net importation of goods and services from other countries
- (vi) small ineffective private sectors and large inefficient public sectors, which places the burden on the national governments in directing and achieving economic development;
- (vii) the absence of a sound educational system which may translate into a deficient accounting education system; as a result the accounting profession in developing countries is weak;
- (viii) unequal wealth distribution, regional imbalances, balance of payments deficits, and a lack of connection between domestic savings and the investments needed by the country’s enterprises, with the savings of most local investors going out of

³ HDI is a statistical tool used to measure a country's overall achievement in terms of its social and economic dimensions.

the country and the main part of investments in the country being externally funded.

Despite the developing countries sharing certain common characteristics, as highlighted above, the degree of seriousness of these problems differs from one developing country to another. Hence, the concept of developing countries does not refer to a homogenous cluster in terms of their stages of economic development (Chand 2005), nor of development of their accounting professions (Perera 1989; Wallace 1990).

For instance, Ezenwoke and Tion (2020, p. 10) concluded that, despite the mounting tendency towards the implementation of IFRSs in Northern Africa countries (Tunisia, Sudan, Algeria, Egypt, Morocco and Libya), they have not yet come to terms with adopting IFRSs. This is due to the prevalence of Islam and religion that underpins their political, cultural, and legal environments. An additional reason is if a country sees its current financial reporting quality as high, together with its capability to produce sufficient internal capital, at that point it might struggle to shift to a different financial reporting standard (Graham *et al.* 2017). It should also be borne in mind that some developing countries are more developed than others. Similarly, some of the countries are rich and have more natural or capital resources (e.g. Libya, Saudi Arabia, and Nigeria) than others (such as Afghanistan, Pakistan and Yemen) (Wallace 1990). Consequently, developing countries have been referred to as an ill-defined group of dissimilar countries that are predominantly located in Africa, Asia, Latin America, Oceania, and the Middle East (Wallace 1990). These countries have been categorized into four main groups by Wallace (1990), which still broadly applies, despite subsequent economic and political changes:

- (i) Those emerging economies that are undergoing rapid industrialization with positive future prospects, such as Brazil, India, Malaysia, Singapore, South Korea and Taiwan (the latter three are now developed nations);
- (ii) Countries endowed with plentiful natural resources but lacking meaningful development, due to their colonial heritage and difficulties in achieving good governance, resulting in the wasteful management of both human and natural resources; examples in this case include countries like Libya, Indonesia, Nigeria and Saudi Arabia;

- (iii) The countries of the former Central and Eastern European communist bloc, which, although already industrialized, are in the process of setting up the market economies that would ensure economic growth in a competitive world;
- (iv) Countries that lack natural, human and capital resources, resulting in them being poor and underdeveloped; countries like Afghanistan and Yemen clearly fit into this category.

Despite the perceived benefits, the above analysis shows that the harmonization of accounting standards in developing countries is a daunting challenge, considering the numerous difficulties, ranging from poverty to bad governance, that are plaguing these countries. However, most developing countries have little or no choice other than to strive to harmonize their accounting standards to conform to the IFRS due to the compelling influence of their colonial heritage and the original accounting systems they inherited from this period. For instance, the United Kingdom bequeathed its economic and legal systems to its colonies (including Fiji, Hong Kong, Kenya, Malaysia, Nigeria and Singapore), along with its education system and cultural legacy (Ashraf & Ghani 2005; Chamisa 2000; Nobes 1998, 2003). Hence, many former British colonies regard the IFRS as being relevant to their national needs, despite the fact that they do not have strong equity markets (Tyrrall *et al.* 2007). In contrast, other developing countries which have dissimilar colonial legacies, such as most Arab and/or Muslim countries (e.g. Iran) may not be very receptive to the IFRS-type accounting system and may even consider it inappropriate to their national development (Tyrrall *et al.* 2007).

Arguments follow about the dissimilarities in the financial reporting environment across authorities that accept IFRSs (Maradona & Chand 2018). Likewise, its significance and relevance remains uncertain (Trimble 2018). For example, full IFRS implementation may impact deleteriously on African Countries' FDI and perceived fraud (Houqe & Monem, 2016). On the other hand, other academic contributions demonstrate a positive impact of IFRSs on earnings' value-relevance (Odoemelam *et al.*, 2019), income smoothing (Uwuigbe *et al.* 2016), and environmental pollution (Efobi 2015). Accordingly, research on IFRS adoption in Africa has received substantial academic attention (Ezenwoke & Tion 2020).

Against the backdrop of the reservations shared by some researchers, who believe that harmonization of accounting standards in developing countries to conform with IFRS may be

irrelevant to the national needs of these countries, many developing countries are vigorously pursuing harmonization of their accounting standards (Choi & Mueller 1984; Radebaugh *et al.* 2006; Tyrrall *et al.* 2007). These include Bahrain, Egypt, Fiji, Ghana, Indonesia, Jordan, Malaysia, Nigeria, Oman, Philippines, Singapore, South Africa, Thailand, the United Arab Emirates, and Zimbabwe.

The governments of many developing countries are evaluating how appropriate the IFRS are likely to be, given their national needs. This would require weighing the comparative benefits and drawbacks of different approaches to harmonizing their domestic accounting standards with the IFRS and subsequently choosing the best pathway to implement this process with minimal problems. A typical example is Libya, which is an important country in North Africa, and is endowed with vast crude oil reserves, but has experienced difficult periods ranging from autocratic regimes to international isolation and sanctions. These have adversely affected its national development. Nevertheless, there were renewed efforts by the former Libyan government to integrate with the international community and one of such ways is to harmonize its domestic accounting standards with the IFRS. Hence, it is imperative to assess the relevance of harmonization of accounting standards in Libya, as well as any impediments to implementation and their subsequent impacts.

4.10 Adoption of IFRS: Case studies of developed countries

The alleged purpose of convergence with or adoption of the IFRS issued by the IASB is to improve the usefulness of financial information across the globe and thus to facilitate international trade. However, the diversity of factors (e.g. environmental, socio-economic, legal, political, cultural) that characterize countries across the world, the non-mandatory nature of the IFRS, and the lack of political will in many countries have combined to hinder IFRS adoption and implementation (Callao *et al.* 2007). Moreover, both the implementation and impact of the adoption of the IFRS are likely to vary across economies, due to the diversity of the countries (Callao *et al.* 2007; Schleicher *et al.* 2010). For instance, it is clear that the implementation and impact of the adoption of IFRS in a developing country will be different from the results in a developed country.

Considerable effort has been made by international and regional institutions to promote harmonization across the globe through the adoption or convergence with the IFRS, without

much success, except in the developed countries with strong capital markets, such as many of the European Union (EU) countries and the USA (Callao *et al.* 2007; Gastón *et al.* 2010). The next section will consider the implementation of IFRS in developed countries and highlight the differences in both the initial motivations for adoption and the implementation of IFRS of these countries. The countries chosen are a representative selection of the developed EU countries, both recently joined members and founding members of the EU, and also the USA. The European countries chosen in this study are all highly-developed economies, which have already utilized IFRS standards over a considerable period of time.

4.10.1 Developed countries of western, southern and central Europe

As explained in previous chapters, the move to harmonize EU accounting standards was based on the belief that the harmonization of accounting practices and standards would result in a free flow of financial information. This free flow of information, in a comparable form, was considered to be a fundamental requirement for the development of an integrated financial market within the region (Canibano & Mora 2000). This is because the adoption of a single set of accounting rules could enable companies to access capital through the capital markets without the need to formulate reconciliatory financial statements using the formats of other accounting standards (Tweedie 2004). Thus, harmonization of accounting standards within the EU would also result in the more efficient operation of the European capital markets, which would thus be more cost-effective. Furthermore, the aim was to provide a level playing-field, which would allow all EU companies to compete for financial resources, both in the EU market and other markets (McLeay *et al.* 1999).

This decision to adopt the IFRS for its publicly-operated firms was part of the attempt to generate a common European capital market, and to foster stronger capital markets and better financial transactions within the Eurozone. Thus, the European parliament issued Regulation 1606/2002, according to which it became mandatory for firms listed on any European stock market to draw up their consolidated financial statements according to IFRS (Gastón *et al.* 2010; Zéghal *et al.* 2011). Based on this directive, all listed EU firms have been obliged to use IFRS since 2005 (Delvaille & Ebberts 2005; Pacter 2005; Whittington 2005).

The overall European implementation of IFRS began in 2000 once the EC ruled that, from 2005, IFRS was to be applied by all listed EU companies. However, the process was considered to require a degree of flexibility and this was achieved through a staged process.

To assist in the smooth process of implementation, member states were permitted to exempt three categories of companies from adopting IFRS until 2007: firms which were listed in both EU and non-EU markets; those which were using US GAAP as their domestic accounting standards; and companies that only had bonds publicly-traded. In addition, those non-EU firms which were listed in the EU could still use their domestic GAAP standards until 2007. The EU Regulation (1606/2002) also gave the member states individual flexibility in deciding whether they would require or allow IFRS to be employed by unlisted companies or in the unconsolidated statements of a parent company.

For accounting standards to be accepted for use in the EU, they need be recognized by the Accounting Regulatory Committee (ARC), of the EU Commission, which is made up of representatives from the governments of the member states. The ARC is, in turn, advised by a group of accounting experts known as the European Financial Reporting Advisory Group. Thus, the way that the IFRS are applied in the EU may differ from the way they are applied in other places, providing additional flexibility to conform to the local systems and practices. For instance, the ARC did not initially agree with the stipulations of IAS 39 (Financial Instruments: Recognition and Measurement). This led to the amendment of IAS 39, by omitting the option that financial liabilities could be recorded at fair value (Jaruga *et al.* 2007). The IASB collaborated with the EU on how best to eliminate a further inconsistency in relation to hedge accounting.

The adoption of the IFRS by the EU in 2005 was a major achievement for the IASB and this decision duly encouraged many other countries to adopt IFRS. For example, as well as the EU Member States, the European IAS regulation now also applies to Iceland, Liechtenstein, and Norway, which are European Economic Area (EEA) members. In fact, almost all industrialized nations have either converged with or adopted the IFRS. As emphasized above, the member states were given some form of liberty to implement the adopted standards within the limit of the enacted Act. However, only a limited number of studies have explored the views of key stakeholders (including the users) on the application of IFRS in different EU countries and how appropriate these are to the country's own needs and situation (Albu *et al.* 2011; Ballas *et al.* 2010; Ballas & Tzovas 2010; Caramanis & Papadakis 2008; Cole *et al.* 2011; Dunne *et al.* 2008; Navarro-García, & Bastida 2010; Tasios & Bekiaris 2012; Vellam 2012). In addition, it has been shown that the implementation of IFRS is not exactly uniform throughout the Eurozone, due to the differences in the accounting systems among its

members (Vellam 2012). Thus, it is necessary to review the adoption of the IFRS by some individual EU member states to critically highlight possible differences in the implementation of the IFRS across the Eurozone, and the particular problems and issues experienced in different countries. For this purpose, countries have been selected for this discussion so as to represent two main types of EU countries. The first group is countries that were already members in 2002 (so they were part of the negotiation process, and presumably their needs and views were taken into account when the law was formulated). The second group is countries that joined after 2005-07, when the law came into existence, so presumably they had to adopt the national rules that were already in place.

4.10.1.1 Belgium

As a longstanding member of the EU, Belgium incorporated the EU regulation 1606/2002 into its accounting system along with the other EU members at that time. Prior to the adoption of IFRS, by the EU, the Belgian accounting regulator had already adopted IFRS to enable a small group of companies which met pre-specified criteria to arrange their combined financial statements in agreement with IAS. This was done in order to enhance the potential of these companies to source finances from outside Belgium (Jermakowicz 2004). Following the endorsement of IAS Regulation 1606/2002, by the Belgium Parliament and the council of the European Union, the Belgian Accounting Standards Commission proposed further reforms concerning the implementation of the IFRS Regulation (Jermakowicz 2004). For example, in 2004, the Belgian government made compliance with IFRS mandatory for publicly-traded firms other than banks, insurance companies and structured investment firms (Jermakowicz 2004). With all the necessary infrastructures in place, all listed companies on the Belgian Stock Market could then choose to produce financial reports under IFRS without obtaining approval from the Belgian Banking Commission (Jermakowicz 2004). So, Belgium is an example of a small and flexible country that was ready for harmonization, and had already started to adopt IFRS, so it was a very smooth and easy transition.

4.10.1.2 Denmark

As an EU member state, Denmark also had to conform to the EU Regulation 1606/2002/EC. However, the first step in harmonization in Denmark was undertaken earlier, in 2001, when, based on the intention that the IFRS would come into widespread use, the Danish government updated the Financial Statement Act (which was based on a combination of the 4th and 7th EC Directives) (Holm *et al.* 2008). This was done by passing the Danish Annual Accounts Act, under which all Danish organizations apart from banks and insurance companies were

required to draw up their annual accounts according to IFRS (Nielsen 2009). However, using the flexibility given to national governments in the EU regulation, the Danish government exempted listed companies from complying with IFRS in the individual financial statements of companies within a corporate group, although from 2009 listed non-group businesses were required to draw up their financial statements in conformity with IFRS.

In line with the EU Regulation and following an IFRS executive order endorsed by the Danish Parliament, the Danish Commerce and Companies Agency issued IFRS guidelines for listed companies. However, organizations in the financial sector, such as banks and other institutions involved in insurance and credit provision and investment management, are regulated and supervised by the Danish Financial Supervisory Authority, an organization reporting to the Danish Ministry of Economic and Business Affairs. This supervisory authority also accepted IFRS executive orders for accounting practices, including the obligation to implement IFRS, in conformance with the EU Guidelines (Holm *et al.* 2008).

Denmark has historically had a close association with the United Kingdom and has adhered to the Anglo-Saxon custom of having rather flexible reporting regulations (Chalmers *et al.* 2007; Hansen 2001). In these Anglo-Saxon countries, according to Bebbington and Song (2003), it has been considered more important to comply with accounting principles and standards than laws; and the priority has been to provide relevant and timely information to assist stakeholders in investment and policymaking. According to Mueller *et al.* (1991), other continental countries, in contrast, tend to have closer links to their banks as the main suppliers of capital in those countries. Thus, financial accounting practices are more legalistic and extremely conservative, being chiefly aimed to inform the banks, and as a basis for calculating revenue for tax purposes.

From the above explanation, it can be seen that Denmark has shown flexibility in adapting and implementing the provisions of IFRS to match its existing more principle-based accounting practices. It has allowed some exemptions where appropriate.

4.10.1.3 Germany

The initial stimulus to change the system of financial reporting in Germany was that existing national accounting regulations appeared to stop firms from fully benefiting from global capital markets (Ebke 1997). Under this pressure from the capital market, the German

government initially issued a law (*Kapitalaufnahmeerleichterungsgesetz*, ‘Law to facilitate borrowing of capital’, in 1998) allowing listed German companies to use either IFRS or US GAAP instead of presenting their consolidated accounts in conformity with the German HGB (*Handelsgesetzbuch*, Commercial Code). This development marked a fundamental shift in the direction of international convergence of accounting practices.

As a consequence of the adoption of the EU Regulations, German listed companies were obliged to follow IFRS from 2005 in their consolidated accounts. According to the rules for this transition (article 9 in the EU Guidelines), those listed companies that had used US GAAP in the past would be required to use IFRS from 1 January 2007. The Accounting Law Reform Act, which also came into force on 1 January 2005, also required that the accounts of any firms applying for listing on the stock exchange should conform to IFRS. Non-publicly-traded companies are also allowed to apply IFRS in their consolidated accounts, if they choose. However, if the company opts to apply IFRS, it must meet all IFRS requirements. The law also provides the choice for businesses to apply IFRS in the separate accounts intended for publication, but it should be noted that this is only for information purposes. This is because all companies are also required to present their separate financial statements in conformity with the German Commercial Code (HGB) for calculating the amount of tax owed and the dividends to be paid. Therefore, the HGB continues to be compulsory for individual accounts in Germany, although a firm might only make public its IFRS accounts. Additionally, the Accounting Law Reform Act included many other significant alterations in the requirements for financial reporting (Haller & Eierle 2004). For instance, according to this law, all companies have to provide a cash flow statement for their consolidated accounts, regardless of whether they are listed companies.

Unlike Belgium and Denmark, Germany has given permission even for non-listed companies to implement IFRS, but they still have to use the Germany commercial code to pay the tax, so the IFRS process and the tax collection function are separated in the implementation process.

4.10.1.4 Greece

In Greece, Iatridis and Rouvolis (2010) examined the effects of implementing IFRS on financial performance. The results disclose that the profitability, liquidity and growth, as financial measures, diminished in the first year of adoption, which might be ascribed to the IFRS reasonable value orientation and the transitional expenditures associated with adoption.

However, organizations presented improved financial measures in the following year. A parallel outcome was also posited by Fitó, Gómez, and Moya (2012) who examined the outcomes of the transition from Spanish GAAP to IFRS-based Spanish Accounting Standards on 12 financial ratios. The outcomes suggest that the presentation of IFRS has important consequences on most financial ratios, particularly those in the balance sheet. Additionally, the delayed tax liability displays additional liabilities that were not recognized in the balance-sheet prior to IFRS. Furthermore, Ntaikou, Vousinas, and Kenourgios (2018) examined the expected consequence of accepting IFRS 9 on the Greek banking system's financial performance. They determined that the nonappearance of in-print annual reports organized by banks based on IFRS 9 does not permit the accurate impact on the financial performance of banks to be assessed.

As explained above, according to the EU Regulation issued in 2002, publicly-traded firms have to prepare their consolidated accounts according to the IFRS. It should be noted that the IFRS are designed chiefly as a way of providing information, in the form of financial statements to investors, as the chief stakeholders in a company (IASB *Framework*, par. 10). For this reason, the IFRS are not 'debt and tax oriented', and thus contrast with the accounting guidelines in code-law nations such as Greece. IFRS are written in such a way as to reflect financial gains and losses in a timely manner (Barth, Landsman & Lang 2008); and to produce balance sheets that are more informative than those which were traditionally prepared in most continental countries (Ball 2006).

Greek corporations are mainly funded by banks and via a debt-oriented capital market (Tsalavoutas *et al.* 2012). Nevertheless, since 2000, the Athens Stock Exchange (ASE) has been regarded as an advanced market (Mandikidis 2000), which reflects the increased importance of obtaining equity from capital markets. By 2006, there were 317 listed companies with a total market capitalization of €158 billion. Foreign investors held over 50% of the market capitalization of ASE's FTSE 20 companies (Central Security Depository 2006, cited in Tsalavoutas 2012). This fact suggests an increased interest in Greek companies as far as international investors are concerned.

In the Greek market, there is a high concentration of owner/managers, who, as proprietors, will be directly participating in management and therefore less dependent on financial statements to supply information about their own company's performance (Tzovas 2006).

Like Belgium, and other countries with the continental approach, financial reporting in Greece is conventionally closely associated with the revenue system (Ballas *et al.* 1998), and businesses strive to find strategies which will reduce their tax liabilities (Baralexis 2004; Tzovas 2006). Corporations also use income-smoothing (i.e. their goal is to create income stability over time) strategies, since stakeholders (particularly in code-law countries) traditionally prefer more stable earnings, without major fluctuations (Ball, Kothari & Robin 2000). Although IFRS became obligatory for all Greek listed companies in 2005, both the adoption and implementation of IFRS in Greece has been particularly difficult, not only due to the major differences mentioned above between the accounting systems, but also owing to a lack of preparation of the businesses concerned and a shortage of certified public accountants (Spathis & Georgakopoulou 2007).

The implementation of IFRS in Greece included, among others, nine standards which put forward new accounting rules or put an end to accounting practices that permitted management of earnings - these were intended to curtail creative accounting practices (Tsalavoutas & Evans 2010). The more clearly laid out requirements of IAS 37⁴, were anticipated to trigger an upsurge in provisions. In addition, the measurement of financial assets, loans and receivables investments was expected to be affected by IAS 32⁵ and also IAS 39.⁶ The previous option to acquire the company's own shares and then to recognize these as assets was also curtailed by IAS 32. A further reduction in asset values was brought about by the stricter rules on the specification of what constitutes damage, in IAS 36⁷, while IAS 2⁸ also necessitates that damage to inventories should be specified and acknowledged. (By contrast, under Greek GAAP, only disclosure was necessary.) For example, the stricter recognition criteria imposed by IAS 38⁹ were likely to lead to a decrease in shareholders' equity, for the reason that companies were obliged to write off expenditures on research and start-up costs, both of which had formerly been capitalized.

⁴ *Provisions, Contingent Liabilities and Contingent Assets*

⁵ *Financial Instruments: Disclosure and Presentation*

⁶ *Financial Instruments: Recognition and Measurement.*

⁷ *Impairment of Assets*

⁸ *Inventories,*

⁹ *Intangible Assets*

Iatridis and Rouvolis (2010) examined the impact of the transition from Greek GAAP to IFRS on the financial results of all non-financial Greek firms listed on the Athens Stock Exchange. In addition, they scrutinized the influences that had led companies to make voluntary IFRS disclosures in advance of the mandatory adoption time and also the degrees of earnings management under IFRS. They established that the implementation of IFRS led to instability in both key income statement and balance sheet measures of Greek firms. However, they concluded that, despite the negative impact of the introduction of IFRS in the initial twelve months, probably owing to the changeover costs, there was a significant improvement in companies' financial measures over the longer-term.

As a very different case, Greece has many local business owners whose main focus is to reduce their tax liabilities. This might be a reason for initial difficulty in implementing IFRS.

4.10.1.5 Poland

Polish accounting practices developed along two separate routes, after 2006, as a result of Poland's accession to the EU (Grabinski, *et al.* 2014). In terms of the accounting regulations applied, there are two groups of organizations: listed companies that use IFRS, and those non-listed companies which follow accounting practices that conform to the Polish Accounting Act. This twofold scheme is the consequence of Poland's acceptance of the EU Regulation 1606/2002 to adopt IAS/IFRS in the consolidated financial statements of their listed companies and also for banks and insurance companies (Grabinski, *et al.* 2014).

As a member state, the acceptance of IFRS entailed significant changes in accounting practices in Poland, which actually involved more than just the observance of EU Directives in the direction of the integration of IAS into local regulation (Grabinski, *et al.* 2014). Polish translations of all the IAS/IFRS adopted by the European Commission were published in the official journal of the EC. Adopting IFRS in Poland was a huge undertaking for Polish companies. It meant that they had to invest in costly financial and accounting computer systems for their financial transactions and accounting calculations, as well as developing new accounting strategies plus reappraising asset values and depreciation techniques.

Grabinski *et al.* (2014) examined the impact of IFRS implementation in Poland, particularly in terms of cost-benefit analysis. They found that the benefits resulting from implementing IFRS in Poland were dependent on a company's size and its financial structures and also

related to its access to foreign investment reserves. Generally, the larger companies were found to be most likely to gain the maximum benefit from better quality financial statements, which usually resulted in reduced capital costs (Grabinski *et al.* 2014). However, they also found that implementing IFRS involved higher accounting costs and that expensive training was needed for staff in accounting and finance departments. Because of these factors, the costs involved in auditing financial statements increased (Grabinski *et al.* 2014).

The experience of Poland shows the effects of a full-scale commitment to IFRS. Poland's approach required the full translation of the IFRS package and a high level of investment. It resulted in major changes in accounting practices.

4.10.2 United States of America (USA)

Whilst there are still many disparities between US GAAP and IFRS, these are rapidly being reduced and the USA has demonstrated strong commitment to pursuing internationally accepted accounting standards through a variety of measures. This progress towards union or harmony of the US GAAP and IFRS, since the establishment of the IASB in 2001, reflects the determination of both the US FASB and the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) to further the development of a single set of high-quality global accounting standards.

Following the agreement of the FASB and IASB to collaborate on all future key schemes, a 'Framework for Advancing Transatlantic Economic Integration between the United States and the European Union' was jointly signed in April 2007 by the then presidents of the USA, European Council, and European Commission (EC). According to this agreement, US GAAP and IFRS would 'be recognized in both jurisdictions without the need for reconciliation, by 2009 or possibly sooner' (Bush, Merkel & Barroso 2007, p. 10). A few months later, the SEC (2007a) proposed removing the need for 20-F reconciliation for foreign companies using IFRS in their reports, and, shortly after this, following a unanimous vote by the SEC Commissioners; the 20-F settlement was finally abandoned for businesses using IFRS.

4.10.2.1 Advantages of using IFRS for companies registered with the US SEC

It was thought that IFRS would increase comparability with rivals: according to Gannon *et al.* (2007) of Deloitte, US corporations might favour reporting using IFRS if their main competitors use IFRS, particularly in sectors such as investment, insurance, automobile manufacturing, pharmaceuticals, and communications. According to these researchers,

comparability in reporting standards would enable investors to compare like-with-like when viewing the results. IFRS offers specific opportunities to US corporations with international operations: Gannon *et al.* (2007) identified these as follows:

- Standardization of accounting and financial reporting strategies - This would assist consistency in terms of accounting strategies and financial statements in those countries where use of a local system of reporting is also obligatory and enable easier comparison of financial information and tax preparation.
- Centralization of processes - The adoption of IFRS throughout the whole company would reduce its dependence on local accounting resources for statutory reporting; and training programmes could be standardized.
- More stringent controls - For statutory reporting purposes, companies would be able to assign a single owner, thus enabling the quality and publication of financial statements to be controlled more effectively in different regions.
- Better cash management - Where subsidiaries pay out dividends on the basis of financial statements prepared locally, cash flow planning could be improved by using the same standards across different countries.

Similarly, the former Chairman of IASB, Sir David Tweedie (2007a) pointed out that as accounts of US corporations' overseas subsidiaries were increasingly being prepared according to IFRS, permitting US corporations to apply IFRS would consequently decrease the costs involved in compliance and consolidation and reduce the likelihood of errors relating to the conversion between different forms of presentation and consolidation processes. He suggested that all SEC-registered companies, which have their headquarters in the USA, should be offered the same choices as those not registered in the US to avoid US-based companies, particularly those in certain sectors, suffering a competitive disadvantage.

This last point was also echoed by Johnson (2007) of BDO, who justified his opinion by mentioning particular discrepancies between IFRS regulations and those of US GAAP in their rules for revenue recognition in the technology sector, in particular. He explained that under IFRS, revenue growth can be more promptly reported by a business. This is owing to the fact that, as mentioned earlier in this chapter, IFRS is inherently principles-based, and thus offers more flexibility in respect to the timing of returns recognition. In summary, even

the largest economy in the world (as at the date of writing), the USA sees the benefit of moving towards international standardization of accounting systems.

4.11 Adoption of IFRS: Case studies of emerging countries

4.11.1 The outcome of accounting standards on financial performance

The fiscal presentation of a company is a measure of achievement that echoes the ability of a company to harvest revenues. Several financial ratios have to be utilized in a company's performance measurement, including working capital turnover ratio, fixed asset turnover ratio, debt turnover ratio, interest coverage ratio, and debt service coverage ratio (Salah 2020). Moreover, Zeller (2019) posited nine IFRS-based ratios that are reliable and comparable regardless of dissimilarities between nations: asset relationship, asset turnover, capital structure, expense insight, fixed asset usage, inventory turnover, liquidity, profitability margin, and performance return.

A number of developing countries have adopted IFRS or are in the process of its implementation to heighten their companies' financial performance, for instance the United Arab Emirates, Saudi Arabia, Egypt, Tunisia, and Algeria (Salah 2020). The implementation process is costly and difficult (Jermakowicz & Gornik-Tomaszewski 2006). Consequently, a number of academic studies have attempted to scrutinize whether the adoption of the IFRS has had an effect on the key financial ratios and the market response to this kind of advantage. Scholars utilized numerous financial ratios to determine financial performance (Abdul-Baki *et al.* 2014, Adeuja 2015, Parrott 2017). As explained by Wang and Welker (2011), the conversion from local GAAP to IFRS ensures in a change in the company's financial results, which might cause stockholders to reappraise the company's equity.

Many researchers have highlighted the numerous benefits of harmonization, which include the enhancement of comparability, improving the quality of financial statements and facilitating international trade. However, as pointed out earlier, some commentators have argued that IFRS has been designed based on the environment of developed countries and will not be beneficial to the developing countries. In fact, these researchers argue that the adoption of IFRS by developing countries will be harmful and exploitative to those countries. According to these researchers, the multinational companies and the developed countries are

the main beneficiaries of harmonization and adoption of IFRS globally (Jermakowicz 2004; Veneziani & Teodori 2008).

Despite such debates between proponents and opponents, harmonization with (and adoption) of IFRS has gained favour in recent years. Since most developed countries have either adopted or are converging with IFRS, the wave of adoption has shifted to developing countries, which are also hoping to improve the transparency, quality, and comparability of the financial reports produced by their business sectors (Jermakowicz 2004; Veneziani & Teodori 2008). However, evidence suggests that lack of political commitment, stemming from local culture and national preconceptions and prejudices is usually among the factors that prevent the adoption and implementation of IFRS (Callao *et al.* 2007). Nevertheless, many developing countries have already adopted IFRS and many more are considering following suit. Developing countries generally adopt standards currently used by developed nations, due to lack of resources to develop their own accounting standards and because of the high cost involved in the process of developing specific domestic accounting standards (Bandyopadhyay & McGee 2012). In addition, Nobes (2008) and Zeff (2010) point out that those countries which adopt tend to be under the influence of international bodies, such as the IMF, the OECD and the World Bank, which provide them with the financial and technical support needed to adopt internationally-acceptable accounting standards, i.e. the IFRS. It is thus important to examine how less developed countries can manage to adapt these standards from the more demanding level used in the international context to a form more suited for their local economies.

The studies on the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region disclose a change in accounting practice between IFRS and local GAAP that affects the financial performance of companies. Investors from France, for this reason, have shifted their attention and resources to a range of MENA countries because of earlier colonialism. The majority of MENA area nations are affected by both civil law and *Sharia'a* law, which affects the framework of accounting activities (Salah 2020, p. 7).

This section, Section 4.11, will review the adoption and implementation of the IFRS by five developing countries: Romania, Egypt, Algeria, Tunisia, and Oman. These countries (other than Romania) were chosen based on their geographical proximity and similarity in both religion and culture to Libya. Section 4.13 will consider the case of Libya adopting IFRS.

4.11.1.1 Romania

Romania has been generally regarded as an outlying part of the advanced industrialized states of Western Europe. Boia (2012) suggests that, although, by recently joining the EU, Romania has become ‘an extension of Western Europe’, it remains a ‘borderland’ on the eastern margin. Historians have shown how the present economic gap between Romania and Western countries has gradually widened (Murgescu 2010) and that closing this gap is one of the major challenges for the Romanian people.

In Romania, Neag (2014) examined the consequence of the mandatory shift to IFRS on firms’ financial performance. The study revealed that there were no important differences for either net income or shareholders’ equity. However, it found that IFRS had a positive impact on the stock-market. In addition, Espinosa *et al.* (2015) analyzed 43 organizations to examine the effect of IFRS on nine financial ratios and the market response regarding this implementation. They stated that IFRS considerably affected profitability and investment ratios but did not affect leverage or price-earnings ratios. The authors further posited that the market did not remunerate this kind of initiative. This outcome could be owing to the fact that assets and liabilities under IFRS are at fair values which creates volatility in the statement of financial position statistics. The allocation of some unrealized profits and losses to both statements of financial performance and other comprehensive income might influence profitability and liquidity ratios.

The present adoption of the IFRS has a dual origin and purpose. Although the introduction of IFRS is mainly the result of two major external factors - globalization and Romania’s recent accession to the EU, it also has a domestic motivation - the perception of IFRS as a modernizing influence, in that an internationally agreed set of standards might be beneficial for Romanian companies in accessing capital in international markets (Ionaşcu *et al.* 2014).

However, it must be borne in mind that the adoption of IFRS is not in itself guaranteed to generate economic expansion; this is because the disclosure of accounting information does not intrinsically generate worth, but the information only gains worth when it is employed in financial decision-making. Even if it may be considered as unsuitable for the immature economy of Romania (‘a form without substance’ - Munteanu 2003), as a globally accepted accounting system, making an important contribution to the success of worldwide capital markets (Capron 2005), adoption of IFRS might allow Romanian businesses access to these

international marketplaces. In addition, it can bring some advantages to the local economy, for instance, by improving corporate governance practices or reducing the cost of capital.

Romanian accounting bodies were in favour of widening mandatory use of IFRS for several reasons (Ionaşcu *et al.* 2014). As well as citing the general recommendations of the IMF, World Bank, and other international bodies, they pointed to the need to encourage transparent and comparable financial statements by aligning the procedures with international practice, and how this could establish an attractive investment environment, on account of the ‘interest of the state to protect itself from possible foreign capital outflows by means of exploiting inconsistencies in accounting treatments applied by companies belonging to multinational groups’ (Ionaşcu *et al.* 2014, p. 322).

Thus, in the implementation of IFRS in Romania, the aim was that IFRS should be used in the individual financial statements of companies listed on a regulated market, which would remove the existing practice of ‘double reporting’ for these companies (in which two reports were prepared: one using IFRS, and another following local accounting standards (Ionaşcu *et al.* 2014). Thus, as a recent new member of EU, which intends to modernize its economy quickly, Romania has adopted IFRS very comprehensively.

As a group of diverse countries, the EU is trying to develop a harmonized system and each country has faced different issues, but they share the same goal - to improve their business environment. The relevance of these issues and what can be learned from their experience for this study will be discussed in Section 4.12 in the context of Libya.

4.11.1.2 Egypt

Egypt is one of the significant nations in the MENA area and has robust financial bonds with many countries globally. Egypt is a good example of the tensions between economic, political, religious and cultural issues existing in the MENA region. Since the early-1990s, the Egyptian government has adopted significant restructuring plans for the economy and has aimed to activate the Egyptian stock exchange (Mokhtar *et al.* 2018).

Egypt has undergone a significant movement towards democracy and transparency in recent years, and, additionally, is a rare example among developing countries of the transformation of the economic system from a state-controlled model to a capitalist model. Over the years,

the Egyptian regulators have undertaken a range of actions, initially aimed at improving the planned economy and then assisting in the transition back to a capitalist economy, including the establishment of local financial reporting standards closely modelled on IFRS.

According to Hassan (2008, p. 470), the IFRS was selected as the most suitable benchmark for various reasons, which included 'The Egyptian regulators' sources of knowledge, the lack of domestic investors' desires to change the Egyptian financial reporting regulations and the immature accounting profession that is incapable of professionally enforcing new standards'. Furthermore, implementation of the IFRS, although not easy, particularly in relation to the cultural context of a developing country, could assist the transformation to an entrepreneurial economy. This validates the small number of modifications that have been made in the Egyptian Accounting Standards to accommodate the local culture (Dahawy *et al.* 2002).

The Egyptian government understood that comprehensive corporate financial reporting and the adoption of IFRSs are essential necessities for the achievement of its privatization package assumed in the 1990s (ROSC 2002). However, the use of Egyptian Accounting Standards (EASs) that are based completely on the IFRS disregards the point that IFRS are based on the Anglo-American approach to financial reporting and echo Western social standards (Flower 1997). Therefore, the EASs do not conform to the nature of Egyptian social principles (El-Rashedy 2006). This results in tension between the disclosure obligation of IFRS/ EAS and privacy as a leading accounting value in Egypt (Dahawy & Conover 2007).

Hassan (2008) identifies four differences between the Egyptian Accounting Standards (EAS) and the IFRS. The first difference lies in EAS 1, the major Egyptian Accounting Standard, and is associated with the way financial reports are presented. According to this regulation, the expenditures on profit distribution to employees and the board of directors should be directly taken off the retained earnings, rather than charging them as expenses, as would be done under IAS, without reducing the income figure shown in the statement. This would subsequently affect the earnings-per-share calculations. The second difference concerns depreciation and revaluation of fixed assets, which is not allowed under EAS 10, except in certain legally approved circumstances, unlike the provisions of IAS 16.

The third difference is in regards disclosure of financial institutions. According to EAS 19, general provision for loans must be built up in a cumulative way, through reducing income in the income statement, whereas IFRS 7 stipulates that provisions should be taken out of the owner's equity. The final discrepancy occurs in EAS20, concerning leasing. In line with the legal codes of the domestic laws, the lessor is required to keep the asset in its accounting book and depreciate it, while the rental payments are reported by the lessee as expenditures - this is the opposite procedure to what is required by its counterpart, IAS 17.

Hassan's (2008) study shows how, as a country trying to move from state control, Egypt established local accounting standards which were modelled on IFRS but retained some existing practices, which demonstrates Egyptian caution in implementing IFRS.

Sawy (2016) compared the quality of financial reports between the Egyptian Accounting Standards and IFRS. The outcomes disclosed the decline of earnings management under IFRS, which improved the quality of the financial reports. Similarly, Ebaid (2016) discovered that the implementation of IFRS amplified the quality of accounting in Egypt as a civil-law country. Furthermore, Mansour *et al.* (2017) studied the moderating role of IFRS on the relationship between earnings management and financial organization registered in the Egyptian Stock market. The findings demonstrated an important moderating relationship for IFRS. Another study examined the consequence on the financial performance of one manufacturing company registered on the Egyptian market for the transition from Egyptian Accounting Standard 20 to IFRS16 - it shows a considerable increase of 17.57 percent of total liabilities due to the lease liabilities (Abdalwahab 2018).

Using a sample of 31 developing countries, Mhedhbi and Zeghal (2016) performed univariate and multivariate analyses to identify the association between the implementation of IFRS and the performance of emerging capital markets. Their findings indicate that IFRS is positively associated with the performance of capital markets in developing countries.

In many cases, it can be presumed that variances between IFRS and local GAAP could have been instigated by conceivable first-time implementation mistakes, because not all organizations were in the same way ready for the IFRS application process. According to Khamis (2016), Egyptian auditors and accountants have an inadequate appreciation of IFRS 15. Remarkably, academic contributions studied do not reveal any influence on the ratio of

functioning cash flow, as it was not influenced by amendments in accounting standards. Relying on cash flow investigation is recommended, particularly in instances where accounting performances are subject to hesitation or management's sole discretion. Another suggestion is that investors can rely on new ratios that place unrealized profits and losses, not disclosed in the statement of financial performance, into the comprehensive-ROA and the comprehensive-ROE. The comprehensive income is utilized in the numerator rather than net income (Salah 2020, p. 8).

However, Khamis (2016) concluded that Egyptian accountants and auditors were not yet prepared to embrace IFRS 15 as they perceived that the standard is too difficult to apply because of dissimilar commercial divisions. The study also recommended that training and education packages are important for trainers and accountants. They can help them to gain a comprehensive and profounder understanding of the theoretical underpinnings of the standards and their presentation across diverse businesses.

4.11.1.3 Algeria

In Algeria, Haya (2011) and Ramzy (2015) aimed to determine whether the implementation of IFRS had an influence on firms' financial presentation. The findings illustrate that IFRS considerably affected the financial performance ratios and intensified the value-relevance of the financial reports. These findings would be pleasing to those in the pro-IFRS camp.

In exploring the acceptance of foreign accounting schemes, by recently independent states, it has been noted that, whilst some states have been more successful than others in the implementation of these schemes, they were not always successful in adapting these schemes to suit their cultures (Wallace 1999). The Algerian context for harmonization of the accounting system was focused on two underlying factors, Algeria's desire to shake off its colonial past and its earlier attempts, like Egypt, to adopt a Soviet-influenced economic model. In the case of Algeria, the French *Plan Comptable General* (PCGF) was relatively advanced in comparison with the United Nations' approved system. Thus, the Algerian accounting profession retained the PCGF when Algeria obtained its freedom in 1962. This decision could also have been owing to the lack of professionals in the Algerian accounting profession - under colonial rule, no Algerians had qualified in accountancy (Labidi 1982).

It was not until April 1975 that the decision was made to substitute the French PCG system, which was regarded as inappropriate to the needs of the new communist economy, with an indigenous Algerian accounting scheme known as the *Plan Comptable National* (PCN) (NAP75). With this intention, the Algerian National Accounting Council 20 systematically adjusted its accounting framework in order to be able to firmly control the innovative type of business referred to as the 'socialist enterprise'. The view at that time was that, since Algeria was no longer a French colony, an appropriate postcolonial accounting system was required. Consequently, by abandoning the colonial accounting system, Algeria completed the forced removal of the colonial administrative regime. Obviously, this was a significant event.

Under the influence of the Soviet model of central planning, the Algerian government accompanied this new business model by an extensive selection of state control measures. These controls had two purposes: one to guarantee that the uses of public funds were restricted to legal purposes and the other to make sure those socialist enterprises adhered to the central plans. This was to demonstrate that socialist states 'strive programmatically to place an entire national economy under direct or indirect control' (Belkaoui 1985, p. 46). Thus, the socialist regime forced the local accounting organizations to accept a uniform accounting scheme designed around the needs of the national macroeconomic planning system and reflecting the main principles of the socialist economy.

In 2007, in place of the national accounting plan, which had been in use since 1975, the Algerian accounting regulator issued the Act 07-11, with the intention of bringing the Algerian Accounting Plan (referred to as NAP75) into line with the IFRS (The Algerian National People's Assembly, 2007). Although Algeria continued to confront both short-term and medium-term challenges (African Economic Outlook report, 2012), requiring the country to make more radical economic and fiscal improvements and reduce regional economic disparities, the IMF 2012 report pointed to solid economic growth in recent years, based on growing oil revenues and generally sound macroeconomic policies.

As a former colonial country with oil resources, which then moved to a state-controlled economy, where the main principle was to ensure that public money was properly used, Algeria is now moving forward to a modern economy and provides an encouraging model for its western neighbour, Libya.

4.11.1.4 Tunisia

It is very important in this thesis to examine the adoption of IFRS in Tunisia, due to its geographic proximity to Libya and also because it is another Islamic nation. The strategic importance of the quality of annual reports in Tunisia is reflected in the emergence of many developments in the economy related to the information environment of the Tunisian Stock Exchange, the predicted harmonization with the IFRS, and the development of corporate governance in Tunisian businesses (Chakroun *et al.* 2012).

Tunisia has a local stock exchange referred to as *Bourse des Valeurs Mobilières de Tunis* (BVMT), which is only open to Tunisian companies. All financial statements are officially reported according to the Tunisian GAAP. Tunisian listed companies are not permitted to use IFRS in preparing of financial statements. This may be attributed to the similarity of Tunisian accounting principles and their conceptual framework to the IFRS.

In fact, the Tunisian accounting standards have been effectively based on IFRS since 1995. Therefore, local Tunisian GAAP and IFRS are almost identical. Hence, all statutory financial statements must be drawn up in conformity with Tunisian GAAP. It should be noted that Tunisian firms have tended to try to achieve a very high quality of accounting information in order to attract the attention of financial analysts and thus investors (Healy *et al.* 1999; Lang & Lundholm 1993). This has, however, created high expectations on the part of local financial analysts and portfolio managers in Tunisia relating to the expected quality of corporate disclosure (Chakroun 2012). However, information disclosures in the annual report are not yet strictly regulated in Tunisia, which means that local companies are still using local accounting standards and not the IFRS, in their annual reports (Chakroun *et al.* 2012).

There are few studies on disclosure quality in emerging markets (Beyer *et al.* 2010; Botosan 2004), but Ball, Kothari and Robin (2000) do point out that, if there is not strong enforcement of shareholder rights and disclosure standards, then the quality of disclosure tends to be very poor, regardless of actual disclosure standards. Thus, Tunisian adoption of harmonized standards is not enough without strong enforcement of reporting practices.

The implementation of IFRS is not a straightforward choice between binary opposites (Camfferman & Zeff 2018). According to Elad (2015), areas of dissimilarity in IFRS adoption for Algeria, Morocco and Tunisia include the standard of conformity with IFRS

concerning coping with registered companies, forms of IFRS, and constitutional filing for registered and unlisted businesses. Elad (2015) concluded that Algeria has the highest extent of IFRS conformity (83%), followed by Morocco (50%), and lastly, Tunisia with a level of zero conformity (0%). Institutional theory may very well be able to explain the sheer diversity in IFRS conformity rates across these three countries.

Furthermore, empirical studies have investigated the impact of socioeconomic and political factors on the willingness of Egypt, Libya, Jordan, and the United Arab Emirates to use IFRS (Boolaky *et al.* 2018). The research emphasised the role of institutional development directed to the current accounting efforts in the four countries and presented a well-designed comparison between these nations and other emerging countries where IFRS is practiced (Boolaky *et al.* 2018). In addition, it discovered that Egyptian accounting standards converged with IFRS, whereas United Arab Emirates and Jordan decided to adopt IFRS entirely (Boolaky *et al.* 2018).

Impediments for the adoption of IFRS in Algeria, Morocco, and Tunisia

The process of IFRS adoption in developing countries can be protracted, as shown by the cases of Algeria, Morocco, and Tunisia. Many obstacles and hindrances have been encountered as explained below.

Firstly, the institutions are still fragile and accountants are unwilling to adopt transparency as a result. Equity markets are not well-advanced and most Moroccan executives consider accounting as a formality and not as an administrative instrument that develops business processes and improves decision-making (Ben Otman 2006).

Secondly, auditors in these countries are acquainted with a fiscal-oriented accounting archetype, where the main aim is to decrease taxes. This is because the relationship between accounting and taxation in Tunisia is such that tax rules dominate over principles of accounting (Slama & Klibi 2017).

A study by Boumediene *et al.* (2016) investigated the views of Tunisian Certified Public Accountants who reported the key difficulties associated with the adoption of IFRS to be:

(a) Businesses prepare their financial statements primarily to be consistent with tax rules. The differences between the tax procedures of the Tunisian accounting system and the IFRS are unquestionably a hindrance to a better adoption of these standards; and the final tax hindrance is the inclination of tax management with regards to the adoption of the IFRS (Boumediene *et al.* 2016, p. 62).

(b) Small and medium enterprises' accountants are inclined to fulfil the requirements of their senior managers by decreasing their responsibilities, which leads to recording decreased profits and worsening expenditures. Likewise, Morocco has a fiscal-oriented accounting system (Haoudi 2015). For instance, the General Code of Accounting Normalization accords more significance to the income statement compared to the balance sheet, because the General Code of Accounting Normalization sets out the basis for calculating taxable income by adjusting gross accounting income (Haoudi 2015).

(c) According to Saidi (2013), accountants in Algeria worked under a fiscal-oriented system, until 2010 when the transfer to the Accounting and Financial System occurred. The necessary financial statements mandated by PNC 1975 are actually closer to corporate tax return practices than to genuine financial statements. This fiscal-oriented system may also discourage the adoption of IFRS. Morocco suffers from the nonexistence of a quality assurance system and the lack of ongoing professional education and training (ROSC 2002). Moreover, the quality of institutions of higher education and college programmes in accounting and auditing need to be enhanced and made more pertinent to current IFAC-issued International Education Standards. The continuing revisions of IFRS and the gap between the announcement of IFRS and the potential adoption of IFRS in Francophone North African nations might signify additional challenges for the convergence to IFRS. We also need to consider translation from English to French or Arabic languages, which is an additional source of delays (Maradona & Chand 2018).

In conclusion, the higher conformity mark with IFRS witnessed for Algeria compared to Morocco and Tunisia can be generally explained by institutional theory factors and principles (coercive, normative, and mimetic pressures). Firstly, coercive pressures in terms of the high foreign investment flows into Algeria through the last twenty years; secondly, normative pressures exercised by the overriding influence of global Big-4 audit organizations, and

thirdly, mimetic pressures ensuing from Algeria's robust commercial rapport with the European Union compared to Morocco and Tunisia (Khlifa *et al.* 2020).

4.11.1.5 Oman

In Oman, Rawashdeh (2003) examined the effect of changing from local GAAP to IFRS on the stock prices of 18 organizations registered on the Amman Stock Exchange. The findings show an important influence on the stock prices of organizations adopting IFRS compared to non-adopting firms.

The transition of Omani reporting practices has been underlined by the principle of a commitment to enforcing compliance while allowing flexibility for the local situation in terms of the position of Islamic institutions, and also a gradual change for SMEs. Since 1986, Oman has mandatorily adopted the IFRS for all listed companies apart from Islamic institutions (Al Hussaini *et al.* 2008; Al-Shammari *et al.* 2008; Shankaraiah & Rao 2004). Following the adoption of IFRS, most listed companies did not initially comply with the directives of the financial authority to apply the IFRS in preparing their consolidated financial reports. However, the establishment of a Capital Market Authority (CMA) in 1998 and a Disciplinary Committee in 1999 ushered in a new era of enforcement of the IFRS. Unlike the situation in Tunisia, the Capital Market Authority (CMA) and the Disciplinary Committee enforce the application of IFRS by compelling the listed companies to comply with the directives of the Omani financial regulators, while the compliance of Omani Central Bank and its subsidiaries to the stipulated standards (e.g., IFRS) is normally monitored by independent auditors (Al Hussaini *et al.* 2008). The Omani local stock exchange (Muscat securities market) is also required to comply. Although IFRS is not yet mandatory for SMEs, there have been some initial moves from the CMA towards this requirement. However, adoption of IFRS for SMEs would require a Royal Decree, so this development is at an early stage. Oman is at the third stage of adoption, in which it is not yet mandatory for the Islamic institutions to apply the IFRS.

Although it is not in North Africa, three principles can be found in Oman's flexible approach to adopting IFRS which could be relevant to Libya's case. These are: some exemptions for Islamic financial institutions; a reasonable level of actual enforcement of IFRS, and staged introduction of IFRS for SMEs.

4.12 Conclusion

In considering the situation of the selected developed nations in moving towards harmonization, several themes emerge. The first is readiness to adopt. For example, Belgium had a very easy transition, because it was already following the IFRS practices. Another theme is the flexibility regarding existing practices, especially where accounting reports have functions for tax assessment and collection. Germany addressed this problem by retaining a dual system under which companies prepare accounts under the domestic system and also under IFRS, for publication purposes. Denmark also showed flexibility in adapting its traditional Anglo-Saxon practices in implementing IFRS. The third theme concerns commitment and enforcement. Rather than showing flexibility, Poland is very committed to harmonization, for instance through providing a complete translation, investing heavily, and making radical changes to accounting practices. Similarly, although a very recent EU member, Romania adopted and enforced IFRS very completely and rigorously - it too was willing to give up its previous accounting practices. This was a probable response to exiting communism and needing to quickly develop its business capabilities in a remote part of Europe, far away from established trading routes and business networks.

Greece is a special case in the EU, because it was a localized economy which included many business owners who were mainly interested in reducing tax liabilities. However, despite these issues, and its general lack of readiness and accounting expertise, it did bring about an apparent improvement in companies' financial measures after one year.

Although the USA has such a strong economy, it has also shown commitment to the importance of international accounting standards and moved to support these.

With regard to emerging economies, although the situation is different, the themes of readiness, flexibility, and commitment are still relevant. Both Egypt and Algeria have shown commitment to modernizing from state-control and also flexibility in keeping customary accounting practices. However, Tunisia, although it was well prepared and very committed, lacked sufficient enforcement. In contrast, Oman, as well as showing great commitment in adoption and enforcement of IFRS, also showed real flexibility in terms of accommodating its pre-existing local religious and business environment. All of these points could provide

important lessons in the Libyan context. The Libya context is described and discussed in Section 4.13, and finally conclusions on the issues of adoption are drawn in Section 4.14.

Chapter 4 Part C: Literature review (context of Libya)

4.13 Context of Libya

4.13.1 Introduction

Libya is a developing Arabic-Muslim nation and is an important hub in North Africa that is currently undergoing extreme political instability following the removal of the Colonel Gaddafi government. The Gaddafi government strived to overcome the over-dependence on crude oil by diversifying its economy, which prompted it to provide every incentive to attract foreign investors to invest in sectors other than the petroleum industry. As already emphasized above, one of the best ways to attract this FDI base involves the adoption of the IFRS, which improves the transparency and quality of financial reporting in a country such as Libya and assists in improving comparability (Jermakowicz 2004; Veneziani & Teodori 2008). These potential benefits arising from the adoption of the IFRS have prompted many developing countries, including Libya, to seriously consider the adopting the IFRS as a means of eliminating any hindrance to foreign investors. However, in addition to the need to promote foreign investment in Libya, there may be other factors (e.g. external influences) that have influenced this emerging economy to pursue the adoption of IFRS.

As with most emerging economies, there is likely to be an enormous external pressure on Libya from the multinational corporations, World Bank, United Nations, and other Western organizations to adopt the IFRS to improve the bilateral trade relationship between Libya and other countries.

At present, the relatively new Libyan stock exchange lacks credibility and reputation. Hence, it is only patronized by Libyan companies. Although the Libyan Stock Exchange stipulates that companies listed on this exchange must apply IFRS, none of them currently do so. Instead, most companies in Libya prepare their statutory accounts in accordance with local GAAP. This means that, in terms of its readiness, although the Libyan government has considered adopting IFRS, no plans for implementation or convergence have yet been drawn up by the Libyan body responsible for setting standards.

Cerne (2009) and Masoud (2014a) concluded that the then Libyan government was not prepared nor did it possess a forthcoming plan suitable to use with developed countries'

accounting systems so as to adopt the IFRS in Libya. Similarly, no plans have yet been announced, to the researcher's knowledge, for the application of IFRS to tax reporting or for SMES. Although, like most North African and Middle East countries (e.g. Bahrain), pursuing the adoption of IFRS is a worthwhile objective that will benefit Libya, it is bound to be accomplished only gradually (Joshi *et al.* 2008).

Furthermore, the Libya authorities should approach the adoption of IFRS with caution and emulate other developing countries that have successfully adopted the IFRS in phases and also learn from the experience of developed countries. The flexibility shown by Oman towards Islamic Institutions and SMEs, as described above, provides an example of this approach. However, the implementation of IFRS is likely to be problematic and slow, as in the case of Greece. Although that economy is developed, it is still weak (Iatridis & Rouvolis 2010). Again, the implementation of IFRS in other developing economies was a daunting challenge due to diversity of political and cultural contexts, and the fact that globalization is 'a complex process affecting organizations and countries in different ways and to different degrees' (Guler *et al.* 2002).

Lourenco *et al.* (2015) posited that, based on a robust practical consensus, even after IFRS adoption, country-specific features like the predominant legal structure, cultural settings, institutional processes, and the dissimilarities between IFRS and local standards will have a crucial influence on the implementation of the IFRS. Therefore, the next section examines Libya's political, economic, and cultural contexts in terms of how these factors affect the country's readiness and commitment, and how much flexibility or level of enforcement will be needed for complete implementation of IFRS.

4.13.2 The relevance of IFRS to Libya

(i) Political environment

The political environment is one of the most dominant influences in shaping the accounting standards of any nation. Like those of Tunisia and Algeria, described above, the Libyan economic environment has been greatly influenced by a long history of domination by colonial and foreign powers, mainly the Europeans, due to its strategic geographical location. In contrast to Algeria and Tunisia, French influences are not present, since the colonial-era powers were British, German, and Italian. However, the dominant social forces are those of the Arabic culture and Islamic religion (Ritchie & Khorwatt 2007). In addition, Libya

endured international isolation (e.g. through sanctions) for several decades after its independence in 1969. These legacies are not favourable to the harmonization of the IFRS in Libya. For instance, under a future democratic dispensation there may be more freedom-of-choice, transparency, and liberalization of investments. Additionally, Libya may come out of its international isolation by making an effort to integrate into the international community; and the international community must play its part by welcoming Libya back and not punish the Libyan people for the actions and alleged actions of its leaders. This means that, as with Romania and Poland when they entered the EU, the Libyan economic environment may well become aligned to that of the Western World, which is relevant to its readiness and the effective implementation of the IFRS. However, Libya's readiness for adoption of IFRS is likely to be affected by the stage of development of its present accounting system.

(ii) Accounting system

The accounting profession has been regarded as weak in many developing countries and Libya is not an exception (Ahmad & Gao 2004). Despite the existence of a few accounting bodies, such as the Libyan Association of Accountants and Auditors (LAAA) and the State Accounting Bureau (SAB), there is a desperate need to improve the accounting profession in the country (Ahmad & Gao 2004). Accounting reform cannot be carried out in isolation but must be carried out simultaneously with economic reforms in other sectors such as banking, pension, tax and the legal system (Tyrrall *et al.* 2007). Consequently, the harmonization of the Libyan accounting standards with the IFRS may well help to bring about much-needed improvement across a wide range of sectors.

(iii) The capital market

It is generally believed that the IFRS was developed for matured economies with well-established stock exchanges, like those described above in the EU and the USA. This point weakens the relevance of IFRS to the present-day Libya, which established its stock exchange as recently as 2007. The Libyan Stock Exchange lacks international reputation, hence only a few Libyan companies are listed. It is very likely that the impact of a series of international sanctions, over-dependence on petroleum resources and an inadequate financial reporting system in Libya are some of the numerous factors that have weakened development of the Libyan Stock Exchange. As mentioned earlier, it is frequently maintained by academics and others that, if they are to access the international capital markets, emerging economies need to apply IFRS to their reporting practices (Faraj & Akbar 2010). Although Libya needs

to overcome some of the challenges of implementing IFRS, some commitment has already been demonstrated by earlier actions in the banking sector and by the Stock Exchange regulations. The importance of adopting IFRS by all Libyan banks is stated in the Banks Law No. 1 (2005). In addition, the Libyan Stock Exchange Law No. 134 of 2005 requires all companies listed on the Libyan SE adopt IFRS (Zakari 2014).

(iv) The private-sector factor

The Libyan economy has depended predominantly on revenues derived from the exportation of petroleum products for several decades. Most of the enterprises in Libya are publicly-owned, with a very small private sector, which is focused on the oil industry. Because it could demand from its publicly-owned organizations any information which it required, in a suitable form, the Gadaffi government did not really need the publication of annual reports concerning its public enterprises (Nobes 1998). Nevertheless, with the advent of political change in Libya, the country is likely to seek to undertake vigorous reform by encouraging economic activities that are presently in the public sector to move into the private sector. Although the shift of economic activities from public to private sector is likely to take place slowly, it increases the potential relevance of IFRS to the Libyan economy. The experience of Egypt in making a similar transition from state-control to a freer economy, and its flexible and cautious approach to gradually adopting IFRS, could provide lessons for Libya.

4.13.3 The potential impediments to implementation of IFRS in Libya

Contemporary academic contributions emphasize that implementation of IFRS in Libya will be problematic due to several factors. These include absence of technical expertise and the insufficient knowledge of Libyan professional auditors, the struggle to improve its current accounting structures and lack of a guiding structure to handle economic and social growth. Other factors include recent developments in the accounting profession, including IFRS, and poor education and training of auditors (Schachler, Al-Abiyad & Al-Hadad 2012).

The majority view is that (IFRS) adoption in Libya will face problems such as the weakness of professional accountancy organization, absence of an autonomous oversight body, discrepancy of current regulations and controlling structures of accounting in Libya. Other factors include recent development of accounting profession, lack of economic growth, deficiencies in technical skills and insufficient knowledge of Libyan professional auditors, as well as fragile accounting education (Masoud 2014, Mohamed 2014).

Like other developing countries, Libya is bound to face several problems that may hinder the effective implementation of IFRS. Many of these points were mentioned by my survey and interview respondents. Some of the obstacles that may hinder the effective implementation of IFRS in Libya are considered below.

(i) Language barrier

Durocher and Gendron (2011) emphasize that an accounting language that is not unified creates difficulties for investors to draw company comparisons, so an integrated global financial reporting standard may enhance accounting qualities and investment decisions (Liu *et al.* 2011). There has to be a unified language among countries that wish to adopt the IFRS, since IFRS is the global language which is widely accepted by international investors (Bui *et al.* 2020, p. 167). As such, it appears that the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya is important to improve investments, provide high quality and costless information, and allow companies to harmonize and standardize their transactions and disclosure.

As the IFRS standards are written in English, one of the barriers faced by many countries is that the business and accounting professions cannot access them easily. Poland tackled this problem through a major project of translating and publishing the entire IFRS documentation. Arabic is the official language of Libya. English is not an official language¹⁰ in Libya and there is lack of expertise among the accountants to be able to communicate in English. The curriculum and the directions for the IFRS are in English, and this is a major hindrance for the accountants (Buzied 1998).

Consequently, to make a strong commitment towards implementation, translation of IFRS into Arabic must be undertaken for the users in Libya to effectively apply these standards in their financial reporting. However, as for other non-English speaking countries, there is bound to be a degree of erroneous translation from English into Arabic. Furthermore, there may be misinterpretation of imprecisely translated items in the IFRS, thereby resulting in the preparation of faulty financial reports. To avoid this requires the employment of highly qualified professional translators. This point was addressed by my interviewees.

¹⁰ Nor the mother tongue either.

(ii) Islamic culture

Azmi (2010) points out that Islam determines not only the form of prayers but also the commercial transactions which the Muslims must deal with in their lives (p. 3). In addition, Dowa *et al.* (2007, p. 172), stated that ‘religion is a cultural obstacle to the adoption of IFRS in some countries and some institution’. According to Lewis (2001, p. 106), ‘Islamic economic and financial moralities have a straight effect on accounting strategies and practices which, contains the institution of ‘*Zakat*’, the prohibition of ‘*Riba*’ (financial interest), and the institution of an interest-free economic system’. This indicates that the conventional balance-sheet by Western standards does not conform to Islamic principles of accounting, mainly the *Zakāt* issue (charitable giving) (Wilson 2004, p. 1), which may also constitute an obstacle to the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya.

Another barrier to the effective implementation of the IFRS in Libya is the Islamic culture of the people. Libya is predominantly an Islamic nation and thus its accounting system contains many aspects of the Islamic tradition. For instance, as in Oman, *Sharia’a* banking is enshrined in the accounting system of Libya. There are some irreconcilable differences between the *Sharia’a* banking system (which is based on religious codes) and IFRS (which is based on secular codes). The most notable difference is the prohibition on drawing interest. Moreover, the tax principles of these contrasting accounting standards are very different. For these reasons, the full adoption of IFRS may not be possible in Libya; otherwise, there will be conflicts between the two accounting systems. Any chance of Libya adopting the IFRS would require some form of modification to eliminate possible conflict between the *Sharia’a* and IFRS. Joshi *et al.* (2008) investigated the obstacles to adoption of IFRS by Islamic banks and other financial institutions and offered three possible options:

- a.) These entities should simply continue to observe Islamic Accounting Standards regardless of the convergence;
- b.) It should be mandatory for them to adopt IFRS; or
- c.) These organizations should be obliged to provide reconciliation with IFRS as well as preparing financial statements using Islamic Accounting Standards.

Oman chose to follow option (a), in the initial stages at least.

(i) Low level of education

The literacy level in Libya is relatively low (91% total, including 96.7% for men and 85.6% for women) (CIA World Fact Book 2021). Tertiary education rates are especially poor.

Hence, the necessary pool of highly-skilled professionals needed for the effective application of IFRS in Libya will be lacking, as was the case in Egypt. Thus, there is need for the Libyan government to develop the manpower needed to sustain the implementation of the IFRS; otherwise the adoption of IFRS will only result to non-compliance or wrong application of these sets of standards. Poland has set a good example in addressing this problem by investment in the changes needed for successful implementation.

(ii) Poor infrastructure

There is also a lack of necessary infrastructure needed to sustain the adoption of IFRS in Libya. The level of accounting education is inferior compared to that in other developing countries that have successfully adopted IFRS (BooLaky 2010). Similarly, the Information Technology needed for the effective implementation of IFRS in Libya is either lacking or there is a shortage of expertise to manage the enormous amount of information that normally accompanies the application of IFRS. Again, Poland's private sector investment in expensive accounting and finance computer systems for their accounting and finance transactions provides a model to solve this problem.

(iii) Instability of the government

Most countries that have successfully adopted and implemented IFRS have a track record of stable democracy. Libya is currently in transition away from a state-owned economic system. The new ruling parties may not be able to sustain the adoption and implementation of IFRS, because changes in government usually disrupt smooth implementation. Consequently, there is need for the new governments in Libya to stabilize before the adoption of IFRS at a future date. I explored this theme at length in interviews with study participants. Algeria's progress in changing its accounting system from one that reflected the main principles of the socialist economy to one in line with the principles of the market economy is, for Libya, an encouraging vision.

(iv) Corruption

Corruption is also the continuing problem of most developing countries and constitutes an obstacle to the effective implementation of the IFRS. Libya's score for the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) (2020) is 17/100, while it is ranked at 173 out of 180 countries, where a ranking of 180 out of 180 would indicate the most corrupt (Transparency.org 2021). For example, fraud, particularly in the form of bribery and corruption, and money laundering

is often a problem in developing economies and emerging markets, and Libya is no exception. The adoption of IFRS in a corrupt society is bound to fail, because most users of the adopted standards are likely to collect ‘kick-backs’ or bribes to manipulate financial reports. Consequently, there is a need for Libya to tackle its corruption problems before the adoption of the IFRS. One way to reduce corruption is through enforcement of disclosure. In Oman a disciplinary committee was set up to promote enforcement, whereas in Tunisia there was a lack of enforcement, which meant the adoption process was not as completely successfully as it should have been, despite people’s initial readiness.

Yapa *et al.* (2010) suggest that one of the features that might be a hindrance to harmonizing accounting standards is the weakness of the professional accounting bodies, as the IASB needs a strong effort to apply the accounting standards successfully. Similarly, Mir and Rahaman (2005) emphasize that the most difficult feature of the adoption of the international standards relates to the procedure of implementation rather than to the content of the individual standards. In the same vein, Barth *et al.* (2008) have argued that the effects of features of the financial reporting structure rather than the standards themselves could eliminate any improvement arising from higher quality accounting standards. However, according to Masoud, the most substantial of these restrictions that hinder the adoption of IFRS in Libya are lack of technical skills and adequate knowledge among auditors in Libya. He claims that (2014, p. 131): ‘The lack of technical skills and insufficient knowledge of Libyan specialized auditors was one of the major implementation problems of IFRS in Libya as emphasized by Schachler *et al.* (2012), Laga (2012), Masoud (2014), and Zakari (2014).’ This adds to the difficulties arising from the deficiency of financial reports and the lack of proper auditing standards, inconsistency in existing laws and difficulties related to taxation and absence of enforcement.

Studies by Zehri and Chouaihi (2013) and Masoud (2014b) in the Libyan context also indicate that, as in other developing countries, limited knowledge and expertise could hinder the IFRS implementation. The rest of this section discusses each factor follows:

1. Lack of technical skills and adequate knowledge among auditors in Libya

Masaud (2013, p. 1) pointed out that a bachelor’s degree is the only requirement to be admitted to the Libyan Association of Accounting and Auditing (LAAA) as a full-member, along with some practical experience. There is also no requirement to undergo continuous

professional training after becoming a full-time member of the LAAA. Usually the firms hiring accountants and auditors do not conduct any training programmes for furthering the skills of their accountants. Many scholars have noted that this system often creates impediments within the process of accounting education in Libya. The most dissuading factor is the curriculum itself, that is considered to be grossly outdated compared to international standards and the lack of proper learning materials that do not allow students to develop a strong background in accounts and auditing in Libya when compared to most modern nations. There are insufficient resources while one is practising as an accountant in Libya, as the LAAA does not possess the capability and resources to judge and monitor the effectiveness, practicability, and quality of training programmes and modules or the training providers. Historically, Libyan accounting lecturers themselves have been considered to lack the necessary experience and quality to teach both the theory and practice of accounting/auditing within the context of the International Financial Reporting Standards (Buzied 1998; Kilani 1988). These are some of the obstacles that the companies and the accounting profession must first overcome before they can consider implementing the IFRS.

The LAAA is responsible for the development of and implementation of the IFRS through the process of training and classes. However, historically, it has lacked the authority to do so (Bait-El-Mal *et al.* 1973; Kilani 1988). Hence, accountants in Libya are unlikely have the skills to cope with the international standards of accounting applicable through the IFRS. The accountancy education system in Libya does not include the IAS/IFRS in its curriculum. Thus, without basic knowledge of these systems, accounting professionals in Libya are not able to prepare any financial statements within the bounds of these standards (Bayoud 2013).

The problem is compounded by the fact that the professionals that prepare the accounting curriculum are not very confident that they can incorporate the IAS/IFRS standards. This results in the accountants in Libya following the old system of accounting and presents a problem for the implementation of IFRS (Faraj & Essa 2014). These findings of Faraj and Essa (2014) corroborate the findings of previous scholars such as Aileme and Akande (2012), Albu and Albu (2012), Aljifri and Khasharmeh (2006), Boolaky (2012), Kapoor and Ruhela (2013), Mahmud and Russell (2003), and Marchall and Rossman (1989).

2. Inconsistency in existing laws

The accounting practice in Libya is governed by a number of laws issued and promulgated to guide accounting. However, although this form of governance provides some guidelines in the preparation of accounting records, such principles and rules do not specify the accounting principles that accountants need to follow. Therefore, the implementation of the IFRS would be in contradiction to the existing laws and regulations regarding accounting in Libya. The present legal and regulatory framework that is prevalent in accounting in Libya needs to be reconsidered so that the IFRS can be implemented efficiently. Such changes need to be made to reflect the real issues that are related to the economy and society.

The IFRS is independent of local and national legal structures. It is often seen that the national accounting norms and systems depend on one or the other. Thus there is requirement of either a common-law or a coded-law system. Protective regulations, for example unfair trade and antitrust regulations, often affect the way accounting is done. In Libya, this is a problem for the effective implementation of IFRS (Buzied 1998).

3. Taxation: IFRS adoption could generate difficulty

The necessity for political reforms that embrace and encourage the implementation of the IFRS has been emphasized (Ball, 2006). In addition, Ball, Robin and Wu (2003) stressed that legal avenues educational requirements, and political influences must be in place so as to assist the implementation of the IFRS. Moreover, Armstrong *et al.* (2007) and Soderstrom and Sun (2007) claimed that political and business differences might constitute important difficulties in the progress towards the adoption and implementation of the IFRS.

The tax laws in Libya affect accounting practices in Libya by influencing the practices of financial reporting. These regulations in tax policy and laws do not produce information conforming to the international standards of accounting and thus the implementation of IFRS is made difficult by the law (Masoud 2014).

Hung and Subramanyam (2007) note that the IFRS are independent of tax reporting considerations, as the value (net income) plays a greater (lesser) valuation role under IFRS than under local GAAP. They also claimed that while the IFRS adjustments to book-value are generally value relevant, the adjustments to income are generally value-irrelevant. This represents an obstacle to the proper implementation of the IFRS.

The Libyan income tax law, formulated and enacted in 1968, was replaced by the Libyan *Income Tax Law* No. 64 of 1973 and subsequently law number 11 was added to the law in 2004 which had a great influence on accounting practices in Libya. In the new law, several accountancy issues were specified, for example, specific methods and rates were defined for calculating depreciation for different assets. Depreciation of establishment costs over a period of three to five years was to be calculated by the straight-line method. Another example of the tax law influencing accounting is that the distinction between operating income and extraordinary income was not made.

4. Absence of enforcement

Another obstacle is seen in the lack of enforcement to implement IASs/IFRS by external auditors, the Libyan Accounting Bureau (LAB), and the Libyan Stock Market (LSM) (Shareia 2014).

5. The deficiency of financial reports and proper auditing standards resulting from insufficiency of national accounting structures

Every aspect of the accounting and auditing profession is regulated and managed by the LAAA as well as in the implementation of the laws and regulations associated with accounting as set by the government in Libya. The association is also responsible for the organization and improvement of the conditions and environment of the profession of accounting and auditing. However, an early study by Buzied (1998) concluded that the LAAA did not have enough resources and capability to completely and efficiently monitor the accounting and auditing needs. He noted that accounting and auditing firms were free to choose their own methods and practices to suit their needs and the needs of the client. However, there was a lack of consultation and defining of the gaps between the regulations and the practices existing in the country. This encouraged attempts to minimize the gap between practice and regulations but also meant the inclusion of international norms in accounting was not possible (Buzied 1998).

A recent study conducted by Faraj and Essa (2014) found little change, and this factor was emphasized as the strongest of the factors that may be considered as challenges or difficulties affecting the implementation of IFRS by Libyan companies listed on the Libyan Stock Market (LSM).

4.14 Conclusion

The adoption and implementation processes of IFRS have been a daunting challenge to most countries, particularly developing countries. These processes also differ among countries because of differences in a range of factors, which include the environment and socio-cultural, political, historical, and economic factors. As seen from the cases discussed in this chapter, most countries review the IFRS and adopt those sections that are relevant to the needs of their economies and cultural contexts, and the implementation of these standards depends on several factors, which include the necessary infrastructure and the political motivation to enforce the implementation of the IFRS. It was clear from Chapter 4 Part B that even among the member states of the EU, there has been variation in the form of IFRS implementation.

Similarly, developing countries such as Libya are also bound to face many challenges regarding the implementation of the IFRS. Some of the challenges encountered by these countries include: a weak accounting profession; language barriers (i.e. the requirement for high quality translation); cultural differences, particularly in the emerging Islamic economies discussed above, and widespread corruption. As Chapter 4 has pointed out, these challenges require a solution involving flexibility, but also a high level of commitment and enforcement.

Harmonization of accounting standards in Libya is a huge and daunting task. The adoption of IFRS by Libya would be beneficial for effective communication of accounting practices and financial statements with other countries (i.e. beyond the shores of Libya) and would improve the quality of reported financial statements. Consequently, accounting practices such as reporting of financial statements would probably become more transparent and instil confidence in both local and foreign investors. Hence, harmonization will very likely attract foreign investors to invest in the Libyan economy. This will help to stimulate and diversify the Libyan economy away from being a major exporter of crude oil to becoming a producer and exporter of other commodities (which may include farm produce and exploration and exploitation of minerals other than crude oil).

Nevertheless, the adoption of the IFRS without any modification will pose problems to the Libyan people because of their historical and cultural heritage. Libya is predominantly an Islamic country with a brutal and difficult colonial past. Hence, it will be more beneficial for Libya to adopt IFRS with appropriate modification to meet the local socioeconomic needs of

its people. Using the lessons from the experience of the countries with both developed and emerging economies, and the models they provide, this study will attempt to identify the modifications needed and the stages of implementation that would be feasible and effective. This will include investigating how the Libyan authorities can establish a clear timetable for the adoption and make appropriate plans and time to put in place the necessary infrastructure, including the development of suitably qualified professionals to start the process of adoption of these standards. My interviewees and survey respondents for the present project have provided extra advice and insight on potential implementation problems and plans. In the next chapter of this thesis, I present and explain the quantitative results. The qualitative results are then presented and discussed in Chapter 6, before Chapter 7 summarizes and concludes the work.

Chapter Five - Quantitative results

5.1 Introduction

The main focus for readers of this thesis should be the quantitative results and, for that reason, I present these findings first. First, within this chapter, I present the demographic results section, which summarizes the demographic characteristics of the survey respondents. After this, I discuss all of the statistically significant survey results on a question-by-question basis. I then explain how the results vary significantly (or not) based on the various demographic characteristics. In the succeeding chapter, I discuss and explore the qualitative findings and relate them to institutional theory. For all statistical tests I used the statistical package SPSS, version 14.

5.2 Demographic results

1. Gender

Table 5.1 shows the sample divided up according to the professed genders of the respondents. I note that the highest percentage of individuals in the sample is male, with a percentage of 83.33%; while the percentage of female respondents is 16.67%. Although it is changing rapidly, I still conclude that the Libyan accounting and business sector is at present male-dominated, and hence I expect that masculine practices and discourses is likely to dominate.

Table 5.1 - Gender distribution

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative
Male	255	83.33	83.33
Female	51	16.67	100
Total	306	% 100	

Figure 5.1 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of gender

2. Age

Table 5.2 shows age distribution for the sample, where I find that 37.91% of the total sample is aged from 30-40 years, with 31.05% aged from 41 to 50. The percentage of the individuals who are over the age of 60 years is very small, at only 0.65%. On balance, the respondents are mostly from the younger age brackets (defined as up to 40 years old). However, this weighting towards younger people is representative of the finance industry age distribution structure in Libya.

I believe that the distribution of the age groups of the respondents in the sample is diverse and sufficient, and therefore it is likely that the overall set of answers will be informative and that we can test to see whether answers vary systematically according to age-group.

Table 5.2 - Age distribution of the sample

Age	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative
Under 30	70	22.88	22.88
30-40	116	37.91	60.78
41-50	95	31.05	91.83
51-60	23	7.52	99.35
Over 60	2	0.65	100
Total	306	100	

Figure 5.2 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of age

3. Position

Table 5.3 shows the results relating to the job title, and it is noted that the highest percentage is for 'staff accountant', with a percentage of 36.60%, closely followed by 'auditor'(35.29%), followed by 'senior accountant' (19.61%).

It is clear from the above that the job titles of the individuals in the research sample are diverse and at the required level, and thus, the respondents are likely to be sufficiently aware of the goals of the study. They will also have the knowledge and experience to be able to contribute informed responses.

Table 5.3 - The sample distribution in terms of job title

Position	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative
Owner/partner	2	0.65	0.65
Senior accountant	60	19.61	20.26
Staff accountant	112	36.60	56.86
Auditor	108	35.29	92.16
Academic accountant	24	7.84	100
Total	306	% 100	

Figure 5.3 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of job title

4. Professional experience

Table 5.4 shows the result for the respondents' professional experience. It is noted that the highest percentage (38.89%) is for those for with over twelve years of experience, while 17.65% of respondents have 3-6 years of experience, and 14.05% have of 9-12 years of experience. Thus, over 50% of the respondents have nine or more years of experience (52%).

As a result of their accumulated of experience, the respondents are likely to be sufficiently aware of what the IFRS may offer to Libya. Therefore, the opinions of sample members can be relied upon to produce results that serve the objectives of the study.

Table 5.4 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of experience

Professional experience	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative
1-2 years	34	11.11	11.11
2-3 years	22	7.19	18.30
3-6 years	54	17.65	35.95
6-9 years	34	11.11	47.06
9-12 years	43	14.05	61.11
Over 12 years	119	38.89	100
Total	306	% 100	

Figure 5.4 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of experience

5. Place of education:

Table 5.5 shows the results of the sample distribution in terms of education, where I find that respondents educated in Libya account for 87.58% of the sample, while British educated respondents account for 6.21%, while other percentages are distributed among various other countries.

Because as many as 87% of the sample is Libyan-educated, the sample may not be diverse enough to make definite conclusions about the effect of place of education on results. This lack of diversity was not within my control as the researcher.

Table 5.5 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of place of education

Place of education	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative
Libya	268	87.58	87.58
UK	19	6.21	93.79
USA	3	0.98	94.77
Other Western countries	4	1.31	96.08
Other Arabic countries	8	2.61	98.69
Rest of the world	4	1.31	100
Total	306	% 100	

Figure 5.5 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of place of education

6. Qualifications:

Table 5.6 shows the results of the sample distribution in terms of academic qualification, where I find that 56.54% of the respondents hold a bachelor's degree, and 18.63% hold a master's degree while only 5.23% hold a doctorate. The remaining 17.32% hold a diploma.

I believe that the range of academic qualifications held by the individuals of the sample is varied and sufficient, and therefore it is possible to rely on the answers of the sample members and obtain information related to how level of qualification affects the survey results. Figure 5.6 presents the qualification levels in graphical form.

Table 5.6 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of academic qualifications

Qualification	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative
High School	6	1.96	1.96
Diploma	53	17.32	19.28
Bachelor	173	56.54	75.82
MSc	57	18.63	94.44
PhD	16	5.23	99.67
Other	1	0.33	100
Total	306	100	

Figure 5.6 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of academic qualifications

7. Accounting training courses:

Table 5.7 shows the results of the sample distribution in terms of training courses, where we find that 52.61% of the total sample attend a session once a year and the other proportions are distributed at various intervals from ‘once a month’ upwards. It is noticed that 28.10% of the respondents answer, ‘not applicable’. ‘Not applicable’ might mean either ‘no training’ or ‘training at irregular intervals;’ and so less attention will be placed upon the results for this group of respondents.

I believe that the attendance at training courses for the respondents is varied and sufficient, and therefore it is possible to rely upon the answers of the sample members. The information will allow us to observe how frequency of training courses affects the survey information provided by respondents (see Figure 5.7). However, as mentioned, less attention will be given to results for the ‘not applicable’ group as it is hard to know exactly what ‘not applicable’ means in each individual case.

Table 5.7 - The sample distribution in terms of training courses attended

Accounting training and courses	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative
Once a month	15	4.90	4.90
Once every three months	18	5.88	10.78
Once every six months	25	8.17	18.95
Once a year	161	52.61	71.57
Other	1	0.33	71.89
Not Applicable	86	28.10	100
Total	306	100	

Figure 5.7 - Distribution of the research sample in terms of accounting cycles

5.3 Correlation matrices

Table 5.8(a)

		AGE	Experience
AGE	Pearson Correlation	1	.750(**)
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	306	306
Experience	Pearson Correlation	.750(**)	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	306	306

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01).

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05).

Table 5.8(b)

		AGE	Qualification
AGE	Pearson Correlation	1	.058
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.314
	N	306	306
Qualifications	Pearson Correlation	.058	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.314	
	N	306	306

Table 5.8(c)

		Experience	Qualification
Experience	Pearson Correlation	1	-.012
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.838
	N	306	306
Qualifications	Pearson Correlation	-.012	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.838	
	N	306	306

The correlation matrices for the interactions of three variables, age, experience, and qualifications, are presented above. No correlations are computed for other variables, as it is not clear, theoretically, how they might correlate with each other. For example, it is hard to rate and rank job titles, other than ‘staff accountant’ and ‘senior accountant’, so any correlation number would be close to meaningless. It is impossible to rank ‘academic’ against ‘auditor’ or against, as another example, ‘senior accountant’. Similarly, neither place of qualification nor frequency of training courses, *a priori*, would appear to correlate with other variables.

The first correlation coefficient, in Table 5.8(a), shows that age and years’ experience are, as predicted, significantly positively correlated with each other at the 1% level. The correlation coefficient is +0.750 (sig = 0.000). As expected, younger (older) people have fewer (more) years of professional experience behind them. Statisticians believe that multicollinearity becomes a problem for interpretation of results when r exceeds +0.7 or +0.8. Where this happens, the separate effects of each variable, on the dependent variable, become very difficult to disentangle. Here I note that the correlation coefficient is on the borderline for multicollinearity.

Secondly, Table 5.8(b) reports no significant correlation between age and qualification, where age is placed in ascending order and highest qualification is placed on the bottom of the list for that variable. The correlation coefficient here is marginally positive ($r = +0.058$)

but it is not significant even at the 5% level. If anything, older people tend to be better qualified, which sounds reasonable, progressively as they grow older. But it is very important to note that this relationship is not statistically significant. There could be younger people with MSc and PhDs, such as career academics, and this factor cancels out the anticipated positive relationship caused by people securing higher and higher degrees.

Lastly, according to Table 5.8(c), there is no significant correlation between qualification and experience ($r = -0.012$, $\text{sig} = 0.838$). The marginally negative coefficient suggests that younger people are ambitious to secure higher qualifications, while those with many years' experience got into the system earlier when educational requirements and expectations were lower. This factor cancels out the expected positive correlation caused by people gaining more experience at the same time as they work towards higher qualifications.

5.4 Question-by-question results

Presentation and discussion of the survey results in question-by-question order:

1. Survey question (2.1 to 2.2). To what extent are Libyan professionals aware of the international financial reporting standards? Do you feel you have sufficient knowledge of IFRS?

Table 5.9 - The frequency, percentage, and any square measure of the responses of the study sample indicating the extent of Libyan professionals' awareness of IFRS

Question	Yes		No		Missing		Total	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%			
Q2.1	180	58.82	126	41.18	0	0	306	9.529**	0.002
Q2.1.1	113	36.93	67	21.90	126	41.18	306	11.756**	0.001
Q2.1.1.1.	113	36.93	0	0.00	193	63.07	306	110.035**	0.000
Q2.1.2	42	13.73	84	27.45	180	58.82	306	14.000**	0.000
Q2.2	300	98.04	6	1.96	0	0.00	306	282.471**	0.000
Q2.2.1	124	40.52	176	57.52	6	1.96	306	9.013**	0.003

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01), (*) statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

Table 5.9 shows the frequency distribution and the percentage of the study sample answers on the axis in descending order, and a test for independence, the Chi-Square test of independence. The results of the study indicate, through the percentages, for the respondents' answers, the majority of the sample believe that: they have sufficient awareness and knowledge of the IFRS for preparing financial reports (Q2.1); the IFRS have a positive impact on financial reports (Q2.1.1.1); and, through the sample people's experiences, IFRS plays an important role in improving the quality of financial reports (Q2.2). The answers for Q2.2 suggest that nearly all respondents would be willing to apply the standards. However, the answers to Q2.2.1 show that most respondents believe that Libya is not suited for these standards (although 40% dispute this conclusion). The reasons for this at the moment are most probably political due to severe governmental instability.

The significant results for these survey questions support the proposition that institutional theory is a valid explanatory theory here because the IASB seems to have secured a large measure of support and acceptance in Libya, as well as elsewhere. Isomorphic pressures are working powerfully to ensure conformity with conventional global practices, in the accounting arena, as represented by the IASB's set of IFRS. Coercion may be implicit in many settings, but overall the pressures appear to be primarily normative and mimetic.

The pros and possible difficulties in applying the IFRS in Libya:

3.1 Do you agree that applying the IFRSs will have a potential positive impact on financial reports in the Libyan reality?

Table 5.10 – Potential positive impact of IFRS on Libyan financial reports

Q	Valid	Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
1	YES	293	95.75	256.209**	0.000
2	NO	13	4.25		
Total		603	001		

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

Table 5.10 shows the frequency distribution and percentage of study sample responses to the statement, and the Chi-Square test of independence. The results overwhelmingly suggest that almost all respondents (293 out of 306, or 96%) believe that using IFRS will have a positive impact. Very few respondents disagreed (only 13 or 4%). The concept of IFRS appears to be strongly supported in Libya, at least among this sample of accounting and finance professionals. The high level of positive support suggests that the IFRS are not widely seen as an unwarranted foreign intrusion into the Libyan accounting environment.

3.2 Factors expected to affect the process of applying these standards in Libya

Table 5.11 - Factors expected to affect the process of applying these standards in Libya

Factors	Yes		No		Total	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%			
F3	189	61.76	117	38.24	306	16.941	0.000
F12	181	59.15	125	40.85	306	10.248	0.001
F1	135	44.12	171	55.88	306	4.235	0.040
F2	119	38.89	187	61.11	306	15.111	0.000
F6	105	34.31	201	65.69	306	30.118	0.000
F11	97	31.70	209	68.30	306	40.993	0.000
F4	96	31.37	210	68.63	306	42.471	0.000
F16	93	30.39	213	69.61	306	47.059	0.000
F8	92	30.07	214	69.93	306	48.641	0.000
F13	76	24.84	230	75.16	306	77.503	0.000
F14	69	22.55	237	77.45	306	92.235	0.000
F15	64	20.92	242	79.08	306	103.542	0.000
F5	62	20.26	244	79.74	306	108.248	0.000
F9	54	17.65	252	82.35	306	128.118	0.000
F10	49	16.01	257	83.99	306	141.386	0.000
F7	39	12.75	267	87.25	306	169.882	0.000

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

Table 5.11 shows the frequency distribution and the percentage of the study sample answers about the axis, in descending order, and Chi-Square test of independence results.

The respondents think that the two factors which will most significantly affect IFRS implementation are instability of government (62%) and corruption (59%). These are typical and widespread problems in the Third World. However, the Libyan situation from 2014-present, the period of the Second Libyan Civil War, is particularly precarious and difficult, even by regional standards. There are, in fact, two groups claiming governmental authority in Libya: (1) the US and EU-backed Government of National Accord (GNA), led by Prime Minister Fayed al-Sarraj, and based in the capital-city Tripoli, and (2) the House of Representatives, led by Marshal Khalifa Haftar, commander-in-chief of Libyan National Army, and based in Tobruk, near the border with Egypt. This group was 'elected' in 2014 based on only 18% of the voter turnout. Various sources report that the country has experienced severe problems since 2014, including frequent electrical blackouts, the near cessation of business activity, and the exodus of a large number of Libyans to nearby and other countries. Most departing Libyans have fled to Egypt, Tunisia, Italy or Malta. Some applied for asylum and have ended up in the UK, France, Germany, and Italy. A farcical situation has been achieved whereby both governments in Libya have issued visas and rejected the validity of the visas issued by the other one. The fact that the country is in such a depressing situation means that adopting IFRS is, and should be, well down the list of priorities. Without a stable government with an effective judicial system, the IFRS set of standards will not be enforceable even if they are adopted. Adopting IFRS is a difficult and expensive process and it requires political stability and economic growth before it can even be attempted.

After the first two factors, there is a significant gap until we reach the third most significant factor, 'language barrier', which was selected by 44%, followed by 'low level of education' (39%) and 'political factors (34%)'. These factors are predictable and not surprising. No easy solutions are available and improvement will take time and effort. The accounting profession cannot right the ship by itself - it needs to wait for political stability. Over time, a more educated accounting profession will improve the quality and up-to-date nature of accounting education. (One limitation of the question is that 'education factors' could be perceived to mean either 'all education' or 'accounting education' and we have no way of knowing how the phrase was interpreted.) There is also some presumed correlation between some factors,

e.g. instability of government, corruption, and political factors are partly describing the same thing. However, as all are frequently chosen by respondents, the results for these three factors are mutually supportive.

‘Financial factors’, ‘complexities of tax laws and statutory accounting’ and ‘cultural factors’ are not generally perceived to be major barriers to implementation. There is also some category overlap here, because complexities of tax law are also financial factors. The results regarding cultural factors and religion also reinforce each other – neither is expected to make a major difference. It is possible that accountants generally do not pay much attention to cultural aspects and religion, i.e. they separate their working lives from their private lives (however, see later discussion). The impacts of culture and religion may be more obvious after actual IFRS implementation has actually occurred.

Few respondents believe that ‘Islamic culture’ will have a sufficient negative effect on implementation (16%). This is an important result because some writers have suggested that it could pose a major problem. Interviewees in the qualitative study said that it would be simple to remove some IFRS standards in Libya if they did not match with Islamic requirements (see Chapter 6, Qualitative results). The factor respondents were least concerned about was ‘social factors’ (13%). One problem with the wording of this question was that the meaning of ‘social factors’ was not made clear and it could overlap with ‘cultural factors’. The high rank of ‘language barriers’ among the factors suggests that major long-term efforts must be made in Libya to improve English-language skills and the number and quality of translators. The recent, post-2014 ‘brain drain’ of talented people to other countries has made this problem much worse in the short-term.

The findings here relate less directly to institutional theory. Government instability and corruption are internal factors, within Libya, which are generally perceived highly negatively. They do not impact upon the perceptions about IFRS directly, although they may contribute to a picture forming whereby the IASB appears to be efficient and incorrupt because it is seen as a direct opposite to the local reality. The presence of translation and incompatibility issues suggest that there are still widespread concerns about a shift to total conformity with IFRS. Isomorphic forces and pressures are strong, but there remain resistance and concerns.

Q3.3. Will the IFRSs have potential impacts on financial reporting?

Table 5.12 – Potential impacts of IFRS on financial reporting

Q	Valid	Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
1	YES	298	97.386	274.837	0.000
2	NO	8	2.614		
Total		306	100		

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

Table 5.12 shows the frequency distribution and the percentage of study sample answers for the statement, and the result of the Chi-Square test of independence. It can be seen that the vast majority (298 or 97%) of respondents believe that the IFRS will have potential impacts on financial reports. Only a very small number of people (8 or 3%) think that IFRS will not have any potential impact. Perhaps the word ‘material’ should have been added to this question so that it read ‘material potential impacts’. Again, this is a very strong result. Opinions on this issue do not seem to be divided at all. Thus, isomorphic forces appear to have been extremely effective in shaping people’s views on IFRS.

Q3.3.1 What is the nature of these effects?

Table 5.13- Nature of the effects of IFRS adoption

Q	Valid	Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
1	Positive	298	97.386	274.837	0.000
2	Negative	8	2.614		
Total		603	001		

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

Q3.3.1.1 If the effects are negative, it will have a reflection on ...

Table 5.14 – Negative effects of adoption

Factor	Yes		NO		Total	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%			
F1	14	4.575	297	97.059	306	252.562**	0.000
F4	14	4.575	292	95.425	306	252.562**	0.000
F3	3	0.980	303	99.020	306	294.118**	0.000
F2	2	0.654	304	99.346	306	298.052**	0.000

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

The respondents' answers indicate that the majority of the sample believes that the negative effects of adoption of IFRS for the preparation of financial reports would be either minimal or non-existent (see Table 5.13). However, if negative effects were found (see Table 5.14), they would primarily occur in the governmental sector in Libya, with a smaller negative effect on external investors. Presumably, external investors (foreign and local) are assumed to be sophisticated users who can adjust reports for changes in accounting policies. Overall, very, very few respondents predicted any negative effects of adoption of IFRS. There appears to be no sizeable 'fear factor'. Isomorphic forces appear to have been extremely effective in producing positive opinions on IFRS and its standard-setting apparatus. The only way to get some contrary answers might be to ask for opinions about individual IFRS standards.

4. What is the need to apply the international financial reporting standards and perceptions of Libyan professionals about their entry to the accounting profession in Libya?

Q4.1 Is there an urgent need by users of accounting data and information in Libya to adopt the international financial reporting standards?

While visual observation here may not be able to determine with certainty whether the numbers of Yes and No responses are significantly different, the Chi-square test shows that

the difference is significant at both the 1% and 5% levels (refer to Table 5.15 below). Most respondents do not believe that there is an urgent need to adopt IFRS (181 or 59% compared to 125 or 41%). This suggests a very cautious attitude, perhaps because respondents are aware of the contextual difficulties of implementation. They do support IFRS but they take a circumspect attitude about it - it does not need to happen right away. There seem to be far more pressing matters to attend to now in Libya than setting up a new accounting regime based on global practices ultimately derived from the West. While this result might appear to contradict institutional theory, instead it should be seen only as a negative comment on the local political, institutional, and social context. The IASB still looks better by comparison.

Table 5.15 – Urgent need to adopt the IFRS, or otherwise

Q	Valid	Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
1	YES	181	59.150	10.248**	0.001
2	NO	125	40.850		
Total		306	100		

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

Q4.1.1 Who is concerned with this?

Table 5.16 – Concerns of user groups

Factors	Yes		NO		Total	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%			
F4	168	54.902	138	45.098	306	2.941	0.086
F1	101	33.007	205	66.993	306	35.346**	0.000
F3	27	8.824	279	91.176	306	207.529**	0.000
F2	25	8.170	281	91.830	306	214.170**	0.000

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

Table 5.16 shows the frequency distribution and percentage of study sample answers about the statement, and the Chi-Square test of independence. These results suggest that all of the user groups together might add up to a combined urgent need to implement. On the other hand, taken individually, the user groups (apart from perhaps users from the public sector) are not thought to perceive that implementation is urgent. Only one-third (101 or 33%) believe that users think that implementation in the public sector is urgent. The percentages are much lower for perceptions about users in the private sector (9%) and foreign investors (8%). This may suggest that users are more concerned with poor quality reporting and low accountability in the public sector as compared to in the private sector. Therefore, many see adoption of IFRS in the public sector as the key way to improve accounting, accountability, and corporate governance. By contrast, most people believe that the accounting quality of the private sector is satisfactory and/or that users know how to convert private sector accounts to any desired format.

Q4.2 What are the international standards for the preparation of financial reports and appropriate in the Libyan reality, what types of amendments are supposed to be made?

Table 5.17 - Necessary modifications for the IFRS

Type of Modifications	Yes		NO		Total	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%			
M4	120	39.216	186	60.784	306	14.235**	0.000
M5	108	35.294	198	64.706	306	26.471**	0.000
M1	88	28.758	218	71.242	306	55.229**	0.000
M2	64	20.915	242	79.085	306	103.542**	0.000
M3	54	17.647	252	82.353	306	128.118**	0.000

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

Table 5.17 shows the frequency distribution and the percentage of the study sample answers on the axis in descending order, and the Chi-Square test of independence. The lowest number of respondents chose ‘stability of the accounting system in the Libyan environment’ (54 or 18%) and ‘internal control systems’ (64 or 21%) as being factors needing modification. This suggests that respondents are generally happy with the standard of internal control in Libya (although 21% are not). The other option is confusing, as ‘stability of the accounting system in the Libyan environment’ appears to contain two separate concepts, although perhaps inter-related. Confusion associated with this alternative might explain the low number of Yes respondents. Although logically ‘All of the above’ should have the least number of Yes responses, it has the second highest number (35%). The highest number of Yes responses (120 or 39%) relates to ‘the accounting system itself’. Moreover, 61% of respondents still thought that ‘accounting systems’ do not need to be modified before IFRS is implemented. Nevertheless, this still appears to be the weakest link.

Q4.3 How will the introduction of the IFRS be perceived by the main actors involved in accounting matters in Libya?

Table 5.18 - Perceptions of IFRS adoption

#	Valid	Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
1	Optimistically	267	87.2549	169.882**	0.000
2	Pessimistically	39	12.7451		
Total		306	100		

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

There was a mixture of responses to this question. The majority (267 or 87%) believes that the introduction of IFRS will be perceived optimistically by the main actors involved in accounting matters in Libya. By contrast, only 39 people (13%) believe that IFRS introduction will be perceived pessimistically. This result means that there is unequivocally an overall optimistic perception about the general level of optimism felt towards IFRS. In other words, the respondents are optimistic about people being optimistic. If these perceptions are accurate, this is good news for IFRS supporters both overseas and in the country. It does suggest that attitudes are generally positive within the accounting profession. This is important because pessimistic attitudes would slow adoption and lower the quality of IFRS reporting after adoption. Perceived problems relate to the level of education, language-barriers, and political factors. All of these, and especially political factors, are beyond the direct control of the accounting profession. Institutional theory is supported, in these findings, as people are optimistic about the ability of isomorphic forces to positively influence others, presumably after one has already been convinced by the IFRS' merits oneself.

What are the factors to be taken into consideration while making the required adjustments?

Q5.1 What are the potential implications of the future application of IFRSs?

Table 5.19 – Implications of future adoption

Factors	Yes		NO		Total	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%			
F1	243	79.412	63	20.588	306	105.882**	0.000
F3	154	50.327	152	49.673	306	0.013	0.909
F2	17	5.556	289	94.444	306	241.778**	0.000

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

Table 5.19 shows the frequency distribution and the percentage of the study sample answers about the axis in descending order, and the Chi-Square test of independence.

The results here are interesting and conclusive. The clear majority (243 or 79%) perceives that IFRS will improve the quality of financial reporting, while only 63 people (21%) disagree. This conclusion is unambiguous - the accounting profession in Libya believes that IFRS-based accounting standards are of higher quality than the accounting policies used at present. This is a clear vote of support for the IASB. However, only a bare majority (154 Yes compared to 152 No) thinks that Libyan financial reporting will be more acceptable to international financial markets after IFRS adoption. Of course, a difference of 2 people out of 306 people is *not* a statistically significant difference. It is hard to reconcile these two findings - it may mean that accountants focus on the quality issue and can give a clear verdict here, whereas they may be less well-informed about overseas opinions and unwilling to speculate. Only 17 people (6%) think that IFRS will not add value. The problem here is the double negative which a No answer creates (289 people or 94%). Despite this problem, most respondents clearly believe that IFRS will either add value or keep value at the same level. In

hindsight, I should have avoided writing questions where the predicted most common response would be a double negative.

Q5.2 to Q5.4 Factors to consider while making the required adjustments

Table 5.20 – Factors to consider

Question	Yes		NO		Total	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%			
Q5.4	301	98.366	5	1.634	306	286.327**	0.000
Q5.3	293	95.752	13	4.248	306	256.209**	0.000
Q5.2	258	84.314	48	15.686	306	144.118**	0.000

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

Table 5.20 shows the frequency distribution and the percentage of the study sample answers about the axis in descending order, and the Chi-Square test of independence.

The respondents believe that each one of the three factors listed individually and separately in Q5.2 to Q5.4 - ‘government regulations’, ‘international guidelines’, and ‘training courses’ - will have a positive impact on IFRS implementation. The percentage of Yes responses ranges from 84% (government regulations) to 98% (training courses). Again, the attitude demonstrated here seems to be unquestionably positive - there is the belief that every little bit of support and help given to Libyan accountants will aid implementation. However, respondents are more cynical, relatively speaking, about the benefits of Libyan government regulations - 16% thought they would not be helpful. As the country is in serious political turmoil and two rival groups both claim to have governmental authority, the relative cynicism towards government regulations is completely understandable. Obviously politicians need to get their own political houses in order first before trying to put their regulatory marks upon the accounting sphere. By contrast, guidance from outside of the country (‘international guidelines’) was widely perceived to be very useful indeed, with 301 people (98%) choosing the Yes response for this option. The belief that more training courses are always preferred to fewer is also nearly universally held (96%). The IASB would have good reasons to be happy

with these results, but, along with the business communities of all nations, it should be deeply concerned about the political problems which are now the major barrier to implementation. Institutional theory is supported as survey respondents are far keener on receiving guidance from international sources and training courses, rather than from government regulations. The first two factors are associated with the highly-regarded, high-status IASB and the associated global accounting environment. Even local training courses would be taught by people connected with the global accounting elite, and trained in dominant international practices, and so their popularity shows the success of isomorphism in driving change.

5.5 Variation of results based on demographic variables

Presentation and discussion of the results:

Are there statistically significant differences in survey question responses caused by variations in demographic variables?

To test whether there is a role for the sample characteristics represented (age, gender, academic degree, experience) in the level of application of the IFRS in Libya. One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used on the mean of the sample vocabulary answers on all variables (as a dependent variable), with one of the demographic characteristics of the study sample used as an independent variable, the results were as follows:

Null hypotheses: There is no statistically significant role for the characteristics of the sample in the level of application of the IFRSs in Libya.

Alternative hypothesis: There is a statistically significant role for the characteristics of the sample in the level of application of the IFRSs in Libya.

1. Gender:

Table 5.21 - Arithmetic mean and T-test values for answers attributed to gender

Q	VARIABLES	MALE		FEMALE		MEAN DIFFERENCE	T-TEST	SIG
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation			
Libyan professional awareness of the IFRS								
1	Q2.1	1.600	0.491	1.529	0.504	0.071	0.933	0.351
2	Q2.5	1.980	0.139	1.980	0.140	0.000	0.000	1.000
The potential advantages of and difficulties with IFRS implementation in Libya								
3	Q3.1	1.961	0.194	1.941	0.238	0.020	0.632	0.528
The most difficult factors which might affect IFRS implementation in Libya?								
4	Q3.2.3	0.616	0.487	0.627	0.488	-0.012	-0.157	0.875
5	Q3.2.12	0.584	0.494	0.627	0.488	-0.043	-0.571	0.569
6	Q3.3	1.973	0.164	1.980	0.140	-0.008	-0.319	0.750
7	Q3.4	1.094	0.293	1.176	0.385	-0.082	-1.734	0.084
The need to apply the IFRS and the perceptions of Libyan professionals regarding their introduction into the Libyan accounting profession								
8	Q4.1	1.580	0.494	1.647	0.483	-0.067	-0.882	0.378
The IFRS to be appropriate in the Libyan context what types of modifications are required?								
9	Q4.2.4	0.329	0.471	0.471	0.504	-0.141	-1.931	0.054
10	Q4.3	1.122	0.327	1.157	0.367	-0.035	-0.688	0.492
Factors which should be considered for the modifications required								
the potential implications of the implementation of the IFRS for the future								

11	Q5.1.1	0.804	0.398	0.745	0.440	0.059	-0.714	0.476
12	Q5.1.3	0.494	0.501	0.549	0.503	-0.055	-1.690	0.092
13	Q5.2	1.827	0.379	1.922	0.272	-0.094	-2.100*	0.038
14	Q5.3	1.953	0.212	1.980	0.140	-0.027	-1.159	0.249
15	Q5.4	1.980	0.139	2.000	0.000	-0.020	-2.254*	0.025

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

The only statistically significant difference between male and female respondents was revealed in relation to Q5.2 and Q5.4 (Table 5.25). A higher percentage of women than men are optimistic about the ability of ‘government regulations’ (Q5.2) and ‘training courses’ (Q5.4), respectively, to assist in the implementation of IFRS in Libya. This is an important result. It shows that, on average, women are more positive and optimistic about IFRS implementation than men. However, the results can be interpreted in various ways. Women seem to be more careful and cautious - they are more likely to want to wait for outside assistance and are more willing to learn. They are nervous about proceeding without extra help. Possibly they fear making mistakes and perhaps being punished within their organization. By contrast, men seem more self-confident in their own abilities and less dependent on outside support. Strangely, however, there was no significant difference in relation to Q5.3 - both groups think similarly about the ability of ‘international guidelines’ to assist in implementation. Men appear as keen as women to receive outside support from outside of the country, i.e. international guidelines. However, women value local support from government or from local trainers more highly than men do. Men may be more cynical about the local extremely unstable political situation and the competence of local training course ‘experts’. Thus these findings are not unexpected.

I now discuss results on gender which border on statistical significance but which do not quite reach it. Women perceive more frequently than men that the ‘stability of the accounting system in the Libyan environment’ (Q4.2.4) is a necessary modification before IFRS can be appropriate for the Libyan environment (variable significant at the 10% level). This response can reflect more caution on the part of women, who think that more changes and support are

needed in the areas of the accounting system, the Libyan environment, and the interaction between these two factors.

At the 10% significance level, I note that the response to Q5.1.3 also fits into this category. Women more often than men think that the adoption of IFRS will assist in making Libyan financial reporting more acceptable to international markets. This reflects perhaps a more global outlook among women and more optimism among women but also less satisfaction with the status quo, where Libyan companies follow a mix of American and British standards. Women perhaps are more concerned than men in making Libyan businesses better regarded overseas and doing all things possible to remove remaining impediments to overseas recognition and success. There are no other statistically significant or nearly-significant results to discuss for the gender variable.

The significant gender results are broadly consistent with institutional theory. Women seem to be more eager to seek guidance from government and training courses than men. This suggests that they are more impressed by, and possibly coerced by, institutional global pressures heading towards conformity and notions of development and progress, which the IFRS embody. Isomorphic pressures seem to influence women more than men in this context. If the IFRS is seen as ‘progress’, then women seemed to be more impressed by this notion. Historically, women also want to be perceived as obedient, teachable, adaptable, and responsible.

2. Age :

Table 5.22-A - Arithmetic mean and F-test value for answers between search variables attributed to age

Variables		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Q2.1	Between Groups	0.560	4	0.140	0.573	0.683
	Within Groups	73.558	301	0.244		
	Total	74.118	305			

Q2.5	Between Groups	0.016	4	0.004	0.206	0.935
	Within Groups	5.866	301	0.019		
	Total	5.882	305			
Q3.1	Between Groups	0.393	4	0.098	2.451*	0.046
	Within Groups	12.055	301	0.040		
	Total	12.448	305			
Q3.2.3	Between Groups	1.374	4	0.343	1.458	0.215
	Within Groups	70.891	301	0.236		
	Total	72.265	305			
Q3.2.12	Between Groups	0.200	4	0.050	0.204	0.936
	Within Groups	73.738	301	0.245		
	Total	73.938	305			
Q3.3	Between Groups	0.125	4	0.031	1.230	0.298
	Within Groups	7.666	301	0.025		
	Total	7.791	305			
Q3.4	Between Groups	0.329	4	0.082	0.850	0.495
	Within Groups	29.112	301	0.097		
	Total	29.441	305			
Q4.1	Between Groups	9.876	4	2.469	11.601**	0.000
	Within Groups	64.062	301	0.213		
	Total	73.938	305			
Q4.2.4	Between Groups	0.618	4	0.155	0.672	0.612
	Within Groups	69.264	301	0.230		
	Total	69.882	305			

Q4.3	Between Groups	1.072	4	0.268	2.447*	0.046
	Within Groups	32.958	301	0.109		
	Total	34.029	305			
Q5.1.1	Between Groups	0.585	4	0.146	0.891	0.470
	Within Groups	49.444	301	0.164		
	Total	50.029	305			
Q5.1.3	Between Groups	1.788	4	0.447	1.800	0.129
	Within Groups	74.709	301	0.248		
	Total	76.497	305			
Q5.2	Between Groups	0.083	4	0.021	0.154	0.961
	Within Groups	40.388	301	0.134		
	Total	40.471	305			
Q5.3	Between Groups	0.461	4	0.115	2.891*	0.023
	Within Groups	11.987	301	0.040		
	Total	12.448	305			
Q5.4	Between Groups	0.020	4	0.005	0.314	0.868
	Within Groups	4.898	301	0.016		
	Total	4.918	305			

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

Table 5.22-B

AGE	Q3.1	Q4.1	Q4.3	Q5.3
Under 30	1.99	1.69	1.20	1.96
30-40	1.98	1.76	1.12	1.97
41-50	1.91	1.40	1.11	1.95
51-60	1.96	1.26	1.00	1.96
Over 60	1.97	1.50	1.50	1.50
Total	1.96	1.59	1.13	1.96

Table ANOVA (5.22-C)

Comparisons		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Q3.1 * AGE	Between Groups	.393	4	.098	2.451	.046
	Within Groups	12.055	301	.040		
	Total	12.448	305			
Q4.1 * AGE	Between Groups	9.876	4	2.469	11.601	.000
	Within Groups	64.062	301	.213		
	Total	73.938	305			
Q4.3 * AGE	Between Groups	1.072	4	.268	2.447	.046
	Within Groups	32.958	301	.109		
	Total	34.029	305			
Q5.3 * AGE	Between Groups	.461	4	.115	2.891	.023
	Within Groups	11.987	301	.040		
	Total	12.448	305			

Based on the results shown in Tables 5.22-A, B & C, in terms of variation of the results according to age-bracket, I find, four significant associations at the 5% level (using the F-test). I will ignore the results for the over-60s, as only 2 individuals feature in this category. To recap the earlier results, note that the number of people in each age-bracket was as follows: Under 30: 70, 30-40: 116, 41-50: 95, 51-60: 23, and over 60: 2. I now discern whether there are any clear upwards or downwards trends, indicating that opinion varies by age, and focus on these results.

The first significant finding, for Q3.1, is only just significant, with an F-statistic of 2.451 (sig = 0.046). For this there is a marginal downward trend, with mean responses as follows: Under 30: 1.99, 30 -40: 1.98, 41-50: 1.91, and 51-60: 1.96. This result suggests that younger people are more positive that IFRS will have potential advantages for financial reporting in Libya. This result is expected, as older accountants may be more socially conservative and fearful of change. They are set in their ways and may worry that learning a new set of

accounting standards will be a burdensome task. Younger people will be more in tune with global developments and less committed to existing ways of doing things. In terms of institutional theory, isomorphic pressures seem to have been slightly more effective in targeting and converting the young to a pro-IASB stance than the old.

Out of the four significant results, by far the most significant is for Q4.1 (F-test statistic = 11.601, sig = 0.000). This would be the second most significant finding overall, so far. As with Q3.1 (but the effect here is far stronger) younger accountants are more likely to believe that there is a necessity felt by users to adopt the IFRS, as compared to older accountants. Mean responses by age-brackets are: Under 30: 1.69, 30-40: 1.76, 41-50: 1.40, and 51-60: 1.26. Clearly there is a significant downward trend here, with older people being more likely to provide a No response. However, it is interesting that Under 30s have 1.69 mean and 30-40s have a 1.76 mean. This could be because Under 30s are less likely to have sustained important interaction with clients compared to 30-40s who are more likely to be at or near the peak of their career trajectory. Those 31-40-year-olds may be responding to actual declared preferences of users for IFRS, as stated by senior management of client companies. By contrast, the Under-30s may be voicing a subjective opinion or a personal opinion based on interactions with more junior client company staff. Older accountants also may have been partially sidelined and less in tune with demands for IFRS standards, or they are blinded by their pre-conceptions that demands by users for IFRS are minimal.

For Q4.3, the F-statistic was 2.447 and the significance was 0.046. The level of significance for this result is very close to that attained by Q3. There is also a clear downward trend here, with mean responses being: Under 30s: 1.20, 30-40: 1.12, 41-50: 1.11, and 51-60: 1.00. This result shows that older accountants are more likely than younger accountants to perceive that the main accounting actors will view IFRS introduction pessimistically. In fact, in the 51-60 category, the number of optimistic responses is equal to the number of pessimistic responses. Younger people appear to be much more willing to adopt and embrace new systems. This result confirms prior expectations. Older accountants may fear being sidelined by the rise of IFRS, as their skill-set and experience will become out of date. They may fear that learning the IFRS at their age will impose an unreasonable burden on their shoulders. In fact, some might contemplate early retirement (Probert 2020) rather than risk seeing their existing skill-set dramatically devalued.

In some ways, we see here younger accountants perhaps projecting their own optimism on to users as a whole, while older accountants project their pessimism on to the entire population of users. This is a more masculine response (Connell 1995) than admitting that pessimism is purely due to a personal fear of one becoming out of date in one's knowledge. Social hierarchies in the workplace are also under threat – the rise of IFRS would see younger accountants rise in status and older accountants decline in status. This decline in status could prove to be extremely upsetting for many people, particularly men.

The fourth and last significant result for the interaction of Yes responses with age was for Q5.3. The F-statistic was 2.891 and the significance level was 0.023. The question was whether providing 'international guidelines' would contribute positively to IFRS implementation. The numbers of mean responses were: Under30s: 1.96, 30-40: 1.97, 41-50:1.95, 51-60:1.96. The mean was 1.50 for over-60s but this result should not be relied upon as only 2 people were in the over-60s category.

Consistently with expectations, this result suggests that younger users are marginally more optimistic about the potential of 'international guidelines' to assist in IFRS implementation. Interestingly, the Q5.4 significance result, regarding whether training courses might help adoption, was insignificant. Training courses are a relatively hierarchical and traditional teaching method, whilst also allowing for 'face-saving', as everyone sits in the audience together as equals and anonymous. Therefore, older accountants may be well-disposed towards such courses even if IFRS is the subject-matter. Training courses are the great leveller and everyone maintains his/her 'face' and self-respect in the classroom or seminar room. Ignorance can be hidden from public view. By contrast, older accountants may be suspicious towards guidance from overseas, perceiving it to be unwarranted and patronizing - it puts their authority and place in the hierarchy under the microscope. It appears that isomorphic pressures to conform to a globally accepted accounting regime have less persuasive power with older accountants.

3 Position:

Table 5.23-A - Arithmetic mean and F-test value for answers between search variables attributed to Position

Variables		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Q2.1	Between Groups	2.759	4	0.690	2.910*	0.022
	Within Groups	71.358	301	0.237		
	Total	74.118	305			
Q2.5	Between Groups	0.066	4	0.017	0.857	0.490
	Within Groups	5.816	301	0.019		
	Total	5.882	305			
Q3.1	Between Groups	0.454	4	0.113	2.848*	0.024
	Within Groups	11.994	301	0.040		
	Total	12.448	305			
Q3.2.3	Between Groups	1.411	4	0.353	1.498	0.203
	Within Groups	70.854	301	0.235		
	Total	72.265	305			
Q3.2.12	Between Groups	0.451	4	0.113	0.462	0.764
	Within Groups	73.487	301	0.244		
	Total	73.938	305			
Q3.3	Between Groups	0.098	4	0.024	0.958	0.431
	Within Groups	7.693	301	0.026		
	Total	7.791	305			
Q3.4	Between Groups	0.358	4	0.089	0.926	0.449

	Within Groups	29.083	301	0.097		
	Total	29.441	305			
Q4.1	Between Groups	13.154	4	3.288	16.284**	0.000
	Within Groups	60.784	301	0.202		
	Total	73.938	305			
Q4.2.4	Between Groups	0.486	4	0.121	0.527	0.716
	Within Groups	69.397	301	0.231		
	Total	69.882	305			
Q4.3	Between Groups	0.298	4	0.074	0.664	0.618
	Within Groups	33.732	301	0.112		
	Total	34.029	305			
Q5.1.1	Between Groups	0.397	4	0.099	0.601	0.662
	Within Groups	49.633	301	0.165		
	Total	50.029	305			
Q5.1.3	Between Groups	0.501	4	0.125	0.496	0.739
	Within Groups	75.996	301	0.252		
	Total	76.497	305			
Q5.2	Between Groups	0.455	4	0.114	0.855	0.491
	Within Groups	40.016	301	0.133		
	Total	40.471	305			
Q5.3	Between Groups	0.067	4	0.017	0.409	0.802
	Within Groups	12.380	301	0.041		
	Total	12.448	305			
Q5.4	Between Groups	0.036	4	0.009	0.550	0.699

	Within Groups	4.883	301	0.016		
	Total	4.918	305			

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

Table 5.23-B

Position	Q2.1	Q3.1	Q4.1
Owner/partner	1.50	2.00	2.00
Senior accountant	1.52	2.00	1.55
Staff accountant	1.50	1.97	1.79
Auditor	1.69	1.91	1.34
Academic accountant	1.71	2.00	1.83
Total	1.59	1.96	1.59

ANOVA Table 5.23-C

Comparisons		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Q2.1 * Position	Between Groups	2.759	4	.690	2.910	.022
	Within Groups	71.358	301	.237		
	Total	74.118	305			
Q3.1 * Position	Between Groups	.454	4	.113	2.848	.024
	Within Groups	11.994	301	.040		
	Total	12.448	305			
Q4.1 * Position	Between Groups	13.154	4	3.288	16.284	.000
	Within Groups	60.784	301	.202		
	Total	73.938	305			

Through Tables 5.23-A, B & C, I note that, in terms of the significant correlations between Yes responses and position, there were only three statistically significant questions this time. The three significant questions were Q2.1, Q3.1 and Q4.1 whereas, for age, the significant questions were Q3.1, Q4.1, Q4.3, and Q5.3. As we can see, two of the three significant questions for position are also significant with respect to age. This suggests that there may be some positive correlation between age and position. However, as positions cannot be unambiguously ranked from highest to lowest (e.g. where would 'academic' rank within any hierarchy?), I did not compute the correlation coefficient between age and position. To recap, the numbers in each position category were as follows: Owner Manager: 2, Senior accountant: 60, Staff accountant: 112, Auditor: 108, and Academic accountant: 24. The number of owner/managers is too small for reliable inferences to be drawn and hence they do not feature in this discussion.

Question 2.1 asks: 'Do you feel you have appropriate knowledge of IFRS?' It is perhaps surprising that the mean responses for this variable were not significantly correlated with age. For Q2.1, F-statistic for correlation with position was 2.910 and significance level was 0.022. The means for each position were: Senior accountant: 1.52, Staff accountant: 1.50, Auditor: 1.69, and Academic: 1.71. The results here are interesting and revealing, but not at all surprising. Academics have the highest knowledge (and perhaps the highest self-confidence about their own knowledge). Also, auditors have recent experience of a much wider range of companies and sectors than do staff accountants, and hence it is expected that their IFRS knowledge will be better. A minor problem with this question is that it cannot separate out one's true knowledge of IFRS from one's self-confidence about one's knowledge of IFRS. However, within the survey format, it is hard to see how such a problem could be solved.

Question 3.1 asks: 'Do you agree that implementation of IFRS will have advantages for financial reporting in Libya?' The F-statistic here was 2.848 (which is very close to the 2.910 recorded for Q2.1) and the significance level was 0.024. Economically, we could regard the results for Q2.1 and Q3.1 as being of equal significance. The mean responses for each position were as follows: Senior accountants: 2.00, Staff accountants: 1.97, Auditor: 1.91, and Academic: 2.00. Unlike the situation with age, we should not look for clear downward or upward trends, as these positions (i.e. jobs), whilst clearly different, are not ranked in order of seniority, apart from senior accountant/staff accountant.

Senior accountants and academics, being the most global in outlook, are the most optimistic for this question. I observe here that auditors are slightly more sceptical. Interestingly, auditors with the most knowledge of IFRS (Q2.1) are more sceptical, whereas senior accountants, with relatively less knowledge, are more optimistic. I might be witnessing some ‘virtue-signalling’ behaviour here on the part of senior accountants.

Possibly, auditors, having the most intense daily, practical experience with all accounting regimes, have seen some of the practical problems associated with IFRS. They may have audited some IFRS-based accounting statements either in Libya or overseas. Academics may feel duty bound ethically to support a global accounting system, so that they are not seen as backward or provincial by not having IFRS accepted in Libya. They could research IFRS adoption locally and this may have future career pay-offs in terms of journal article publications. They would also find it easier then to collaborate and co-author with foreign academics on IFRS-issues. Their better language skills may also mean that language barriers are less of a problem for academics.

The most significant result for position, by some significant margin, is Q4.1. Question 4.1 asks ‘Do you think there is a necessity felt by the users of accounting information in Libya to adopt the IFRS?’ The mean responses for each position are: Senior accountant: 1.55, Staff accountant: 1.79, Auditor: 1.34, and Academic: 1.83. Again, academics generally perceive that users demand IFRS. Staff accountants are reasonably positive about this perception, as compared to senior accountants and auditors. The result for auditors is somewhat strange. We may see some cynicism creeping in: they feel knowledgeable about IFRS, but they do not perceive that users demand it. Staff accountants, although relatively isolated in their jobs as compared to auditors, still perceive that there is high demand from users for IFRS. How do they know this? Are they saying what they believe the researcher wants them to say? Possibly they worked as auditors in the past and are reflecting upon a past time when there was more user demand for IFRS. We recall that along some dimensions, there were significant variations in survey responses between 2015 and 2018. There was an extremely high T-statistic for Q4.1 along this dimension ($t = 29.679$ sig = 0.000) with there being a dramatic decline in the percentage of people perceiving that users demand IFRS adoption in Libya between these two dates. We have argued that this reflects a greater concern about ongoing political instability in 2018 compared to 2015. Staff accountants in 2018 may have been auditors in 2015 and they are expressing an opinion in 2018 which actually reflects their

experiences of three years earlier. Going from auditor to staff accountant is an extremely common career path in nearly every country.

One clear and important conclusion here is the obvious role played by academics in supporting isomorphic forces to conform and modernize, coming from overseas hegemonic sources. They then begin to embody these same forces in their own words and actions, so that they become effective evangelists in spreading the message of IFRS.

4 Professional Experience :

Table 5.24-A - Arithmetic mean and F-test value for answers between search variables attributed to professional experience

Variables		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Q2.1	Between Groups	2.174	5	0.435	1.813	0.110
	Within Groups	71.943	300	0.240		
	Total	74.118	305			
Q2.5	Between Groups	0.033	5	0.007	0.334	0.892
	Within Groups	5.850	300	0.019		
	Total	5.882	305			
Q3.1	Between Groups	0.229	5	0.046	1.124	0.347
	Within Groups	12.219	300	0.041		
	Total	12.448	305			
Q3.2.3	Between Groups	0.564	5	0.113	0.472	0.797
	Within Groups	71.700	300	0.239		
	Total	72.265	305			
Q3.2.12	Between Groups	1.772	5	0.354	1.473	0.198
	Within Groups	72.166	300	0.241		

	Total	73.938	305			
Q3.3	Between Groups	0.120	5	0.024	0.942	0.454
	Within Groups	7.670	300	0.026		
	Total	7.791	305			
Q3.4	Between Groups	0.377	5	0.075	0.778	0.566
	Within Groups	29.064	300	0.097		
	Total	29.441	305			
Q4.1	Between Groups	8.404	5	1.681	7.694**	0.000
	Within Groups	65.534	300	0.218		
	Total	73.938	305			
Q4.2.4	Between Groups	0.769	5	0.154	0.668	0.648
	Within Groups	69.113	300	0.230		
	Total	69.882	305			
Q4.3	Between Groups	1.791	5	0.358	3.332**	0.006
	Within Groups	32.239	300	0.107		
	Total	34.029	305			
Q5.1.1	Between Groups	0.929	5	0.186	1.135	0.342
	Within Groups	49.100	300	0.164		
	Total	50.029	305			
Q5.1.3	Between Groups	3.792	5	0.758	3.130**	0.009
	Within Groups	72.704	300	0.242		
	Total	76.497	305			
Q5.2	Between Groups	0.759	5	0.152	1.147	0.335
	Within Groups	39.711	300	0.132		

	Total	40.471	305			
Q5.3	Between Groups	0.094	5	0.019	0.455	0.809
	Within Groups	12.354	300	0.041		
	Total	12.448	305			
Q5.4	Between Groups	0.043	5	0.009	0.533	0.751
	Within Groups	4.875	300	0.016		
	Total	4.918	305			

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

Table 5.24-B

Experience	Q4.1	Q4.3	Q5.1.3
1-2 years	1.68	1.32	.38
2-3 years	1.82	1.14	.36
3-6 years	1.67	1.13	.54
6-9 years	1.82	1.03	.32
9-12 years	1.67	1.07	.70
Over 12 years	1.39	1.12	.53
Total	1.59	1.13	.50

ANOVA Table 5.24-C

Comparisons		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Q4.1 * Experience	Between Groups	8.404	5	1.681	7.694	.000
	Within Groups	65.534	300	.218		
	Total	73.938	305			
Q4.3 * Experience	Between Groups	1.791	5	.358	3.332	.006
	Within Groups	32.239	300	.107		
	Total	34.029	305			
Q5.1.3 * Experience	Between Groups	3.792	5	.758	3.130	.009
	Within Groups	72.704	300	.242		
	Total	76.497	305			

Through scrutinising Table 5.24-A, B & C, I note that, with respect to years of experience, there are three highly significant results at better than the 1% level. There are no borderline significant results. This should make the analysis easier. Q4.1 asks whether ‘you think that there is necessity felt by the users of accounting information to adopt IFRS?’ the F-statistic here is 7.694 (sig = 0.000). The mean Yes responses are as follows: 1-2 years experience: 1.68, 2-3 years experience: 1.82, 3-6 years experience: 1.67, 6-9 years experience: 1.82, 9-12 years experience: 1.67, and over 12 years experience; 1.39. The category with the highest number of respondents is over 12 years (119 persons). The category with the least number of respondents is 2-3 years (22 persons). The trend here is basically downwards with more experienced individuals (who will be older on average) perceiving that users have less necessity for IFRS adoption. (Readers will recall from the discussion above that age is significantly positively correlated with years of experience.) Older people with more experience may have the *least* confidence in their own ability to master IFRS and may be projecting this on to users (consciously or unconsciously).

There is a bi-model distribution here with the highest percentage of Yes responses shared by the 2-3 years' and the 6-9 years' experience years category. This is a harder result to interpret. Q4.1 responses were also significantly impacted by age and position. Academic accountants could be of any age but staff accountants are often in the 2-3 and 6-9 years' experience brackets. Staff accountants had a high percentage of Yes responses (mean = 1.79). The 30-40s have the highest percentage of Yes responses (mean = 1.76), whilst the 51-60s have the lowest (mean= 1.26). The older people are clearly also those with the most years of experience. So there is not much new information here which the age results do not already tell us. The 30-40s probably matches up largely with the 6-9 years' experience category. The 2-3 years' experience category is probably partially submerged within the broad Under-30s category. This 'submerged' result can be seen clearly when we note that there were 70 Under-30s but only 22 (total) with 2-3 years' experience. Therefore, the results for the 2-3 years' experience may provide us with only a small piece of extra information.

There is a significant result for Q4.3, which asks whether the main actors in Libya will perceive IFRS optimistically or pessimistically. The F-statistic is 3.332 (sig = 0.006). The mean responses are : 1-2 years: 1.32, 2-3 years: 1.14, 3-6 years: 1.13, 6-9 years: 1.03, 9-12 years: 1.07, and Over 12 years: 1.12. There is a clear downward trend here with a small movement back upwards by the time we get to 9-12 years' experience. On average, the least experienced, followed by the most experienced, think that actors will respond optimistically. Those in the middle categories think actors will respond pessimistically.

We saw above that older respondents generally think that actors will view IFRS adoption optimistically. With age significantly positively correlated with years of experience, my finding of significance here is consistent with my finding for the age variable. However, the upward movement in the curve at Over 12 years' experience (compared to 9-12 years) is hard to explain. One possible argument is that fear about IFRS reduces for the very experienced respondents, either due to their strong knowledge of IFRS and/or the fact that their job is more likely a strategic/supervisory role with little actual calculation work involved. They would trust the work of their subordinates. A second, not unrelated, reason is virtue-signalling, where people perceive that the response best suited to their own personal interests is the 'optimistic' response. Yet it is hard to reconcile the upward swing here at Over 12 years with the result for the age variable where the curve is consistently downward-sloping.

The third and final significant result is for Q5.1.3. The question concerns whether you believe a potential implication of IFRS adoption is acceptability in international financial markets. The F-statistic is 3.130 (sig = 0.009). The mean responses are: 1-2 years: 0.38, 2-3 years: 0.36, 3-6 years: 0.54, 6-9 years: 0.32, 9-12 years: 0.70, and Over 12 years: 0.53.

This is a basically, but not consistently, a downward slope. Those with less experience generally perceive that IFRS adoption will aid capital markets. The people with less experience have a more global outlook and are not confining their attention only to the domestic situation. Largely working against the overall downward trend are the two bi-modal peaks at 3-6 years' and 9-12 years' experience. People in those categories are more aware of how Libyan accounting will be perceived in international markets. Those people may have more significant networks and associations with international financial market users. Possibly the association comes from recent auditing work, for those with 3-6 years' experience, and raising capital for those with 9-12 years. We cannot gain any extra insights from the results for age and position for this variable, as neither of these is significant. In addition, academic accountants could be of any age and years' of experience which will work to muddy the results. Results overall suggest that results are clearer and easier to interpret when academics are placed in their own separate category, as in the results based on position.

5 Place of Education:

Table 5.25-A - Arithmetic mean and F-test value for answers between search variables attributed to place of education

Variables		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Q2.1	Between Groups	4.084	5	0.817	3.499**	0.004
	Within Groups	70.034	300	0.233		
	Total	74.118	305			
Q2.5	Between Groups	0.017	5	0.003	0.171	0.973
	Within Groups	5.866	300	0.020		
	Total	5.882	305			

Q3.1	Between Groups	0.235	5	0.047	1.155	0.332
	Within Groups	12.213	300	0.041		
	Total	12.448	305			
Q3.2.3	Between Groups	1.000	5	0.200	0.842	0.521
	Within Groups	71.265	300	0.238		
	Total	72.265	305			
Q3.2.12	Between Groups	1.081	5	0.216	0.890	0.488
	Within Groups	72.857	300	0.243		
	Total	73.938	305			
Q3.3	Between Groups	0.224	5	0.045	1.774	0.118
	Within Groups	7.567	300	0.025		
	Total	7.791	305			
Q3.4	Between Groups	0.410	5	0.082	0.848	0.516
	Within Groups	29.031	300	0.097		
	Total	29.441	305			
Q4.1	Between Groups	1.921	5	0.384	1.601	0.160
	Within Groups	72.017	300	0.240		
	Total	73.938	305			
Q4.2.4	Between Groups	1.637	5	0.327	1.439	0.210
	Within Groups	68.246	300	0.227		
	Total	69.882	305			
Q4.3	Between Groups	0.339	5	0.068	0.604	0.697
	Within Groups	33.690	300	0.112		
	Total	34.029	305			

Q5.1.1	Between Groups	0.729	5	0.146	0.887	0.490
	Within Groups	49.301	300	0.164		
	Total	50.029	305			
Q5.1.3	Between Groups	1.365	5	0.273	1.090	0.366
	Within Groups	75.132	300	0.250		
	Total	76.497	305			
Q5.2	Between Groups	0.330	5	0.066	0.494	0.781
	Within Groups	40.140	300	0.134		
	Total	40.471	305			
Q5.3	Between Groups	0.038	5	0.008	0.182	0.969
	Within Groups	12.410	300	0.041		
	Total	12.448	305			
Q5.4	Between Groups	0.031	5	0.006	0.376	0.865
	Within Groups	4.888	300	0.016		
	Total	4.918	305			

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

Table 5.25-B

Place of Education:	Q2.1
Libya	1.55
UK	1.89
USA	2.00
Other Western countries	1.50
Other Arabic countries	1.88
Rest of the world	2.00
Total	1.59

ANOVA Table 5.25-C

Comparisons		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Q2.1 * Place	Between Groups	4.084	5	.817	3.499	.004
	Within Groups	70.034	300	.233		
	Total	74.118	305			

Through inspection of Table 5.25-A, B & C, I note that there is only one significant result for this variable, place of education. This could be due to a number of factors. One is obviously the relatively weak explanatory power of the category itself. A second is that as many as 268 out of 306 survey respondents (87.58%) were educated in Libya, which weakens the overall explanatory power for this variable. It appears that age, position, and years of experience, generally speaking, have stronger effects on response variations as compared to place of education. This is not unexpected, especially, in recent years where business-school education globally has become more standardized and less diverse. Essentially, everybody is

taught very similar things and the IFRS have global dominance and near universal acceptance within accounting education circles.

The only significant variable is for Q2.1. The F-statistic is 3.499 (sig = 0.004). The question asks whether you feel you have appropriate knowledge of IFRS. Results are totally consistent with expectations. Mean responses are: Libya: 1.55, UK: 1.89, USA: 2.00, Other Western countries: 1.50, Other Arabic countries: 1.88, and rest of the world: 2.00. Libya has 268 respondents and UK has 19 (6.21%). All other categories have fewer than 10 people each so less attention will be given to their results.

Basically, those people educated in Libya were less satisfied with their IFRS knowledge than those educated in either UK or USA. The Libyan lecturers may have less knowledge themselves and be less equipped to teach the material. Furthermore, having an overall British education may assist students in understanding the historical, economic, social, and political context behind the IFRS. British educators' own self-confidence may be picked up by their students who assume that such self-confidence is always justified because of the high-quality of the education. A number of discursive and symbolic factors can then work ideologically to support and justify the high level of self-confidence, which has been projected outwards. Those educated in 'Other Arabic countries' (8 people or 2.61%) may have received a good education, possibly from expatriate staff, in the Middle East region, where education is better funded than in Libya. It might also be lower self-confidence among Libyan graduates which causes them to rank their own competence as relatively low compared to UK/USA graduates. Practical measures of actual competence, rather than perceived competence, would be one avenue to address this problem in future research.

These results again support institutional theory. UK- and US-educated people are more likely to support IFRS than Libyan-educated. The isomorphic forces are more powerfully effective in winning the battle for hearts and minds when influences are closer, as when students get educated in USA or UK. There is coercive power in action, and embedded in structures, as textbooks and examinations teach and exalt IFRS standards and associated Western worldviews. The students also have invested time, effort, and money in their own education and hence have self-interested reasons in affirming its worth. They also have more confidence in their own knowledge, because the IFRS teaching and local culture and institutions reinforce each other, whereas this will not be true for Libyan-educated students.

6 Qualification:

Table 5.26-A - Arithmetic mean and F-test value for answers between search variables attributed to Qualifications

Variables		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Q2.1	Between Groups	7.413	5	1.483	6.668**	0.000
	Within Groups	66.704	300	0.222		
	Total	74.118	305			
Q2.5	Between Groups	0.023	5	0.005	0.240	0.945
	Within Groups	5.859	300	0.020		
	Total	5.882	305			
Q3.1	Between Groups	0.058	5	0.012	0.279	0.924
	Within Groups	12.390	300	0.041		
	Total	12.448	305			
Q3.2.3	Between Groups	1.050	5	0.210	0.885	0.492
	Within Groups	71.215	300	0.237		
	Total	72.265	305			
Q3.2.12	Between Groups	1.856	5	0.371	1.545	0.176
	Within Groups	72.081	300	0.240		
	Total	73.938	305			
Q3.3	Between Groups	0.104	5	0.021	0.810	0.544
	Within Groups	7.687	300	0.026		
	Total	7.791	305			
Q3.4	Between Groups	0.448	5	0.090	0.926	0.464

	Within Groups	28.993	300	0.097		
	Total	29.441	305			
Q4.1	Between Groups	1.634	5	0.327	1.356	0.241
	Within Groups	72.304	300	0.241		
	Total	73.938	305			
Q4.2.4	Between Groups	1.071	5	0.214	0.934	0.459
	Within Groups	68.811	300	0.229		
	Total	69.882	305			
Q4.3	Between Groups	0.348	5	0.070	0.621	0.684
	Within Groups	33.681	300	0.112		
	Total	34.029	305			
Q5.1.1	Between Groups	0.834	5	0.167	1.017	0.408
	Within Groups	49.196	300	0.164		
	Total	50.029	305			
Q5.1.3	Between Groups	0.813	5	0.163	0.644	0.666
	Within Groups	75.684	300	0.252		
	Total	76.497	305			
Q5.2	Between Groups	0.486	5	0.097	0.729	0.602
	Within Groups	39.985	300	0.133		
	Total	40.471	305			
Q5.3	Between Groups	0.115	5	0.023	0.558	0.732
	Within Groups	12.333	300	0.041		
	Total	12.448	305			
Q5.4	Between Groups	0.028	5	0.006	0.348	0.884

	Within Groups	4.890	300	0.016		
	Total	4.918	305			

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

Table 5.26-B

Qualification	Q2.1
High School	1.17
Diploma	1.40
Bachelor	1.56
MSc	1.84
PhD	1.75
Other	2.00
Total	1.59

ANOVA Table 5.26-C

Comparisons	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	7.413	5	1.483	6.668	.000
Q2.1 * Qualification Within Groups	66.704	300	.222		
Total	74.118	305			

From the results shown in Table 5.26-A, B & C, I note that there is also only one significant result for qualification, which suggests that this variable has relatively low explanatory power as compared to age, position, and years of experience. There were fewer than 10 people in both the 'high school' and 'Other' categories, so they will be disregarded. The numbers of people in the other categories are as follows: Diploma: 53, Bachelor: 173, MSc: 57, and PhD:

16. The only significant result, as with place of education, is Q2.1 which asks whether you perceive that you have appropriate knowledge of IFRS. The F-statistic is 6.668 (sig = 0.000), which, in both statistical and economic terms, is a highly significant result. Mean responses are as follow: high-school: 1.17, Diploma: 1.40, Bachelor: 1.56, MSc: 1.84, PhD: 1.75, other: 2.00. This is a clear and unambiguous result with the line being a definite upward curve. On average, the higher the person's education level, the more self-confident she/he is about her/his own perceived knowledge of the IFRS. However, as all other results are insignificant, education level does not appear to substantially impact on opinions about factors affecting IFRS adoption. The slight drop from 1.84 to 1.75 as we go from MSc to PhD may be due to the students' PhD topics often being, in part or fully, of a philosophical, sociological or theoretical nature. Often these topics do not require actual use of IFRS or any calculations based upon IFRS.

7 Accounting training and courses:

Table 5.27-A - Arithmetic mean and F-test value for answers between search variables attributed to Accounting training and courses

Variables		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Q2.1	Between Groups	3.571	5	0.714	3.038*	0.011
	Within Groups	70.546	300	0.235		
	Total	74.118	305			
Q2.5	Between Groups	0.043	5	0.009	0.441	0.820
	Within Groups	5.839	300	0.019		
	Total	5.882	305			
Q3.1	Between Groups	0.120	5	0.024	0.582	0.714
	Within Groups	12.328	300	0.041		
	Total	12.448	305			
Q3.2.3	Between Groups	2.730	5	0.546	2.356*	0.041

	Within Groups	69.535	300	0.232		
	Total	72.265	305			
Q3.2.12	Between Groups	1.566	5	0.313	1.298	0.265
	Within Groups	72.372	300	0.241		
	Total	73.938	305			
Q3.3	Between Groups	0.080	5	0.016	0.622	0.683
	Within Groups	7.711	300	0.026		
	Total	7.791	305			
Q3.4	Between Groups	0.258	5	0.052	0.530	0.754
	Within Groups	29.183	300	0.097		
	Total	29.441	305			
Q4.1	Between Groups	3.418	5	0.684	2.908*	0.014
	Within Groups	70.520	300	0.235		
	Total	73.938	305			
Q4.2.4	Between Groups	0.434	5	0.087	0.375	0.866
	Within Groups	69.448	300	0.231		
	Total	69.882	305			
Q4.3	Between Groups	0.741	5	0.148	1.335	0.249
	Within Groups	33.288	300	0.111		
	Total	34.029	305			
Q5.1.1	Between Groups	0.431	5	0.086	0.521	0.760
	Within Groups	49.599	300	0.165		
	Total	50.029	305			
Q5.1.3	Between Groups	1.102	5	0.220	0.877	0.497

	Within Groups	75.394	300	0.251		
	Total	76.497	305			
Q5.2	Between Groups	2.708	5	0.542	4.303**	0.001
	Within Groups	37.762	300	0.126		
	Total	40.471	305			
Q5.3	Between Groups	0.057	5	0.011	0.274	0.927
	Within Groups	12.391	300	0.041		
	Total	12.448	305			
Q5.4	Between Groups	0.050	5	0.010	0.620	0.684
	Within Groups	4.868	300	0.016		
	Total	4.918	305			

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

Table 5.27-B

Courses	Q2.1	Q3.2.3	Q4.1	Q5.2
Once a month	1.53	.53	1.40	2.00
Once every three months	1.89	.67	1.50	1.89
Once every six months	1.60	.52	1.40	1.88
Once a year	1.63	.56	1.58	1.89
Other	1.00	1.00	1.00	2.00
Not Applicant	1.47	.76	1.72	1.70
Total	1.59	.62	1.59	1.84

ANOVA Table 5.27-C

Comparisons		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Q2.1 * courses	Between Groups	3.571	5	.714	3.038	.011
	Within Groups	70.546	300	.235		
	Total	74.118	305			
Q3.2.3 * courses	Between Groups	2.730	5	.546	2.356	.041
	Within Groups	69.535	300	.232		
	Total	72.265	305			
Q4.1 * courses	Between Groups	3.418	5	.684	2.908	.014
	Within Groups	70.520	300	.235		
	Total	73.938	305			
Q5.2 * courses	Between Groups	2.708	5	.542	4.303	.001
	Within Groups	37.762	300	.126		
	Total	40.471	305			

The last variable to be discussed in this quantitative findings chapter is frequency of Training Courses. Somewhat surprisingly, as I had thought that this was probably the least important of all the demographic variables, there are four significant results here.

The most common option chosen was 'Once a year' (161 people or 52.61%) and the second most common option was 'Once every six months' (25 people or 8.17%). And 86 people selected 'Not Applicable' (28.10%). It is hard to interpret this option - did they complete any training courses or was the training on an irregular basis?

Q2.1 was again significant for this variable (F-statistic = 3.038, sig = 0.011). This question asked respondents whether they perceived that they had appropriate knowledge about IFRS.

Mean responses were: 'Once a month': 1.53, 'Once every three months': 1.89, 'Once every six months': 1.60, 'Once and a year': 1.63, and 'Not Applicable': 1.47. Clearly, the 'Once every three months' category had the highest percentage of people who perceived that they had appropriate knowledge. They have frequent training courses which must have improved both their expertise and their self-confidence. The result here may be muddled by other demographic factors, such as place of education and qualification level.

The lower percentage for 'Once a month' might suggest either that training which is too frequent is counter-productive and/or that this category includes relatively lower-qualified people with Libyan, rather than UK/USA, education. There is a significant result for this question in relation to 'position' with auditor and academic having the highest percentages of Yes responses (mean responses of 1.69 and 1.71 respectively). Auditors and academics are probably also in the category of people with relatively frequent training courses ('Once a month' or 'Once every three months'). Extensive and frequent training courses are more common within auditing firms than within corporations.

The second significant result is with respect to Q3.2.3 (F-statistic = 2.356, sig = 0.041). There is a significant association between Yes responses and training courses for the factor 'instability of government', i.e. Instability of government is perceived to be a factor which will make IFRS implementation difficult. The mean responses are as follows: 'Once a month': 0.53, 'Once every three months': 0.67, 'Once every six months': 0.52, 'Once a year': 0.56, and 'Not Applicable': 0.76. Those who put 'Not Applicable' are more concerned about instability of government. It is very difficult to interpret this response as we cannot be sure what 'Not Applicable' means in each individual case. There appears to be no obvious logic behind the fluctuating mean responses for the other categories. As there is only one person in the 'other' category, the 1.00 mean response for this category is meaningless. By definition, it would be equal to 0.000 or 1.000. Those with a training course every three months appear to be relatively more concerned about political instability. The only explanation the researcher can think of is that more training courses suggest or create a more modern, liberal-minded, and conscientious outlook. This could mean that such people have become disillusioned about the political instability in Libya.

The third significant variable in relation to training courses is Q4.1 (F-statistic = 2.908, sig = 0.014). This question asks whether the respondents perceive that users feel a necessity for the adoption of IFRS in Libya. The mean responses here were: 'Once a month': 1.40, 'Once every three months': 1.50, 'Once every six months': 1.40, 'Once a year': 1.58, and 'Not Applicable': 1.72. It is difficult to explain the result that fewer training courses reduce the perception that users feel that IFRS adoption is necessary. Some other variables may be muddying the waters here. Those people with 2-3 and 6-9 years' experience, staff accountants, academic accountants, Under-30s, and 30-40s are those who perceive generally that users feel that IFRS adoption is a necessity. Academic accountants may have ticked the 'Not Applicable' box or have training only once a year. Younger staff accountants with 2-3 years' experience may have training courses once every three months. Possibly, the results are picking up two separate groups of people here who both generally perceive that users groups feel that IFRS adoption is a necessity. Both these groups have more familiarity with the details of IFRS, and are more likely to have global mindsets and outlooks.

For Q5.2 the final significant result is for the question which asks whether respondents think that government regulations will have a positive impact on IFRS implementation in Libya. The F-statistic is 4.303 (sig = 0.001). The mean responses are: 'Once a month': 2.00, 'Once every three months': 1.89, 'Once every six months': 1.88, 'Once a year': 1.89, and 'Not Applicable': 1.70. This suggests that the vast majority of people in all categories, but especially the 'once a month' people, think that 'government regulations' will have a positive effect on IFRS implementation. In fact, every single one of the 15 respondents in the 'Once a month' category (100%) chose a Yes response. On average, these might be younger auditors and staff accountants with less experience but more extensive networks and more liberal and global outlooks. However, despite these speculative suggestions, neither age nor experience nor position produces a significant result for this variable.

**Table 5.28-A - Arithmetic mean and T-test value for answers between search variables
attributed to variations between two samples**

Q	VARIABLES	2015		2018		MEAN DIFFERENCE	T-TEST	SIG
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation			
Libyan professional awareness of the IFRS								
1	Q2.1	1.612	0.489	1.559	0.498	0.053	0.933	0.351
2	Q2.5	1.976	0.152	1.985	0.121	-0.009	-0.552	0.582
The potential advantages of and difficulties with IFRS implementation in Libya								
3	Q3.1	1.971	0.169	1.941	0.236	0.029	1.267	0.206
the most difficult factors which might affect IFRS implementation in Libya?								
4	Q3.2.3	0.682	0.467	0.537	0.500	0.146	2.625**	0.009
5	Q3.2.12	0.635	0.483	0.537	0.500	0.099	1.745	0.082
6	Q3.3	1.976	0.152	1.971	0.170	0.006	0.319	0.750
7	Q3.4	1.124	0.330	1.088	0.285	0.035	0.987	0.324
The need to apply the IFRS and the perceptions of Libyan professionals regarding their introduction into the Libyan accounting profession								
8	Q4.1	1.971	0.169	1.118	0.323	0.853	29.679**	0.000
The IFRS to be appropriate in the Libyan context what types of modifications are required?								
9	Q4.2.4	0.400	0.491	0.294	0.457	0.106	1.931	0.054
10	Q4.3	1.100	0.301	1.162	0.370	-0.062	-1.611	0.108
Factors which should be considered for the modifications required								
The potential implications of the implementation of the IFRS for the future								

11	Q5.1.1	0.818	0.387	0.765	0.426	0.053	1.137	0.257
12	Q5.1.3	0.524	0.501	0.478	0.501	0.046	0.791	0.430
13	Q5.2	1.829	0.377	1.860	0.348	-0.031	-0.736	0.462
14	Q5.3	1.965	0.185	1.949	0.222	0.016	0.695	0.487
15	Q5.4	1.976	0.152	1.993	0.086	-0.016	-1.108	0.269

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01)

(*) Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05)

To test whether there were differences between the two research samples (2015, 2018) in the level of application of the IFRS in Libya, a T-test was used for the mean of responses to the sample items on all variables (as a dependent variable) with the two sample classes as an independent variable, so the results were as in the tables, where the hypotheses were:

Null hypotheses: There are no statistically significant differences between the two samples in the level of application of the IFRSs in Libya.

Alternative hypothesis: There are statistically significant differences between the two samples in the level of application of the IFRS in Libya,

Some of the surveys were distributed in 2015 and some in 2018. The reason is that I changed universities and my Director of Studies requested that I increase the survey sample size. In terms of these two sets of results, they differed significantly only in relation to two questions (see Table 5.28-A). The first one, ‘instability of government’ (Q3.2.3), had a lower percentage of Yes responses in 2018 compared to 2015. This suggested, as expected, that respondents’ views about political stability became significantly more negative in 2018. There has been no stable government since 2011 and, as the situation has progressed, people have become more worried and negative overall. A change in government during this period did not improve stability. As such, it was expected that people would become more worried by 2018 about ‘political instability’ having the potential to adversely affect any future IFRS implementation.

A very significant result occurs in relation to Q4.1. A much lower percentage of people in 2018 felt that users feel that it is necessary to adopt IFRS. The mean declines from 1.971 (2015) to 1.118 (2018) and the T-test value is 29.679 (sig=0.000). I had originally expected at the commencement of the project that support for IFRS would grow over time as people felt more in tune with the needs and possibilities of globalization. One reason for my extremely important result here could be that in 2018 people felt that it was more urgent to improve the domestic political stability of Libya than to worry about accounting issues.

Adding support to this argument is the nearly-significant result for Q4.2.4 (T-statistic =1.931, sig =0.054). This result shows that, on balance, respondents were becoming more cynical and negative about the quality of the internal control systems in Libya. The reason here could be that political instability worsened between 2015 and 2018 and so I argue that policing and quality improvement for internal control also became weaker. The stability of the system has worsened and so has people's confidence in the system. They now perceive that internal controls are weaker and so more improvement would be needed before Libyan companies can successfully implement IFRS. The IFRS assume a Western First World environment of relative political stability and a sphere of well-functioning civil society.

5.6 Conclusion

Overall, my respondents in Libya appear to be willing to embrace the change associated with adoption, even if this means they go through a steep learning curve in practice. Quantitative results show that older respondents are more nervous and sceptical about IFRS adoption. At their age, they may feel that learning a whole new system is too burdensome and not worth the trouble. However, academics, because of their inclinations and connections to global networks, are very knowledgeable about IFRS and supportive of the change to IFRS.

There are two interesting and important findings about the impact of gender on attitudes: firstly, compared to men, women prefer to undertake more training courses to learn to use IFRS. This can be explained by Connell's (1995) theory of 'hegemonic masculinity' whereby men value achievement and success, through their own efforts and striving, whereas women have the culture of wanting to learn more about topics within mutually-supportive groups. Secondly, women feel that 'government regulations' will help in IFRS adoption whereas men do not. This result perhaps points to women's more optimistic and law-abiding tendencies, as compared to men's resistance and cynicism. However, both feel that 'international guidance' from *somewhere else* will assist adoption, which demonstrates humility and the belief that, at present, the knowledge-base for IFRS primarily exists overseas and not locally. This attitude could be viewed as weakness by certain people overseas, though once local people gain more IFRS knowledge this result might shift. At the present time, there is the belief that expertise exists 'out there' (Baulch 2003, 2007) and not here. This might be why older men are not willing to 'buy into' the idea of embracing and learning a new system where expertise resides elsewhere and not with them. The results reveal that isomorphic pressures have been powerfully effective in generating support for IFRS, and especially among younger respondents, academics, and the UK//US-educated groups. They then embody these isomorphic forces and become extensions of the hegemonic IASB regime. In the next chapter, I present qualitative results and link the qualitative findings with the quantitative results by drawing various comparisons.

Chapter Six - Qualitative findings

6.1 Introduction

This chapter presents qualitative results concerning the perceived paybacks and challenges of adoption and implementation of IFRS in an emerging country, namely Libya. The interviews were conducted with 11 General Managers from Libya, one of whom (as of October 2021) is now deceased. All of these interviewees were and are experts in IFRS (please refer to Table 3.5). This chapter reports the qualitative results from these 11 interviews and identifies a number of apparent benefits and challenges likely to accompany the adoption of and implementation of IFRS in Libya. These results build upon, and must be interpreted within the context of, the quantitative results chapter presented previously.

Noteworthy among the alleged benefits perceived by the interviewees were the simplicity of comparing financial data across borders, attracting investors, FDI, and unified language and concepts for accounting and financial transactions. The prominent perceived challenges were: (1) the lack of professional expertise and knowledgeable accountants; (2) lack of appropriate degrees and further educational development among the Libyan accountants; (3) aspects of prevailing Islamic regulations and culture that run contrary to the Anglo-based ideology and worldview inherent in the IFRS; (4) the incessant modifications to IFRS; (5) the perception of users themselves regarding their implementation; and (6) the inherent difficulties of accurately translating and interpreting the IFRS for their adoption and implementation in Libya. Nevertheless, the respondents also emphasized that the mandatory application and implementation of IFRS in Libya will be of net benefit, especially for reducing the cost of information, increasing its quality, and ameliorating the problems of maintaining the capital market in Libya. They also accentuated the necessity for well-educated, competent, and multilingual staff to augment and eventually replace the current employees. These qualitative results will help to fill the gap in empirical research regarding the perceived benefits and challenges of IFRS adoption and implementation in emerging and Arab countries, particularly Libya.

6.2 Setting the scene

The proper management and control of a country's accounting structure necessitates effective valuation and assessment of its current accounting quality (Judge, Li & Pinsker 2010; Singh & Newberry 2008). Consequently, it becomes important for nations adopting the

International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) to assess the perceived benefits and challenges that come with IFRS adoption, from the stakeholders' standpoint, so as to efficiently control accounting development (Samaha & Khelifa 2016). Particularly, employing institutional theory as a framework will aid in determining the frequency and value of institutional conformity to the institutional norms of suitable international accounting conduct and performance (Ramanna & Sletten 2014).

As stated by institutional theory scholars, organizations need to conform to societal norms of suitable practice to ensure continued ongoing backing from their stakeholders (Covaleski & Dirsmith 1995). As explained in Chapter 3 (about theory), these isomorphic pressures can be described as coercive, normative or mimetic. The isomorphic pressures are linked to the political and regulatory structures that are applied by the worldwide system of MNEs, FDI, and the IMF, on which businesses are contingent for critical assets and continuing existence (Guler *et al.* 2002). The second pressure is normative isomorphic pressure, as conceptualized by DiMaggio and Powell (1991), which represents the collective values that generate conformity of belief and effort in institutional settings. These values are necessary for a comparable form of accounting education, backed by all international accounting experts, and for continuing partnership with professional institutes in the accounting sphere (Haunschild 1993). According to DiMaggio and Powell (1983), mimetic isomorphic pressures represent the propensity of social actors to emulate what they see as fruitful and legitimate social actors, both institutions and people. In same vein, a country's exposure to external competition and trade enforces businesses to emulate the standards of best practices (Wei, Liu, Song & Romilly 2001). Consequently, mimetic pressures might ensue because of co-operation with trade associates and MNEs. A network effect may ensure a degree of conformity in terms of adoption and implementation of the IFRS (Ramanna & Sletten 2014).

There is considerable emphasis on these institutional pressures in emerging economies like Libya, since these countries often pursue and court FDI and receive other assets from developed nations and worldwide businesses. Consequently, through the lens of institutional theory, researchers might be able to observe some moderating effects that would assist developing countries like Libya in adopting and conforming to the IFRS if there are potential perceived paybacks to users and stakeholders, which include 'national agencies, business organisations, investors, policy makers, regulators, customers, among others' (Mbawuni 2018, p. 101). The sections that follow present the emerging themes relating to either the

perceived benefits and/or the drawbacks of IFRS adoption and implementation in the Libyan context (according to the 11 interviewees). In the chapter’s Conclusion, I then relate these findings to institutional theory.

6.3 Emerging themes for question one

The adoption and implementation of the IFRS underpins investment and leads to adequate financial information.

Figure 6.1 – Emerging themes for question one

Key concept	Key authors	Key findings
1. The necessity of the IFRS implementation and adoption to encourage and enable investment	Serafeim, and Serafeim (2013), Liu, Yao, Hu, and Liu (2011), Chua, Cheong, and Gould (2012) Durocher and Gendron (2011), Ball (2006), Daske, Hail, Leuz, and Verdi (2008)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. There has to be a unified language among accountants to facilitate disclosure and adequate information. 2. The adoption and implementation of the IFRS will encourage investment decisions.

The adoption and implementation of the IFRS will avoid losses [meaning ‘criticism’] in the accounting evaluation of the financial statements of companies and of course beneficial for attracting investment in the Libya (MH).

The implementation and adoption of the IFRS is a need, rather, it is must for all companies in all sectors, because it is easy to analyze, accurate and provide[s] clear and adequate information so as to attract foreign investment in the country (TH).

Due to fast pace of accounting in the global economy, the language of the IFRS become[s] a need for those companies that wants to keep pace with the speed of the financial world, like the Libyan Stock Market, and has to be unified. The implementation and adaptation of the IFRS is necessary so as to attract foreign investment, [and to] inform external investors that we are implementing IFRS measures that ... [are] the base of control, evaluation, monitoring, and judging the financial statements of companies operating in all sectors in the country (MA).

We are not alone, so standardization and harmonization in the accounting measurements will allow us to deal with transparency and disclosure [of] our transaction[s] to obtain trust of mutual external investors and internal as well (SAB).

As illustrated by the above quotations, at least five of the interviewees believed that adoption and implementation of the IFRS would aid in attracting investment to Libya and encourage foreign investors to come into the country with more investments. This result is consistent with the findings of other studies, for example, Daske, Hail, Leuz and Verdi (2008). These authors confirm that investors expect IFRS implementation to enhance comparability of financial statements, boost transparency, benefit investors, and intensify financial reporting quality. Moreover, according to Chen, Young, and Zhuang (2013), adopting the IFRS and IFRS disclosures of foreign peers would aid managers and investors to more accurately monitor investments and, ultimately, make better investment decisions. Other possible paybacks that might well ensue by adopting and implementing the IFRS have been identified, including external compatibility, financial transparency, a decrease in information expenses, increased visibility in more efficient markets, and promotion of competition (Ball 2006; Horton, Serafeim, & Serafeim 2013).

In addition, my respondents duly emphasized the necessity of a unified language that would be brought about by adopting and implementing the IFRS in Libya, so as to reduce costs and provide high-quality information, which in turn would aid in attracting FDI. This perception is also confirmed by other authors, for example, Durocher and Gendron (2011), who emphasized that accounting language that is not unified creates difficulties for investors in drawing up company judgments, while an integrated global financial reporting standard enhances the quality of accounting and thus investment decisions (Liu, Yao, Hu & Liu 2011). As such, it appears that the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya is a valuable option, in order to improve investments, provide high-quality and low-cost information, and allow investors to harmonize and standardize their transactions and disclosures. Thus, application of the IFRS should deliver benefits to the country.

6.4 Emerging themes for question two

The challenges faced in the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya.

Figure 6.2 – Emerging themes for question two

Key concept	Key authors	Key findings
1. The challenges that face the IFRS implementation and adoption in Libya	Schachler, Al-Abiyad, and Al-Hadad (2012); Laga (2012); Masoud, (2014) Mohamed (2014) Ball (2006) Ball, Robin and Wu (2003), Armstrong et al. (2007) Soderstrom and Sun (2007) Schipper (2005).	1. Political division is an obstacle for the adoption of IFRS. 2. The lack of awareness, training, education, and regulatory framework impedes the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya.

The political divisions and the lack of regulatory board that issue[s] laws and legislations that encourage the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya constitute[s] a big obstacle (MM).

Of course the political division is the main hindrance ... [to] the implementations and adoption of the IFRS in Libya; we need political reform to issue and encourage adaptation and implementation of the IFRS so as to be in parallel with the international community, increase and leverage the tax and control tax avoidance, and encourage disclosure. In addition to the lack of laws' consistency to adopt the IFRS in Libya (SAB).

We are lacking political regulations and laws that encourage the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya. In addition, the current accountants are lacking the knowledge, training and education of the IFRS which also constitute big obstacles for the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya (AMA).

As we see from the above quotations, these three respondents emphasized that the political divisions and the lack of laws and legislations and absence of suitably qualified professionals were among the obstacles that would hinder the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya. This is consistent with both my quantitative findings and the conclusions of other researchers. For example, Ball (2006) stresses the necessity for political reforms that embrace and encourage the implementation of the IFRS. In addition, Ball, Robin and Wu (2003) confirm that a well-functioning legal system, educational requirements, and positive political influences must be in place to assist the implementation of the IFRS. Moreover, the respondents' views were in agreement with findings from other academic results. For example, political and business differences might continue to constitute major difficulties in

the progress towards the adoption and implementation of the IFRS (Armstrong *et al.* 2007; Soderstrom & Sun 2007). My quantitative findings reveal more concern about political instability in the country in 2018 *as compared to 2015*. The interviews took place in August 2018, and the interview responses appear to mirror the survey responses from the same year. Libya is very unstable politically with two power-bases, one in the west and one in the east. The parliament is in the east but there is another government controlling the capital city in the west. There needs to be more political stability before investor confidence can increase.

Although we are encouraging the adoption of the IFRS in the Libyan accounting board, but, we are lacking knowledge, training, education, laws and regulations that might support our endeavours towards the implementation and adoption of the IFRS in Libya, plus, the political division that divide the country into political parties that [are] lacking the knowledge and expertise toward the adoption of the IFRS in Libya (MA).

We are lacking the awareness, knowledge, education, training, legislations so as to encourage the adoption, and implementation of the IFRS in Libya. Plus to the absence of regulatory framework in the country, these are some of the challenges that impede the implementation of the IFRS in Libya (TMA).

As illustrated by the above quotes, two respondents confirmed that the lack of awareness, knowledge, training, and regulatory frameworks were among the challenges faced for the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya. The findings for this current theme are consistent with those of previous studies, which emphasized that implementation of IFRS in Libya will be problematic owing to many challenges, including: (1) lack of technical skills and inadequate knowledge of Libyan professional accountants; (2) the difficulties involved in improving its existing accounting structures; (3) a poor regulatory framework to deal with economic and social improvements; and (4) insufficient education and training of accountants (please refer to articles by Laga 2012; Masoud 2014; Schachler, Al-Abiyad & Al-Hadad 2012). In addition, Mohamed (2014) listed: (1) the weaknesses of the professional accountancy board; (2) lack of an independent oversight body; (3) inconsistency of existing laws and regulatory frameworks of accounting; (4) the lack of technical abilities; (5) Libyan professionals' insufficient knowledge; and (6) fragile accounting education as among the obstacles that face the implementation and adoption of the IFRS in Libya. In the same vein, Ball (2006) points out that the adoption of IFRS is an economic and political experience and it is widely agreed that the country's legal and political systems determine the success or otherwise of the adoption and implementation of the IFRS (Schipper 2005).

As such, it appears that the political division in Libya plus the lack of awareness of accounting knowledge, lack of a regulatory framework, lack of education, training, and skilled professional accountants are among the challenges that would plague the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya. Professional judgement, based on professional experience, is vital for successful IFRS implementation. For example, judgement is needed to properly estimate depreciation rates, asset revaluations and writedowns, bad-debt provisions, and writing off of non-performing loans (Ball, Robin & Wu 2003).

6.5 Emerging themes for question three

Fighting corruption and tax avoidance through the adaptation and the implementation of the IFRS.

Figure 6.3 – Emerging themes for question three

Key concept	Key authors	Key findings
1.The benefits of the IFRS implementation and adoption in Libya	Kythreotis (2015), Leuz and Oberholzer-Gee, (2006), Isa (2014), Sanusi, (2010), Bakre and Lauwo (2016)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Fighting corruption and tax avoidance through the adaptation of the IFRS 2. Transparency, disclosure, and accountability were the main criteria for the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya.

The adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya is essential to aid against the corruption that is [prevalent] in the country. The IFRS is characterized by transparency and disclosure that enforce organization[s] to declare their expenses, prevent tax avoidance, and fight corruption (MOA).

The adoption and implementation of the IFRS will aid the fair division of the Libyan wealth and fight corruption due to its international measurements and transparency. We have now two prices for currency - one in the black market, while the other is in the Libyan banks. By adopting the IFRS this discrepancy will disappear and corruption will be fought (SAB).

In these quotations, these two respondents state clearly their beliefs that the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya will aid in fighting corruption, tax avoidance, and the dominance of the black market in Libya. This is due to the international standards, disclosure, and transparency that the implementation of the IFRS carries with it. My quantitative findings also show that corruption is widely perceived to be a factor which makes IFRS adoption more difficult. The findings of this theme support previous findings and conclusions of other

authors. For example, Kythreotis (2015, p. 2) holds that: ‘The degree of corruption, among other things, indicates the non-implementation of laws, weak enforcement of legal sanctions and the existence of non-transparent economic transactions.’ In addition, the accounting structure sometimes operates side-by-side with serious levels of corruption (Leuz & Oberholzer-Gee 2006). Moreover, Sanusi (2010) and Isa (2014) both found in their studies that increasing the level of transparency through the adoption of the IFRS was the main weapon in fighting corruption due to IFRS’ disclosure and transparency components. Furthermore, Bakre and Lauwo (2016) conclude that adoption of IFRS can decrease corruption by increasing levels of accountability and transparency. Thus, the respondents believe that the adoption and implementation of the IFRS is necessary to fight corruption, tax avoidance, and black-market activities, due to the system’s transparency and high accountability levels.

6.6 Emerging themes for question four

The incompatibility of the Islamic-infused national culture with the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya

Figure 6.4 – Emerging themes for question four

Key concept	Key authors	Key findings
1.The Islamic-based culture is not compatible with the adoption and implementation of some of the IFRS standards in Libya	Azmi (2010), Dowa, et al. (2007), Lewis (2001), (Wilson 2004), Zeff (2007), Sylwia and Steve (2010)	1. The incompatibility of the Islamic culture with the adaptation and implementation of the IFRS in Libya. 2. Incompetent accountants and poor translation impede the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya.

Of course the Islamic religion constitutes an obstacle for the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya. For instance, we have had article 1 for 2013 that prohibit the obtaining of financial interests in banks in Libya, and then return in 2018-19, but other banks in the west of the country did not recognize the financial interest and followed the Islamic principles of financial interests, which influence the accounting system in the country. In addition, financial interests and tax is *Ribā* [unjustified increment in borrowing or lending money] and prohibited in the Islamic religion which will also affect the adoption and implementation of the IFRS badly (ISA).

Yes, there is conflict between the Islamic orders and the adoption and implementation of the IFRS regarding the financial interests, tax, transactions, because ... the Islamic *Sharia'a* [religious law] consider benefits as *Ribā*, and interests on fund as illegal (MOA).

In our culture, there are some issues related to the lending and borrowing from banks to individuals and vice versa: for instance, in Islam we cannot give a lender a fixed rate of benefits on his/her deposit, which is the case in all the Western banks, nor can banks share risks with the borrowers, which also contradict with the accounting system and the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya (BMK).

In line with the above quotes, at least three of my interviewees confirmed that the Islamic religion, which is deeply embedded in Libyan culture, with regulations for financial behaviour, poses challenges for the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya. The religion has relevance in Muslims' financial transactions and daily activities, and these transactions are conducted differently to the transactions in the West and the accompanying accounting regulations differ accordingly. This is consistent with the findings of other authors. For example, Azmi (2010, p. 3) points out that Islam determines not only prayers, but even the commercial transactions which the Muslims must deal with in their lives. According to Dowa *et al.* (2007, p. 172): 'Religion is a cultural obstacle to the adoption of IFRS in some countries and some institutions.' I would argue that 'obstacle' is the wrong English-language word here because a religious practice should not be assigned a negative label.

Moreover, some respondents in the current research pointed out that the financial interest that banks give to savers is prohibited according to the Islamic *Sharia'a* which refers to it as *Ribā*; this also illustrates how the financial system is influenced by Islamic regulations and principles that are different from the principles of the IFRS and free economy. This issue has been discussed in the literature. For example, according to Lewis (2001, p. 106), 'Islamic economic and financial moralities have a straight effect on accounting strategies and practices, which contain the institution of '*Zakāh*', the prohibition of '*Riba*' (financial interest), and the institution of an interest-free economic system.' This indicates that the conventional balance sheet, drawn up by Western standards, does not follow Islamic principles of accounting, particularly regarding the issue of *Zakāh* (charitable giving) (Wilson 2004, p. 1). This factor also constitutes a challenge in regards to the adoption and implementation of IFRS in Libya. However, some of my respondents suggested that standards conflicting with religion can be taken out of the IFRS 'package' before

implementation in Libya. This suggests that this issue can be ‘solved’ pragmatically, from inside of the country, as long as foreign investors accept these choices made locally.

Furthermore, some respondents suggested that the lack of professional accountants together with poor translation of the IFRS also constitute a hindrance to the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya. This is also consistent with the conclusions of other researchers. For example, Zeff (2007, p. 296) states that: ‘Harmonization and standardisation of financial reporting will be severely hampered because of poor translation’ which is not an easy process. Translation may be different from one translator to another. Therefore, dissimilar translations will hinder the comparison of financial statements that are the product of the application of standards. It is recommended that the translation of IFRS into other languages ought to be prepared by a professional commission of the IASB, in order to avoid the misunderstandings that might ensue from dissimilar translations (Dowa *et al.* 2007, p. 175).

The respondents’ widespread view that a lack of well-educated and professional accountants hinders the adoption and implementation of IFRS in Libya is corroborated by the findings of other research studies. For instance, Dowa *et al.* (2007, p. 175) argue that technical skill and expertise are cultural obstacles to the adoption of IFRS in many nations and some organizations. Tomaszewski & Showerman (2010, p. 68) conclude that the important challenge for the accounting profession is the ‘availability of professionals with sufficient education and experience’. Thus, incompatibility of Islamic regulations, poor translation, and the lack of skills and expertise combined with poor understanding and interpretation of the IFRS, constitute cultural and social challenges for adoption in developing and poor countries. Successful adoption depends predominantly on the availability of qualified human and material potentials (Dowa *et al.* 2007, p. 175). In the quantitative results chapter, respondents said that ‘language barriers’ were perceived as a major implementation hindrance, but ‘cultural factors’ were not. The way the survey was written assumed that language barriers were not a part of cultural factors but were a separate issue.

6.7 Emerging themes for question five

The difficulty of translating and interpreting the IFRS for its adaptation and implementation in Libya.

Figure 6.5 – Emerging themes for question five

Key concept	Key authors	Key findings
1. Translating and interpreting the IFRS is needed to aid their adoption and implementation in Libya	Azmi (2010), Dowa, et al. (2007), Lewis (2001), (Wilson 2004), Zeff (2007), Sylwia and Steve, (2010), Tsakumis et al.(2009), Doupnik and Richter (2003), Evans (2004)	1. The inherent difficulties of accurately of translating and interpreting the IFRS for its adaptation and implementation in Libya 2. The need for well-educated, competent and multilingual staff as a replacement for the current employees.

I don't think the translations of the IFRS will [be] fit for purpose, because other countries have tried to interpret the IFRS concepts and terminology, and they found the interpretations from English to their language were not the same. Some definitions in one language do not mean the same meaning in other language[s] and doing so will harm comparability; consequently, in that case, the process of adopting and implementing the IFRS will be hindered (ISA).

Jordan, Saudi Arabia and other countries tried to rely [on] the interpretation of the IFRS in an unprofessional and not rigorous way that hindered the process of the IFRS in their countries, as such, in my opinion. Instead of translating the IFRS to be in parallel with our language, why do ... we [not] try to educate our staff with multilingual skills and abilities to cope with the IFRS concepts and terminology? (MOA).

In my opinion, the translation and interpretations of the IFRS will incur severe problems because the concepts and terminology are not identical from one culture and country to another. As it happens in the EU, [with efforts] to interpret the IFRS in different language, they realize that the best option is to leave it as it is (BMK).

I do not think there is a need to translate and interpret the IFRS concepts and terminologies unless you have educated and competent staff to do so, since any misinterpretations of the IFRS terminology and concepts will adversely deteriorate the whole meaning (TMA).

As seen in these quotes, these four interviewees believed that accurate translation of the International Financial Reporting Standards is deemed infeasible in the case of Libya, and they were concerned that an unsuccessful translation will harm and adversely affect the comparability of accounting in Libya. In addition, the translation will be hindered due to the

lack of well-educated and multilingual staff and poor interpretation of the IFRS concepts and terminology. This point of view corroborates other academics. One example is Tsakumis *et al.* (2009, p. 35) who warn that '[t]ranslation of IFRS into various languages poses another threat to accounting comparability'. Similarly, Zeff (2007, p. 296) asserts that poor translation is a serious threat to harmonization and standardization of financial reporting. The procedure of translating the IFRS is a difficult process, and dissimilar interpretations by different individuals will delay the comparison of financial statements. One respondent suggests that it would be better to improve accountants' foreign-language skills rather than translate the IFRS poorly.

Moreover, my respondents confirmed that the IFRS could not be translated, as they will lose their meaning, concepts, and terminology, and even the EU countries have experienced problems with the IFRS translation and realized that it is better to leave it as it is in the English language. This is also in parallel with other academic findings. For example, it has been posited that 'standards cannot be translated into other languages without some distortion of meaning', For instance the word 'remote', which is used in IAS31 and IAS 37, can be translated into Spanish as 'vasto', 'remoto' or 'lejano' (online translation dictionary www.freedict.com) (Tsakumis *et al.* 2009, p. 38).

Furthermore, respondents also thought that the translation may affect the quality of comparability in the IFRS, which concurs with the views of Hellmann *et al.* (2010, p. 3) that, if the interpretation of IFRS into different European languages is not well-organized or thorough, it interferes with comparability. Douplik and Richter (2003, p. 15) found multiple 'uncertainties' in terminologies existing between English-speaking and German-speaking auditors; these variances in interpretation may be owing to a cultural effect or poor translation and clumsy mapping of certain expressions in the target language. Consequently, it is obvious that absence of a precisely comparable expression in the two languages may create confusion over interpretations of accounting reports.

Thus, confusion due to the language, concepts and vocabulary used can greatly hamper the implementation of IFRS. It may even lead to bad investment decisions, due to a misinterpretation of the wordings used in financial statements (Evans 2004, p. 211).

6.8 Emerging themes for question six

Users value the IFRS benefits over the traditional financial statements in Libya.

Figure 6.6 – Emerging themes for question six

Key concept	Key authors	Key findings
1. Users' comparisons of the procedures of preparing traditional financial statements with implementation and adoption of the IFRS in Libya	Daske and Gebhardt (2006), Bova and Pereira (2012), (Barth, (2008) and Leuz (2003), Taiwo and Adejare (2014), Dunne <i>et al.</i> (2008), Aharony <i>et al.</i> (2010), Barth <i>et al.</i> (2006)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Users value the benefits of IFRS over the traditional financial statements in Libya. 2. Users perceive the IFRS as providing more adequate information for assisting investments in Libya than the traditional financial statements.

In comparison the financial statement with the IFR, the IFRS ... will be costless, IFRS theoretically better echo the fundamental economics of a transaction, enable better communications with specialists, investors, financial markets and other users of financial statements, reduce the political costs of transacting business and attract foreign investors. The IFRS also has single set of principles that reduce the cost, and of high quality and transparent accounting standards and value-relevant for users (ISA).

The adoption and implementation of the IFRS will be better than the current financial statement[s] for users as it contain[s] mechanism that provide the sufficient information needed for investors, protecting them. [It is] more transparent and [aids the] capital market; [it] aid[s] in increasing liquidity and higher comparability, and [is lower] cost than the traditional financial statements (MOA).

For users, the preparing the financial statement costs time and effort, and does not provide the transparency and disclosure that the IFRS can provide. It also provides better communications with users due to the qualitative characteristics that the IFRS will impose to be inserted in the financial statement[s] based on the guidelines of the IFRS (BMK).

For users, the financial statement based on the IFRS will include [better measurement of] assets; total liabilities and net profit that cannot be found in the traditional financial statement that was based on the GAAP, it is also easy to comprehend for foreign investors the financial statements with dissimilar GAAPs for users and foreigners alike (TMA).

As seen in the quotations above, four respondents of the current research stated their belief that the adoption and implementation of the IFRS in Libya would provide excellent value-relevant, high standards of quality and transparency and at low cost of time and money for users, as compared to the traditional financial statements. Senior accounting managers in

Libya emphasized that the procedures of IFRS will better record liabilities and net profit compared to the traditional financial statements based on the traditional GAAP in Libya. This is in accordance with other academic findings. For instance, Bova and Pereira (2012) suggest that nations implementing IFRS have faith that IFRS are high-quality and transparent accounting standards, since IFRS financial statements are extra value-relevant and transparent, in comparison with financial statements prepared consistent with the GAAPs (Daske & Gebhardt 2006). The respondents also confirmed that they perceived the adoption and implementation of the IFRS are inexpensive in terms of indigenous users and investors, and very easy to understand compared to the traditional financial statements based on different GAAPs. This corresponds with other academic findings, that, for users, the IFRS improve the capital market and are able to entice foreign investors (Pricope 2016) and bring a wide range of capital assets into an economy (Barth 2008) and also that the IFRS is inexpensive as a single set of financial statements without translation and easier for stockholders to comprehend than statements prepared based on dissimilar GAAPs (Leuz 2003). In addition, a study conducted by Taiwo and Adejare (2014) found that those who prepare financial statements perceive that increased financial profits could result from IFRS adoption, which is less costly for businesses.

Moreover, interviewees in the current research confirmed the perceptions of users regarding the procedures of preparing the financial statements after the adoption of the IFRS, as the latter will entail low cost, and provide high comparability and transparency levels; they will also be inexpensive and beneficial for external investments. This corresponds with other academic results, which cite many benefits for users, including greater comparability of financial statements across firms working in dissimilar countries, inexpensive application, access to international capital by enabling cross-border listings, and, eventually, higher worldwide investments (Aharony *et al.* 2010; Dunne *et al.* 2008).

In addition, some interviewees in the current research emphasized that users perceive the IFRS as providing accurate and adequate information that could help users to determine their decisions on investments and this information is of greater use for investors as compared to the traditional financial statements. This result also supports similar claims by other authors. For instance, according to Dunne *et al.* (2008) the IFRS are shareholder-oriented and stimulate the impartial value approach to performance by integrating extra information into the financial statements, as well as transferring innovative information to the marketplace so

as to support stockholders in making soundly-based conclusions and forecasts of an organization's future financial prospects. Thus the application of IFRS is an indicator of higher accounting quality and transparency (Barth *et al.* 2006). There is a dispute, however, about what constitutes high-quality reporting: for Holthausen and Watts (2001), high accounting conservatism (defined as the tendency to defer gains and bring forward losses) means high quality. However, Barth, Beaver, and Landsman (2001) instead claim that high reliability (accuracy or conformity to the facts) represents high-quality. For them, conservatism becomes an unnecessary tradition which is a hindrance to quality. The authors also disagree on the primary purpose of accounting - for the first authors it is in contracting and for the second authors it is in share valuation.

Thus, it is apparent that some respondents perceive the IFRS as having higher value, high levels of comparability, transparency, liquidity, and information compared with the traditional financial statements in Libya. The IFRS are of apparently high value and assistance for attracting potential investments, according to the interviewees, based on transparency and sufficient information for decision-making. As previously presented, the quantitative findings also show that users generally support IFRS adoption but perceive that there are many challenges ahead if IFRS adoption is chosen. There is a high degree of similarity between this study's quantitative and qualitative findings. Accountants in Libya appear to be optimistic and willing to embrace the change associated with adoption even if this means they must go through a steep learning-curve in practice. Quantitative results show that older accountants are more nervous and sceptical about IFRS adoption. At their age, they may feel that learning a whole new system is too burdensome and not worth the trouble. Because of their theoretical inclinations, and connections to global networks, academics are especially knowledgeable about IFRS and supportive of a change.

6.9 Application of institutional theory

Based on these qualitative findings, the perceived benefits and challenges associated with the adoption of IFRS in Libya can be summed up. I believe that the results demonstrate the value of institutional conformity to societal norms of suitable behaviour or performance; in the context of the present study, this means the adoption and implementation of IFRS in Libya. Accordingly, these qualitative findings can be very useful for specialists, academics, and policy makers of IFRS in Libya. The results show strong support for IFRS generally but

people are worried about the impacts of political instability, corruption, language barriers, and the fact that religious practices create a business and societal culture which is incompatible with the British cultural worldview and free-market economy assumed by IFRS. This worldview sharply separates the entity from its owners and others outside the entity and also sharply separates private views and actions from corporate ones, although even in the West this is changing to an extent due to the rise of CSR activities. Whereas, in 1970, Milton Friedman argued that individuals and not corporations should give to charitable causes, this view is now not generally accepted. However, these Libyan respondents were cheerfully pragmatic, and simply said that IFRS standards not compatible with Islamic practices can be removed from the complete package of standards. This seems to be a reasonable solution; I do not want to adopt an extreme neo-liberal position by saying that religious and cultural bases for actions should be viewed as regressive and anti-modern.

In line with institutional theory, Libya as the context of the study, as a developing nation, the alleged benefits of IFRS adoption and implementation would comprise: the ability of the country to attract FDI based on the credibility which Libya will gain in world capital markets; the reduction of information cost and improved quality; the enhanced allocation of resources; better movement of capital; better understanding of risk and return, and controlling tax avoidance, each of which will aid Libya in enhancing the national accounting quality of the country. There are social pressures worldwide to adopt IFRS as the 'best' and 'standardized' accounting technology. Our respondents mostly agree with these international hegemonic views, in line with neo-liberal identities and agendas and a global form of travelling business hegemonic masculinity (Connell 1995). Hence they are keen to adopt IFRS. This shows the clear presence of isomorphism, consistent with institutional theory. There is primarily normative and mimetic isomorphism present, with an aspect of coercive too, given the global power of the institutions which drive the modern neo-liberal agenda worldwide. If these institutions are negative or hostile, there can be serious reputational and financial damage imposed on both nations and individual corporations. These hegemonic legitimating institutions include the IASB, the IMF, the World Bank, and the UN.

6.10 Summary

In this chapter, I have presented the qualitative results and drawn conclusions about the results in line with the predictions of institutional theory. I have also attempted to link the main quantitative results with the key qualitative findings. Generally speaking, both of these sets of results are mutually-consistent and mutually-reinforcing, a fact which is of obvious comfort to me as the researcher and which should allow the careful reader to have confidence in the complete set of findings. Although all three types of isomorphism are probably confirmed by the data, this does not mean that my respondents are passive and dominated by foreign agendas. They also have realistic concerns. Some of these concerns are not within the direct control of accountants, such as political turmoil and a widespread culture of corruption. Unless these factors are resolved, then accountants can't do much beyond sit and wait for the situation to improve, or they can emigrate. If they emigrate in large numbers, this will nearly certainly lower the quality of the accounting profession in the future, and eventual IFRS implementation will become even harder. In the next and final chapter, I present a summary of results, followed by conclusions drawn, limitations, suggestions for further research, and recommendations for practice.

Chapter Seven – Conclusion

7.1 Introduction and personal reflections

This chapter provides, firstly, a summary of the main quantitative and qualitative results, followed by my concluding remarks, a section on contribution to knowledge, a section on limitations, a section on policy recommendations, and (lastly) a set of suggestions for further research. Since the study was first conceived, substantial change has occurred in Libya, and there has been a wholesale loss and destruction of political institutions and social stability. The democratic nirvana has failed to materialize (yet), and we have reached the ludicrous situation of two groups both claiming to be the legitimate national government, one based in the west and one in the east. On 24th December 2021, there is an election planned to elect one nationwide government. However, between the idea and the reality falls the shadow.

All these events were discouraging for me both in my capacity as a researcher and in my capacity as a Libyan citizen. My topic seemed almost futile as the national disintegration has meant that IFRS adoption is surely a secondary consideration at best. This perception is confirmed by my survey respondents who were relatively upbeat about political stability in 2015, but much less so three years later. Lest this study be accused of being akin to ‘shifting deckchairs on the *Titanic*,’ I must reiterate that political, economic, and social stability are needed first in Libya and that IFRS adoption is definitely now a secondary consideration. However, over the longer-term, the topic remains important and will not go away. Readers should bear both the immediate and the longer-term Libyan contexts in mind.

7.2 Summary of quantitative results

(a) Age and years of experience of survey respondents are significantly positively correlated with each other at the 1% level.

(b) There is no correlation between age and qualification of respondents, where highest qualification is placed lowest on the list for that variable. This would suggest that some younger people (including academics) are pursuing higher degrees.

(c) There is no significant correlation between qualification and years of experience.

(d) The majority of the sample believe they have sufficient awareness and knowledge of the IFRS for preparing financial reports (Q2.1).

(e) The majority believe that IFRS will have a positive impact on financial reports (Q2.1.1.1).

(f) The majority believe that IFRS plays an important role in improving the quality of financial reports (Q2.2).

(g) Nearly all respondents would be willing to apply the IFRS standards (Q2.2).

(h) Most respondents believe that the Libyan context is not suitable for these standards (although 40% dispute this conclusion) (Q2.2.1).

(i) The results overwhelmingly suggest that close to all respondents (293 or 96%) believe that using IFRS will have a positive impact in Libya (Q3.1). Therefore, the concept of IFRS is very widely supported in Libya, and this will encourage the IASB.

(j) The respondents think that the two factors which will most significantly affect IFRS implementation are instability of government (61%) and corruption (59%). These results support my statements made in the opening section of this chapter.

(k) After the first two factors, there is a sizeable drop until we reach the third most significant factor, 'language barriers,' which was selected by 44%. After that, in order, we have 'low level of education' and 'political factors'. The accounting profession cannot right the ship by itself because it needs to wait for political stability.

(l) An overwhelming majority (298 or 97%) believes that the IFRS will have a potential impact on financial reports (Q3.1).

(m) Most respondents do not believe that there is an urgent need to adopt IFRS (181 or 59% compared to 125 or 41%). (Q4.1). This suggests a very cautious attitude, probably because respondents are aware of the current contextual problems within the country.

(n) Users are more concerned with poor quality reporting and low accountability in the public sector as compared to in the private sector.

(o) A clear majority (243 or 79%) perceive that IFRS will improve the quality of financial reporting, while only 63 people (21%) disagree. One conclusion is fairly clear - the accounting profession in Libya believes that IFRS based accounting standards are of a higher quality than the accounting policies used at present.

(p) The respondents believe that each one of the three factors listed individually and separately in Q5.2 to Q5.4 - 'government regulation,' international guidelines,' and 'training courses' - will have a positive impact on IFRS implementation. The percentages of Yes responses range from 84% (government regulations) to 98% (training courses).

(q) A higher percentage of women than men are optimistic about the ability of government regulations and training courses, respectively, to assist in the implementation of

IFRS in Libya. Women appear to be less cynical and more willing to learn from diverse sources than men. Being able to statistically separate out women's and younger people views from the rest is a clear highlight of my empirical work.

(r) Younger people are more positive than older people that IFRS will have potential advantages for financial reporting in Libya. The optimism and energy of the young may well prove to be a driving force for change in future years. The overseas, Western education received by many younger respondents clearly was a big influence on their worldviews.

(s) Younger accountants are more likely than older accountants to believe that there is a necessity felt by users to adopt the IFRS.

(t) Older accountants are more likely than younger accountants to perceive that the main accounting actors will view IFRS introduction pessimistically.

(u) Younger accountants are marginally more optimistic about the potential of international guidelines to assist in IFRS implementation.

(v) Academics have the highest knowledge of IFRS (and perhaps the highest self-confidence about their own knowledge). Auditors have experience of a much wider range of companies and sectors than do staff accountants, and hence it is expected that their IFRS knowledge will be better.

(w) Senior accountants and auditors, being more global in outlook, are the most optimistic about the proposition that IFRS adoption will have advantages for financial reporting in Libya.

(x) Academics generally perceive that users demand IFRS. Auditors have knowledge about IFRS, but many auditors do not perceive that users demand it. Auditors' opinions may reflect general concerns about the current high level of political instability in Libya. Academics' views seem to be a function of their Western education and global networks.

(y) More experienced people, who are older on average, perceive that users have less necessity for IFRS adoption. Older people with more experience may have least confidence in their own ability to master IFRS and may be projecting this on to users (consciously or unconsciously). They may be nervous about wholesale change.

(z) The least experienced accountants, followed by the most experienced, think that the main actors will respond optimistically to IFRS adoption. Those in the middle categories think that actors will respond pessimistically.

(aa) The respondents with less experience generally perceive that IFRS adoption will aid capital markets. The people with less experience have a more global outlook and are not confining their attention only to the domestic situation.

(bb) Those people educated in Libya are less satisfied with their IFRS knowledge than those educated in either UK or USA. The Libyan lecturers may have less knowledge themselves and be poorer in teaching the material, which impacts negatively upon their own students. Furthermore, having an overall British education may assist students in understanding the historical, economic, social, and political context behind the IFRS.

(cc) On average, the higher the person's education level, the more self-confident she/he is about her/his own perceived knowledge of IFRS. This is self-explanatory.

(dd) Survey respondents were more concerned about political instability's negative effects on IFRS implementation in 2018 than they were in 2015. A lower percentage of people in 2018 felt that users feel that it is necessary to adopt IFRS. One reason for this extremely important result could be that people felt in 2018 that it was more urgent to improve the domestic political stability for Libya than to worry about accounting issues.

7.3 Summary of additional qualitative results (beyond the quantitative)

(a) Noteworthy among the perceived benefits of IFRS adoption were the simplicity of comparing financial data across borders; attracting investors; FDI; and unified language and concepts for accounting and financial transactions.

(b) The prominent perceived challenges were: the lack of professional expertise and knowledgeable accountants; lack of appropriate degrees and further educational development among the Libyan accountants; aspects of prevailing Islamic regulations and culture that run contrary to the Anglo-based ideology and worldview inherent in the IFRS; the incessant modifications to IFRS; the perception of users themselves regarding its implementation; and the inherent difficulties of accurately translating and interpreting the IFRS for its adoption and implementation in Libya.

(c) Interviewees in the qualitative section of the study said that it would be simple to remove some IFRS standards in Libya if they did not match with Islamic requirements.

7.4 Concluding remarks

In considering the situation of the selected developed nations in moving towards harmonization, several themes emerge. The first is readiness to adopt. For example, Belgium had a very easy transition, because it was already following the IFRS practices. Another theme is the flexibility regarding existing practices, especially where accounting reports have

functions for tax assessment and collection. Germany addressed this problem by retaining a dual system under which companies prepare accounts under the domestic system and also under IFRS, for publication purposes. Denmark also showed flexibility in adapting its traditional Anglo-Saxon practices in implementing IFRS. The third theme concerns commitment and enforcement. Rather than showing flexibility, Poland is very committed to harmonization, for instance through providing a complete translation, investing heavily, and making radical changes to accounting practices. Similarly, although a very recent EU member, Romania adopted and enforced IFRS very completely and rigorously – it, too, was willing to give up its previous accounting practices. This is probably a response to exiting communism and needing to quickly develop its business capabilities in a remote part of Eastern Europe, which is far away from established business networks.

With regard to emerging economies, although the situation is different, the themes of readiness, flexibility, and commitment are still relevant. Both Egypt and Algeria have shown commitment to modernizing from state-control and also flexibility in keeping customary accounting practices. However, Tunisia, although it was well prepared and very committed, lacked sufficient enforcement. In contrast, Oman, as well as showing great commitment in adoption and enforcement of IFRS, also showed real flexibility in terms of accommodating its pre-existing local religious and business environment.

The experience of Egypt in making a similar transition from state-control to a freer economy, and its flexible and cautious approach to gradually adopting IFRS, could provide lessons for Libya. Although, it is not in North Africa, three principles can be found in Oman's flexible approach to adopting IFRS which could be relevant to Libya's case. These are some exemptions for Islamic financial institutions; a reasonable level of actual enforcement of IFRS; and staged introduction of IFRS for SMEs.

Harmonization of accounting standards in Libya is a huge and daunting task. The adoption of IFRS by Libya would be beneficial for effective communication of accounting practices and financial statements with other countries (i.e. beyond the shores of Libya) and would improve the quality of reported financial statements. Consequently, accounting practices such as reporting of financial statements would probably become more transparent and instil confidence in both local and foreign investors. Hence, harmonization will very likely attract foreign investors to invest in the Libyan economy. This will help to stimulate and diversify

the Libyan economy away from being a major exporter of crude oil to becoming a producer and exporter of other commodities (which may include farm produce and exploration and exploitation of other minerals other than crude oil).

Nevertheless, the adoption of the IFRS, without any modifications, will pose problems to the Libyan people, because of their historical and cultural heritage. Libya is predominantly an Islamic country with a brutal and difficult colonial past. Hence, it will be more beneficial for Libya to adopt IFRS with appropriate modifications to meet the local socioeconomic needs of its people. Using the lessons from the experience of the countries with both developed and emerging economies, and the models they provide, this study has attempted to identify the modifications needed and the stages of implementation that would be feasible and effective. This includes investigating how the Libyan authorities can establish a clear timetable for the adoption and make appropriate plans and time to put in place the necessary infrastructure, including the development of suitably qualified professionals to start the process of adoption of these standards. My interviewees and survey respondents, for the present project, have provided extra advice and insight on potential implementation problems and plans.

The majority view is that (IFRS) adoption in Libya will face problems from the weakness of the professional accountancy organization, absence of an autonomous oversight body, discrepancy of current regulations, and controlling structures of accounting in Libya. Other factors include recent development of the accounting profession, lack of economic growth, deficiencies in technical skills and insufficient knowledge of Libyan professional auditors, and fragile accounting education (ATU *et al.*, 2016; Masoud, 2014, Mohamed, 2014).

7.5 Contributions to knowledge

(a) The research has contributed to the literature on IFRS by determining its suitability to the Libyan financial environment, given that the standards are composed from a Western perspective and assume an entirely different business culture.

(b) This study also aims to contribute to the Libyan context by raising interest in the establishment of local regulatory bodies in accounting and auditing to standardize and codify accountancy practices in Libya.

7.6 Limitations

One limitation or shortcoming of the study was that I commenced it in 2011 but did not conclude it until 2021. My study was disrupted and it received a substantial boost in 2017 when I shifted university. Originally the study was designed to be purely cross-sectional, based only on survey data collected in 2015. Had this remained the case the study would have been streamlined and simplified. The 2015 data could then reasonably be held to be an effective and clean test of conditions existing in the period when the research questions were written and the literature review prepared (2011-13). At my new University, I was asked to give out the survey again, in 2018, and also do some interviews. I believe that this was a fortuitous turn of events as I could add a longitudinal dimension to the cross-sectional dimension. Some results were significantly impacted by a new independent variable, 2018-versus-2015. These results make sense and are explained at length in the quantitative results chapter. Therefore, although the ten-year interval between study conception and completion opened the door to many confounding influences, caused by social and political changes, the new variable is able to systematically capture the net effect of these changes on certain respondent perceptions. The two-year gap, 2015-16, when I was not actively working on the thesis, was frustrating at the time, but it did yield clear benefits, in hindsight, because there was a sizeable three-year gap between the first and second round of surveys. Had there been only (say) a one-year gap, there would have been little point in testing for significant differences in responses across the two dates. Although readers are the ultimate judges and juries in relation to any academic work, I believe that overall the study has benefitted by the collection of further data in 2018 and the continuation of the study up to 2021.

There were also delays in the final write-up due to communication problems when the first coronavirus lockdown hit Scotland on 23rd March 2020. Unfortunately, my Director of Studies was not able to be contacted by internet for a two-month period as there were delays in getting Wi-Fi set up at his home due to demands being placed on the overall system.

I found it difficult to access people for this research, although, in the end, I was reasonably satisfied with the interviewee sample size, all things considered. The interviewees did *not* generally give interesting or detailed answers and this was a disappointment. It could be addressed in follow-up studies by a more persuasive and skilful interviewing style, which still must not traverse the boundary between the ethical and the unethical. Having two interviewers and conducting focus groups might also allow for more revealing and interesting

answers and conversations to emerge. This would allow for the two interviewers to plan their interview approach in advance and discuss the interview findings together afterwards. Interviewing retired people and/or recently unemployed persons might have meant that we could have got a subgroup of interviewees who were more willing to offer detailed and controversial opinions. This would have enhanced the quality and usefulness of the data. One positive feature of the existing survey sample, which must be highlighted, is the diversity of genders, ages, and job occupations reached (although they are all from public-sector bodies).

To be very honest and frank with the reader, I was discouraged by the decline in Libya's political, economic, and social health following 2011; this adversely affected my mood as I queried the ongoing relevance and significance of my topic against the backdrop of dramatic change. Simplistic narratives of 'good' people and 'bad' people, both within and outside the country, were depressing, as reality on the ground is complex and media networks like to put people into moral categories to enhance the simplicity and popularity of their narratives. This simplification of the debate was discouraging as I was committed to reaching a sophisticated academic understanding of events and the context as a whole.

7.7 Recommendations for change

In this thesis, I have applied institutional theory to the adoption and implementation of IFRS as applicable in the Libyan context. I find that stakeholders of IFRS, such as corporations, investors, policy-makers, and national regulators, can, in the future, take advantage of the normative pressures for the adoption and implementation of IFRS in Libya. I suggest that stakeholders encourage and support more training of appropriate accounting specialists in the applications of IFRS in Libya. Accordingly, based on my research I recommend that accounting and financial management instructors concentrate on increasing programmes that integrate the IFRS into the content of accounting curricula at all levels of Libyan education. In addition, there should be formal and informal training opportunities to raise awareness of IFRS among non-professional accounting employees, and accounting education and training packages for all levels of education and accounting staff. These are long-term ideals, for the accounting realm, and, of course, they are no substitute for political and social stability. Political and social stability will allow more foreign experts to come to the country to help with the IFRS adoption and training and may encourage Libyans based in Tunisia and elsewhere to return.

A short case-study from the Fiji islands is illuminating and relevant. The Fiji Institute of Accountants, run by a now deceased expatriate Scotsman for many years, was able to thwart a government takeover and maintain professional activities and professional values over time, through regular training courses, professional seminars, and social functions. Creating the atmosphere, ambience, and ethics of a professional accounting culture is vital. This is where the Libyan professional bodies need to lay their focus upon. Intangibles, such as professional identity and professional pride, are very important. Where these things are present, there will be more of a will to collectively resist future government control, which is often a self-interested political act designed to create a cowered environment where independent voices are suppressed.

The former Gaddafi government offered scholarships for overseas education for PhD students and all the other levels. This has continued, but to a lesser extent. This far-sighted programme needs to be accelerated once again. Scholarships should also be directed towards talented school-children and school-leavers.

7.8 Suggestions for further research

Because all interviews were done in Tripoli, future research could benefit by interviewing people located in other parts of the country. Because of the political situation and lack of safety, I only interviewed people from the capital during 2018. COVID-19 travel restrictions in 2020-21 stopped me from going back to collect more data from other parts of the country. Many experts from Libya are living overseas, and future researchers should either wait for people to return or go to some of those other countries to interview Libyan expatriates.

Research could go beyond the present study by surveying and interviewing people from outside my four chosen organizations. Interviewees should be selected from the private-sector in future studies. I also interviewed only general managers - this could be expanded on by future researchers. In addition, a case-study approach on certain industries might be useful, for example, the oil and gas industry. An example of an industry-specific approach was the PhD thesis of Ramadan Kanan, where he looked at the impact of culture and budgeting in the Libyan oil industry. In the long-term, Libya may be in a position to contribute to global accounting developments in this industry, in co-operation with the IASB and other countries.

By the end of December 2021, I hope that there will be one stable national government. Then the focus can shift back to topics like IFRS adoption. By that stage, the speed of developments should pick up and academic research can and should pick up as well. This study can be replicated at various points in the future to monitor the strategies used for actual IFRS implementation (if it is ever attempted) and the actual problems encountered.

References

- Abdalwahab, AO, Abdullah, AM & Marwan, GA 2018, 'The impact of transition from EAS 20 to IFRS 16 on financial performance'.
- Abdul-Baki, Z, Uthman, AB & Sannia, M 2014, 'Financial ratios as performance measure: a comparison of IFRS and Nigerian GAAP', *Accounting and Management Information Systems*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 82-97.
- Abotalib, YM 1998, *Accounting theory within a new thought framework*, Ein Shams Bookshop, Cairo.
- Abozied, M 2005, *Al-Musibah fi Libya jozurayha haziroha wa subhul tatviriha (Accountancy in Libya: its origin and current development)*, 1st edn, Al dawal Academia lil Nashar watiba'a watalef wa tarjuma, Tripoli.
- Adeuja, YO 2015, 'A comparative approach to the impact of IFRS (International Financial Reporting Standards) on the performance of banks in Nigeria', Eastern Mediterranean University (EMU) and Doğu Akdeniz Üniversitesi (DAÜ).
- Aharony, J, Barniv, R & Falk, H 2010, 'The impact of mandatory IFRS adoption on equity valuation of accounting numbers for security investors in the EU', *European Accounting Review*, vol. 19, pp. 535-78.
- Ahrens, T 2008, 'Discussion: overcoming the subjective-objective divide in interpretive management accounting research', *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, vol. 33, pp. 292-7.
- Algadi, H & Mamoon, H 2000, *International accounting*, 1st edn, Scientific Publishing and Distribution Press, Amman.
- Ali-Hassan, H 2005, 'Theories used in IS research institutional theory', York University, Heslington, York, England.
- Allison, HE & Hobbs, RJ 2006, *Science and policy in natural resource management: understanding system complexity*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Armstrong, C, Barth, M, Jagolinzer, A & Riedl, E 2007, 'Market reaction to the adoption of IFRS in Europe' (Working paper), Stanford University, Stanford, CA.
- Ashour, S & Samia, S 1993, *Introduction to analytical statistics*, 1st edn, Faculty of Commerce Publishing, Cairo.
- Atu, OG, Raphael, IA & Atu, OEOK 2016, 'Challenges of the implementation of IFRS in less developed and developing countries', *Igbinedion University Journal of Accounting*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1-26.
- Awayiga, JY, Onumah, JM & Tsamenyi, M 2010, 'Knowledge and skills development of accounting graduates: the perceptions of graduates and employers in Ghana', *Accounting Education: an International Journal*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 139-58.
- Azmi, S 2010, *An Islamic approach to business ethics*, viewed January 14, 2014, <<http://alhaqqsociety.wordpress.com>>.
- Bakre, OM & Lauwo S, 2016, 'Privatisation and accountability in a 'crony capitalist' Nigerian state', *Critical Perspectives on Accounting*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 45-58.
- Ball, R 2006, 'IFRS: pros and cons for investors', *Accounting and Business Research International Accounting Policy Forum*, pp. 5-27.

- Ball, R, Robin, A & Wu, JS 2003, 'Incentives versus standards: properties of accounting income in four East Asian countries', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, vol. 29, pp. 1-51.
- Barth, ME 2006, 'Including estimates of the future in today's financial statements', *Accounting Horizons*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 271-85.
- Barth, ME 2008, 'Global financial reporting: implications for US academics', *The Accounting Review*, vol. 83, no. 5, pp. 1159-79.
- Barth, ME, Beaver, WH & Landsman, WR 2001, 'The relevance of the value relevance literature for financial accounting standard setting: another view', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, vol. 31, nos. 1-3, pp. 77-104.
- Baulch, E 2003, 'Gesturing elsewhere? The identity politics of the Balinese death/thrash metal scene', *Popular Music*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 195-215.
- Baulch, E 2007, *Making scenes: reggae, punk, and death metal in 1990s Bali*, Duke University Press, Durham, NC.
- Baxter, J & Chua, WF 2003, 'Alternative management accounting research: whence and whither?' *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, vol. 28, pp. 97-126.
- Bebbington, J, Gray, R & Laughlin, R 2001, *Financial accounting: practice and principle*, 3rd edn, Thomson Learning, London.
- Beitmal MA 1990, 'Synopsis of an inventory and evaluation of the accounting standards in Great Jamahiriya', *Economic Research magazine*, Benghazi Economics Research Centre, vol. 2, no. 1.
- Bettner, MS, Robinson, C & McGoun, E. (1994) 'The case for qualitative research in finance', *International Review of Financial Analysis*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 1-18.
- Biber, SNH 2010, *Mixed methods research: merging theory with practice*, the Guilford Press, New York.
- Bjorck, F 2004, 'Institutional theory: a new perspective for research into IS/IT security in organisations,' *Proceedings of the 37th annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, Hawaii, USA, Track 7, p. 70186b.
- Boolaky, PK, Omoteso, K, Ibrahim, MU & Adelopo, I 2018, 'The development of accounting practices and the adoption of IFRS in selected MENA countries', *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 327-51.
- Boumediene, SL, Zarrouk, R. & Tanazefi, I 2016, 'Obstacles to the adoption of the IAS/IFRS in Tunisia', *Journal of Applied Business Research*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 621-36.
- Bova, F & Pereira, R 2012, 'The determinants and consequences of heterogeneous IFRS compliance levels following mandatory IFRS adoption: evidence from a developing country', *Journal of International Accounting Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 83-111.
- Broadbent, J. 1992, 'Change in organisations: a case study of the use of accounting information in the NHS', *British Accounting Review*, vol. 24, pp. 343-67.
- Bryman, A & Bell, E 2003, *Business research methods*, 1st edn, Oxford University Press, Gosport, Hampshire:
- Bui, NT, Le, OTT & Dao, HM 2020, 'Estimation of benefits and difficulties when applying IFRS in Vietnam: from business perspective', *International Journal of Financial Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 165-79.

- Burrell, G & Morgan, G 1979, *Sociological paradigms and organizational analysis*, Gower Publishing, Hants, England.
- Camfferman, K & Zeff, SA 2018, 'The challenge of setting standards for a worldwide constituency: research implications from the IASB's early history', *European Accounting Review*, vol. 27, pp. 289–312.
- Cerne, K 2009, 'Influential factors of country's accounting system development', *Economic Research Journal*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 66-97.
- Chua, WF 1986, 'Radical developments in accounting thought', *The Accounting Review*, vol. 61, no. 4, pp. 601-32.
- CIA World Fact Book 2021, '*CIA World Fact Book - Libya*, viewed August 24, 2021, <http://cia.gov/the-world-fact-book/countries/libya>.
- Connell, RW 1995, *Masculinities*, University of California Press, Berkeley, CA.
- Cooper, D, Lowe, EA, Puxty, AG & Willmott, H 1985, 'The regulation of social and economic relations in advanced capitalist societies: towards a conceptual framework for a cross national study of the control of accounting policy and practice', *Proceedings of the Interdisciplinary Perspectives in Accounting Conference*, University of Manchester, Manchester, England.
- Covaleski, MA & Dirsmith, MW 1995, 'The preservation and use of public resources: transforming the immoral into the merely factual', *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, vol. 20, nos. 2/3, pp. 147-73.
- Creswell, JW 1998, *Qualitative inquiry and research design: choosing among five traditions*, Sage, Thousand Oaks, CA.
- Creswell, JW 2008, *Educational research: planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*, Pearson Education, Upper Saddle River, NJ.
- Dahawy, K, Merino, BM. & Conover, TL 2002, 'The conflict between IAS disclosure requirements and the secretive culture in Egypt', *Advances in International Accounting*, vol. 15, pp. 203–28.
- Daske, H. & Gebhardt, G 2006, 'International financial reporting standards and experts' perceptions of disclosure quality', *Abacus*, vol. 42, nos. 3-4, pp. 461-98.
- Denzin, NK & Lincoln, YS 1994, 'Introduction: entering the field of qualitative research', in NK Denzin & YS Lincoln (eds), *Handbook of qualitative research*, Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks, CA, pp. 1-17.
- DiMaggio, PJ & Powell, WW 1983, 'The iron cage revisited: institutional isomorphism and collective rationality in organizational fields', *American Sociological Review*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 147-60.
- DiMaggio, PJ & Powell, WW 1991, *The new institutionalism in organizational analysis*, University of Chicago Press, Chicago.
- Donaldson, L, 1985, *In defence of organisation theory*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, MA.
- Doupnik, S,& Richter, M 2003, 'Interpretation of uncertainty expressions: a cross-national study', *Accounting Organizations and Society*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 15-35.
- Dowa, A, Elgammi, AM, Elhatab, A & Mutat, HA 2017, 'Main worldwide cultural obstacles on adopting international financial reporting standards (IFRS)', *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 172-79.

- Ebaid, IES 2016, 'International accounting standards and accounting quality in code-law countries: the case of Egypt', *Journal of Financial Regulation and Compliance*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 41-59.
- Edwik, AA 2007, 'Oil dependency, economic diversification and development: a case study of Libya', PhD thesis, University of Salford, Salford.
- Efobi, UR 2015, 'IFRS adoption and the environment: is Africa closing her eyes to something?' *Beyond the UN Global Compact: Institutions and Regulations (Advances in Sustainability and Environmental Justice, Vol. 17)*, pp. 169-95.
- Elad, C 2015, 'The development of accounting in the Franc Zone countries in Africa', *The International Journal of Accounting*, vol. 50, no. 1, pp. 75–100.
- El-Rashedy, MSM 2006, 'Societal culture and its impact on financial accounting standards setting with a reference to the Egyptian standards', *Contemporary Business Research Journal*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 1–51.
- Ezenwoke, O & Tion, W 2020, 'International financial reporting standards (IFRSs) adoption in Africa: a bibliometric analysis', *Cogent Social Sciences*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp.1-20.
- Espinosa, C, Maquieira, C, Diaz, F & Abarca A 2015, 'Adoption of IFRS in an emerging market: the Chilean case', *Academia Revista Latinoamericana de Administración*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 442-60.
- Evans, L 2004, 'Language, translation and the problem of international accounting communication', *Accounting and Accountability Journal*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 200-48.
- Fadallah, A 1996, *International accounting*, 1st edn, Scientific Books Publishing, Cairo.
- Faraj, S & Essa E 2014, 'Challenges facing IASs/IFRS implementation by Libyan listed companies', *Universal Journal of Accounting and Finance*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 57-63.
- Fitó, A, Gómez, F & Moya S 2012, 'Choices in IFRS adoption in Spain: determinants and consequences', *Accounting in Europe*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 61-83.
- Florou, A. & Pope, PF 2012, 'Mandatory IFRS adoption and institutional investment decisions', *The Accounting Review*, vol. 87, no. 6, pp. 1993-2025.
- Flower, J 1997, 'The future shape of harmonization: the EU versus the IASC versus the SEC', *The European Accounting Review*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 281-303.
- Freud, S 1962, *The ego and the id*, WW Norton & Co., New York.
- Freud, S 2002, *Civilization and its discontents*, Penguin Classics, London.
- Gioia, DA & Pitre, E 1990, 'Multiparadigm perspectives on theory building', *The Academy of Management Review*, vol. 15, pp. 584-602.
- Graham, A, Nandialath, AM, Skaradzinski, D & Rustambekov, E 2017, 'Macroeconomic determinants of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) adoption: evidence from the Middle East North Africa (MENA) region', *Accounting & Taxation*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 39-48.
- Guba, EG & Lincoln, YS 1998, 'Competing paradigms in qualitative research', in NK Denzin & YS Lincoln (eds), *Handbook of qualitative research*, Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks, CA.
- Guler, I, Guillen, M. & Macpherson, J 2002, 'Global competition, institutions, and the diffusion of organizational practices: the international spread of ISO 9000 quality certificates', *Administrative Science Quarterly*, vol. 47, pp. 207-32.

- Haoudi, K 2015, 'Transition to IFRS in Morocco: theoretical foundations, benefits and issues', *International Journal of Innovation and Applied Studies*, vol. 10, pp. 1299-311.
- Hassard, J 1990, 'An alternative to paradigm incommensurability in organization theory', in J Hassard & D Pym (eds), *The theory and philosophy of organizations*, Routledge, London and New York.
- Haunschild, PR 1993, 'Interorganizational imitation: the impact of interlocks on corporate acquisition activity', *Administrative Science Quarterly*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 564-92.
- Holden, MT & Lynch, P 2004, *Choosing the appropriate methodology: understanding research philosophy*, Irish Research Council for the Humanities and Social Sciences, viewed 13 November 2013, <[http://repository.wit.ie/1466/1/Choosing_the_Appropriate_Methodology_Understanding_Research_Philosophy_\(RIKON_Group\).pdf](http://repository.wit.ie/1466/1/Choosing_the_Appropriate_Methodology_Understanding_Research_Philosophy_(RIKON_Group).pdf)>.
- Holthausen, RW & Watts, RL 2001, 'The relevance of the value-relevance literature for financial accounting standard setting', *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, vol. 31, nos. 1-3, pp. 3-75.
- Hopper, T & Powell, A 1985, 'Making sense of research into the organizational and social aspects of management accounting: a review of its underlying assumptions', *Journal of Management Studies*, vol. 22, no. 5, pp. 429-65.
- Houqe, MN & Monem, RM 2016, 'IFRS adoption, extent of disclosure, and perceived corruption: a cross-country study', *International Journal of Accounting*, vol. 51, no. 3, pp. 363-78.
- Hussey, J & Hussey, R 1997, *Business research: a practical guide for undergraduate and postgraduate students*, Palgrave, Basingstoke.
- Iatridis, G & Rouvolis, S 2010, 'The post-adoption effects of the implementation of International Financial Reporting Standards in Greece', *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 55-65.
- Igba, MZ 1997, *International accounting: a global perspective*, 1st edn, South Western College Publishing, New York.
- International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS). 2021. IFRS Advisory Council (<https://www.ifrs.org/groups/ifrs-advisory-council/#members>: accessed 09. Oct 2021)
- Isa, MA 2014, 'Dimensions of IFRS transition roadmap's information content in LDCS: a case of Nigeria', *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 164, pp. 621-6.
- Jermakowicz, EK & Gornik-Tomaszewski, S 2006, 'Implementing IFRS from the perspective of EU publicly traded companies', *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, vol. 15, no. 2, 170-96.
- Jonsson, S & Macintosh, NB 1997, 'Cats, rats, and ears: making the case for ethnographic accounting research', *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, vol. 22, nos. 3-4, pp. 367-86.
- Judge, W, Li, S & Pinsker, R 2010, 'National adoption of international accounting standards: an institutional perspective'. *Corporate Governance: an International Review*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 161-74.
- Kakkuri-Knuuttila, ML, Lukka, K & Kuorikoski, J 2008, 'Straddling between paradigms: a naturalistic philosophical case study on interpretive research in management accounting', *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, vol. 33, pp. 267-91.

- Khalifa, MA 1998, 'Lectures in international accounting', Higher Studies Academy for Economic Research, Tripoli.
- Khamis, AM 2016 'Perception of preparers and auditors on new revenue recognition standard (IFRS 15): evidence from Egypt', *JurnalDinamikaAkuntansi dan Bisnis*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp.1-18.
- Khlif, H, Ahmed, K & Alam, M 2020, 'Accounting regulations and IFRS adoption in francophone North African countries: the experience of Algeria, Morocco, and Tunisia', *The International Journal of Accounting*, vol. 55, no. 1, pp. 1-36.
- Krauss, SE 2005, 'Research paradigms and meaning making: a primer', *The Qualitative Report*, vol. 10, pp. 758-70.
- Kythreotis, A 2015, 'The interrelation among faithful representation (reliability), corruption and IFRS adoption: an empirical investigation', *International Journal of Business and Economic Sciences Applied Research (IJBESAR)*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 25-49.
- Laga, M 2012, 'Obstacles of adopting and implementation of IFRS in Libya', *European Journal of Business and Economics*, vol. 7, pp. 1-3.
- Laughlin, R 1995, 'Methodological themes: empirical research in accounting: alternative approaches and a case for 'middle-range' thinking', *Accounting, Auditing and Accountability Journal*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 63-87.
- Leuz, C 2003, 'IAS versus US GAAP: information asymmetry-based evidence from Germany's new market', *Journal of Accounting Research*, vol. 41, no. 3, pp. 445-72.
- Leuz, C & Oberholzer-Gee, F 2006, 'Political relationships, global financing, and corporate transparency: evidence from Indonesia', *Journal of Financial Economics*, vol. 81, no. 2, pp. 411-39.
- Lewis, M 2001, 'Islam and accounting', *Accounting Forum*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 103-27.
- L'Huillier, B 2011, 'The hitchhikers guide to paradigms: tripping on methodology', College of Business, Prince Mohammad Bin Fahd University, Al Khobar, Saudi Arabia.
- Libya State 1974, *The Official Gazette, Law No.116 of 1973 to organise the accounting profession in Libya*, pp. 251-68.
- Libyan Stock Market 2011, 'History of stock market, Libya', Libyan Stock Market, viewed 1 September 2012, <<http://libyastockmarket.com/history.asp>>
- Lincoln, Y. & Guba, E 1985, *Naturalistic inquiry*, Sage, Thousand Oaks, CA.
- Lourenço, I & Manuel, EM 2015, 'Main consequences of IFRS adoption: analysis of existing literature and suggestions for further research', *Revista Contabilidade and Finanças*, vol. 26, no. 68, pp. 126-39.
- Maradona, AF & Chand, P 2018, 'The pathway of transition to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in developing countries: evidence from Indonesia', *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, vol. 30, pp. 57-68.
- Marx, KH & Engels, F 1987, *Introduction to a critique of political economy: the German ideology*, student edition, Lawrence & Wishart, London.
- Masadeh, W, Mansour, E & Al-Salamat, W 2017, 'Changes in IFRS 3 accounting for business combinations: a feedback and effects analysis', *Global Journal of Business Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 61-70.

- Masoud, N 2014, 'Libya's IAS/IFRS adoption and accounting quality: what lessons from the European Union experience', *International Journal of Accounting and Financial Reporting*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 118-141.
- Matar, M 2005, *An analytical study for accounting standards in Kuwait and Saudi Arabia, compared with the International Accounting Standards*.
- Matar, M 2006, 'The importance of harmonization in the application of International standards', *Alyarmouk Research Magazine*, vol. 9, no. 4.
- Mbawuni, J 2018, 'Perceived benefits and challenges of IFRS adoption in Ghana: views of members of Institute Of Chartered Accountants, Ghana (ICAG)', *International Journal of Financial Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 99-114.
- Meyer, JW & Rowan, B 1983, 'Institutionalized organizations: formal structure as myth and ceremony', in JW Meyer, B Rowan, & TE Deal (eds), *Organizational environments ritual and rationality*, Sage, Beverly Hills, CA.
- Mhedhbi, K & Zeghal, D 2016, 'Adoption of international accounting standards and performance of emerging capital markets', *Review of Accounting and Finance*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 252-72.
- Mingers, J 2001, 'Combining IS research methods: towards a pluralist methodology', *Information Systems Research*, vol. 12, pp. 240-59.
- Mokhtar, E, Elharidy, A & Mandour, M., 2018, 'Compliance with IFRs: the case of risk disclosure practices in Egypt', *Arab Economic and Business Journal*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 1-14.
- Morgan, G & Smircich, L 1980, 'The case for qualitative research', *Academy of Management Journal*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 491-500.
- Mueller, GG 1997, *Accounting: an international perspective*, Irwin, New York.
- Nduna, LT & van Zyl, C 2020, 'A benefit segmentation framework for a nature-based tourism destination: the case of Kruger, Panorama and Lowveld areas in Mpumalanga province', *International Journal of Tourism Cities*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 953-73.
- Neag, R 2014, 'The effects of IFRS on net income and equity: evidence from Romanian listed companies', *Procedia Economics and Finance*, vol. 15, pp. 1787-90.
- Ntaikou, D, Vousinas, G & Kenourgios, D 2018, 'The expected impact of IFRS 9 on the Greek banking system's financial performance: some theoretical considerations and insights', *Proceedings of the ninth National Conference of the Financial Engineering and Banking Society*, Athens, Greece.
- Odoemelam, N, Okafor, RG & Ofoegbu, NG 2019, 'Effect of international financial reporting standard (IFRS) adoption on earnings value relevance of quoted Nigerian firms', *Cogent Business and Management*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 1-22.
- Oliver, C 1991, 'Strategic responses to institutional processes', *Academy of Management Review*, vol. 16, pp. 145-79.
- Orlikowski, WJ & Baroudi, JJ 1991, 'Studying information technology in organisations: research approaches and assumptions', *Information Systems Research*, vol. 2, pp. 1-28.
- Parker, LD & Roffrey, BH 1997, 'Methodological themes, back to the drawing board: revisiting grounded theory and the everyday accountant's and manager's reality', *Accounting, Auditing, and Accountability Journal*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 212-47.

- Parrott, KM 2017, 'A quantitative study on the difference between US GAAP and IFRS measuring comparability with financial ratios', Northcentral University, San Diego, CA.
- Patton, MQ 1990, *Qualitative evaluation and research methods*, 2nd edn, Sage, Newbury Park, CA.
- Powell, WW & DiMaggio, PJ 1991, *The new institutionalism in organizational analysis*, University of Chicago Press, Chicago.
- Probert, R 2020, 'How has digitalisation affected the accounting industry?' Honours dissertation, the University of the West of Scotland, Paisley.
- Ramanna, K & Sletten, E 2014, 'Network effects in countries' adoption of IFRS', *The Accounting Review*, vol. 89, no. 4, pp. 1517-43.
- Rawashdeh, M 2002, 'Effects of introducing international accounting standards on Amman stock exchange', *Journal of American Academy of Business, Cambridge*, vol. 3, nos. 1-2, p. 361.
- Reason, P 1998, 'Political, epistemological, ecological and spiritual dimensions of participation', *Studies in Cultures, Organisations and Societies*, vol. 4, pp. 147-67.
- Reed, M 1985, *Redirections in organizational analysis*, Tavistock, London.
- ROSC 2002, 'Accounting and auditing: Arab Republic of Egypt: report on the observance of standards and codes (ROSC)', World Bank. Washington, DC, USA.
- Roshwan, AO 2000, *Study and evaluation of International Accounting Standards*, GPCFA, Riyadh.
- Ryan, B & Scapens, RW 2002, *Research method and methodology in finance and accounting*, Thomson, London.
- Salah, W 2020, 'The International Financial Reporting Standards and firm performance: a systematic review', *Applied Finance and Accounting*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 1-10.
- Samaha, K & Khlif, H 2016, 'Adoption of and compliance with IFRS in developing countries: a synthesis of theories and directions for future research', *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 33-49.
- Sanusi, LS 2010, 'Growth prospects for the Nigerian economy', Convocation lecture delivered at the Igbinedion University, Okada, Edo State, Nigeria.
- Sartre, J-P 2020, *Being and nothingness*, Routledge, London.
- Schachler, M, Al-Abiyad, S & Al-Hadad, A 2012, 'Evaluation of the suitability of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) for application in emerging North African countries: a literature review and a research agenda', *Journal of Modern Accounting and Auditing*, vol. 8, no. 12, pp. 1773-9.
- Schipper, K 2005, 'The introduction of International Accounting Standards in Europe: implications for international convergence', *European Accounting Review*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 101-126.
- Shareia, B & Irvine, H 2008, 'The use of accounting information in the economy of Libya: an historical approach', *Proceedings of the twelfth World Congress of Accounting Historians*, Istanbul, Turkey.
- Shareia, B 2016, 'The present role of accounting information systems in meeting the development needs: the case of Libya', *International Journal of Business, Humanities and Technology*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 17-28.

- Singh, RD & Newberry, S 2008 'Corporate governance and International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS): the case of developing countries', in M Tsamenyi & S Uddin (eds), *Corporate governance in less developed and emerging economies (research in accounting in emerging economies, Vol. 8)*, Emerald Group Publishing Limited, Bingley, vol. 8, pp. 483–518.
- Slama, F & Klibi, MF 2017, 'Accounting development in a changing environment: the case of Tunisia', *International Journal of Law and Management*, vol. 59, pp. 756–75.
- Soderstrom, NS & Sun, KJ 2007, 'IFRS adoption and accounting quality: a review', *European Accounting Review*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 675-702.
- Taiwo, FH & Adejare, AT 2014, 'Empirical analysis of the effect of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) adoption on accounting practices in Nigeria', *Archives of Business Research*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 1-14.
- Tan, H, Wang, S & Welker, M 2011, 'Analyst following and forecast accuracy after mandated IFRS adoptions', *Journal of Accounting Research*, vol. 49, pp. 1307–57.
- Taskumis, G, Campbell, D & Douppnik, T 2009, 'IFRS: beyond the standards (international financial reporting standards)', *Journal of Accounting*, vol. 207, no. 2, pp. 34-9.
- Tomaszewski, GS & Showerman, S. 2010, 'IFRS in the United States: challenges and opportunities', *Review of Business*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 61-71.
- Transparency.org 2021, *Corruption Perceptions Index - Libya*, viewed August 24, 2021, <<http://transparency.org/en/cpi/2020/index/nzi>>.
- Trimble, M 2018, 'A reinvestigation into accounting quality following global IFRS adoption: evidence via earnings distributions', *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, vol. 33, pp. 18-39.
- Watts, RL & Zimmerman, JL 1978, 'Towards a positive theory of the determination of accounting standards', *The Accounting Review*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 112-34.
- Watts, RL & Zimmerman, JL 1986, *Positive accounting theory*, Prentice-Hall, Englewood-Cliffs, NJ.
- Watts, RL & Zimmerman, JL 1990, 'Positive accounting theory: a ten year perspective', *The Accounting Review*, vol. 65, no. 1, pp. 131-56.
- Wei, Y, Liu, X, Song, H & Romilly, P 2001, 'Endogenous innovation growth theory and regional income convergence in China', *Journal of International Development*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 153-68.
- Wilson, R 2004, *Regulatory challenges posed by Islamic capital market products and services*, University of Durham, Durham UK.
- Yapa, S, Jacobs, K & Hout, C 2010, 'Revolution and the accountant: the practice and profession of accounting in Cambodia', *Proceedings of the sixth Asia Pacific Interdisciplinary Research in Accounting Conference*, Sydney, Australia, pp. 1-25.
- Zakari, MA 2014, 'Challenges of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) adoption in Libya', *International Journal of Accounting and Financial Reporting*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 390-412.
- Zeff, S 2007, 'Some obstacles to global financial reporting comparability and convergence at a high level of quality', *The British Accounting Review*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 290-302.

Zehri, C & Abdelbaki, A 2013, 'Does adoption of international accounting standards promote economic growth in developing countries?' *International Open Journal of Economics*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1-13.

Zeller, T 2019, 'An IFRS-based taxonomy of financial ratios', *Accounting Research Journal*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 20-35

Appendices

Questionnaire

Dear participant:

The International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) have been issued to provide guidance on the preparation of annual financial reports. This may give the opportunity for Libyan professionals to improve their skills in order to achieve international standards in the preparation of financial reports.

The attached questionnaire is part of a PhD study that examines to what extent the adoption of IFRS in Libya can be successful. To assist in this research, please provide answers to the questions in the questionnaire.

Your answers will contribute to developing the accounting profession in Libya and improving the quality of financial reporting.

Any information that you provide will be dealt with confidentially, and will be used only for the purpose of this study.

Thank you for participating in this research.

Mohamed Abdurahman

Tel: 00218927824770

Email: Mohamed.Abdurahman@uws.ac.uk

School of Business and Enterprise

University of the West of Scotland

United Kingdom

Part 1: Participants' information

1.1 Your position

- Owner/partner
- Senior accountant
- Staff accountant
- Auditor
- Academic accountant
- Other

Specify

1.2 Age

- Under 30
- 30-40
- 41-50
- 51-60
- Over 60

1.3 Gender

- Male
- Female

1.4 Your qualification

- High School
- Diploma
- Bachelor
- MSc
- PhD
- Other

Specify.....

1.5 Place of education

- Libya
- UK
- USA
- Other Western countries
- Other Arabic countries
- Rest of the world

1.6 Your professional experience

- 1-2 years
- 2-3 years
- 3-6 years
- 6-9 years
- 9-12 years
- Over 12 years

1.7 Your Accounting training and courses attendance as part of Continuing Professional Development (CPD)

- Once a month
- Once every three months
- Once every six months
- Once a year
- Other

Specify

Part 2: Libyan professional awareness of the IFRS

2.1 Do you feel you have appropriate knowledge of IFRS? Yes No

If **No** could you please go to **2.1.2**.

2.1.1 If **Yes**, do you apply them in your institution? Yes No

If **Yes**, do you think the adoption of the IFRS have a positive impact on financial reporting?

- Yes No

2.1.2 If you do not have sufficient awareness of the IFRS, do you know any other institutions which have already applied IFRS?

- Yes No

2.2 Experience has confirmed that the IFRS can play a significant role in improving the quality of financial reporting. Therefore,

Would you be willing to apply them? Yes No

If **Yes**, do you agree that the current accounting environment in Libya is appropriate for the application of the IFRS? Yes No

Part 3: The potential advantages of and difficulties with IFRS implementation in Libya

3.1 Do you agree that implementing the IFRS will have potential advantages for financial reporting in the Libya? Yes No

Please specify reasons

.....

3.2 Previous implementations of the IFRS have faced many difficulties, including the following. What do you think will be the most difficult factors which might affect IFRS implementation in Libya?

Please tick any which are appropriate.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Language barrier | <input type="checkbox"/> Islamic culture |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Low level of education | <input type="checkbox"/> Poor infrastructure |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Instability of government | <input type="checkbox"/> Corruption |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Accounting system | <input type="checkbox"/> IT modification |
| <input type="checkbox"/> The complexities of tax law and statutory accounting | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Political factors | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic factors |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Social factors | <input type="checkbox"/> Financial factors |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Administrative factors | <input type="checkbox"/> Regulatory factors |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Cultural factors | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |

Please add others

3.2 Do you agree that IFRS in Libya will have potential implications for financial reporting? Yes No

3.3.1 If yes, will these be? Negative Positive

If negative, this will reflect on?

- The Libyan public sector institutions
- The private sector in Libya
- The Foreign investors
- All of the above
- Others (please specify)

Part 4: The need to apply the IFRS and the perceptions of Libyan professionals regarding their introduction into the Libyan accounting profession

4.1 Do you think there is necessity felt by the users of accounting information in Libya to adopt the IFRS? Yes No

If yes, who are they?

You can tick all the appropriate boxes.

- The Libyan public sector
- The private sector in Libya
- The Foreign investors
- All of the above
- Others (please specify)

4.2 In order for the IFRS to be appropriate in the Libyan context what types of modifications are required?

- In the accounting system, itself
- In the internal control systems
- The stability of the accounting system in the Libyan environment
- The consistency of the Libyan accounting system with the international system
- All of the above factors
- Others ([please specify)

4.3 How will the introduction of the IFRS be perceived by the main actors involved in accounting matters in Libya? Optimistically Pessimistically

Part 5: Factors which should be considered for the modifications required

5.1 What are the potential implications of the implementation of the IFRS for the future?

- The quality of financial reporting will be improved
- The adoption of IFRS will not add value
- By adopting the IFRS, Libyan financial reporting will be more acceptable in international financial markets
- Others (please specify)

.....

5.2 Do you think government regulations will have a positive impact on the actual implementation of the IFRS in Libya? Yes No

Please specify

5.3 Do you think providing ‘international guidelines’ to Libyan professionals will positively contribute to and facilitate the implementation of the IFRSs in Libya?

- Yes No

How?

5.4 Previous experiments confirmed that by introducing IFRS into training curricula played essential role in implementing IFRS. Do you think that introducing the IFRS into training curricula will have a positive impact on their actual implementation in Libya?

- Yes No

Thank you.